

**Regulation of pro-inflammatory
responses in a simple *in vitro* model of
chronic oxidant exposure in COPD**

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Author's declaration

I hereby declare this thesis has been composed by myself and that it has not been submitted for a DBA, Dprof, EngD, PhD or comparable academic degree. The work contained within this thesis has been carried out independently at the University of the West of Scotland.

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Fawziye Tarhini

Dedication

I dedicate the doctoral research work performed in this project to my loving family, especially to my husband without you for sure I wouldn't be able to complete my studies. Thank you so much!

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Whose blessing started by the name of almighty God, First and foremost I would like to praise and thank God, the Almighty, who has granted me countless blessings and opportunities, so that I have been finally able to accomplish the thesis.

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“Always dream and shoot higher than you know you can do. Do not bother just to be better than your contemporaries or predecessors. Try to be better than yourself.”

William Faulkner

ABSTRACT

Purpose: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is caused by long-term exposure to pollutants such as cigarette smoke (CS) that stimulates an inflammatory response and produces oxidants that cause oxidative stress (OS) which is considered the main cause of COPD. Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) is one of many oxidants identified to be elevated in the breath condensates of COPD patients resulting in OS and it has been found to be associated with enhanced inflammation. Chronic inflammation is another key feature of COPD that persists long after smoking cessation and is driven by multiple pro-inflammatory cytokines and OS. Inflammation and OS can lead to permanent epigenetic modulation patterns of genes that are correlated with COPD. Protease-activated receptor 2 (PAR2) has been identified as a critical and key protease sensor and driver of pathology in several inflammatory diseases including asthma, but the roles of this receptor in COPD are still unclear. This study aimed to understand how chronic exposure to H₂O₂ alone or in combination with other inflammatory mediators influences cell response relevant to COPD lung pathogenesis, and whether these challenges alter DNA methylation levels of the PAR2 promoter region, to reveal potential implications for, and mechanistic insights into, COPD development.

Methods: H₂O₂ was used as a model oxidant to establish an *in vitro* chronic oxidative stress system. BEAS-2B cells were exposed chronically in a repeated exposure manner to H₂O₂ for 2 h/day for 3 days at different concentrations, alone or in combination with inflammatory mediators (LPS, TGF- β and TNF- α ; constant exposure for 48 h). Effects of pre-treatment with a selective IKK-2 inhibitor (TPCA-1) was investigated to assess the contribution of the NF- κ B pathway. Cell viability was assessed by MTT assay. Cytokines were measured by ELISA, intracellular ROS production was detected by 2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate (CM-H₂DCFDA) assay and mRNA transcript levels were assayed by qPCR. Model development experiments were performed using primary human bronchial epithelial cells from healthy and COPD donors (HBEC/COPD-HBEC). Methprimer software was used to predict the CpG islands/sites of the *F2RL1* promoter region, and TFBS and JASPAR software were used to identify potential motifs and their binding sites. DNA from treated and untreated cells was isolated and bisulphite treated. Bisulphite-specific PCR was performed and PCR products were purified and sequenced, prior to quantitative analysis (University of Glasgow Polyomics).

Results: Cells tolerated a repeated exposure of H₂O₂ up to 15 μ M in BEAS-2B, 25 μ M in HBEC and 50 μ M in COPD-HBEC alone or in combination with 10 ng/ml of TGF- β and TNF- α or 500 ng/ml of LPS with only moderate impact on viability (MTT), and no effect on visual appearance/morphology. Intracellular ROS were significantly elevated in the presence of either LPS or H₂O₂, with an additive effect of combined treatment. H₂O₂ stimulated modest or no release of IL-8 and IL-6 alone but synergistically enhanced LPS-induced IL-8 and IL-6.

Comparative RT-qPCR showed heightened transcript expression in COPD-related genes (*IL6*, *IL8*, *RELA*, *F2RL1*, *SOD2*, *CAT*, and *NFE2L2*). Interestingly, the mRNA transcript level of *SOD2* gene was observed to be significantly elevated in HBEC when treated with LPS and H₂O₂ compared to COPD-HBEC. This differential response of the *SOD2* gene suggested an impaired antioxidant response to challenge in cells from COPD patients. Pre-treatment with TPCA-1 effectively suppressed LPS-induced IL-6 and IL-8 and significantly inhibited H₂O₂-enhanced LPS induction of pro-inflammatory cytokines in BEAS-2B, HBEC and COPD-HBEC, suggesting that oxidative stress-driven cytokine release was largely mediated via activation of the NF-κB pathway, likely canonical. TPCA-1 also suppressed stressor-stimulated levels of *IL6*, *IL8* and *RELA* transcripts.

Bioinformatics packages detected two CpG islands in the *F2RL1* promoter region, one overlapping with the *F2RL1* coding sequence with potential CpG sites, and with specific binding sites of key transcription motifs. Results from Sanger sequencing of this region revealed successful bisulphite conversion of bisulphite-specific PCR products, and analysis provided insight into the role of DNA methylation in the *F2RL1* promoter, with potential implications for receptor activity under COPD-related challenges.

Conclusion: Repeated exposure to H₂O₂ induced minimal inflammatory response but synergistically enhanced the effect of inflammatory mediators on cytokine release and COPD-related gene expression, including *F2RL1* encoding the key inflammatory orchestrator PAR2. These data suggest that *in vitro* combined exposure models may be useful to study the effects of complex epithelial cell challenges relevant to COPD pathology. The synergistic effect of COPD-relevant stimuli in combination was effectively inhibited by blocking a single pathway (NF-κB), including a transcriptional component. These findings in a simple oxidative stress model further support the potential for NF-κB blockade as a therapeutic strategy to ameliorate chronic inflammation in COPD.

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List of symbols and abbreviations

<i>AP-1</i>	Activator Protein 1
ATCC	American Type Culture Collection
BAL	Broncho Alveolar Lavage
β -arr	β -arrestins
BS-MSP	Bisulphite Conversion- Methylated Specific PCR
BSP	Bisulphite Specific PCR
BS primers	Bisulphite-specific Primers
<i>CAT</i>	Catalase
CCL-18	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 18
<i>CDKN2A</i>	Cyclin Dependent kinase Inhibitor 2A gene
<i>CHRNA3/5</i>	Nicotinic Acetylcholine Receptors
CM-H ₂ DCFDA	Chloro-methylchlorodihydrofluorescein Diacetate
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
COPD-HBEC	COPD- Human primary Bronchial Epithelial Cells
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide 2
COPD	Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease
COX-2	Cyclooxygenase-2
CRP	C-reactive protein
CS	Cigarette Smoke
d	Days
DMSO	Dimethyl Sulfoxide
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DNMTs	DNA Methyltransferase Enzymes
DPBS	Dulbecco's Phosphate-Buffered Saline
ECL	Extra Cellular Loop
EC	Endothelial Cells
EGF	Epidermal Growth Factor
EIF	Eukaryotic Translation Initiation Factor
ELISA	Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay
EMT	Epithelial-Mesenchymal Transition
ETS	Environmental Tobacco Smoke
ERK 1/2	Extracellular Signal-Regulated Kinase
EWAS	Epigenome Wide Association Studies
FBS	Fetal bovine serum
FEV ₁	Forced Expiratory Volume in 1
FVC	Forced Vital Capacity
<i>F2RL1</i>	F2R Like Trypsin Receptor 1

<i>GATA4</i>	GATA Binding Protein 4
<i>GAPDH</i>	Glyceraldehyde-3-Phosphate Dehydrogenase
GOLD	Global Initiative for Chronic Lung Disease
GPCR	G Protein Coupled Receptor
GSH	Glutathione
GWAS	Genome-Wide Association Studies
h	Hours
hAEC	Human Airway Epithelial Cells
HATs	Histone Acetyltransferase
HBEC	Human primary Bronchial Epithelial Cells
HBSS	Hanks' Balanced Salt Solution
HCL	Hydrochloric Acid Solution
HDAC2	Histone deacetylase 2
HDAC6	Histone deacetylase 6
HHIP	Hedgehog interacting protein
4-HNE	4-Hydroxynonenal
HKGs	House keeping Genes
HMOX	Heme-Oxygenase
OH [·]	Hydroxyl radical
H ₂ O ₂	Hydrogen peroxide
ICS	Inhaled corticosteroids
IL	Interleukin
IL-1 β	Interleukin 1 beta
IL-6	Interleukin 6
IL-8	Interleukin 8
IRF3	Interferon Regulatory Transcription Factor 3
LPS	Lipopolysaccharide
MBP	Methyl-Binding Proteins
MDA	Malondialdehyde
MEK	Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinase
5-MeC	5-Methyl-Cytosine
<i>MGMT</i>	O-6-Methylguanine-DNA Methyltransferase
Min	Minutes
MMP	Matrix Metalloproteinase
MTT	Methylthiazolyldiphenyl-tetrazolium Bromide
μ M	Micromolar
m-TFA	Mitochondrial Transcription Factor
NADPH/NOX2 oxidase	Nicotinamide Adenine Dinucleotide Phosphate Oxidase 2
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information

NE	Neutrophil Elastase enzyme
NEMO	NF- κ B Essential Modulator
NF- κ B	Nuclear Factor Kappa B
<i>NFE2L2/Nrf2</i>	Nuclear Factor Erythroid 2-Related Factor 2
NO	Nitric Oxide
Obs/Exp	Observed/Expected
O ₂	Oxygen
OS	Oxidative Stress
PAMPs	Pathogen-Associated Molecular Patterns
PAR	Proteinase-Activated Receptor
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction
PMT	POST-Translational Modification
PUFAs	Polyunsaturated Fatty Acids
<i>qPCR</i>	Quantitative Real Time PCR
RNA	RNA Ribonucleic Acid
RNS	Reactive Nitrogen Species
ROS	Reactive Oxygen Species
RT	Room Temperature
SERPINA1	Serpin Family A Member 1
SERPINA	Serine Protease Inhibitor
SDS	Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate
<i>sDHA</i>	Succinate Dehydrogenase A
s	Seconds
O ₂ ⁻	Superoxide Anion
SNP	Single Nucleotide Polymorphism
SOD2	Superoxide Dismutase
SP-1	Specificity Protein 1
TBE	Tris/Borate/EDTA
TETs	Ten-Eleven Methylcytosine Dioxygenase
TGF- β	Transforming Growth Factor Beta 1
THS	Tobacco Heating System
TLR4	Toll Like Receptor 4
Tm regions	Transmembrane Regions
TNF- α	Tumour Necrosis Factor alpha
(CH ₃) ₃ COOH	Tert-Butyl Hydroperoxide
TRAM	TRIF-Related Adapter Molecule
TRIF	Toll/IL-1 Receptor-domain Containing Adaptor Inducing Interferon
TSS	Transcription Start Site
UC	Ulcerative Colitis
UTR	Untranslated Region
WHO	World Health Organization

Chapter 1. Introduction

1.1. Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD)

1.1.1. Global initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) definition of COPD

GOLD's (Global Initiative for Chronic Lung Disease, 2017) definition of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD): "Is a common, preventable and treatable disease that is characterized by persistent respiratory symptoms and airflow limitation that is due to airway and/or alveolar abnormalities usually caused by significant exposure to noxious particles or gases" (Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung, 2022; (Chen, 2022). According to a World Health Organisation report (WHO, 2022), COPD is projected to be one of the top three causes of death, making it the third most impactful killer disease worldwide. It was estimated that COPD caused around 3.23 million deaths in 2019, nearly 90 % of these deaths is patients under 70 years of age reported to be in low and middle-income countries (Halpin *et al.*, 2019).

1.1.2. Introduction to COPD

COPD is characterised by airflow limitations that is partially reversible, severe inflammation in the airways, as well as systemic effects or comorbidities (Decramer, Janssens and Miravitlles, 2012; Christenson *et al.*, 2022). In COPD, conditions such as chronic inflammation lead to progressive airflow obstruction and severe destruction of parenchymal tissue (King, 2015). The main contributors to the progressive worsening of lung function are the narrowing of the small airways due to mucus overproduction, also, the proliferation of the smooth muscle cells and fibrosis (Figure 1.1) (Shen *et al.*, 2018). This is also associated with morphological destruction of the lungs represented by the destruction of alveoli structure (emphysema) and chronic bronchitis (airway wall thickening of bronchioles less than 2 mm in diameter)(Kim *et al.*, 2015). Symptoms of COPD include: breathing difficulty especially during physical activities (dyspnea) (James *et al.*, 2021), chronic cough that may produce mucus (Cho *et al.*, 2016), sputum production (Anon.,2016), wheezing and chest tightness (Qaseem *et al.*, 2011; Goërtz *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 1.1. Histopathology of COPD small airways

(A) Normal airway with open lumen **(B)** Small airway lumen filled with mucus **(C)** Acute inflammation and mucus surrounded by thick airway wall **(D)** Chronic inflammation: fibrosis and hyperplasia of smooth muscle cells accompanied by fibrosis resulting in the obstruction of the airway (Jin Hwa Lee *et al.*, 2014).

1.1.3. Epidemiology and prevalence

Globally, the existing prevalence data of COPD varies widely, partly due to the method of diagnosis, survey methods and classification of COPD (Lindberg *et al.*, 2005). It was noticed that the prevalence of COPD was higher when the disease was diagnosed by spirometry alone without considering the combination diagnosis of spirometry and symptoms (Kim and Criner, 2015). Met-analysis studies and systematic reviews reported evidence that COPD is very common and highly prevalent in smokers and ex-smokers compared to non-smokers, in age group ≥ 40 comparing with people < 40 and in men compared to women (Varmaghani *et al.*, 2019). Previously, the Burden of Obstructive Lung Disease (BOLD) study and further larger scale epidemiological studies estimated that in 2010, the number of COPD cases was 384 million with a prevalence of 11.7% worldwide (Adeloye *et al.*, 2015); however, there is an expectation for a projection in COPD prevalence over the next 40 years (Vos *et al.*, 2015). In 2019, it was estimated that there were around 3 million deaths from COPD each year, this is

expected to rise to be over 5.4 million death annually by 2060 due to the ageing population in countries that are with high income, also due to an increase in cigarette smoking (CS) prevalence in developed countries (WHO, 2021).

The morbidity of COPD in terms of prolonged symptoms, days lost from work, and permanent disability compounds the disease burden (Mannino *et al.*, 2015). Different from many other diseases that are encountered by physicians, COPD is a preventable disease in the majority of detected incidences. The reason behind this is that the main etiologic feature is well-known and completely avoidable (Vogelmeier *et al.*, 2017a). The burden of COPD is predicted to increase in the coming decades due to noticeable projections in smokers' ratio, pulmonary ageing population, obesity, and outdoors/indoor pollution is also identified (Dharwal and Naura, 2018).

It was reported that since 1964, the prevalence of smoking in the United States has decreased from 40% to approximately 15% when the first Surgeon General's report declared that smoking is the main risk factor of COPD development (Rosenberg and Kalhan, 2016). However, more than 36 million Americans are counted as current smokers and a large group of former smokers who subjected themselves to a high risk of COPD development and other smoking-related diseases (Vijayan, 2013). It is vital to note that the majority of smokers started smoking in their teens and early 20s (Claus F. Vogelmeier *et al.*, 2017b).

Within the UK, the Department of Health (DoH) estimated in 2021 that around 1.17 million people (1.9% of population) were diagnosed with COPD. COPD prevalence, incidence and mortality rates are highest in Scotland and the north of England. Prevalence and incidence of COPD are over twice as high in the most deprived areas and population quintile in comparison to the least (Department of Health, 2021). It has been reported that 30,000 people die from COPD per year in England and Wales, making it the second greatest cause of death from lung disease and the UK's fifth biggest killer (Snell *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, COPD in UK is a major financial burden on the health system and economy, due directly to hospital admissions and time lost from work (Barnes 2007;Gruffydd-Jones, 2008). Annually, the estimated cost for COPD treatment is over £800 million in addition to £2.7 billion in lost working days in the UK

alone (Department of Health, 2021). This indicates that COPD poses severe social and economic problems that need to be addressed.

1.1.4. Diagnosis

COPD is diagnosed according to the symptoms, signs of the disease and medical history of the patient. Subsequently, spirometry is the test that is utilised to definitively assess lung function, this measures how much air a patient can inhale, and exhale, taking into account how quickly a pateint can exhale the air. Spirometry represents an irreversible decrease in forced expiratory volume in 1 (FEV₁) level, and the ratio of FEV₁ on forced vital capacity (FVC) (Table 1.1). Furthermore, X-ray and quantitative computed tomography (CT) are also used to assess lung structure and function (Mets, de Jong *et al.* 2012). Consequently, the chest CT scans evaluate lung density, which is indirectly proportional to lung airspace enlargement known as emphysema (Berndt, Leme and Shapiro, 2012).

Table 1.1. GOLD classification of air flow limitation severity and COPD stages according to the predicted percentage of FEV₁ ratio (Chen, 2022)

GOLD stage		Severity	Spirometry In patients with FEV₁/FVC <0.7, (based on post-bronchodilator FEV₁)
1		Mild	FEV₁ ≥ 80 % predicted Sometimes chronic cough
2		Moderate	FEV₁ = 50-80 % predicted With shortness of breath typically developing on exertion
3		Severe	FEV₁ = 30-50 % predicted Greater shortness of breath, reduced exercise capacity and repeated exacerbations
4		Very severe	<30 %, FEV₁ predicted

			with respiratory failure or signs of right heart failure
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1.1.5. Pathology

The characteristics of COPD pathological changes are mainly detected in lung parenchyma, pulmonary vasculature and in the airways (MacNee, 2006). Pathological changes due to COPD includes chronic inflammation, with an increase in inflammatory cells influx such as macrophages and T lymphocytes into different parts of the lung, this is also associated with structural modifications due to extensive repeated injury following by repair. These structural and inflammatory changes in the airways rise with persist even after smoking cessation and it can be linked to severity of the disease (Barnes, 2017). In COPD, two types of conditions are identified due to the amplified inflammation, chronic bronchitis, it is characterised by mucus hypersecretion that can further block the narrowed airway and becomes more inflamed. Patients develop chronic cough trying to clear the airways (Kim and Criner, 2013). Emphysema, it affects the air sacs in the lung, also the walls between them, it is characterised by the destruction of the alveolar membrane, where they become damaged and less elastic. In this condition the air is trapped inside the lung due to the collapse of the small airways when trying to exhale (Wang *et al.*, 2018) (Figure 1.2). These identified characteristics of COPD lead to a progressive decline in lung function.

A)

B)

Figure 1.2. Lungs with COPD

Types of COPD: (A) Chronic bronchitis characterised by inflamed airway and mucus hypersecretion. (B) Emphysema, characterised by collapsed air sacs. Figure created by Biorender

1.1.6. Pathophysiological changes of COPD

The primary feature of COPD is the restriction of airflow that is generally not fully reversible. A progressive decline of FEV₁, partial emptying of lungs during expiration, and consequent dynamic hyperinflation are all main outcomes that are resulted from the loss of alveolar sacs elasticity which is due to emphysematous destruction of parenchyma, as well as the remodeling of the small airway compartments (O'Donnell, 2006); accordingly, COPD is an umbrella term that covers group of respiratory diseases such as emphysema and chronic bronchiolitis (GOLD, 2008). COPD is characterised by chronic bronchitis, chronic obstruction and remodeling of the airway (small airway diseases), and emphysema which causes the progressive decline in lung function (Vestbo *et al.*, 2013a). Each of these conditions is characterised by their own unique features that contribute to the regular obstruction of airflow through the respiratory airways (Hurst *et al.*, 2010). Normally, the lung function depends on continuous oxygen supply and removal of carbon dioxide, this is carried on by a mechanism known as simple diffusion that takes place between blood and the alveoli. This exchange process is pivotal for survival (Clancy and Nobes, 2012). With age, lung function decreases gradually, however, in COPD patients this deterioration is enhanced, mainly due to smoking cigarettes as well as due to other COPD risk factors (Figure 1.3).

Figure 1.3. Lung function decreases naturally due to age

Smoking cigarettes can speed up the breakdown leading to COPD development in smokers at young age. Adapted from (Fletcher and Peto, 1977) and (Bednarek *et al.*, 2006).

1.2. Risk factors

COPD is a multifactorial disease, and many risk factors contribute to its development. Some of these risk factors can be modifiable, which means that they can be changed to reduce the risk of developing COPD. The risks include CS, poor socioeconomic status, occupational exposure to noxious particles and organic dust, biomass fuel combustion, indoor and outdoor pollution and environmental tobacco smoke (ETS). Whereas other risks are considered non-modifiable, this means cannot be avoided due to genetic factors, ageing and respiratory infection (Clancy and Nobes 2012; Forteza, Casalino-Matsuda *et al.*, 2012; Berndt, Leme and Shapiro, 2012) (Figure 1.4).

Figure 1.4. Risk factors contributed to the development of COPD

Smoking cigarettes is the fundamental risk factor; however, not all smokers develop COPD, which is also associated with other risk factors such as genetic/epigenetics, aging, proteases/anti-proteases imbalance and early onset. Also environmental challenges such as air pollution and continuous exposure to toxic particles that are responsible for oxidative stress generation, all these factors contribute to increase in susceptibility of an individual to COPD (Salvi and Barnes, 2009). Image was created by Biorender

1.2.1. Environmental challenges

Smoking cigarettes is the main risk factor that contributes to COPD development; however, only 20% of smokers develop symptomatic COPD (Terzikhan *et al.*, 2016). Other environmental challenges also have a major effect in COPD development (Souto-Miranda *et al.*, 2020). Here are some of the environmental challenges that may lead to COPD development.

1.2.1.1. Outdoor air pollution

Emission of toxic pollutants from motor vehicles and industries are the main causes of outdoor air pollution that have been identified as an important public health problem (Ko and Hui, 2012; Elbarbary *et al.*, 2020). In a community-based study, it has been observed that there is a direct proportion between higher traffic density during peak times, the lower the values of FEV₁ and FVC among the population (Kan *et al.*, 2011; (Nitschke *et al.*, 2016). A cohort study performed by the Danish Diet, Cancer and Health department involving 57,053 subjects reported that the incidence of COPD among the participated subjects is significantly correlated with nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) levels (Andersen *et al.*, 2011; Fisher *et al.*, 2016). Toxic pollutants such as ozone and nitrogen dioxide trigger the production of airway oxidative stress, bronchial hyper reactivity, and airway pulmonary and systemic inflammation (Ko and Hui, 2012; Lee *et al.*, 2021).

1.2.1.2. Indoor air pollution

Environmental cigarette smoke, nitrogen dioxide, carbon monoxide, biological allergens and volatile organic compounds are all main sources of indoor air pollutants (Van Tran, Park and Lee, 2020). Environmental tobacco smoke and exposure to biomass smoke are leading causes of COPD development (Shetty, D'souza and Anand, 2021). Worldwide, an estimation of around 3 billion people use biomass fuel as the main source of energy for cooking, heating and lighting (FitzGerald and Carlsten, 2011; Pathak, Gupta and Suri, 2020). Biomass fuel

combustion products are the main source of energy used daily in rural areas without appropriate indoor ventilation (Pathak, Gupta and Suri, 2020). Furthermore, women are more exposed to indoor pollutants compared to men as they spend more time inside the house, which makes them more prone to develop COPD (Hu *et al.*, 2010; Shetty, D'souza and Anand, 2021). However, a meta-analysis study revealed that exposure to biomass smoke is a risk factor for COPD development in both men and women (Hu *et al.*, 2010).

1.2.2. Effect of cigarette smoke on lung inflammation

Tobacco smoking is the main risk factor that is linked to COPD. Cigarette smoking is a complex mixture of oxidants/free radicals, and various chemical compounds including aldehydes that can induce the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), that triggers the production of oxidative stress (OS) in the lungs (Machin *et al.*, 2017). Cigarette smoke may alter the defence function of epithelial cells, thus making the lung more susceptible to infections (van der Vaart, Postma *et al.*, 2004; Yaghi, Zaman *et al.*, 2012). The immune system and physical barriers protect the human lungs from harmful environmental mediators such as viruses, fungi, bacteria, and pollution (Nikota and Stampfli, 2012); however, continuous exposure to CS affects these barriers by increasing epithelial permeability and damaging mucociliary clearance processes (Forteza, Casalino-Matsuda *et al.*, 2012).

1.2.2.1. Acute effect of CS on lung inflammation

The innate immune system is rapidly activated when the body is under acute exposure to CS (Lin *et al.*, 2021); this is associated with an elevated level of neutrophil influx into the airways that enhances the release of different proteolytic enzymes such as myeloperoxidase, serine proteases (e.g. elastase, cathepsin G) (Massena *et al.*, 2015) and bactericidal/permeability-increasing proteins that can cause serious damage to the lungs (Theprungsirikul *et al.*, 2021).

The acute mechanism is highly controlled by two important signalling pathways: Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR-4) and interleukin IL-1R1 that rely on the activity of an adaptor protein, known

as MyD88 (McDonough *et al.*, 2011). However, the specific blockage of IL-1R or the TLR-4 significantly reduces lung inflammation that is related to smoking cigarettes (Oh and Sin, 2012; Doz *et al.*, 2008). In contrast, the elimination of TLR-4 in transgenic mice does not abrogate the cigarette smoke-related emphysema in the chronic cigarette smoke exposure model. This suggests that acute inflammatory changes due to smoking cigarettes may not be directly responsible for COPD development (Maes *et al.*, 2006).

1.2.2.2. Chronic effects of CS on lungs

COPD initiates in the small airways as a reaction to chronic exposure to toxic gases and noxious particles that are mainly related to smoking cigarettes (Christenson *et al.*, 2022b). The innate immune system is the first line of defence and is activated immediately as an initial response to chronic exposure to chemical and toxic gases (Hiemstra, McCray and Bals, 2015). The innate immune system includes a variety of cells including epithelial and inflammatory cells, such as macrophages and neutrophils, which patrol the airways for microbes and irritants (Nurwidya, Damayanti and Yunus, 2016). The second line of defence is adaptive immunity, which is highly represented by T lymphocytes (Brusselle, Joos and Bracke, 2011). According to the disease severity, the level of all inflammatory cells increases dramatically in the small airways of COPD patients compared to healthy lungs (Eapen *et al.*, 2017). In patients diagnosed with class 4 COPD (the most severe according to GOLD), almost all small airways contain alveolar macrophages, neutrophils, CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ lymphocytes (Hogg, Paré and Hackett, 2017).

Furthermore, chronic exposure to cigarette smoke is correlated with histological changes in COPD lung features. This is linked to overexpression of mucus in the small airways that increase gradually with disease progression (Lu and Zheng, 2013). GOLD stage 4 COPD identifies that an average of ~15% of the total luminal area of small airways is occupied with mucus compared to healthy smokers where only less than 5% of the luminal area is full with mucus (Hogg *et al.*, 2004a). Consequently, the hyper-expression of mucus in the small airways is considered the single most vital histological risk factor that contributes to the mortality of patients with severe COPD stage. Neither inhaled nor oral corticosteroid medications can

block mucus overexpression in the airways (Sze *et al.*, 2015), which may suggest why these medications do not seem effective to decrease mortality levels among COPD subjects.

1.2.3. Emergence of genetic alterations in COPDs

Susceptibility to COPD is also influenced by genetic risk factors (Ragland *et al.*, 2019). COPD is a complex disease with a multifactorial background, based on the interaction of genetics and environmental factors. Environmental factors are strongly related to disease development (Corhay, Frusch and Louis, 2012); however, evidence shows that COPD is known to aggregate in families suggesting that genetic factors have a great impact that can lead to COPD (Hobbs and Hersh, 2014). The interaction between genetics and environmental factors has been a research focus largely due to the discovery of a deficiency in α_1 -antitrypsin protein (Laurell and Eriksson, 1963), which is considered the main genetic factor that is associated with COPD disease (Hall and Sayers, 2019). *SERPINA1* gene, which encodes α_1 -antitrypsin (AAT) is the circulating serine protease inhibitor (serpin) that is abundant at high levels. Genetic mutations can cause a systemic deficiency in AAT (AATD) that can lead to liver failure and chronic lung diseases (Jeanmonod, Rebecca and Suzuki, 2018). In patients with AATD, progressive destruction of small airway structure and alveoli were detected, this was believed to be the basis of the imbalance hypothesis of protease/anti-protease of COPD (Greene *et al.*, 2016)(Figure 1.4).

Individuals who are suffering from this deficiency are homozygous for a mutation in *SERPINA1* (Qiu *et al.*, 2015). Each person has two coding genes for α_1 -antitrypsin, one from the maternal origin and the other from the paternal origin. The normal allele of α_1 -antitrypsin is the *M* allele, which has a complement of another *M* allele, leading to a normal α_1 -antitrypsin gene with two *MM* alleles (Suárez-Lorenzo *et al.*, 2018). Individuals with *M* type have a normal level of α_1 -antitrypsin gene circulating in the blood at a level of $254 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{dl}^{-1}$ (Ling and Chapman, 2012; Cazzola *et al.*, 2020). Mutation in one variant allele, termed as *Z* allele causes an alteration in the amino acid sequence of α_1 -antitrypsin, which impairs the secretion of this

protein from the liver causing serious liver damage, and only small amounts of this protein enter the blood (Qiu *et al.*, 2015).

Furthermore, people who are heterozygotes with one *M* and one *Z* allele (*MZ* genotype) have moderate levels of circulating α 1-antitrypsin in a range of 62-151 mg.dl⁻¹ of normal levels and it has a reduced effect to neutralise neutrophil elastase. However, the most common abnormal phenotype of α 1-antitrypsin is the homozygous form that is associated with the *ZZ* genotype; individuals who exclusively express the *Z* gene have very low circulating levels of α 1-antitrypsin (≤ 30 mg.dl⁻¹). Patients with COPD suffer mainly from the deficiency of α 1-antitrypsin (have the *ZZ* genotype) and they are homozygous for a mutation in *SERPINA1* gene (Cazzola *et al.*, 2020). The deficiency of ATT protein accounts for between 1-5 % of COPD cases which means that there are other candidate genes that are highly associated with COPD pathogenesis, and this is an insufficient genetics factor to account for heterogeneity in COPD (Cho *et al.*, 2014).

Recently, meta-analysis studies and integrative genomic studies detected the presence of different polymorphisms in COPD candidate genes, such genes are: *CHRNA3/5*, *HHIP*, *FAM13A*, *IREB2* (Kim and Lee, 2015) (Table 1.2). For example, in genome-wide association studies (GWAS) of COPD cohorts, Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (SNP) within *FAM13A* was associated with chronic bronchitis, airway obstruction, emphysema and COPD susceptibility (Lee *et al.*, 2014; Cho *et al.*, 2012). Also, the *CHRNA3/5* locus is associated with emphysema and smoking intensity in COPD (Liao, Lin and Christiani, 2013). The *CHRNA3/5* region is highly related to nicotine addiction (smoking behaviour in COPD). *HHIP* gene encodes a membrane glycoprotein that is important for the morphogenesis of the lung. More recently, a functional variant upstream from *HHIP* has been found in a COPD GWAS, in chromosome 4q31, suggesting that the variant may affect promoter activity, lowering the expression of the *HHIP* gene (Kim and Lee, 2015). The silencing of *HHIP* in airway epithelial cell lines leads to a change in gene expression affecting pathways related to the extracellular matrix and cell growth in the lungs, which are processes relevant to COPD pathogenesis (Hodge *et al.*, 2013).

Although genetic contributors are well identified in COPD, inconsistent results of some genetic approaches suggest that not only genetics, but other factors are highly involved in COPD development; such factors may be related to epigenetic modifications (Jeanmonod, Rebecca and Suzuki, 2018). Epigenetic mechanisms are considered to be essential in developmental processes or contribute to disease states as they help to regulate gene activity in mammalian cells (Roth & Sweatt, 2011). The rapidly growing field of epigenetics has promising potential outcomes because if gene expression is altered, it can be amendable to develop new therapeutic strategies and treatments (Celli, 2012). Hobbs and colleagues, reported 9 genome important loci in COPD genetic studies/ These are shown in Table 1.2 (Hobbs *et al.*, 2017).

Table 1.2. Identified susceptibility loci and their encoding genes detected by GWAS

loci	protein	Protein function	Reference
FAM13A	Family with sequence similarity 13 member A	Signalling GPCR & Rho GTPase	(Chen <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
HHIP	Hedgehog Interaction protein	Embryonic development	(Zhao <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
TGFβ2	Transforming growth factor beta-2	Produces TGF-β2	(Parker <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
HTR4	5-hydroxytryptamine receptor 4	Serotonin receptor	(Hodge <i>et al.</i> , 2013)
CHRNA5	Cholinergic receptor nicotinic alpha 5 subunit	Nicotinic acetylcholine receptor	(Diabasana <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
RIN3	Ras and Rab interactor 3	Vesicle mediated transport	(Janson <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
CYP2A6	Cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily A member 6	Cytochrome P450	(Bray <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
GSTCD-NPNT	Glutathione S-Transferase C-terminal Domain containing	Cytochrome P450	(Henry <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
IL27-CCDC101	Interleukin 27	IL27 formation	(Hobbs <i>et al.</i> , 2016)

1.2.4. Infections and Inflammation

Infections are a not main cause of COPD development nor do they initiate the disease, but they have an important role in worsening the symptoms and lung function in patients with pre-existing COPD. Among the different respiratory tract infections, viral infection was recognised as the main microbiological agent responsible for exacerbations of clinical COPD symptoms (Postma, Bush and van den Berge, 2015).

Interestingly, infections that occurred in the respiratory tract during the childhood stage may elevate the risk for consequent COPD development at later stages life, suggesting an important additional role for infection in enhancing COPD development. This could be a reason to explain why not all smokers develop COPD and non-smokers are subjected to COPD development (Sethi and Murphy, 2008). Childhood respiratory tract infection contributes to the alteration of lung development and function during childhood, this makes the lung more prone to develop COPD at later time. Subsequently, when an individual starts to smoke with a lower lung function due to childhood respiratory infections, these individuals are more likely to suffer from unhealthy lung function due to heavy smoking later in the life, which can be the driver of COPD development (Hogg, Paré and Hackett, 2017). Both smokers and COPD patients are highly susceptible to respiratory infection, which is the central factor of exacerbations in patients with COPD, particularly during severe disease stages (GOLD 3 and 4) (Churg, Cosio *et al.*, 2008).

At severe stages of COPD and during exacerbations, patients show evidence of persistent systemic inflammation, identified by either measuring the level of circulating cytokines, chemokines and acute-phase protein or by detecting several abnormalities in circulating cells (Barnes, 2016). Several studies proposed that persistent pulmonary inflammation can derive the secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines and chemokines into the blood circulation (Tkáč, Man and Sin, 2007; Kany, Vollrath and Relja, 2019). The increase of these inflammatory mediators can trigger other organs such as the liver, bone marrow, and adipose tissues to secrete elevated levels of interleukins (IL-6 and IL-8), C-reactive protein (CRP), fibrinogen and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) into the circulation (Agustí and Faner, 2012). The outcome of

this mechanism is the development of persistent low-grade systemic inflammation (Tkáč, Man and Sin, 2007). Moreover, the development of systemic inflammation can initiate major COPD comorbidities including: heart failure, heart diseases, osteoporosis, lung cancer and pneumonia (Thomsen *et al.*, 2012b).

1.2.5. Accelerated ageing of the lung in COPD

Ageing is a main risk factor that is linked with most chronic diseases (Levandowski *et al.*, 2016). Ageing is defined as the continuous degeneration of vital cells and tissues that have a key impact on organs' function and development (Lange, David M Halpin, *et al.*, 2016; Maurya, Kumar and Chandra, 2017). Due to ageing mechanisms, important organs start to lose their vital functions gradually. The lung is one of the delicate tissues that is highly affected by ageing mechanisms that have a great impact on declining lung function. Furthermore, it is reported that pulmonary function starts to decline progressively at the age of 25 years (Mercado, Ito and Barnes, 2015).

It was postulated that accelerated ageing of the lung is mainly due to dysfunction of anti-ageing regulators including sirtuin-1 and FOXO proteins that are preliminary reduced due to heightened levels of oxidative stress in the lung (Barnes, 2015; Mercado, Ito and Barnes, 2015b). In the peripheral lungs of COPD patients, the expression of sirtuin-1 is significantly reduced, and this observation was confirmed *in vitro* using oxidative stress (OS). The latter causes a potential reduction in the activity and expression of sirtuin-1 that significantly increased MMP-9 expression level (Nakamaru *et al.*, 2009; Barnes, 2015).

In recent years, COPD has been defined as a disease that accelerates lung ageing (Ito and Barnes, 2009). COPD progresses in an age-dependent manner, representing a direct link between COPD pathogenesis and ageing (Lange, Halpin, *et al.*, 2016). In normal ageing mechanisms, different physiological modifications occur in the lung, such as airways and air sacs losing their elasticity that causes trapping of air inside the air sacs, which leads to the enlargement of distal air spaces, and decline in lung function (Figure 1.5) (Meiners, Eickelberg

and Königshoff, 2015; Boe, Boule and Kovacs, 2017). These features are also characteristics of COPD, an adult at the age of 60 is two to three times more likely to develop COPD compared to a younger age adult, indicating that COPD is more prevalent in an ageing population (MacNee, 2016). The reduction of telomere (TL) sequence length at the end of chromosomes arrests the cell cycle and triggers senescence, making telomere shortening a biomarker of ageing (Maurya *et al.*, 2017). Also, COPD was found to be associated with premature ageing via telomere shortening. Córdoba-Lanús *et al.* declared in their study that TL shortening was identified as an accelerated process in smokers and patients with COPD, and this rate of attrition depends on baseline TL length (Córdoba-Lanús *et al.*, 2017). In patients with COPD, different markers are associated with cellular senescence in emphysematous lungs; such hallmarks are defective autophagy, activation of PI3 kinase–mTOR signalling, stem cell debilitation, aberrant microRNA profiles, mitochondrial dysfunction, immunosenescence, epigenetic changes, low-grade chronic inflammation, and decreased anti-ageing molecules; all suggesting accelerated lung ageing in patients with COPD (Claus F Vogelmeier *et al.*, 2017). With ageing, an elevation in basal levels of oxidative stress and inflammation was reported (Savale *et al.*, 2009).

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Figure 1.5. Model of ageing and decline of pulmonary function with time.

Curve A (red) shows normal changes of lung function over time. Curve B (blue) represents a reduced lung growth and consequently, the lung function shows a decrease in the peak level. Curve C (green) indicates a premature decline in lung function. Curve D (dashed red line) shows an accelerated decline in lung function. The horizontal dashed grey line depicts the level where COPD starts to develop (Meiners, Eickelberg and Königshoff, 2015).

1.2.6. Treatments

There is a rising challenge in developing specific treatments for COPD due to the multifactorial risks that contribute to its development (Barnes, 2010). A combination between pharmacological and non-pharmacological approaches are currently applied in the management of COPD. Pharmacological treatments include bronchodilators, inhaled corticosteroids (ICS), combination therapy and long-term oxygen therapy (LTOT). Non-pharmacological options are smoking cessation, pulmonary rehabilitation, mechanical ventilation and lung-volume-reduction surgery (LVRS) (Vogelmeier *et al.*, 2017c). ICS and bronchodilators are the interventions that are frequently prescribed among all the treatments (Barnes, 2011).

Bronchodilators are symptomatic relief medications including β_2 -agonists, which may be short-acting (Salbutamol) or long-acting (Salmeterol, Formoterol), or anti-muscarinic drugs like Tiotropium. Although these medications are able to improve FEV₁ in some patients, their overall effect on enhancing lung function, reducing inflammation and the impact of exacerbations remain poor (Bhome, 2012; Barnes, 2011). Moreover, ICS is also prescribed to manage inflammation in COPD patients. These medications are used either alone or in combination with bronchodilators; however, there is little evidence to support remarkable benefits to COPD patients (Hakim, Adcock *et al.* 2012). ICS administration has slightly significant effects on some important COPD pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-8 and tumour necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), and on MMP levels (Barnes, 2007). GOLD recommends using antibiotics and ICS for symptomatic treatments in patients with COPD exacerbation and whose FEV₁<50% of predicted (Tan *et al.*, 2018; GOLD, 2011; Mackay and Hurst, 2012). Although glucocorticoids are widely and effectively used therapies in treatment of many inflammatory and chronic diseases, in COPD these medications are not particularly effective as in asthma (Barnes and Adcock, 2009). This ineffectiveness was reported to be due to OS that reduces the activity and expression of histone deacetylase 2 (HDAC2), an enzyme which is important for suppressing proinflammatory genes that are activated by histone acetylation (Zhang *et al.*, 2018) OS induces the activation of PI3K- δ , and reduces HDAC-2 expression, thus

suppressing its activity, causing an epigenetic phosphorylation and ubiquitination of this epigenetic regulatory enzyme. Furthermore, the levels of peroxynitrate are elevated in the lungs of COPD patients, these in turn inactivates HDAC-2 activity by tyrosine nitration and ubiquitination (Barnes, 2020a). This effect of OS on HDAC-2 activity prevents the acetylation of glucocorticoid receptors (GR), that is essential for suppressing NF- κ B activity, that suppress the anti-inflammatory effects of corticosteroids (Adcock *et al.*, 2007; Khan *et al.*, 2014).

1.3. Pathogenesis of COPD

1.3.1. Proteases, anti/proteases hypothesis

Proteases also referred to as proteinases are essential enzymes that defend the body against pathogens. Dysregulation of proteases is associated with serious destruction of lung tissues and build-up of inflammation mainly observed in emphysema. In COPD, there is an imbalance between proteases and anti-proteases favouring the proteases over the inhibitor enzymes (Verma, Dixit and Pandey, 2016). This can be of a positive outcome on infection, only if it is perfectly regulated, otherwise the increased level of proteases can cause serious damage to lung tissues. Exposure to CS can induce the accumulation of neutrophils, macrophages and CD8+ T lymphocytes in the airways and alveolar space (Strzelak *et al.*, 2018). Consequently, macrophages and neutrophils are the main sources of proteases in lungs. In COPD patients, an increased number of neutrophils were detected in sputum and peripheral lung airways of subjects with COPD, and this is correlated with an elevated level of neutrophil elastase enzyme (NE) which can impair lung function (Lee *et al.*, 2015). Thus, the hyper activated neutrophils produce an excessive level of NE that overwhelms the activity of serine proteases inhibitors causing the development of emphysema.

Matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), are one of the important families of proteases that are implicated in the pathophysiological changes in COPD. MMPs were detected at a high level in many lung diseases including COPD. The main mechanism of these enzymes is to cleave

structural proteins such as elastin and collagen that have an important role in COPD pathogenesis (Johnson, 2016). Various MMPs were detected in smoking-related emphysema, most importantly: MMP-7, MMP-9, and MMP-12. These MMPs are detected in a high level and are found to degrade elastin (Gharib, Manicone and Parks, 2018). Pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β trigger the release of MMP-9 and NE from activated macrophages and neutrophils respectively from COPD patients (Gramegna *et al.*, 2017).

1.3.2. Oxidant-antioxidant imbalance

The imbalance between oxidants and anti-oxidants is a major factor that can cause pathophysiological changes in the lung that promotes COPD development (Van Eeden and Sin, 2013). Oxidative stress is generated when the body is unable to produce enough anti-oxidants to neutralise oxidant levels that are generated by reactive oxygen species (ROS) caused by environmental challenges (e.g. air pollution, cigarette smoking, occupational exposure (Fischer, Voynow and Ghio, 2015a). OS was found to be further increased during exacerbation. Amplification of OS reduces the expression of antioxidant enzymes such as SOD2 and catalase, mainly due to the impaired activation of Nrf2 transcription factor that regulates expression of antioxidant genes (Liu, Gao and Ci, 2019).

During OS, generated ROS causes an oxidative decomposition of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), which in turn initiates chain reactions that lead to the formation of a variety of reactive carbonyl species. Among them, 4-hydroxy-trans-2-nonenal (4-HNE) is an aldehyde that consequently react by the so-called Michael addition mechanism with cysteine, histidine and lysine residues in proteins, to establish relatively stable adducts known as advanced lipid peroxidation end products (Houghton, 2012; Miyazawa *et al.*, 2012; Nakamura, Cho and Lipton, 2012). The 4-HNE modified proteins have been found in the lung of smokers and COPD patients (Liochev, 2013; Neves, 2013).

There are two main sources of oxidants that are involved in damaging the lung, these are from endogenous and exogenous source (Figure 1.6). Sources of OS may be single or both exogenous and endogenous (Barnes, 2020a).

1.3.2.1. Exogenous sources of ROS

Exogenous causes of OS comprise ROS produced mainly from CS such as tar. Tar is formed of two main classes of oxidants, the carbonyl and the free radical, both are associated with high damage to the DNA, lipid membrane, protein, and carbohydrate, as well as being highly involved in severe airway inflammation (Wongpaiboonwattana *et al.*, 2013a). Other sources of exogenous ROS are environmental pollutants mainly air pollution involves exposure to NO_x, mainly nitric oxide (NO₂), ozone and small particulate matter (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}) generated by diesel exhaust fumes (Adamkiewicz, Liddie and Gaffin, 2020a), and infections that are the result of bacteria, viruses, and fungi (Fischer, Voynow and Ghio, 2015a). Exposure to household air pollution oxidants are vital sources of exogenous ROS, biomass smoke produced from wood and animal dung secretes high concentrations of NO₂ and particulate matter in unventilated houses (Balmes, 2019). The COPD phenotype in non-smokers from Low and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs) was found to be very similar to smoking COPD patients and shared a similar pattern of inflammation (Salvi *et al.*, 2020). This means that chronic exposure to inhaled irritants is a well-known factor for promoting mucosal inflammation mainly driven by OS (Barnes, 2020a).

1.3.2.2. Endogenous sources of ROS

Inflammation and OS generation persist even after smoking cessation in COPD, this is mainly due to endogenous sources of OS (Munakata *et al.*, 2018). The major sources of endogenous ROS are inflammatory responses to inhaled pathogens such as bacteria and viruses, mitochondrial respiration and inflammatory cells. Mitochondria ROS (mROS) are major sources of OS in COPD patients (Birch, Barnes and Passos, 2018). These are produced due to mitochondrial dysfunction in COPD patients that is characterised by leaky membranes due to defects in clearance by mitophagy. Airway epithelial cells from COPD patients promote intracellular ROS production mainly from leaky defective mitochondria (Cloonan *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, airway epithelial cells, macrophages and neutrophils control the endogenous production of oxidants through nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH)

oxidase (NOX₂) enzyme, oxidative burst, and nitric oxide synthase (Miller *et al.*, 2013). The oxidative burst mechanism is expressed via neutrophil-derived myeloperoxidase (MPO) (McGuinness and Sapey, 2017). Some patients with COPD reported increased levels of eosinophils and eosinophil peroxidase is found to be elevated in the sputum of patients with COPD (Kirkham and Barnes, 2013a).

The structural cells in the lungs produce monocyte chemotactic factors that recruit circulating monocytes into the lung, these circulating monocytes trigger the production of high numbers (20–fold compared to healthy) of alveolar macrophages in the lungs of COPD patients (Van Eeden and Sin, 2013). Activated macrophages in COPD patients secrete several inflammatory mediators and generate endogenous ROS including superoxide anions (O₂⁻) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) (Barnes, 2020a). NO_x is the main source of O₂⁻; although O₂⁻ is considered a relatively weak oxidising agent; however, they are rapidly converted to very harmful ROS species such as H₂O₂ and hydroxyl radical, or it is converted to highly reactive peroxynitrite radicals formed when nitric oxide is presented. An increased concentration of H₂O₂ in exhaled breath condensate in patients with COPD was reported (Stefanska *et al.*, 2012). H₂O₂ interferes in several reactions to produce other oxidant species, for example, reactive nitrogen species (RNS) and reactive carbon species (Horiyama *et al.*, 2016).

Neutrophils are recruited at high levels into the lungs of COPD patients. Activated neutrophils from peripheral blood of COPD patients produce ROS mainly during exacerbations (Subramanian *et al.*, 2012). Neutrophils are the main source of MPO that produces very destructive hypochlorous acid that in turn interacts with tyrosine residues in proteins to generate 3-chlorotyrosine. The by-product (3-chlorotyrosine) was found to be significantly elevated in the sputum of COPD patients (O'Donnell *et al.*, 2010a). Marker of OS, 4-HNE lipid peroxidation aldehyde is heightened in the lung of COPD patients, suggesting the production of local ROS within the lung (Rahman *et al.*, 2002a). Moreover, increased level of 4-HNE was detected in the plasma of COPD patients during acute exacerbations (Liu *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, elevated concentrations of a lipid peroxidation product in exhaled breath condensate were found even in patients who are ex-smokers (Zinellu *et al.*, 2016a).

1.3.2.3. Reduction in anti-oxidants

The imbalance between oxidants/anti-oxidants was proposed to be the main driver of COPD pathogenesis. The excessive production of ROS overwhelms the anti-oxidant machinery leading to the generation of OS that promotes COPD development (Kansanen *et al.*, 2013). Nuclear-erythroid 2-related factor 2 (Nrf2, NFE2L2) is a major cellular regulator of cytoprotective responses to OS (Bellezza *et al.*, 2018). It is the master redox-sensitive transcription factor, that controls the expression of several antioxidant genes including NADPH dehydrogenase, heme-oxygenase (HMOX), and superoxide dismutase (SOD)(Li *et al.*, 2022). Nrf2 is highly enhanced in normal non-COPD smokers; however, its activation is reduced and sometimes impaired in COPD patients as a result of an acetylation/deacetylation imbalance favoring acetylation. Histone –deacetylase (HDAC)-2 reduction, causes a reduction in antioxidant gene expression (Mercado *et al.*, 2011a; Barnes, 2020). In COPD, the activity of endogenous antioxidants are impaired amplifying OS in the lungs (Elmasry *et al.*, 2015) (**Figure 1.6. Sources of oxidative stress**Figure 1.6).

Figure 1.6. Sources of oxidative stress

Oxidative stress generated by ROS due to a single source or both endogenous and exogenous sources. (A) Exogenous sources are mainly environmental challenges such as smoking cigarettes and air pollution, whereas (B) endogenous sources are specifically associated with activation of inflammatory cells due to an external pathogen, that activates a plethora of enzymes to cause transport of electrons by NOX2 enzyme to generate free radicals and oxidants such as hydrogen peroxide (Aggarwal *et al.*, 2019). Image created by Biorender.

1.3.3. Inflammatory response in COPD

Inflammation is a key feature of COPD that persists even after smoking cessation. COPD pathogenesis includes elastase/anti-elastase imbalance, chronic inflammation, and the imbalance between oxidants and anti-oxidants, apoptosis and insufficient repair (Shapiro and Ingenito, 2005; King, 2015). Inflammation that is generated by cigarette smoking is an important driver of COPD. The proposed mechanism involves the production of elevated levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines and chemokines, and these have been detected in the serum of COPD patients (Shen *et al.*, 2011). An increase in inflammatory cytokines and inflammation pathways involves neutrophils, T-lymphocytes, B-lymphocytes, and macrophages in lung alveoli and small airways (Fischer, Voynow and Ghio, 2015c). In COPD patients, neutrophils were detected to have an elevated level in both sputum and bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) fluid (Zhu *et al.*, 2014).

1.3.3.1. Role of neutrophils in COPD

Neutrophils are responsible for the secretion of a number of serine proteases including proteinase-3, cathepsin G, and Neutrophil elastase (NE), together with matrix metalloproteinase (MMP)-8 and MMP-9, which can cause serious destruction to the alveolar structure (Singh, 2015). Moreover, when neutrophil chemotactic factors IL-8 and leukotriene B4 (LTB4) are present, neutrophils are able to migrate to the respiratory tract where their survival is prolonged by cytokines, specifically granulocyte colony-stimulating factor (CSF) and granulocyte–macrophage (Lin and Fessler, 2021). Smoking cigarettes enhances the retention of neutrophils in the lung. High concentrations of granule proteins (myeloperoxidase and neutrophil lipocalin) are responsible for the transportation and activation of neutrophils in the airways of the patients with COPD (Aggarwal *et al.*, 2019). Also, neutrophils induce significant damage in the lung tissue by secreting oxidants.

1.3.3.2. Association of macrophages with COPD development

In patients with COPD, macrophages were found to rise markedly 5 to 10 times in airways, lung parenchyma, sputum, and BAL fluid (Meshi et al., 2002; Aggarwal et al., 2019). The level of secreted macrophages can be an indication of the stage and severity of COPD. Inflammatory factors including monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 (MCP-1), LTB₄, TNF- α , IL-8, and ROS can facilitate the development of cellular responses to smoking and inflammation in COPD disease. Also elastolytic enzymes, such as MMP-12, MMP-9, MMP-2, NE, cathepsins K, L, and S are highly produced by alveolar macrophages (Russell et al., 2002; Aggarwal et al., 2019). Among all elastolytic enzymes, MMP-9 is the most dominant secreted elastolytic enzyme in patients with COPD (Gramegna et al., 2017). In addition to elastases, activated NF- κ B is responsible for the over-expression and upregulation of inflammatory proteins in alveolar macrophages (Caramori et al., 2003; Aggarwal et al., 2019), and elevated levels of MCP-1 was reported in sputum and BAL in patients with COPD.

1.3.3.3. T-lymphocytes enhance the development of COPD

Significant increases in T-lymphocyte levels have been detected in lung parenchyma, with CD8⁺ cells (T_c1) showing higher elevation as compared with CD4⁺ cells (T_H1). This is linked to alveolar destruction and to the severity of airflow obstruction (Fischer et al., 2015). Tc1 (interferon- γ) subtype is the key player of T-cells in COPD airways and higher levels of T_c1 were detected in smokers with COPD compared to asymptomatic smokers (Ravensberg et al., 2013). CD8⁺ cell numbers are found to be amplified in patients with airway infections, and it is found that bacterial colonization in the lower respiratory tract of COPD patients is responsible for this inflammatory response (Barnes, 2016).

In patients with COPD, epithelial cells and macrophages release chemokines CXCL9, CXCL10, and CXCL11 which their levels are elevated in COPD patients. CXCL10 is highly expressed by bronchiolar epithelial cells, and this could be the reason behind the accumulation of CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells that express CXCR3 receptor (Saetta et al., 2002;

Barnes, 2016). These chemokines activate CXCR3 receptor on T_H1 and T_C1 cells which releases INF- γ that in turn induces the release of further chemokines (Figure 1.7) (Costa *et al.*, 2008; Barnes, 2017). T_C1 cells are considered cytotoxic cells because they release perforin and granzyme B and TNF- α , which can cause cytolysis and apoptosis of alveolar epithelial cells which can contribute to the development of emphysema (Majo, Ghezzi and Cosio, 2001; Barnes, 2017).

Various protein biomarkers involved in inflammation are presented in Figure 1.7 & Table 1.3. Protein biomarkers involved in COPD inflammation. List of known proteins that are highly involved in COPD development, alongside their function, how these cytokines are associated with COPD development and the references. Adapted from (Aggarwal *et al.*, 2019).

Table 1.3. Protein biomarkers involved in COPD inflammation. List of known proteins that are highly involved in COPD development, alongside their function, how these cytokines are associated with COPD development and the references. Adapted from (Aggarwal *et al.*, 2019)

Protein Biomarker	Function	Associated with COPD	Reference
Haptoglobin	Inhibit heme release from globin. Induces differentiation of fibroblast progenitor cells into lung fibroblasts	Involved in remodeling and fibrosis in COPD	(Verrills <i>et al.</i> , 2011)
α2-Macroglobulin	Binds host or foreign peptides and particles. Serves as a humoral	Airway secretions as a marker of plasma exudation, and is increased in sputum samples in COPD	(Verrills <i>et al.</i> , 2011)

	<p>defence barrier against pathogens in the plasma and tissues.</p> <p>Interacts with and captures virtually any proteinase including serine, cysteine, aspartic, and metalloproteinases, function as a unique “pan-proteinase inhibitor.” α2-Macroglobulin provides negative feedback on the inflammatory response by inhibiting thrombin (coagulation) and plasmin (fibrinolysis)</p>		
Surfactant protein-D	<p>Calcium-binding glycoprotein, member of the collectin family. Regulator of innate immunity capable of</p>	<p>Associated with an increased risk of exacerbation. Increased in COPD</p>	<p>(Zien Alaabden <i>et al.</i>, 2016)</p>

	binding pathogens and facilitating phagocytosis		
club cell secretory protein (CCSP-16)	Anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties in the lung.	Very stable and robust biomarker in plasma. Low serum CC16 was associated with a faster subsequent decline of forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV1)	(Guerra <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
Pulmonary and activation-regulated chemokine (PARC/CCL-18)	Lung-predominant inflammatory protein. Expressed by monocytes	CCL-18 levels were elevated and associated with increased mortality in COPD associated with reduced FEV1, lower exercise capacity	(Kodera <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
C-reactive protein (CRP)	Production is part of the nonspecific acute-phase response to Most forms of inflammation,	Increased CRP levels are associated with poor lung function, reduced exercise capacity and worse quality of life and	Broekhuizen <i>et al.</i> (2006)

	infection, and tissue damage	significant predictor mortality in COPD.	
Interleukin-6 (IL-6)	Inflammatory response to environmental stress such as smoking. It has pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory properties. It is secreted by epithelial cells, CD4 ⁺ , CD8 ⁺ T-cells Macrophages, it activates NK cells, Th17 and Tc17	Serum and bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) levels of IL-6 are increased during exacerbations of COPD	Pourfarzam et al. (2009)
Interleukin-8 (IL-8) (also called CXCL8)	Chemokine with potent chemoattractant properties for Neutrophils. It activates neutrophils, monocytes, NK cells, Th1, Tc1	Increased in patients with COPD. Secreted by epithelial cells and macrophages	Barnes (2008b)
Tumor necrosis factor-α (TNF-α)	Proinflammatory cytokine primarily	Essential in the pathogenesis of COPD by promoting	Gueders et al. (2006)

	produced by activated macrophages	and maintaining the expression and the release of various Proinflammatory mediators, leading to tissue damage and remodelling.	
Adrenomedullin	Vasodilatory bactericidal, and anti-inflammatory activities	Help in differentiating between exacerbation and the stable phase, suggesting that it is an effective biomarker to confirm COPD exacerbation. Levels markedly increase at exacerbation and decrease significantly in the stable phase.	Meng et al. (2014a)
Transforming growth factor-beta (TGF-β)	It is secreted by epithelial cells and macrophages and it	Stimulate fibrosis formation in the small airways , also induces	(Barnes, 2009)

	activates fibroblasts proliferation	proinflammatory cytokines secretion	
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Figure 1.7. Inflammatory cells and protein mediators play an important role in the pathophysiological changes in COPD.

Inflammation is a central component of COPD. Cigarette smoke triggers immune cells to produce a plethora of cytokines, proteases, lipid mediators and chemokines. This can lead to the development of the pathophysiological features of the disease including fibrosis, emphysema, excess mucus production and airway limitation Adapted from (Barnes, 2009).

1.3.3.4. COPD-inflammation related biomarkers

Identification of biomarkers that are correlated with COPD development helps in understanding all the fundamental mechanisms associated with COPD, and thus developing new therapeutic approaches for effective treatment of COPD. A range of COPD biomarkers have been identified so far, which were identified from gene expression profiling of the lung

tissue (Shaw *et al.*, 2014) and factors present in blood and sputum. Many clinical studies found increased levels of pro-inflammatory mediators, such as TNF- α , transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β), interleukin IL-6, IL-8 and IL-1 β , in the serum of patients with COPD when compared with healthy individuals (Peter J. Barnes, 2009). Sputum concentration of IL-8 (Yamamoto *et al.*, 1997), IL-6 (Zhu *et al.*, 2014), neutrophil (Singh *et al.*, 2010) and different pro-inflammatory cytokines were identified at higher levels in patients with COPD compared with the control.

Other potential target blood biomarkers were also recognised including C-reactive protein (CRP) (Broekhuizen *et al.*, 2006), neutrophil elastase (Nikolakopoulou *et al.*, 2014), white blood cell count (Koo *et al.*, 2017), surfactant protein-D (Peck *et al.*, 2018), and pulmonary and activation-regulated chemokine/CCL-18 (Sin *et al.*, 2011).

4-HNE has been found in the lungs of smokers and COPD patients, this can stimulate the release of IL8 and transforming growth factor TGF- β in the lung (MacNee, 2005; (Van Eeden and Sin, 2013)). Increased levels of IL-6, IL-8 and TNF- α levels were detected in sputum from COPD patients, correlating with disease severity (Sinden *et al.*, 1996; Barnes 2004; Daldegan, Teixeira *et al.*, 2005; Galli, Tsai *et al.*, 2008; El-Shimy *et al.*, 2014b). In addition, redox-sensitive transcription factors such as NF- κ B and activator protein 1 (AP-1) are regulated by ROS (Kirkham and Rahman 2006). NF- κ B regulates many inflammatory genes that have been found to be activated by OS, and their expression is increased subsequently in smokers and COPD patients (Di Stefano, Caramori *et al.*, 2002; Edwards, Bartlett *et al.*, 2009). Together, inflammation and ROS production can promote pathophysiological changes correlated to COPD (Zong, Ouyang and Chen, 2015).

1.4. The NF- κ B inflammatory pathway

The nuclear-factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells (NF- κ B) is a key transcription factor that plays an essential role in regulating and controlling DNA transcription, cytokine production and cell survival (Oeckinghaus and Ghosh, 2009; Liu *et al.*, 2017a). The

NF- κ B transcription factor consists of homo and heterodimer proteins classified in two families, the REL family (c-REL, p65/RELA and RELB) and the NF- κ B subfamily proteins (p100 and p105). Upon activation, the NF- κ B proteins are cleaved (p100 to p52 and p105 to p50), following post-translational modification (PTMs) (Dorrington and Fraser, 2019). NF- κ B is considered a master regulator of inflammation in COPD, and is highly expressed during exacerbations (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2021). NF- κ B is found in the cytoplasm in an inactive form, and it is activated by two signalling pathways, the classical (canonical) and the alternative (non-canonical) pathways activation induced by several stimuli including free radicals, cytokines, heavy metals, irradiation, bacterial and viral infection, that target a distinct spectrum of genes. It plays a significant role in regulating the immune responses in infection and it is highly involved in the innate and adaptive immune system (Dorrington and Fraser, 2019).

1.4.1. The classical pathway

In non-stimulated cells, the NF- κ B heterodimer (p65/RELA and p50 subunits) are located in the cytoplasm in an inactive state due to their interaction with the inhibitory I κ B α protein (Zhang and Sun, 2015). The binding of an inflammatory stimulus such as LPS or TNF- α to its receptor leads to a phosphorylation cascade resulting in activation of I κ B kinase complex (IKK) which consists of three subunit, IKK α , IKK β and IKK γ /NEMO that is considered as regulatory molecule (Hinz and Scheidereit, 2014). The IKK complex phosphorylates I κ B α which is targeted for ubiquitination and degradation by proteasomes. Degradation of I κ B α allows the translocation of the NF- κ B p65/50 dimer into the nucleus where it binds to promoter regions of inflammatory genes (Lingappan, 2018). The classical pathway is usually activated by ligands such as LPS, IL-1 β and TNF- α (Liu *et al.*, 2017b)(Figure 1.8).

Figure 1.8. Activation of NF-κB canonical pathway.

The binding of inflammatory stimuli (LPS) to its respective receptor, triggers the IKK complex to phosphorylate the IκBα subunit of NF-κB, which is subsequently degraded by proteasomes, thus translocating the p65/p50 heterodimer into the nucleus and thereby activating downstream inflammatory genes. Image created by bio render.

1.4.2. The alternative pathway

The non-canonical pathway of NF-κB is usually activated in the adaptive immune system and in the development of lymphoid organs. When stimuli such as lymphotoxin B (LTβ), B-cell activating factor (BCAF) and CD40 L binds to their respective receptors LTβR, BCAFRs and CD40, this induces the NF-κB inducing kinase (NIK) to phosphorylate the IKK complex that is formed of two IKK α proteins and is not linked to the IKKγ/NEMO regulatory molecule (Sun, 2011). The IKKα homodimer phosphorylates the protein complex p100/RelB at the C-terminal

domain of p100 protein. The phosphorylated p100 is cleaved by proteolysis to become an active p52 protein. The newly formed heterodimer complex p52/RelB is translocated into the nucleus to induce transcriptional activation of target genes (Katoh, 2017)(Figure 1.9).

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Figure 1.9. Activation of the non-canonical NF- κ B pathway

Following the interaction of LT β with its specific receptor, NIK triggers IKK α phosphorylation that further phosphorylates the p100 subunit of p100/RelB complex. Following phosphorylation, the precursor p100 undergoes proteolysis to become an active p52 protein. This allows the translocation of p52/RelB complex into the nucleus, triggering the activation of specific target genes (Hayden and Ghosh 2004; Khan *et al.*, 2014).

1.4.3. Role of NF- κ B in COPD

NF- κ B is redox-sensitive transcription factor and it is highly regulated by oxidants (Kirkham and Rahman 2006; Khan *et al.*, 2014). In COPD, it was believed that inflammation is mainly driven by the activation of the NF- κ B signalling pathway (Zaynagetdinov *et al.*, 2016). ROS and LPS, main constituents of CS, were found to induce the activation of NF- κ B in COPD patients (Labonté *et al.*, 2014). Enhanced activation of canonical NF- κ B signaling has been detected in

airway epithelium of COPD patients (Zaynagetdinov *et al.*, 2016). Also, higher levels of activated NF- κ B are observed in the bronchial biopsies and inflammatory cells of COPD individuals (Schuliga, 2015a). It was reported that OS triggers the NF- κ B signalling pathway promoting the expression of multiple inflammatory genes and release of cytokines in airway cells that contribute to COPD development (Rabe and Watz, 2017). In eosinophils, NF- κ B induces TNF- α , IL-8 and intercellular adhesion molecule (ICAM)(Kew and Seniukovich, 2014; Cheng *et al.*, 2016). IL-8 produced by neutrophils is highly regulated by NF- κ B. Also, NF- κ B allows the transcription of granulocyte macrophage-colony-stimulating factor (GM-CSF)(Österlund *et al.*, 2009). Epithelial cells plays a central role in COPD pathology, epithelial cells produces IL-8, IL-6, GM-CSF, MUC5AC in response to various invasive insults such as OS, these inflammatory mediators are modulated by NF- κ B (Paplińska-Goryca *et al.*, 2013). Macrophages, orchestrate the inflammatory events in the airway of COPD patients. OS from CS evoked the amplification of inflammatory responses within the macrophage, which subsequently activates NF- κ B and it is signalling pathway. The activation of NF- κ B in macrophages regulates Monocyte chemotactic protein-1 (MCP-1) and IL-8 inflammatory genes (Shimizu *et al.*, 2011). In smooth muscle cells, NF- κ B controls various regulatory genes that are considered vital in COPD pathology, such as ICAM-1, cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), IL-6, CXCL10 (a chemoattractant for mast cells) and IL-8. Hypersecretion of IL-8 by smooth muscle cells in asthmatic subjects promotes NF- κ B binding to *IL8* promoter region (Clarke *et al.*, 2010; Cheng *et al.*, 2016). Additionally, the neutrophils in the sputum of COPD donors show increased NF- κ B signalling following exposure to CSE (Brown *et al.*, 2009; Schuliga, 2015).

1.4.4. Summary

Environmental challenges such as smoking cigarettes and air pollution contain toxic and harmful compounds that are main sources of free radicals generation and amplification of inflammatory responses that are highly involved in the development of inflammatory diseases and cancer (Li *et al.*, 2014). However, the biological processes underlying smoking-induced diseases are still under consideration and need further investigation. One of the proposed mechanisms is that CS triggers a long-term changes in the DNA sequence (not coded by the

DNA itself) which induces a change in the gene-expression that leads to disease development (Kopa and Pawliczak, 2018). Gene expression is a vital mechanism that defines and expresses a cell function (Lee and Pausova, 2013). The process of gene expression which is the transcription of protein-coding genes begins when RNA polymerase II is recruited to the promoter region of a gene and binds to the transcription start site (Danino *et al.*, 2015); however, due to environmental and inflammatory challenges, the transcription initiation can be inhibited or promoted by changes in or near the gene that can alter gene expression (Silva and Kamens, 2021). Interestingly, CS is one of the most powerful environmental inducers of alterations in DNA sequence (Breitling *et al.*, 2011a) such alterations are known as epigenetic modifications which can be an indicator of smoking related diseases such as COPD (Philibert *et al.*, 2016; Lee *et al.*, 2017).

Environmental challenges such as CS, can lead to permanent changes in epigenetic patterns (epimutations) resulting in development of chronic diseases such as COPD (Jeanmonod, Rebecca and Suzuki, 2018).

1.5. Introduction to epigenetics

Epigenetics is defined as the study of heritable changes in gene expression that are not coded by the DNA sequence itself but by posttranslational modifications to nucleic acids and histone proteins (D. D. Zong, Ouyang and Chen, 2015). Three identified key epigenetic modifications are: DNA methylation, post-translational histone modifications (including histone acetylation, methylation, phosphorylation, ubiquitination and sumoylation), as well as non-coding RNAs. The three subclasses of epigenetic markers are believed to be induced by different factors mainly environmental factors (ROS, air pollution etc.), diet, disease, and ageing-related processes (Yang and Schwartz, 2011).

In an organism, all somatic cells originally have the same DNA sequence, but subsequent mutations accumulate over time, which leads to major phenotypes changes in different diseases including COPD and lung cancers. In addition, recent research data have shown that epigenetic mechanisms have great influence in gene expression, particularly in chronic lung

diseases such as asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Consequently, epigenetic modifications provide a linkage between genetic factors and environmental exposures (Jeanmonod, Rebecca and Suzuki, 2018).

1.5.1. DNA methylation

DNA methylation is a well-defined epigenetic process that regulates gene expression by the addition or removal of a methyl group at the carbon five of the pyrimidine ring of cytosine nucleotides to form (5-MeC), mostly it occurs in cytosine-phosphate-guanine 5'-CpG-3' dinucleotides (Law and Jacobsen, 2010). This DNA methylation mechanism has pivotal outcomes on cellular development and differentiation (Smith and Meissner, 2013). The promoter region of a gene is considered the primary target sequence for DNA methylation in mammals; this mechanism is catalysed by DNA methyltransferase (DNMT) enzyme (Clark *et al.*, 2006) family members. DNMTs are enzymes that catalyse the transfer of methyl groups to cytosine residues in DNA. DNMTs enhance the transfer of methyl groups from the cofactor S-adenosylmethionine to the 5th carbon of cytosine rings (Jang *et al.*, 2017). DNMT1 is thought to be the crucial enzyme that integrates such reactions and its primary role is to ensure the maintenance of methylation processes and stability of the chromatin (Shimoda *et al.*, 2014a). 5-Methyl-cytosine (5-MeC) is a highly conserved epigenetic mark among animals and plants (Law and Jacobsen, 2010). DNA methylation is the key epigenetic modification of DNA in mammalian genomes as it instructs the gene expression machinery where and when the gene should be expressed (Yang and Schwartz, 2011). CpG dinucleotides are concentrated mainly in regions of repetitive genomic sequences, gene bodies and intergenic regions (Yang *et al.*, 2014). CpG sites, also known as CG sites, are areas of DNA where a cytosine nucleotide is followed by a guanine nucleotide in a single linear DNA sequence in its 5' → 3' direction. The cytosine and guanine nucleotides are separated by one phosphate group that links any two nucleotides together in a DNA molecule (Morrow *et al.*, 2016). Repetitive genomic sequences encompass around more than 40% of the genome and gene body methylation within coding sequence is responsible for the crucial role of regulation of gene expression (Jones, 2012). CpG sites are highly conserved within the gene promoter/enhancer regions in

areas known as CpG “islands” (Figure 1.10)(X. Yang *et al.*, 2014). CpG sites that are located within promoter/enhancer regions are usually hyper-methylated, these regions become heterochromatic and this will reduce the ability of transcriptional activators to bind specifically to such regions, resulting in silencing of gene expression (Chodavarapu *et al.*, 2010 ; Shukla *et al.*, 2011). Consequently, the CpG methylation mechanism is essential for gene repression and expression (Wu *et al.*, 2018a).

The mammalian DNA methylation machinery is formed of two main components: DNA methyltransferase enzymes (DNMTs) that are responsible for the addition of methyl groups to cytosine residue promoting hyper-methylation, and methyl-binding proteins (MBP) that play crucial roles in the identification and interpretation of the methylation pattern within gene promoter regions (Loth *et al.*, 2014; Liu *et al.*, 2012). Hyper-methylation of CpG islands is generally associated with gene silencing while hypo-methylation contributes to activating gene transcription (Wongpaiboonwattana *et al.*, 2013; Acquah-Mensah *et al.*, 2012). There are two hypotheses to explain the reason behind gene silencing and transcriptional inactivation via DNA methylation. The promoter region contains specific sites and sequences that allows specific and general factors to bind in order to enhance gene transcriptional activity; these sites are known as transcription factor binding sites and transcription factors are the important elements that bind specifically to these regions to control gene expression. It has been suggested that these transcription factors binding sites interact with the CpG islands or CpG sites, which alters the binding of the transcription factors to their cognate recognition sites (Alelú-Paz *et al.*, 2012). The other potential mechanism relies on the fact that MBPs binds specifically to a methylated DNA via a methyl-CpG- binding domain (Zong, Ouyang and Chen, 2015). MBPs in turn interact with the corepressor Sin3A to induce histone deacetylase 1 and 2 that in turn leads to gene silencing (Wan *et al.*, 2012).

A)

B)

Figure 1.10. Schematic representation of DNA methylation.

(A) In a normal cell, a designated area which can be found within the promoter region of a gene is highly associated with CpG sites (red) cluster in areas known as CpG islands. These sites are randomly distributed upstream and downstream relative to the TSS. (B) (1) Addition of methyl group is known as hyper-methylation and this prevents gene expression. (2) Removal of methyl group is known as hypo-methylation and this is associated with gene expression.

1.5.2. Post-translational histone modifications

The nucleosome, which is the basic unit of chromatin, consists of a short DNA segment wrapped around a core histone protein octamer, made up of two copies each of H2A, H2B, H3 and H4, where the 147 bp DNA is enfolded around, and linked by H1 the linker protein (Bayarsaihan, 2011). Histones are the fundamental protein components of chromatin, and play a pivotal role in gene regulation. Modification of the core histones around which the DNA is wound in the chromosome can alter gene regulation by either enhancing or altering gene expression (Lanzuolo, 2012).

When the chromatin conformation structure is closed, this is associated with suppression of gene expression (Robison and Nestler, 2011). Consequently, transcription of certain genes occurs only when the chromatin structure is in an open conformation, with unwind DNA, to provide a convenient condition for RNA polymerase II to transcribe mRNA from the template DNA. The covalent modification of histones is considered a vital epigenetic mechanism that regulates gene expression (Alelú-Paz *et al.*, 2012). A range of post-translational modifications (methylation of lysines and arginines, acetylation, phosphorylation, ubiquitination, SUMOylation, and ADP-ribosylation) take place frequently at the N-terminal tails (Gallinari *et al.*, 2007). The change of core histone electrical charge results in conversion of chromatin structure from the closed form to the open conformation, and results in either activation or inhibition of gene transcription (D. D. Zong, Ouyang and Chen, 2015). Understanding of the molecular mechanism behind epigenetic modification can be of great benefit in order to explain how inflammatory genes become hyper-activated in diseases such as COPD.

1.6. Epigenetic dysregulation and COPD

1.6.1. Role of DNA methylation in COPD

The main epigenetic changes observed in COPD are aberrant DNA methylation, and histone acetylation/deacetylation (Nedeljkovic *et al.*, 2017). Many recent single gene and epigenome wide association studies (EWASs) proved that COPD is a disease highly related to CS which in turn stimulates an inflammatory response in the lung. In addition, smoking elevates the production of ROS that disrupt normal DNA methylation status (Adcock, Caramori and Barnes, 2011b). This can lead to a series of changes in methylation levels of certain COPD associated genes (Burns and Quibell, 2014). Together, inflammation and ROS production may promote pathophysiological changes correlated to COPD. This suggests that DNA methylation changes due to CS play a vital role in the development of smoking-related illnesses such as COPD (Zong, Ouyang and Chen, 2015).

Certainly, new evidence has emerged to indicate that CS is considerably linked to epigenetic modifications in the bronchial epithelium (Belinsky *et al.*, 2002; Buro-Auriemma *et al.*, 2013; Song *et al.*, 2017), lung tissues (Sundar *et al.*, 2017a), blood cells (Breitling *et al.*, 2011; Wan *et al.*, 2012) and sputum cells (Belinsky *et al.*, 2002; Sood *et al.*, 2010).

DNA methylation is the core epigenetic mark that is investigated in all EWASs exploring specific epigenetic dysregulation in smokers that are diagnosed with or without COPD (Belinsky *et al.*, 2002; Breitling *et al.*, 2011). These published EWASs, that analysed 27 K or 450 K methylation sites, have revealed a clear relationship that altered DNA methylation patterns for a number of genes is mainly due to smoking cigarettes (Monick *et al.*, 2012; Zeilinger *et al.*, 2013). For example, the EWAS reported in 2013 by Zeilinger *et al.* detected a difference in methylation levels of 187 CpG sites between current smokers and never smokers in active smokers a reduction in methylation levels was observed (Zeilinger *et al.*, 2013).

Interestingly, DNA methylation could be used as a biomarker to detect COPD disease because the changes in methylation due to smoking were observed to be a partially reversible process, where the methylation level of former smokers was considered an intermediate level among former smokers compared to current and never smokers (Gao *et al.*, 2015a). However, the reversibility of the DNA methylation mechanism is related to the dose as well as to the time/period of smoking exposure, serving as an important indication that DNA methylation could be a vital mechanism and important biomarker that can be detected for COPD development (Bojesen *et al.*, 2017; Zhang *et al.*, 2012).

Important findings showed that there is a great risk of developing COPD and alteration of lung function due to smoking-related differential methylation signals in peripheral blood (Lee *et al.*, 2017; Machin *et al.*, 2017; Qiu *et al.*, 2012; Sood *et al.*, 2010; Wielscher *et al.*, 2015). One interesting result detected is the hypomethylation of CpG site cg02181506 in the *SERPINA1* gene on chromosome 14, this gene was studied as the main genetic factor which was associated with COPD development (Qiu *et al.*, 2011). Furthermore, analysis of sputum samples from smokers revealed that aberrant promoter methylation of the GATA binding protein 4 gene of *GATA4* or *p16* gene also known as cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 2A, *CDKN2A* gene, was found to be connected with low lung function, and this was associated with an increased risk of developing COPD among smokers (Meek *et al.*, 2015; Sood *et al.*, 2010). In addition, methylation status of the *GATA4* gene in airways can independently predict health status in COPD patients (Meek *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, hyper-methylation of the promoter region of lung cancer-associated genes, such as Sulfatase gene 2 (*SULF2*), was observed in DNA samples extracted from sputum of ex-smokers with persistent chronic mucus hypersecretion (CMH), which is a considered as a clinical phenotype of COPD (Bruse *et al.*, 2014).

Remarkably, the aberrant DNA methylation parameters that are highly associated with COPD also include the overexpression of enzymes involved in DNA methylation such as DNA methyltransferase 1 (DNMT1), DNMT3a and DNMT3b. DNMT1 was found to be the most abundant DNA methyltransferase in mammalian cells, and is considered to be the crucial

maintenance methyltransferase enzyme in mammals (Bayarsaihan, 2011). However, DNMT3a and DNMT3b are *de novo* DNA methylation enzymes. Although little information is known about the relationship between DNMTs and COPD, Liu et al. reported a decrease in DNMT1 expression and an augmentation of DNMT3b expression in human bronchial epithelial cells (HBECs) and normal human small airway epithelial cells after prolonged exposure to cigarette smoke condensate (CSC) (Liu *et al.*, 2010). Alongside this, the repetitive DNA sequence of D4Z4, NBL2, and LINE-1 genes revealed a hypomethylation in HBECs exposed to CSC in a time dependent manner (Liu *et al.*, 2010). Additionally, hypermethylation of IL-12R β 2 and WIF-1 promoter sequences are highly associated with the transition of COPD to lung cancer (Suzuki *et al.*, 2010). However, to understand the consequences of aberrant DNA methylation in various cell types, future research must include functional studies investigating (reprogramming of) DNA methylation in specific cell types (Song, Cano-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2017), which eventually may lead to the discovery of new targets for COPD.

1.6.2. Association of ROS and epigenetic methylation in COPD

In patients with COPD some loci were identified as hyper-methylated and others are hypomethylated (Busch et al., 2017; Wilson et al., 2013). Most important loci that were identified as hypermethylated are the gene components of phosphoinositide 3-kinase (PI3K) and serine/threonine kinase (Akt) (PI3K/Akt) complex and antioxidant Nrf2 pathways (Emily A Vucic *et al.*, 2014). The promoter hypermethylation detected in these genes is associated with a reduction in expression of their gene products respectively. The Nrf2 pathway is an important oxidative stress pathway as it has an anti-inflammatory role and protects against OS (Sekine *et al.*, 2019). Consequently, hypermethylation of promoter areas seems to antagonise important protective pathways that have vital roles in regulating pathophysiology of COPD. On the other hand, the HDAC6 promoter region is associated with the hypomethylation mechanism, and this process was clearly seen to be linked with over expression of HDAC6 in COPD (Mahmood *et al.*, 2013). HDAC6 has been reported to contribute to epithelial dysfunction in COPD patients due to cigarette smoke by promoting autophagy (Jeanmonod, Rebecca and Suzuki, 2018).

Many recent, single gene and epigenome wide association studies (EWASs) have emphasised that COPD is a disease highly related to cigarette smoking (CS) which in turn stimulates an inflammatory response in the lung, as well as elevating the production of ROS that disrupts DNA methylation status (Adcock, Caramori and Barnes, 2011b). This can lead to a series of changes in methylation levels of certain COPD associated genes (Burns and Quibell, 2014). Guzmán et al. detected a high percentage of methylation in the promoter region of cyclin dependent kinase inhibitor 2A gene (*CDKN2A*), that encodes two proteins, the INK4 family member p16 and p14arf, and the O-6-Methylguanine-DNA Methyltransferase (*MGMT*) gene that encodes O⁶-alkylguanine DNA alkyltransferase protein, in induced sputum from patients with COPD compared with healthy individuals; dysregulation of these genes is highly related to heavy smoking (Guzmán *et al.*, 2012). Additionally, Wan et al. stated that dynamic changes in genome-wide methylation and site-specific methylation were found in COPD in response to cigarette smoking, and this may explain why the disease worsens progressively even after cessation (Wan *et al.*, 2012).

DNA methylation can play a vital role in developing pulmonary inflammation; Monick et al. proposed that CS can affect DNA methylation levels in both pulmonary alveolar macrophages and lymphoblasts (Monick *et al.*, 2012). Further studies also posit that levels of DNA methylation are highly correlated with CS and elevated levels of CRP, a biomarker of systematic inflammation, in α_1 -antitrypsin deficient subjects (Morrow *et al.*, 2016). This leads to an important conclusion that CS is a key factor that can increase the level of DNA methylation, which results in the local and systematic inflammation of COPD (Zong, Ouyang and Chen, 2015). The process can be linked to OS. In COPD, OS was found to up-regulate the activity and expression of DNA methyl-transferase 1 (DNMT1), the enzyme which is responsible for the hyper-methylation of DNA promoter regions, this in turn causes a modification in gene expression (Patterson *et al.*, 2012).

One of the main contributors to the pathogenesis of COPD is the hyper production of airway mucus. A main controller of mucus production is SAM-pointed domain-containing ETS-like factor (SPDEF). Silencing the expression of this factor results in a reduction in mucus

secretion. Recently, a paper submitted by Song et al. found that SPDEF was hypomethylated in bronchial epithelial cells from COPD patients after growth at an air-liquid interface (ALI) for 2 weeks, when compared to non-COPD cells. This was correlated with an increase in mRNA expression of *SPDEF* and the downstream mucus-related genes Mucin 5AC (*MUC5AC*) (Song, Heijink *et al.*, 2017). Additionally, when *SPDEF* was silenced using clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats (CRISPR) or Zinc-Finger protein (ZFP), the mucus-related gene expression was successfully attenuated, this promotes further reduction in mucus production in lung epithelial cells (Song, Cano-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2017). This shows that epigenetic downregulation of *SPDEF* has a potential impact to produce a stable effect of mucus reduction, which can be a target for a new therapeutic approach to ultimately cure patients with excessive mucus secretion (Wu *et al.*, 2018b).

In summary, epigenetic modifications such as methylation was found to be heavily associated with COPD development and a gene of interest known as Proteinase-activated receptor 2 (PAR2) is one of the genes that has been extensively studied and has been shown to be heavily involved in promoting inflammation and tissue remodelling in the airways (Kunzelmann *et al.*, 2002; Schmidlin *et al.*, 2002; Unice Jk Soh *et al.*, 2010; Arizmendi *et al.*, 2011; Mark N. Adams *et al.*, 2011; Yau, Liu and Fairlie, 2013). It has been shown to play important roles in asthma (Palikhe *et al.*, 2015), but its role in COPD is still under consideration. There is an evidence that PAR2 promoter methylation might be associated with serious inflammation and result in intensive clinicopathological phenotypes (Tahara *et al.*, 2009) also in proliferation and progression of lung adenocarcinoma (Wu, Xu and Cheng, 2021a). The recognition of the role of epigenetic mechanisms in the development of COPD may identify novel targets that hatch new therapies for patients with COPD (Wu *et al.*, 2018b).

1.7. Proteinase-Activated Receptor 2 (PAR2)

Proteinase-activated receptor 2 (PAR2), also known as coagulation factor II receptor-like 1 (F2RL1) or G-protein coupled receptor 11 (GPR11) is a member of the PAR family that also includes PAR1, PAR3 and PAR4. PARs are seven-transmembrane G protein coupled receptors (GPCRs) (Rothmeier and Ruf, 2012; Yau, Liu and Fairlie, 2013). PAR 1, 3 and 4 are classified as thrombin receptors, whilst trypsin and Trypsin-like proteases (TLPs) activates PAR2 (Whitsett and Alenghat, 2014). PAR2 consists of a central domain formed of seven transmembrane helices joined by three extracellular loops (ECL1-3) and three intracellular loops (ICL1-3). PAR2 is formed of two terminus, an extracellular N-terminus that has a signal peptide and pro-domain, and the C-terminus which is located intracellularly (Hamm, 2001; Carroll *et al.*, 2021b). In contrast to other GPCRs, PARs are not activated by *in vivo* binding of soluble ligands, but they are activated by proteolytic cleavage event, mainly by serine proteases of the extracellular amino terminus at Arg36 (human sequence). The new unmasked amino terminus epitope (SLIGKV in human) acts as a “tethered ligand” (TL) (Ramachandran *et al.*, 2009) that folds back and self-activates PAR2 by direct interaction with the extracellular loop (ECL-2) of the GPCR and/or through binding to PAR2 transmembrane regions (Tm regions)(Figure 1.11); consequently, this mode of activation triggers PAR2 intracellular G-protein signalling pathways (Adams *et al.*, 2011).

Figure 1.11. Mode of activation of PAR2

Serine proteases cleave the amino terminus of PAR2 releasing tethered ligand sequence that in turns bind to the extracellular loop 2 (ECL2) and/or to specific PAR2 transmembrane regions (TM regions), which activates the signalling pathways of PAR2. Image created by Biorender.

1.7.1. PAR2 activation and signalling pathways

PAR2 is the only proteases that resists thrombin cleavage and activation (Mihara *et al.*, 2016); however, PAR2 is instead activated by a host of other serine proteases, mainly trypsin that initiates PAR2 inflammatory signalling (Adams *et al.*, 2011) (See Table 1.4 for PAR2 activators (Heuberger and Schuepbach, 2019a). The main protease of mast cells is tryptase, this protease was recognised as an important mediator of tissue remodeling and inflammation (Marone *et al.*, 2000; Saito, 2005). After protyoltic cleavage of the N-terminus of PAR2 by tryptase, the PAR2 signalling pathway is activated to trigger calcium signalling and proliferation (Vuagniaux *et al.*, 2002; Carroll *et al.*, 2021b).

PAR2 activates different signalling transduction pathways according to the activating protease. When proteases such as trypsin and mast cell tryptase cleave PAR2 (Kaufmann,

Schafberg and Nowak, 1998), signalling through G protein α subunit composed of $G\alpha_{q/11}$, $G\alpha_{12/13}$ and $G\alpha_i$ occurs and this is referred to as the “canonical” pathway (Hollenberg *et al.*, 2014). The activation of this canonical pathway triggers the hydrolysis of phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate (PIP_2) that initiates the Ca^{2+} /inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate (IP_3)/PKC signalling pathway (Böhm *et al.*, 1998; Carroll *et al.*, 2021b) resulting in calcium-dependent extracellular signal-regulated kinase ERK 1/2 pathway activation and subsequent activation of NF- κ B, which induces inflammation. Activation of $G\alpha_q$ takes place when TLPs cleave PAR2, this is followed by calcium mobilisation, activation of mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) and promotes inflammatory responses (Macfarlane *et al.*, 2005a). For example, activation of PAR2 in airway epithelial cells, stimulates the secretion of pro-inflammatory mediators, including interleukin IL-8 and IL-6, which contribute to the development and amplification of inflammation in COPD (Menou *et al.*, 2018).

PAR2 is cleaved by neutrophil elastase (NE) and proteinase 3 (PR-3) (Ramachandran *et al.*, 2011) at a “non-canonical site”, to reveal a distinct TL which triggers the activation of alternative signalling pathways (Gieseler *et al.*, 2013) this is defined as “biased signalling pathway” (Hollenberg *et al.*, 2014). Human NE is able to disarm PAR2 by removing the TL, leaving the receptor unresponsive to other TLPs (Ramachandran *et al.*, 2011). NE can further activate the ERK1/2 pathway independent of calcium increase and β -arrestin interactions, this proposed that it activates MAPK via $G\alpha_{12/13}$ pathway (Zhao, Matcalf and Bunnett, 2014). PAR2 signalling duration is controlled by desensitisation and termination mechanisms pathways. PAR2 is not constitutively internalised; however, β -arrestin-1 and -2 bind to PAR2 following its activation to enhance the endocytic internalisation (Soh *et al.*, 2010). PAR2 then dissociate from the G signalling protein complex and is driven to the internalisation machinery, this process terminates the G-protein signalling pathway (DeFea, 2008). Following internalisation PAR2 triggers the ERK1/2 signalling pathway in the cytoplasm via β -arrestin. *De novo* PAR2 synthesis and the process of intracellular accumulation restores receptor reserve to permit its recycling back to the plasma membrane. Furthermore, the mono-ubiquitination process of PAR2 can mediate its lysosomal degradation (Soh *et al.*, 2010).

Table 1.4. PAR2 activating proteases.

List of known PAR2 cleaving proteases in mammalian and non-mammalian, alongside their sources, origin and major cleavage site. Information were taken from Heuberger & Schuepbach, 2019.

Origin	Protease	Source	Major cleavage site	References
Mammalian	Trypsin	Acinar cells	R ³⁶ S ³⁷	Nystedt <i>et al.</i> , 1994; Nystedt <i>et al.</i> , 1995
	Tryptase	Mast cells	R ³⁶ S ³⁷	Molino <i>et al.</i> , 1997
	Matriptase	Epithelial cells	R ³⁶ S ³⁷	Le Gall <i>et al.</i> , 2016
	Neutrophil elastase	Neutrophils	A ⁶⁶ S ⁶⁷	Ramachandran <i>et al.</i> , 2011
	Chymase	Mast cells Fibroblasts Endothelial cells	G ³⁵ R ³⁶	Schechter <i>et al.</i> , 1998
	Mast cell tryptase	Mast cells	R ³⁶ S ³⁷	Sommerhoff ., 2001
	Proteinase-3	Neutrophils	D ⁶² E ⁶³	Ramachandran <i>et al.</i> , 2009
Non-mammalian	Cockroach E1-E3	Cockroach	R ³⁶ S ³⁷	Polley <i>et al.</i> , 2017
	LepA	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	unknown	Kida <i>et al.</i> , 2008
	PenC	<i>Penicillium citrinum</i>	R ³⁶ S ³⁷	Heuberger & Schuepbach, 2019
	<i>S.pneumoniae</i> proteases	<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	unknown	van den Boogaard <i>et al.</i> , 2018

1.7.2. PAR2 Expression

PAR2 has been shown to be expressed in a variety of cells types including epithelial, smooth muscle cells, fibroblasts, nerve cells and bone cells (chondrocytes, osteoclasts, osteoblasts) as well as inflammatory and immune cells (monocytes, T cells, eosinophils, mast cells) (Santulli *et al.*, 1995; Ramelli *et al.*, 2010; Mark N. Adams *et al.*, 2011; Rothmeier and Ruf, 2012; Yau, Liu and Fairlie, 2013; Crilly *et al.*, 2016; Kandel *et al.*, 2016). The levels of PAR2 can be modulated using a variety of stimuli including cytokines (e.g. TNF- α , IL-1 β) and LPS (Ritchie *et al.*, 2007).

1.8. PAR2 in the airways

PAR2 has been extensively studied and has been shown to be heavily involved in promoting inflammation and tissue remodelling in the airways (Kunzelmann *et al.*, 2002; Schmidlin *et al.*, 2002; Unice Jk Soh *et al.*, 2010; Arizmendi *et al.*, 2011; Mark N. Adams *et al.*, 2011; Yau, Liu and Fairlie, 2013). With regard to lung injury and inflammatory responses, most attention on PARs was focused on PAR2 and PAR1. It was found that lung cells such as alveolar macrophages, fibroblasts, pulmonary epithelium and endothelium express highly PAR1 and PAR2. Moreover, inflammatory cells that are recruited to the lung during inflammation process express these receptors (José, Williams and Chambers, 2014). It has been shown to play important roles in asthma (Palikhe *et al.*, 2015). In human airway epithelial cells (hAEC) studies, production of high levels of IL-8 has been linked to PAR2 expression (Miki *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, PAR2 was found to be able to stimulate inflammatory signalling pathways in bronchial epithelial and smooth muscle cells in the airways (Gieseler *et al.*, 2013). Moreover, PAR2 enhances fibro-proliferative mechanisms that promotes the development of inflammatory pulmonary diseases, including asthma, bronchitis and pulmonary fibrosis. Importantly, it was reported that PAR2 expression levels are enhanced on the bronchial epithelium of asthmatic and COPD patients. PAR2 activation stimulates the release of IL-8, IL-6 and prostaglandin E2 in these cells (Gieseler *et al.*, 2013). PAR2 contributes in the progression of lung fibrosis via the production of IL-8 (Carroll *et al.*, 2021b).

Although PAR2 appears to play a vital role in airways inflammation, some studies reported dual activation of PAR2 in the airways. PAR2 activation can be linked to broncho-protection due to the generation of prostaglandin E2 (Peters and Henry, 2009). Several studies demonstrated using *in vivo* models that PAR2 can have an anti-inflammatory protective role. For instance, broncho-relaxation was observed as a result of PAR2 activation in the airways of LPS-treated rats and in guinea pigs with a histamine-induced bronchoconstriction (Hagras and Kamel, 2022). Different factors can be proposed to explain the duality of roles for PAR2 and this require further clarification. Since a range of proteases cleave the receptor, differences in localisation and site of action of PAR2 in the airway, also the variations between species, all should be considered and could explain the reported functional disparities (Carroll *et al.*, 2021b).

Most of research studies to date have targeted the role of PAR2 in asthma but not COPD, arising the benefit of studying the role of PAR2 in the pathogenesis of COPD. Epigenetic modifications, mainly methylation were heavily studied and investigated in inflammatory diseases and cancer, providing an important insight about the role of epigenetic modification in progression and development of a specific disease. Since COPD is mainly caused by chronic exposure to OS and inflammation, which have also been reported as main factors for epigenetic modifications, in this research work, it was pertinent to investigate whether PAR2 expression is regulated by change in epigenetic methylation due to OS and inflammatory stimulants in a COPD-related models. This could provide better insight about the role of epigenetic methylation in COPD development. Previously only one research paper has provided specific focus and evidence that PAR2 promoter methylation is associated with disease, specifically the severe clinical phenotypes of Ulcerative Colitis (UC) (Tahara *et al.*, 2009). This study demonstrated through the use of mucosal specimens from patients suffering from the two different subphenotypes of UC as well as healthy individuals, that DNA methylation status of the PAR2 gene promoter in rectal mucosa correlates with more severe various clinical phenotypes of UC (Tahara *et al.*, 2009). The concepts that were presented in this paper will here be tested in lung epithelia cells (BEAS-2B cells and primary human

epithelial cells from healthy and COPD individuals), and the results will provide hopefully better insight about whether PAR2 methylation has a direct impact or influence in the development of COPD as a response to various stimulants (cytokines or OS).

In possible support of the above, a very recent finding reported that PAR2 hypomethylation regulates PAR2 by enhancing its gene expression, and in turn promotes Lung adenocarcinoma cell cancer cell proliferation, progression, migration and invasion (Wu, Xu and Cheng, 2021a). In this research work, it was hypothesised that OS and inflammatory stimulants can induce a differential change in PAR2 promoter methylation levels which can induce a change in *F2RL1* gene expression that impacts the development of COPD. Accordingly, it was believed that OS and inflammatory stimulants should induce PAR2 promoter hypo-methylation which enhances PAR2 gene expression and this can influence the level of inflammation, a hall mark in lung diseases such as COPD.

Better recognition of the role of epigenetic mechanisms in the development of COPD may identify novel targets that hatch new therapies for patients with COPD (Wu *et al.*, 2018b).

1.9. Main aim and Hypothesis

COPD is a multi-factorial respiratory disease that is mainly developed due to regular exposure to noxious particles and other pollutants such as CS that leads to the formation of ROS and triggers the imbalance between oxidants and anti-oxidants. Moreover, the imbalance between proteases and anti-proteases, inflammation, genetic alterations and epigenetics modifications can also be main causes of COPD development, accordingly, the central aim of this doctoral work is to understand how chronic exposure to ROS modelled by H₂O₂ alone or in combination with other inflammatory mediators (LPS, TNF- α and TGF- β) influences cell response relevant to COPD lung pathogenesis, and whether these challenges alter DNA methylation levels of the PAR2 promoter region, to reveal potential implications for, and mechanistic insights into, COPD development.

The first aim of this project was to develop an appropriate cellular model for the study of COPD pathogenesis and to establish a simple chronic oxidative stress model *in vitro* using transient, repeated exposure to H₂O₂ alone or in combination to a range of pro-inflammatory mediators (LPS, TNF- α , TGF- β) in order to characterise and compare inflammatory responses in BEAS-2B epithelial cells in a model that recapitulated the inflammatory environment of the COPD lung. Furthermore, to assess a potential transcriptional control of NF- κ B in the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines in this model.

The second aim was to investigate whether findings using the BEAS-2B *in vitro* OS model can be also translated to primary cells (HBEC and COPD-HBEC) using H₂O₂ as an oxidant and LPS as model inflammatory stimulus and to compare the cellular responses of HBEC to COPD-HBEC under key experimental conditions. Moreover, to investigate the role of NF- κ B in oxidative stress-induced inflammation in HBEC and COPD-HBEC.

The Third aim was to use *in silico* analysis to investigate, whether or not, PAR2 gene has potential methylation targets and to identify potential PAR2 transcription motifs within PAR2 promoter region in particular transcription factors that are associated with OS. Furthermore, to investigate if OS and inflammatory stimuli affected the differentially methylated levels of potential CpG islands and individual CpG sites identified within the PAR2 promoter region in lung cells (BEAS -2B cells and human primary epithelial cells) using bisulphite sanger sequencing.

Chapter 2. Methodology

All general reagents and chemicals used were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (UK), Thermo Fisher Scientific (UK), Invitrogen (UK), R&D Systems (UK), Santa Cruz Biotechnology (Germany) and of the highest possible commercial grade, and purity available identified by supplier and catalogue number in each of the individual methodologies.

2.1. Bioinformatic tools

2.1.1. Bioinformatics analysis of *H. sapiens* F2R like trypsin receptor 1 (F2RL1 promoter)

2.1.1.1. Selection of the F2RL1 promoter region

The promoter region is located in the 5' position upstream of the defined gene and it is generally divided into a distal promoter, core, and proximal regions (Xin *et al.*, 2018a). The promoter region is considered as the vital DNA element and it is the basic transcription initiation complex, it is the initial binding site of RNA polymerase II, where initiation and regulation of messenger RNA transcription can precisely occurs (Aneja *et al.*, 2008). The National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/>) was accessed to find PAR2 promoter and gene sequence. PAR2 was detected under the name of *F2R* like trypsin receptor 1 [Homo sapiens (human)], it is located in chromosome number 5 in position q13.3, and has an accession number NC_000005.10.

2.1.1.2. Prediction of CpG islands using Methprimer

By default, a CpG island is defined as a segment of DNA rich in GC and CpG dinucleotides (Xin *et al.*, 2018a); CpG islands can be found usually at the 5' UTR (untranslated regions) of genes and are usually considered as initiation markers of gene expression (Aneja *et al.*, 2008). In this study, MethPrimer (Li and Dahiya, 2002) bioinformatics software was used to predict CpG islands in the promoter region of the *F2RL1* gene. Methprimer software 2.0 (2016 version) was accessed through <http://www.urogene.org/methprimer2/>. The online platform tool predicts CpG islands using a simple sliding window algorithm. The algorithm used by the software slides across the sequence at a specific shift value defining and examining the ratio

observed/expected (Obs/Exp) of CpG and % GC (G plus C) content in a specified window size defined by the researcher. A CpG island is defined as a stretch of DNA sequence that by default has a length of at least 200 bp, with a GC content > 50% and an Obs/Exp ratio > 0.6 of CpG dinucleotides (Gardiner-Garden and Frommer, 1987b). The software was used to predict the CpG sites and islands within 2110 kb *F2RL1* (PAR2) promoter region. The bisulfite specific PCR primers option and CpG island prediction option were used for primer selection designed specifically to amplify Bisulphite converted sequences. PAR2 promoter region was then submitted through the Methprimer software by default parameters.

2.1.2. Prediction of transcription factors using Tfsitescan software

Tfsitescan software was accessed using the link <http://www.ifti.org/cgi-bin/ifti/Tfsitescan.pl>. Using the default parameter (IFTI Tfsite, 10896 entries, 7/30/11) and Tfsites query parameters: Mammalian sites, the promoter sequence was submitted and analyzed through the online platform. A list of transcription factors appeared and transcription factors of interest were picked from the list and aligned specifically in their positions within the *F2RL1* (PAR2) promoter region.

2.1.3. Detection of transcription factors binding profiles by JASPAR software

JASPAR software was accessed using the following link <http://jaspar.genereg.net/>, it is a database used to detect transcription factor binding profiles (sites). Results for the transcription factor binding sites appeared as a sequence logo that shows the most frequent base pair in each site. The detected site was aligned with the matching sequence within the *F2RL1* promoter region.

2.2. Cell culture

2.2.1. BEAS-2B cells

BEAS-2B (Human Bronchial Epithelial Cells) were from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC 30-2004, VA, USA). BEAS-2B cells are a broncho epithelial cell line established and isolated from normal human bronchial epithelium obtained from the autopsy of a healthy (non-cancerous) individuals. These cells were transformed by an adenovirus 12-SV40 virus hybrid (Ad12SV40). BEAS-2B maintain typical epithelial morphology and many epithelial functional characteristics (Han *et al.*, 2020). These cells are immortalized, this means that they have been artificially manipulated to proliferate indefinitely and can be grown for prolonged periods *in vitro*.

BEAS-2B cells grow in complete growth media prepared as following: 500 ml RPMI medium 1640 (1X) RPMI Gluta MAX (Gibco, 61870-010), 50 ml of 10 % (v/v) foetal bovine serum (FBS) (Gibco, 1891415), 5 ml 1X Penicillin- Streptomycin (Gibco, 15140122). However, some experiments were performed without serum, or with different serum concentrations (2.5 %, 5 % and 7 % (v/v)).

Cells were thawed in a 37 °C water bath, transferred to a falcon tube with 15 ml warm complete media and centrifuged at 1400 rpm for 5 minutes, then the media was removed and cells were re-suspended in a fresh complete medium and introduced into a T75 (75 cm²) flask, incubated at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5 % CO₂. Cells were checked next day in order to ensure adherence, and media replaced with fresh warm complete media in order to remove dimethyl sulfoxide DMSO (v/v) (Invitrogen, D12345). Confluency of cells was checked after two days; when cells reached 80% confluency, complete medium was removed and discarded, then cells were washed 2x with warm Phosphate Buffer Saline PBS (1X, with no calcium chloride and magnesium chloride)(Gibco, 2007945). Trypsin-EDTA (0.25%) (v/v) (Sigma, T4049-100 ml) was used to detach the cells and they were incubated for 5 minutes at 37 °C with 5 % CO₂. Cells were then re-suspended in complete growth medium to a volume

required to neutralise the trypsin (2x media to trypsin) and spun down at 1400 rpm for 5 minutes. Medium was removed and the cell pellet was re-suspended in complete growth medium. Complete fresh medium (10ml) was then added to T-75 flasks and incubated at 37°C with 5 % CO₂ until next passage; cells were sub-cultured using appropriate dilutions.

Furthermore, cells were frozen in a media prepared as following: 1 ml of complete growth medium with 10% DMSO (v/v) of complete media. After trypsinisation, cells were counted and frozen between 1 and 1.5 x10⁶ cells/ml of freezing medium in cryovials, kept overnight in a -80°C freezer surrounded by isopropanol in order to achieve optimal 1-2 °C/min cooling rate, and in the next day were transferred to liquid nitrogen. Cells were routinely seeded in T-75 cm² flasks with 10 ml of complete RPMI media.

2.2.2. Cell counting

In an Eppendorf tube, 100 µl of trypsinized BEAS-2B cells (in suspension) was added to 100µl Trypan Blue solution (Sigma, T8154-100ML) to prepare a dilution of 1:2 fold dilution. Trypan Blue was used to exclude dead cells from viable cells. Cells were counted by removing 10µl of cell suspension and placing it in a haemocytometer. The haemocytometer was prepared by placing the cover slip on top with both sides of the chambers were filled by the cell suspension in trypan blue solution (10µl were placed in each chamber). The grid was viewed using 10x objective lens, and the viable cells were counted in each square of the grid. The viable cells seen as bright cells, while the non-viable cells were stained in blue. Cells were counted in one square at a time. Cells that were touching middle line on top and left was included; however, cells touching middle line on bottom and right was excluded from cell counting. Once the square was counted, the other four squares were counted respectively. Cells that are found in the middle square were ignored. The average cell count was calculated according to the following equation:

(Cell count in square A+ cell count in square B + cell count in square C +cell count in square D)

The cell count per (ml) was counted by multiplying the average cell count with the dilution factor according to the following equation= Average cell count $\times 10^4 \text{ cm}^3$ (volume of grooves) $\times 2$ (dilution factor).

2.2.3. Primary human bronchial epithelial cells

Normal Human Primary Bronchial/Tracheal Epithelial Cells (HBEC) (ATCC, PCS-300-010) and COPD Human Primary Bronchial/Tracheal Epithelial Cells (COPD-HBEC) (ATCC, PCS-300-013) were purchased from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC). They were isolated from the respiratory tract tissues of healthy and COPD donors. These cells are adherent primary human epithelial cells that maintain epithelial, packed cuboidal morphology. They were purchased as 1 ml vials with $\geq 5.0 \times 10^5$ cells per vial. When grown in Airway Epithelial Cell Basal Media supplemented with Bronchial/Tracheal Epithelial Cell Growth Kit components (PromoCell, c-21160) provide an ideal cell system to propagate bronchial/tracheal epithelial cells in serum-free conditions. Cells were cryopreserved at the second passage to ensure the highest viability and plating efficiency.

The complete growth media is composed of: airway epithelial growth medium (Promocell, c-21060) it is a serum-free medium optimised for the *in vitro* cultivation of epithelial cells. This is a ready-to-use media which means it contains all the growth factors and supplement mix (PromoCell, C-39165) that are necessary for the optimal growth of human airway epithelial cells (Table 2.1).

Table 2.1. Bronchial epithelial cell growth kit

Growth factors and supplements	Final supplement concentrations (after addition to the medium)
Size Bovine Pituitary Extract	0.004 ml/ml
Epidermal Growth Factor (recombinant human)	10 ng/ml
Insulin (recombinant human)	5 µg / ml
Hydrocortisone	0.5 µg / ml
Epinephrine	0.5 µg / ml
Triiodo-L-thyronine	6.7 ng / ml
Transferrin (recombinant human)	10 µg / ml
Retinoic Acid	0.1 ng / ml

Antimicrobial optional media supplement 5 ml of (1X) Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco, 15140122) and 5 ml of Amphotericin B (Gibco, 1978734) were added respectively to the complete growth media.

Human primary epithelial cells (cells from healthy or COPD donors) were thawed by gentle agitation in a 37°C water bath. Cells (5×10^5) were seeded into a T-25 flask (25 cm²) (Corning by Life Sciences, 34519013) with 5 ml pre-warmed complete growth media and incubated at 37 °C, 5 % CO₂. Medium was changed every two days until cells were approximately 80 % confluent and ready to be passaged. Cells were usually passaged when the culture has reached approximately 70% to 80% confluence. Trypsin-EDTA (ATCC, PCS-999-003) and the Trypsin Neutralizing Solution (ATCC, PCS-999-004) were specifically used for the dissociation of primary cells. For each flask, cells were rinsed with PBS (3 to 5 times) to remove any residual medium, and 1-2 ml of Trypsin-EDTA was added to each 25 cm². Cells were incubated for 5 min at 37 °C, 5 % CO₂, then observed under the microscope. When cells were separated from each other and rounded up, the flasks were gently tapped to promote detachment of the cells from the flask surface. When the majority of cells were detached, an equal volume of the

Trypsin Neutralising Solution was added to the flask followed by gentle pipetting the culture to ensure all of the trypsin-EDTA solution had been neutralised. The culture was centrifuged at 1400 rpm for 5 min, the neutralised dissociation solution was aspirated from the cell pellet and cells were re-suspended in 2 to 8 ml fresh, pre-warmed, complete growth medium before further dilution for subculture.

Primary cells freezing medium was prepared as following: 700 μ l of complete growth medium with 200 μ l FBS and 200 μ l DMSO. Cells were counted and frozen at 5,000 viable cells per cm^2 , they were kept overnight at -80°C , and in the next day were transferred to liquid nitrogen. Cells were routinely seeded in T25 cm^2 flasks with 5 ml complete growth media.

2.3. Treatment of BEAS-2B cells and human primary epithelial cells with pro-inflammatory mediators and oxidative stress

BEAS-2B cells, HBEC and COPD-HBEC were seeded at a density of 3×10^4 cells/well in 200 μ l culture media one day prior to exposure to reagents. BEAS-2B cells were treated with different concentrations of TNF- α , TGF- β (2.5-20 ng/ml) and LPS (0.1-10 μ g/ml) with different serum (FBS) concentrations (no FBS, 2.5 %, 5 %, and 10 %). Moreover, primary cells were continuously treated with 500 ng/ml of LPS only. Pro-inflammatory mediators were diluted in complete culture media from the initial stock concentration of each mediator (Table 2.2). Cells were stimulated chronically with different cytokines concentrations for 48 h continuously. At the end of treatments, supernatant was saved for ELISA and cells were collected for further experiments.

Furthermore, BEAS-2B cells were exposed to a range of H_2O_2 (SIGMA, 30 % v/v in H_2O , with initial concentration of 9.8 M) concentrations ranging between 5- 75 μ M for 2 h/day for 3 days in a chronic repeated exposure model in presence or absence of FBS, alone or in combination with TNF- α (10 ng/ml), TGF- β (10 ng/ml) and LPS (100 ng/ml or 500 ng/ml), the latter stimulants were kept in the media in a continuous manner for 48 h. HBEC and COPD-HBEC were treated chronically with H_2O_2 concentrations similar to BEAS-2B cells but only in the

presence or absence of 500 ng/ ml LPS. At the end of this experiment, cell viability was assessed by metabolic activity assay. Also, cells were cultured in 24 well plate at a seeding density of 1×10^5 cells/1.9 cm² in 1 ml complete growth media, supernatants were saved for ELISA and cells were used for DNA and RNA extractions. This model of exposure was referred to as “*standard combined exposure protocol*” (Figure 2.1) and this description of exposure was used consistently in describing the treatments model in this thesis.

Figure 2.1. Standard combined exposure protocol.

BEAS-2B cells, HBEC and COPD-HBEC were seeded 24 h prior the treatments. Cells were exposed to H₂O₂ alone or in combination with inflammatory mediators (LPS/TNF-α and TGF-β) for 2h/day for 3 days in a chronic transient repeated exposure manner. In case of combined treatments, after the 2h/day, combined treatments were removed and replaced with inflammatory mediators, so the inflammatory mediators were always there. Along side with the combined treatments, cells were treated continuously with inflammatory mediators for 48 h (2 days).

Table 2.2. Cytokines used for stimulations

Cytokine	Initial mass	Re-suspended concentration	Manufacture
Recombinant Human (TNF- α)	5 μ g	100 μ g/ml	R&D SYSTEMS, 210-TA-020
Recombinant Human (TGF-β)	5 μ g	100 μ g/ml	R&D SYSTEMS 7754-BH-005
Lipopolysaccharide (LPS)	Provided as a 0.2 μ m filtered aqueous solutions	1 mg/ml	SIGMA L3012-5MG

2.4. Cell viability assays

2.4.1. Metabolic activity assay

Cell viability was indirectly calculated by measuring cell mitochondrial activity. The assay used in this work was methylthiazolyldiphenyl-tetrazolium bromide (MTT) assay (Sigma, MKCF0652), this is a colorimetric assay used to measure cellular metabolic activity as an indication of cell viability. MTT reagent was prepared by dissolving 5 mg of MTT powder in 1 ml of PBS. The reagents were mixed by vortex to ensure that the MTT reagent was totally dissolved in PBS then this was filtered using 0.22 μ m syringe-driven filters (JetBiofil, 131218-150) to sterilise the solution. Prior to add MTT reagent, supernatant was removed, and cells were washed with pre-warmed PBS. PBS was aspirated and cells were incubated with 10 μ l of MTT reagent in 90 μ l pre-warmed media with no FBS at 37°C and 5% CO₂ for 4 h. At the end of the incubation 80 μ l of 10% sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) (Sigma-Aldrich, L3771-25G) was added to BEAS-2B cells to lyse the cells and they were incubated overnight to dissolve the formazan crystals to produce a violet colour solution.

Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) solution (10%) was prepared by dissolving 10g of SDS powder (Sigma-Aldrich, L3771-25G) in 88 µl of 10 M hydrochloric acid solution (HCL) (Sigma-Aldrich, 7647-01-0) and 100 ml of distilled water.

In case of primary cells, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) (Sigma-Aldrich, SHBM2271) worked the best to lyse the cells and for solubilising formazan crystals. After 2-3 h incubation, the MTT reagent was removed and 80 µl of DMSO solubilizing solution was added, then incubated for 30 min at 37°C until cells have lysed and purple crystals have dissolved. The reduction reaction induced a colour change from yellow to purple which is representative of metabolic activity. The absorbance was measured at λ570 nm in a plate reader (BioTeK) using GENE5 software. The absorbance of the violet colour corresponds to cell viability. Each treated well was normalised to the average of the untreated control (cells with no treatments) which was set to 100% viability.

While performing the MTT assay, control (positive and negative which is referred to the vehicle) and blank wells were added to the experiment setup in order to perform the data analysis of the results. Positive control was defined as cells with no treatments and with MTT. This was used to compare the viability of unstimulated cells with the treated conditions. The negative control was added to ensure that there was no contamination within the reagents used (e.g. media or MTT), and this was defined as media (with no FBS) and without cells but with MTT reagent; however, the absorbance reading of the blank (well containing medium only) was subtracted from all samples absorbance. The absorbance readings from test samples (treated cells) was then divided by the positive control (untreated cells) absorbance readings and then it was multiplied by 100 to give cell viability. Blank was added to the plate as the media only (with no FBS) and without MTT. The blank absorbance values were subtracted from all samples as it corresponds to the background absorbance. The formula used to interpret MTT results is below:

$$\% \text{ viable cells} = \frac{(\text{Abs sample} - \text{Abs blank}) \times 100}{(\text{Abs positive control} - \text{Abs blank})}$$

Abs sample: Absorbance of the tested sample

Abs blank: Absorbance of blank (media only with no MTT reagent)

Abs positive control: Absorbance of the control (untreated cells and incubated with MTT)

2.4.2. Trypan Blue exclusion assay

For direct assay of cell viability, BEAS-2B cells were seeded in a 24-well plate at a seeding concentration of 2×10^5 cells /well in 1 ml of complete RPMI media with different serum concentrations and they were stimulated with different insults at different conditions or remained unstimulated (as a control). BEAS-2B cells are adherent cells, therefore, they were re-suspended using 0.25% trypsin (300 μ l /well). Cells were diluted by adding 100 μ l Trypan Blue solution (Sigma-Aldrich) to 100 μ l of cell suspension in a dilution factor of 1:2 (dilution factor of Trypan Blue). As an alternative to a haemocytometer, cells were counted by removing 10 μ l and placing it on a counting slides with dual chamber (Bio-Rad, 145-0011) and cells were counted using an automated cell counter (Bio-Rad, TC 20). Average cell counting was obtained and the percentage of viable cells was calculated as following:

$$(\%) \text{ of viable cells} = \frac{\text{Total number of viable cells per ml of aliquot}}{\text{Total number of cells per ml of aliquot}} \times 100$$

2.5. Measurement of cytokine (IL-6 and IL-8) output from cell supernatant by ELISA

Culture supernatants were assayed for IL-6 and IL-8 content using commercially available enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) according to the manufacturer's specifications using human IL-6 uncoated ELISA kit (Invitrogen, 88-7066-88) and human IL-8 uncoated ELISA kit (Invitrogen, 88-8086-88). Final concentrations in each sample were calculated as the mean of the results; some samples required dilutions in order to fall within linear range of standard curve.

For each cytokine, a microplate 96-well ELISA plate (Greiner bio one, E20103B5) was coated with 100 μ l/well of the appropriate capture antibody (anti-human IL-6 or IL-8) diluted in 1:250 dilution in 1x coating buffer (10x sterile D-PBS prepared by 1:10 dilution in deionised water), the plate was incubated at 4°C overnight. Capture antibody was aspirated and wells were washed three times by ELISA washing buffer and excess liquid was removed. ELISA washing buffer was prepared by using 2.5 ml of 0.05% (v/v) of Tween 20 solution (Fisher Scientific, BP337-500) with 500 ml of 10x DPBS and 4.5 l of deionized water. Wells were blocked for 1 h at RT by adding 200 μ l/well ELISA diluent blocking solution (1% (w/v) BSA, 5% (w/v) sucrose, 0.05% (w/v) sodium azide) prepared by 1:5 dilution of 5x diluent in deionised water.

Recombinant human IL-6 and IL-8 standards were reconstituted in deionized water according to the provided volume that is stated on the label of each standard vial. IL-6 and IL-8 lyophilised standards were reconstituted to a final concentration of 200 μ g/ml and 250 μ g/ml respectively. Serial dilutions (2-fold) were performed starting from the top standard concentration (standard with highest concentration) to prepare 8 serial dilutions in order to make the standard curve. A standard curve was run for each group of microwell strips assayed (e.g.

Figure 2.2). The standard solutions (100 μ l/well) were added to the appropriate wells in duplicate. Cell supernatants were diluted at the proper sample dilution using sample buffer (D-PBS, 0.5 % (w/v) BSA) and 100 μ l/well was added to the corresponding plate wells and incubated for 2 h at RT (or at 4°C overnight to increase sensitivity). Plates were washed three times in wash buffer and detection antibodies were prepared by 1:250 dilution of 250x detection antibody in 1x ELISA diluent and 100 μ l/well of the diluted detection antibody was added to the corresponding plates and incubated for 1 h at RT. The concentrated enzyme horseradish peroxidase (HRP)-conjugated streptavidin was prepared by 1:250 dilution of 250x HRP enzyme (for IL-6 kit) in 1x ELISA diluent or by 1:100 dilution of 100x HRP (for IL-8 kit) in 1x ELISA diluent. Wells were washed up to three times by ELISA washing buffer and 100 μ l/well of Avidin-HRP was added and incubated for 30 minutes at RT. Plates were washed five times by ELISA washing buffer and 1X TMB (3,3',5,5'-Tetramethylbenzidine) solution, acts as a

visualising substrate, was added at a volume of 100 μl /well. The reaction was stopped by addition of 50 μl /well 2N sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) (R&D systems, DY994). A microplate reader (BioTeK) using GENE5 software was used to determine the absorbance (optical density, OD) of each well, read at $\lambda 450\text{nm}$ and also at $\lambda 570\text{nm}$ to account for background noise.

A)

B)

Figure 2.2. Example standard curves for ELISA assays.

For each data set, standard curves for human- recombinant IL-6 (A) and IL-8 (B) were plotted for each group of micro well strips assayed using 4-parameter logistic fit algorithm, actual standard concentrations were plotted on the X-axis and the mean OD at 450 nm was plotted on the Y-axis.

2.6. RNA/DNA extraction and cDNA Synthesis

2.6.1. RNA extraction

BEAS-2B cells and human primary epithelial cells were cultured in 12-well plate or 24-well plate and treated with different insults, cells were harvested at specific time points and RNA was extracted using RNeasy mini kit (Qiagen, 74106) following manufacturer's protocol. Media was aspirated (saved for ELISA) and 350 μ l/well of RLT lysis buffer containing 5% (v/v) 14.3 M β -mercaptoethanol (Gibco, 1359363) was added to each well, RLT buffer was used in order to disrupt the cells. Cells were scraped and transferred into Eppendorf tubes. Cells pellets were stored at -80°C for later use or it was used directly for RNA extraction procedure. Homogenisation was performed by passing the lysate through a syringe and needle. Cell lysate was passed 5-10 times through a 0.45x10 mm needle (BD Microlance 3, 300300) fitted to a

sterile RNase-free syringe (Plastipak, A78 E1085B24). 1 volume of 70 % ethanol (Fisher Scientific) was added to the homogenised samples and mixed by pipetting. Up to 700 µl of lysate with any precipitate that had formed was transferred to an RNeasy spin column placed in 2 ml collection tube and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 15 s. Flow through was discarded and RW1 Buffer (700 µl) was used to wash the column, spin columns were then centrifuged for 15 s at 10,000 rpm. Two consecutive washes were performed by the addition of Buffer RPE (500 µl) to the spin column and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 15 s and then for 2 min. The RNeasy spin column was placed in a new 2 ml collection tube and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 1 min. Spin columns were placed in a new 1.5 ml collection tubes and RNA samples were eluted by adding 50 µl of RNase-free water and centrifuged for 1 min at 10,000 rpm.

2.6.2. Genomic DNA extraction

From a confluent T-75 flask, untreated BEAS-2B cells were collected and DNA extraction was done using Quick-DNA Miniprep Plus Kit (ZYMO RESEARCH, D4086) according to the provided manufacture protocol. Alternatively, BEAS-2B cells and human primary epithelial cells were seeded in 24 well plate, cells were treated with different stimuli (LPS, H₂O₂, LPS and H₂O₂) or remained untreated (as a control). Cells were re-suspended using DNA Elution Buffer according to the initial cell count (< 1 x 10⁶ cells in 100 µl or 1-5 x 10⁶ cells in 200 µl). Bio Fluid & Cell Buffer (200 µl) and Proteinase K (20 µl) were added respectively, samples were then mixed for 10 sec and incubated at 55°C for 10 min when dealing with samples from BEAS2B cells; however, for primary cells, samples were incubated and digested with Proteinase K overnight without affecting the integrity of the DNA and this was performed due to the relatively lower quantities of DNA within these samples.

One volume of Genomic Binding Buffer was added to the digested samples, and these were mixed thoroughly and vortexed for 10-15 s. Samples were transferred to a Zymo-Spin™ IIC-XLR columns in collection tubes and centrifuged at ≥ 12,000 g for 1 min. Collection tubes with the flow through was discarded. DNA Pre-Wash Buffer (400 µl) was added to the spin column in a new collection tube, the mixture was then centrifuged at ≥ 12,000 g for 1 min. g-DNA

wash buffer was added 2x to the spin column, first time at volume 700 µl and second time at volume of 200 µl, each time the mixture was centrifuged at $\geq 12,000 \times g$ for 1 min, and the collection tube was emptied. Spin columns were transferred to clean microcentrifuge tubes and 50 µl DNA Elution Buffer was added directly on the matrix. Samples were then incubated for 5 minutes at RT, then were centrifuged at maximum speed for 1 min to elute the DNA.

2.6.3. Spectrophotometric evaluation of nucleic acid quantity and purity

Spectrophotometric measurements were undertaken to ensure quality and quantity of the eluted RNA and DNA (Nanodrop ND-1000 Spectrophotometer, V3.8.1 software). RNA and DNA ratio values of 260/280 should lie between 1.8 and 2, to be generally accepted as 'pure'. Any value below these indicates contamination from residual extraction compounds such as phenol. For this reason, DNA ratio of 260/280 anything less than 1.60 was avoided in this work because protein contamination can inhibit many downstream applications including bisulfite sequencing. Some of primary cells samples has low 260/230 ratio, samples were further cleaned using spin-columns which improved the ratio. The eluted DNA was stored at -20°C for further applications.

DNase/RNase free water was used to blank the equipment. Using 2µl of sample, the concentration of RNA was determined prior to cDNA synthesis, and the purity of RNA was assessed by the ratio $A_{260}/A_{280 \text{ nm}}$ and $A_{260}/A_{230 \text{ nm}}$. Generally, a ratio of 1.8-2.1 is considered a highly purified RNA.

2.6.4. cDNA Synthesis

Extracted RNA was diluted to the desired concentration in 10 µl using RNase-free water. Precision reverse transcription premix 2 (Primer design, Z-RT-Premix2-48, UK) master mix was used to synthesis cDNA. 20 µl of RT-Premix master mix was dispensed into PCR thin-wall reaction tubes (STARLAB, E4860-0050, Germany) and up to 10 µl of diluted RNA was added to each reaction tube. Samples were incubated and cycled at 42°C for 20 min, in this step the reverse transcription occurred, then at 72°C for 10 min in MyCycler-thermal cycler (BIO-RAD),

the resultant cDNA was diluted to 5 ng/ μ l prior to being diluted and stored at -20 °C for future use.

2.7. Gene expression measured by quantitative Real-Time PCR (RT-qPCR)

Impact of different stimuli on BEAS-2B and human primary epithelial cells gene expression was assessed *via* mRNA level of key human gene markers of oxidative stress (*SOD2*, *CAT* and *NFE2L2*), and inflammation (*IL6*, *IL8*, *F2RL1*, *RELA*, *IL1B*, and *NFKB2*); primers synthesised by Eurofins Genomics, Germany). Primers were picked from peer-reviewed published papers. *GAPDH* and *GNB2L1* were used as housekeeping genes (HKG) with BEAS-2B cells; these were previously reported as appropriate for cells of interest (Khan *et al.*, 2014); however, for primary cells, data for each gene was normalised against *GAPDH* and *EIF* mRNA. An example of dissociation curve of *GAPDH* is shown in Figure 2.3. Primer sequences (forward and reverse) used throughout the experiments are presented in Table 2.3.

Figure 2.3. An example plot of GAPDH dissociation curve

Table 2.3. Primer sequences for HKGs and key human genes of interest used in gene expression experiments

RT Primers (Human)	gene	Forward Primer	Reverse Primer	Source reference of the primers
<i>GNB2L1</i>		CTC CGC CTC TCG AGA TAA GAC	GCA AAC TGG CCA TCT GAG GA	NCBI: 006098.4
<i>IL6</i>		AGG AGA CTT GCC TGG TGA AA	GCT CTG GCT TGT TCC TCA CT	NCBI: NM_000600.3
<i>IL8</i>		AGA CAG CAG AGC ACA CAA GC	ATG GTT CCT TCC GGT GGT	NCBI: NM_000584.3
<i>GAPDH</i>		ACCAGGTGGTCTCCTCTGAC	TGCTGTAGCCAAATTCGTTG	(Diabasana <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
<i>SOD2</i>		ACAGGCCTTATTCCACTGCT	CAGCATAACGATCGTGGTTT	(Li <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
<i>Catalase</i>		TAAGACTGACCAGGGCATC	CAAACCTTGGTGAGATCGAA	NM-001752
<i>NFKB2</i>		GGCTGGTGCTGACATCCAT	CTGCTTCGGGTGTCCTTCTC	(Zhou <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
<i>RELA</i>		GACGACTGCTCTTCCTCCTGTT	TCATCTCCTCCTCTGACACTTCC	(Zhou <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
<i>IL8</i> used with primary cells only		TCTGCAGCTCTGTGTGAAGGTGC AGTT	AACCCTCTGCACCCAGTTTTCT	(Che <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
<i>F2RL1 (PAR2)</i>		GAGCCATGTCTATGCCCTGT	CGATGCAGCTGTTAAGGGTAG	Designed by lab colleague
<i>NFE2L2</i>		CACATCCAGTCAGAAACCAGTG G	GGAATGTCTGCGCCAAAAGCT G	NM_006164
<i>IL1B</i>		CAAAGTCAAAGCGCAAAACA	CTTTATCTGGGGTGTGAGTTAC AA	Designed by lab colleague

2.7.1. Experimental protocol for RT-qPCR

PCR reaction components were prepared according to Table 2.4; components were mixed thoroughly and centrifuged briefly in order to spin down all the components and to eliminate

bubbles. Reaction components (15 μ l) were transferred to MicroAmp Fast 96-Well Reaction Plates [0.1 ml] (Applied Biosystems, UK). Specific cDNA (5 μ l) was added to each reaction well. The plate was sealed with a PCR compatible DNA/RNase/PCR inhibitor free optical adhesive cover (Applied Biosystems, UK) and centrifuged 30 sec on a plate centrifuge (Star Lab Smart Instruments Plate Centrifuge, UK).

Table 2.4. Reaction components for qPCR procedure

Components	Volume per reaction
PowerUp SYBR Green Master Mix (2x)	10 μ l
Forward and reverse primers (1 μl each)	2 μ l
cDNA sample	5 μ l
Nuclease free water	3 μ l

qPCR was performed in StepOnePlus Real-time PCR system machine (Applied Biosystems StepOnePlus Real-Time PCR System; StepOne Software v2.1). The parameters for standard cycling mode (primer $T_m \geq 60^\circ\text{C}$) and for dissociation stage were shown in Table 2.5. All PCR reactions were performed in duplicate, and 5 μ M of each primer was used in 20 μ l total volume, also the concentration of cDNA used in each PCR reaction was 5 ng/ μ l.

Table 2.5. Standard thermocycling mode parameters (primer T_m ≥ 60 °C)

Step	Temperature	Duration	Cycles
UDG activation	50 °C	2 minutes	Hold
Dual-Lock DNA polymerase	95 °C	2 minutes	Hold
Denature	95 °C	15 seconds	40
Anneal/extend	60 °C	1 minute	
Dissociation stage			
Step	Ramp rate	Temperature	Time
1	1.6 °C/second	95°C	15 seconds
2	1.6 °C/second	60 °C	1 minute
3	0.15 °C/second	95 °C	15 seconds

Specific dissociation curve settings were followed while using Applied Biosystem instrument, settings were represented in Table 2.6.

Table 2.6. Melt curve settings (dissociation curve)

Experiment Type	Standard curve
Reagent	SYBR Green chemistry
Reporter	SYBR
Quencher	None
Passive reference dye	ROX
Ramp speed	Standard
Melt curve ramp increment	Continuous

Gene expression was quantified by using delta-delta CT ($\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}$) methods. Quantification of gene expression was calculated relatively against the two HKGs *GAPDH* and *GNB2L1* for BEAS2B cells and *EIF* and *GAPDH* for primary epithelial cells.

2.8. Chloromethyl derivative of 2',7'-Dichlorofluorescein-Diacetate assay for intracellular ROS detection

The ROS Assay kit (Green fluorescence) is a cell-based assay designed to quantitatively measure ROS production in live cells. CM-H₂DCFDA is a general oxidative stress indicator, a derivative of H₂DCFDA, CM-H₂DCFDA is better retained in live cells compared to H₂DCFDA. CM-H₂DCFDA itself is a non-fluorescent compound, it is a fluorogenic probe that diffuses passively into live cells. Under the action of intracellular esterases, the acetate groups of CM-H₂DCFDA are cleaved and its thiol-reactive chloromethyl group reacts with intracellular glutathione and other thiols. This mechanism of action produces a non-fluorescent deacetylated compound H₂DCFDA; however, this compound is rapidly oxidised by intracellular ROS into 2', 7'-dichlorofluorescein (DCF) (Figure 2.4). DCF is a highly fluorescent compound that can be detected either by a microtitre plate reader or fluorescence microscopy.

Figure 2.4. Principle of the CM-H₂DCFDA assay.

CM-H₂DCFDA is a cell permeable probe that penetrates passively into live cells, it is deacetylated by the action of cellular esterases into non-fluorescent compound H₂DCFDA, that it is rapidly oxidized to a highly fluorescent compound DCF due to the presence of ROS.

2.8.1. Cellular CM-H₂DCFDA experimental protocol

CM-H₂DCFDA was purchased in a 50 µg vial (CM-H₂DCFDA, C6827, ThermoFisher Scientific). The work was done in dark as the fluorogenic reagent is highly sensitive to light. The probe was dissolved in 8.6 µl non-sterilised anhydrous dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO, Invitrogen) to yield 10 mM stock concentration solution, this was freshly prepared prior each experiment. A working solution of CM-H₂DCFDA (10 µM) was prepared by diluting the concentrated stock solution of CM-H₂DCFDA with Hanks' Balanced Salt Solution (1x HBSS, Gibco, ThermoFisher

Scientific) with no phenol indicator and with calcium and magnesium, the mixture was protected from light and mixed thoroughly.

Tert-Butyl hydroperoxide ((CH₃)₃COOH, Merck, Sigma-Aldrich) of concentration 100 µM was introduced to cells as a positive control 2 h prior to finishing the experiment. At the end of the experiment, culture media with treatments were removed and cells were washed with 1x HBSS buffer and then incubated with 10 µM of CM-H₂DCFDA for 45 min in HBSS buffer. In each experiment, a few wells were used as a blank where only HBSS solution was added. The fluorescence intensity that results is proportional to the ROS levels within the live cell. The fluorescence of the cells from each well was detected and measured by fluorescence microtitre plate reader (Varioskan Lux plate reader, Thermo Scientific) using SkanIt Software (version 6.0.2, 2019), the excitation and emission spectra were centred at 495 and 525 nm. The parameters were set as shown in Table 2.7.

Table 2.7. Varioskan plate reader settings used during ROS measurement

Parameter	Specifications
Time interval between wells	10 ms
Temperature at start	37 °C
Measurement time	600 ms
Excitation band width	12 nm
Reading Optics	top

The blank (HBSS only) readings were subtracted from all measurements, and fold change between control (untreated cells) and treated cells were determined and data were presented from at least 4 independent experiments as fluorescence intensity (% of control).

2.9. Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) for *F2RL1* promoter region amplification

2.9.1. Primer design

Wild type-specific primers that only amplify unconverted DNA samples from untreated and treated BEAS-2B and primary human epithelial cells were designed manually. Primers were designed in a way that they were placed a few base pairs around the region of interest (not within the CpG island and does not contain any CpG sites). The primer details including (melting temperature) were checked using Thermo-primer analyser through accessing the following link: <https://www.thermofisher.com/uk/en/home/brands/thermo-scientific/molecular-biology/molecular-biology-learning-center/molecular-biology-resource-library/thermo-scientific-web-tools/tmcalculator.html>.

Three different primer sets were designed specifically to amplify each CpG island 1 and 2. Primers sequences and details are shown in Table 2.8.

Table 2.8. Details of forward and reverse primers.

Three sets of primers were used to amplify the two CpG islands within *F2RL1* promoter region.

Forward Primers ID	Primers sequence	T _m °C
F.ISLAND 1 SET1	AATTCTCTAAAGCTTTGGCACTTGG	56
F.ISLAND 1 SET2	GGCCAATTTATCTGGTCTTTCTAAGCTCAC	59.1
F.ISLAND 1 SET3	AATTCTCTAAAGCTTTGGCACTTGG	56
F.ISLAND 2 SET1	GAAGCCCTGTCTGTATCAGTTACCAACCAC	61.8
F.ISLAND 2 SET2	CTCCTGCTATTTGCATTCCAAAGCAGACACC	62.7
F.ISLAND 2 SET3	CTCCTGCTATTTGCATTCCAAAGCAGACACC	62.7
Reverse Primers ID	Primers sequence	T _m °C
R.ISLAND 1 SET1	TGGTAACTGATACAGACAGGGCTTCC	59.8
R.ISLAND 1 SET 2	TGGTAACTGATACAGACAGGGCTTCC	61.9
R.ISLAND 1 SET3	CACTGCAATTGTGGTTGGTAACTGATACAG	59.5
R.ISLAND 2 SET1	GGTTAGGTTTCAGGGAAACCGAAGGAGCAG	63.6
R.ISLAND 2 SET2	CTTGGATGGTGCCACTGCAGGAGAGAGAGG	66.3

2.9.2. Amplification of two CpG islands from untreated BEAS-2B cells (Qiagen)

In order to amplify the two CpG islands that were detected within the 2110 bp *F2RL1* gene promoter region and to optimize the PCR conditions for further experiments, the extracted DNA sample from untreated BEAS-2B cells seeded in a T-75 flask was used as a template for PCR reaction using different primer sets that specifically amplify CpG islands 1 and 2. Lyophilized primers (self-designed, Table 2.8) were purchased from Eurofins Genomics (Germany), and re-suspended by different volumes of nuclease free water according to the initial molecular amount of each primer to yield a concentration of 100 µM per primer. Dilution (1/10) was then done for each primer. The final concentration of primers used in the

preparation of PCR master mix was at 10 μ M. “*HotStartTaq*” Plus DNA polymerase Master Mix kit (Qiagen, 203646) was used to perform the PCR reaction according to the manufacturer protocol. Briefly, kit components (10X Coraload PCR Buffer, dNTP mix, primer solutions and Q-solution) were thawed on ice. PCR reaction components were prepared according to Table 2.9. While performing the experiment, the reaction vessels were kept on ice since “*HotStarTaq Plus*” DNA Polymerase is inactive at RT. A negative control reaction (No Template Control, NTC) was included in each analysis. The NTC contains the same reagents as the reaction for analyses, except that the DNA sample was replaced with the same amount of PCR grade water. In this work it was recommended by the company to use Q-solution. The Q-solution was added to the master mix respectively as an additive that modifies the melting behavior of the DNA and improves the suboptimal PCR caused by templates that have a high degree of secondary structure or high CG content.

Table 2.9. Reaction composition using Qiagen “*HOTSTARTaq Plus*” DNA Polymerase

Component	Volume/reaction	Final concentration
Master mix (10x CoralLoad PCR)	10 μ l	1 x
dNTP mix (10 mM of each)	2 μ l	200 μ M of each dNTP
Forward and reverse primers mix	2 μ l	1 μ M of each primer
HOTStarTaq Plus DNA Polymerase	0.5 μ l	2.5 units/reaction
RNase-free water	variable	-
Template DNA	Variable, according to the concentration of extracted DNA from BEAS-2B cells	$\leq 1 \mu$ g/reaction

The prepared master mix was dispensed into each PCR tube. The DNA template from untreated BEAS-2B cells was added respectively to each individual tubes at concentration of $\leq 1 \mu$ g reaction.

The thermal cycling conditions were programmed according to the optimised manufacture

protocol which are summarised in Table 2.10. An initial heat activation step was performed prior to start of the PCR program, for 5 min at 95 °C. After amplification, PCR products were directly loaded onto a 2 % (w/v) agarose gel without prior addition of a PCR loading buffer and gel tracking dye as the PCR master mix is provided with CoralLoad Concentrate, which contains a gel-loading reagent and gel-tracking dyes.

Table 2.10. Cycling conditions for CpG island PCR (Qiagen)

Step	Temperature	Duration	Cycles
Initial denaturation	95 °C	5 min	1
Denaturation	94 °C	30 s	30 cycles
Annealing	T _m °C = 60 °C	30 s	
Extension	72 °C	1 min	
Final Extension	72 °C	10 min	1
Hold	4-10 °C	infinity	1

2.9.3. Amplification of CpG island 2 of F2RL1 gene promoter region from BEAS-2B and primary epithelial cells (Zymoresearch Kit)

In this work, an alternative kit to Qiagen “HotstartTaq plus” DNA polymerase master mix kit was used. ZymoTaq premix Hotstart DNA polymerase (Zymoresearch, e2004) was recommended to use (Huang *et al.*, 2014) in order to amplify the DNA samples pre and post-bisulphite conversion, also ZymoTaq premix kit uses less DNA concentration per reaction compared to the Qiagen kit and this is useful for bisulphite-specific PCR. After DNA extraction from treated and untreated BEAS-2B and primary epithelial cells (HBEC and COPD-HBEC), PCR reaction using ZymoTaq premix master mix was dispensed to each PCR vessel then appropriate volumes of primers, DNA templates and RNase-free water were added

respectively to a total volume of 50 μ l. The proposed PCR reaction setup that was used in this work is summarised in Table 2.11.

Table 2.11. Zymoresearch kit PCR reaction set-up

Reagent	Volume	Final concentration
Zymotag premix (2x)	25 μ l	1x
Forward and reverse primer at 10 μ M each	2 μ l	0.3-1 μ M
Template	variable: according to the initial concentration of the extracted DNA from each sample	< 200 ng/50 μ l. in this work, 150 ng/ 50 μ l of each sample were used
dd.H ₂ O	up to 50 μ l	
Total volume	50 μ l	

The forward and reverse primer set used in this work was the primer set 1 of CpG island 2 Table 2.12. These are wild-type specific unmodified primers that specifically amplify unconverted DNA (DNA samples that were not treated by bisulphite reagent). Table 2.12 demonstrates the forward and reverse primer sequences that were considered as optimum primers set to amplify CpG island 2 of the *F2RL1* gene promoter region.

Table 2.12. Wild type-unmodified specific oligo primer sequences

Oligo Name	SEQUENCE (5' → 3')
Forward. ISLAND 2 SET 1	GAAGCCCTGTCTGTATCAGTTACCAACCAC
REVERSE. ISLAND 2 SET 1	GGTTAGGTTTCAGGGAAACCGAAGGAGCAG

2.9.4. Cycling conditions for PCR

Similar to Qiagen kit, the PCR reaction was initiated with a heat activation step for 5 min at 95 °C. The PCR reaction was programmed in a thermal cycler according to the optimised cycling protocol in Table 2.13. After amplification, PCR products were directly loaded onto a 2 % (w/v) agarose gel with addition of a gel tracking dye to visualize the DNA bands as the premix is not premixed by a tracking dye. DNA samples were diluted with the 6X TriTrack DNA Loading Dye (Thermoscientific, SM1553, #R1161) by mixing 1 volume of the tracking dye with 5 volumes of the DNA samples.

Table 2.13. ZymoResearch Kit Optimised Cycling Conditions for PCR

Step	Temperature	Duration	Cycles
Initial denaturation	95 °C	10 min	1
Denaturation	95 °C	30 s	35 cycles
Annealing	T _m °C = 66 °C	35 s	
Extension	72 °C	1 min	
Final Extension	72 °C	7 min	1
Hold	4 °C	infinity	1

2.10. Gel electrophoresis

TBE electrophoresis buffer (Thermofisher Scientific, 01196970) was diluted from 10X to 1X by adding 900 ml of de-ionized water (Invitrogen, 10977-049). Alternatively, TBE buffer can be prepared by adding of 108 g Tris base, 55 g of Boric acid, and 9.3 g EDTA to 800 ml of H₂O, the volume were adjusted to 1 l by adding de-ionized water.

The gel (2 %) was prepared by adding 2.6 g of agarose powder (Appleton, LF45150060) to 130 ml of 1x TBE buffer and 2 µl of ethidium bromide (500 µg/ml in H₂O₂; Sigma, MKCC7786). The agarose powder was melted using the microwave and poured into the cast with the comb in

order to solidify the gel. The gel was then placed in the gel tank and the comb was removed to form the wells. PCR samples were loaded into different gel wells alongside with the 100 bp Gene Ruler Express DNA ladder (Thermofisher Scientific, SM 1553). Electrical field (150 V) was applied to the tank via the power supply (Fisher Scientific) for 50 minutes and bands were visualised by gel documentation imaging system. Images and analysis were undertaken on the Syngene G Box, Software GeneSys V1.5.6.0. Images were compiled on ImageJ bundles 1.8.0_172 software.

2.11. Bisulphite conversion of DNA samples.

In order to determine CpG site specific changes and DNA methylation changes within CpG island 2 of *F2RL1* promoter region, the extracted DNA samples from BEAS-2B and human primary epithelial cells were converted by bisulphite reagents using EZ DNA Methylation-Direct Kit (Zymoresearch, D5021). The bisulphite conversion method is considered the most common technique used today to detect and quantify DNA methylation efficiently and accurately. This technique involves treating the methylated DNA samples with bisulphite. The methylated cytosines remains intact and unchanged during the treatment; however, incubation with bisulfite converts the unmethylated cytosines to uracil (Figure 2.5). After conversion, the methylation profile of the converted DNA samples is determined by Bisulphite Specific PCR (BSP) amplification followed by direct bisulphite sequencing (Parrish, Day and Lubin, 2012a).

Figure 2.5. DNA sequencing after CT conversion.

The methylated C^mpG at nucleotide #5 is capped by methyl group, thus it remains intact after bisulphite conversion and is detected as cytosine following PCR and sequencing; however, the unmethylated cytosines at positions # 7, 9, 11, 14 and 15 were completely converted to uracil after bisulphite treatment and detected as thymine after BSP.

2.11.1. Preparation of CT-conversion reagent

Prior to each bisulphite experiment, the CT-conversion reagent was freshly prepared. As it was supplied as a solid mixture, each tube of CT-conversion reagent was centrifuged for 1 min, and 790 μ l of M-solubilisation buffer and 300 μ l of M-dilution buffer were added respectively to each reagent tube. CT-conversion reagent tubes were mixed with frequent shaking for at least 10 min at room temperature. M-reaction buffer (160 μ l) were then added to each reagent tube as the mixture was shaken for another 5 min at room temperature. The CT-conversion reagent was prepared in dark as it is highly sensitive to light.

Ethanol (100 %) at a volume of 96 ml was added to 24 ml of concentrated M-Wash Buffer before use to prepare working M-Wash Buffer.

2.11.2. Experimental protocol

2.11.2.1. Bisulfite conversion of DNA

The first step of the kit requires thermal cycling; in each PCR tube 130 μ l of CT-conversion reagent was dispensed and up to 20 μ l of each DNA sample at a concentration of 500 ng was added respectively. When the volume of DNA was less than 20 μ l, water was used to compensate for the volume. PCR tubes were placed in a thermal cycler (BIO-RAD) and the following steps were performed: 98°C for 8 min, 64°C for 3.5 h and 4°C storage for up to 20 h, for bisulphite conversion. Following the thermal cycling, the bisulphite kit involves washing, desulphonation of cytosines (the final step in the conversion to uracil) (Figure 2.6), and purification of the bisulphite converted DNA for downstream PCR. Zymo-Spin IC Column was inserted into a 2 ml collection tube, and 600 μ l of M-binding buffer was added directly into the column, the bisulphite DNA converted samples from the previous step were loaded at a volume of 150 μ l into the Zymo-Spin IC Column containing the M-binding buffer, each sample was mixed thoroughly by inverting the column for several times. Samples were then centrifuged at a full speed of 12,000 g for 1 min, the flow-through was discarded immediately. This step was repeated using 100 μ l of M-wash buffer. Samples were then incubated with 200 μ l of M-desulphonation buffer for 20 min at 30 °C, followed by centrifugation at full speed for

1 min. Spin columns were placed into 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tubes, 10 μ l of M-elution buffer was placed directly into columns, and samples were then eluted by centrifuging at full speed for 1 min. The eluted DNA was used immediately for downstream applications (BSP) or was stored at -20 °C for later use.

Figure 2.6. Bisulfite conversion reaction

Bisulphite treatment of DNA involves three steps reaction (Sulphonation, Deamination and Desulphonation) where during the last step desulphonation of cytosines takes place, in this step the unmethylated cytosines are converted to uracil.

2.12. Quality control

2.12.1. Assessing DNA quantity after bisulphite-conversion

Treatment with bisulphite is a harsh process that changes the chemical and physical properties of the double-stranded DNA. To assess these changes, Nanodrop calculations were undertaken to ensure the quantity and purity of the converted DNA. As the modified DNA is fragmented and no longer double stranded DNA so the quantity of the converted DNA was assessed as RNA with $\text{Abs}_{260 \text{ nm}} 1.0 \text{ cm} = 40 \mu\text{g/ml}$. The concentration of the fragmented converted DNA was determined by measuring the absorbance at 260 nm (A_{260}) in a spectrophotometer. Only samples with absorbance readings that were greater than 0.15 were used in further experiments as these samples considered having an acceptable yield (Figure

2.7). Nanodrop parameter 10 mm path length was used for quantifying the concentration, an absorbance of 1 unit at 260 nm corresponds to 40 µg of RNA per 1ml ($A_{260} = 1 = 40 \mu\text{g/ml}$). This relationship was frequently used in this work for measurements of samples as they were diluted in water. Therefore, all the converted DNA were diluted in water at a ratio of 1:5. The concentration of converted DNA was calculated using the equation below.

$$\text{Concentration } (\mu\text{g/ml}) = A_{260} \times \text{constant} \times \text{dilution factor}$$

Where:

A₂₆₀: unit is the amount of nucleic acid contained in 1 mL

Constant=40 (conversion factor of RNA)

Dilution factor: dilution factor used in all experiments was 5

Figure 2.7. Accessing concentration and purity of the bisulphite converted DNA

Following bisulphite conversion, the converted DNA samples were diluted in water, and the concentration of each sample was quantified using the A-260 10 mm path length parameter. The converted DNA was assessed as RNA using Nanodrop measurements. Ratios 260/280 and 260/230 were within the required range, this indicated no contaminations and pure samples.

The calculated concentration was then converted to ng/10 μ l and the volume (μ l) of the converted DNA to be taken to have 100 ng of DNA was calculated as (100x10/concentration). Quantifying the concentration of the converted DNA is important in order to load 100 ng /well of converted DNA in an agarose gel to assess the quality of conversion.

2.12.2. Assessing the level of fragmentation and quality of the bisulfite converted DNA

To gauge fragmentation and recovery of the converted DNA, 2% (w/v) agarose gel electrophoresis with a 100 bp marker ladder was used. At least 100 ng/well of converted DNA samples were loaded into the gel, it is crucial to load sufficient material into the gel to allow visualization. Also, an unconverted DNA sample (100 ng/well) was loaded and acted as a control to assess conversion efficiency. Samples were electrophoresed for 45 min in order to separate. The gel was removed from the gel tank and immediately visualised using Syngene G Box, Software GeneSys. The gel was then chilled in an ice bath for 20 min, and visualised again using the Syngene G Box, Software GeneSys. The gel was imaged first time in order to check that the PCR went as expected as the unconverted DNA should show a band; Imaging the gel for the second time was done in order to visualise the DNA as a smear due to fragmentation.

2.13. Bisulphite-Specific PCR testing

2.13.1. Designing primers specific to bisulphite converted DNA

Primer designing software (MethPrimer Express Software v2.0, 2016 version) was used to design the bisulphite-specific primers for methylation mapping. Primers designed were complementary to the bisulphite converted sequence. The software was programmed to design primers for the input sequence. Accordingly, the DNA original sense strand of the *F2RL1* gene promoter region was imported into the software without being virtually bisulphite converted. The bisulphite sequencing PCR (BSP) primers option was selected, and the general parameters for primer design that are recommended by the software were kept as default.

2.13.2. General parameters for primer selection criteria

Self-annealing, GC content, pair complementarity and melting temperature (T_m), are the main constraints that are computed by the MethPrimer software using Primer3's algorithms (Li and Dahiya, 2002). Additionally, other constraints are also applied by the software, such as the T_m difference between forward and reverse primer, and the maximum number of repeated mononucleotides allowed within a primer sequence. In the latter case, the number of 'T' repeats is treated differently by the software compared to other mononucleotides and by default, a maximal number of 8 primer poly T is allowed during primer selection; however, the default value of other nucleotides is 5 (Li and Dahiya, 2002)(Figure 2.8).

General Parameters for Primer Design			
Sequence name (optional):	<input type="text"/>	Output Number (optional):	5 <input type="button" value="v"/>
Target Regions (optional):	<input type="text"/>	"start, size", such as (560, 30)	
Excluded Regions (optional):	<input type="text"/>	"start, size", such as (160, 50 1100, 50)	
Primer T _m :	Min: <input type="text" value="50"/>	Opt: <input type="text" value="55"/>	Max: <input type="text" value="60"/>
Primer Size:	Min: <input type="text" value="20"/>	Opt: <input type="text" value="25"/>	Max: <input type="text" value="30"/>
Primer GC%:	Min: <input type="text" value="10"/>	Opt: <input type="text" value="40"/>	Max: <input type="text" value="80"/>
Primer GC clamp:	<input type="text" value="0"/>	Primer non-CpG 'C's:	<input type="text" value="4"/>
Primer Poly X:	<input type="text" value="5"/>	Primer Poly T:	<input type="text" value="8"/>
Primer T _m diff:	<input type="text" value="5"/>		
Product Size:	Min: <input type="text" value="100"/>	Opt: <input type="text" value="300"/>	Max: <input type="text" value="400"/>
Parameters for BSP primers			
Product CpGs:	<input type="text" value="4"/>		

Figure 2.8. General parameters for designing primers for BSP

The different parameter values were kept as default prior to primer selection.

2.13.3. Bisulfite-Specific PCR primer selection parameters

Primer non-CpG 'C's is a specific constraint that the software used while designing BSP primers. As suggested by the software, the primer set was picked from a region within the original input DNA sequence that has at least 4 non- non-CpG 'C's (Herman et al., 1996). A good primer pair is defined as a set of primers that can cover as many CpG sites as possible within a single PCR amplification. For this reason, another very important and specific option provided by Methprimer software is 'Product CpGs', by default the minimal number of CpG sites that are acceptable by the primer set to span is 4. This is very specific for sequencing PCR, also primers that examine more CpG sites assign higher weighing scores and these usually are

the preferred primer set. Therefore, this parameter drives the software to pick primers that span regions that are very dense with CpG sites, which are thus most interesting for downstream analysis.

The program predicted 5 primer sets, since the predicted CpG Island 2 was greater than the optimum product size (350 bp). For this reason, the software indicates primer pairs that are within the island and span at least two-third of the island (Figure 2.9). Importantly, the predicted primer pair sequences didn't contain any CpGs. According to the suggested parameters provided by the Methprimer software, all the 5 predicted BSP primers were theoretically considered acceptable and good primer pairs, among the five predicted primer pairs, primer pairs 2 and 5 from Figure 2.9 (denoted as primer sets 1 and 2 in the experiments) were used for further experimental work.

BSP Pair 1

Primer name	Sequence (5'-3')	Len	Start	End	Degenerate	CpG's	C's	Self_any	Self_end	Tm	GC%	Stability	Score
F1	TTTTAGGAGTAAGTAAAGATTAAGG	26	65	90	No	0	2	400	0	53.6	26.9	8.5	4.1
R1	AAATCAACCTCTCACCTACCC	22	412	391	No	0	3	200	0	58.5	45.5	8.4	3.4
Product size	Pair start	Pair end	CpG's	Comp_any	Comp_end	Tm	Tm_diff	Score					
348	65	412	31	500	200	75.7	4.9	2.4					

BSP Pair 2

Primer name	Sequence (5'-3')	Len	Start	End	Degenerate	CpG's	C's	Self_any	Self_end	Tm	GC%	Stability	Score
F2	TTTTAGGAGTAAGTAAAGATTAAGG	26	65	90	No	0	2	400	0	53.6	26.9	8.5	4.1
R2	AAATCAACCTCTCACCTACCC	21	411	391	No	0	3	200	0	57.1	47.6	8.4	3.4
Product size	Pair start	Pair end	CpG's	Comp_any	Comp_end	Tm	Tm_diff	Score					
347	65	411	31	500	200	75.8	3.5	1.7					

BSP Pair 3

Primer name	Sequence (5'-3')	Len	Start	End	Degenerate	CpG's	C's	Self_any	Self_end	Tm	GC%	Stability	Score
F3	TTTTAGGAGTAAGTAAAGATTAAGG	26	65	90	No	0	2	400	0	53.6	26.9	8.5	4.1
R3	AAATCAACCTCTCACCTACCC	23	414	392	No	0	4	200	0	57.8	39.1	6.9	2.9
Product size	Pair start	Pair end	CpG's	Comp_any	Comp_end	Tm	Tm_diff	Score					
350	65	414	31	500	200	75.6	4.2	1.6					

BSP Pair 4

Primer name	Sequence (5'-3')	Len	Start	End	Degenerate	CpG's	C's	Self_any	Self_end	Tm	GC%	Stability	Score
F4	TTTTAGGAGTAAGTAAAGATTAAGG	26	65	90	No	0	2	400	0	53.6	26.9	8.5	4.1
R4	AAAAAATCAACCTCTCACCTAC	24	416	393	No	0	5	200	0	57.1	33.3	6.9	2.9
Product size	Pair start	Pair end	CpG's	Comp_any	Comp_end	Tm	Tm_diff	Score					
352	65	416	31	500	200	75.6	3.5	1.4					

BSP Pair 5

Primer name	Sequence (5'-3')	Len	Start	End	Degenerate	CpG's	C's	Self_any	Self_end	Tm	GC%	Stability	Score
F5	TTTTAGGAGTAAGTAAAGATTAAGG	26	65	90	No	0	2	400	0	53.6	26.9	8.5	4.1
R5	AATCAACCTCTCACCTACCC	20	410	391	No	0	3	200	0	55.6	50.0	8.4	3.5
Product size	Pair start	Pair end	CpG's	Comp_any	Comp_end	Tm	Tm_diff	Score					
346	65	410	31	500	300	75.8	2.0	1.4					

Figure 2.9. Visualisation of primer selection results for BSP

Primers for *F2RL1* gene promoter region specifically for island 2 were predicted by Methprimer software. The graphic view shows primers sequences and other important features such as GC percentage, product size, Score and CpGs.

The length of the selected primers should be around 25 to 30 nucleotides. In this work the lengths of set 1 primer pair (referred to BSP pair 2 in Figure 2.9) were 26 with GC-content 27 % for forward primer and 21 nucleotides with GC-content 47.6 % for reverse primer. Set 2 primer pair (referred to BSP pair 5 in Figure 2.9), with 26 nucleotides with GC-content 27 % for forward primer and 20 nucleotides with GC-content 50 % for reverse primer. The length of the PCR product should not exceed 350 bp due to potential DNA degradation during the bisulphite modification that might influence the PCR amplification, in this work the length of the amplicon is maximum 347 bp.

2.14. Annealing temperature gradient polymerase chain reaction

Prior to Bisulphite-Specific PCR, an annealing gradient temperature PCR using samples of bisulphite modified DNA with BSP primers 2 and 5 (Figure 2.9) was undertaken in order to figure out the optimal primer annealing temperature thus to ensure optimal amplification of the specific target. ZymoTaq premix hot start DNA polymerase (Zymoresearch, e2004) was used as described previously in section 2.9.3. Sequences details for BSP primers sets 1 and 2 are presented in (Table 2.14). The same reagent preparations as described in 2.9.3 were followed in this work; however, both primer sets 1 and 2 were used with the same sample of bisulphite converted DNA with each primer set, 10 PCR reactions were prepared with 9 reactions with template and 1 reaction tube as NTC, the PCR tubes were placed horizontally in a gradient thermal cycler (Biometra Tone), with each tube placed in a different column programmed by the thermocycler to have different annealing temperatures. The machine was programmed according to the cycling conditions stated on Table 2.15.

PCR samples were loaded in 2 % (w/v) gel, electrophoresed and imaged using Syngene G box, software Genesys.

Table 2.14. BS primer sequences used for Bisulphite Specific PCR

Oligo Name	SEQUENCE (5'→ 3')	
Forward. ISLAND 2 SET 1	TTTTAGGAGTAAGTAAAGATTAAAGG	} BSP pair 2
REVERSE. ISLAND 2 SET 1	AAATCAACCTCTCACCTACCC	
Forward. ISLAND 2 SET 2	TTTTAGGAGTAAGTAAAGATTAAAGG	} BSP pair 5
REVERSE. ISLAND 2 SET 2	AATCAACCTCTCACCTACCC	

Table 2.15. Cycling conditions for the annealing temperature gradient PCR.

Step	Temperature	Duration	Cycles
Initial denaturation	95 °C	10 min	1
Denaturation	95 °C	30 s	35 cycles
Gradient Annealing Temperature	T _m °C= 57.0 °C (54.7 to 59.9 °C)	35 s	
Extension	72 ° c	1 min	
Final Extension	72 ° c	7 min	1
Hold	4 ° c	infinity	1

2.15. Bisulphite specific PCR (BSP)

After optimising all the conditions for PCR (including primer set selection, specific primer annealing temperature and cycling conditions), BSP was undertaken in order to amplify bisulfite converted samples. In short, BSP primer pair 2 (referred as set 1 later in this work, see Table 2.14) was selected to perform BSP amplification. The BSP procedure was carried out with 10 µl of modified DNA as the template. ZymoTaq PreMix Hot start DNA polymerase was used to perform the BSP PCR reaction. Conditions are summarised in Table 2.16, with annealing temperature 57 °C which was selected as the optimal annealing temperature for primer set 1 after performing the annealing gradient PCR.

Table 2.16. BSP PCR reaction conditions

Reagent	Volume	Final Concentration
Zymotag Premix (2x)	25 μ l	1x
Forward and Reverse Primer at 10 μM each	2 μ l	0.3-1 μ M
Template	10 μ l of bisulfite modified DNA	
dd.H₂O	13 μ l	
Total Volume	50 μ l	

The procedure was followed by an electrophoresis with 2 % (w/v) agarose gel. PCR results of four independent experiments from BEAS-2B cells and two independent experiments from primary epithelial cells were analysed on a Syngene G Box, Software GeneSys.

2.16. Standards quality control: Bisulphite-Specific PCR testing

In order to overcome PCR amplification bias, human methylated & non-methylated DNA Set (Zymoresearch, D5014-2) was used. Details of human methylated and non-methylated DNA set are described in Table 2.17. DNA control samples varying in % methylation were prepared and amplified using BSP. Various concentrations of methylated standards were prepared by mixing 100 % methylated and 0 % methylated DNA (Table 2.18).

Table 2.17. Product specifications of human methylated and non-methylated DNA

	Provided concentration	source	Concentration/μl
Human HCT116 DKO Non-methylated DNA	5 μ g/20 μ l	DNA purified from HCT116 DKO cells [DNMT1 (-/-) / DNMT3b (-/-)].	250 ng/ μ l in buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, 1 mM EDTA, pH 8.0)
Human HCT116 DKO Methylated DNA	5 μ g/20 μ l	DNA purified from HCT116 DKO cells [enzymatically methylated by M.SssI Methyltransferase (EC 2.1.1.37)].	250 ng/ μ l in buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, 1 mM EDTA, pH 8.0)
DAPK1 Primers	20 μ l	Control primers are designed to amplify non-methylated, methylated, and mixed methylation copies of the death-associated protein kinase 1 gene (DAPK1) following bisulfite conversion	20 μ M each primer in TE buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, 1 mM EDTA, pH 8.0)

Table 2.18. Control samples preparation with different methylation levels

% Methylation level	Volume (μl) of methylated DNA	Volume (μl) Non-methylated DNA
0	0	1.6
10	0.8	7.2
25	2	6
50	4	4
75	6	2
100	1.6	0

Methylated and non-methylated DNA used are intact DNA, thus the standards were vortexed thoroughly to distribute evenly in solution. Each standard was centrifuged for 15 s, then centrifuged briefly. They were centrifuged again for 15 s and span down before taking an aliquot. The DNA samples were then modified using the bisulphite conversion method as described in section 2.11.2.1; however, only 2 μ l of each prepared standard was added to the CT-conversion reagent in step 1 of the conversion method.

2.16.1. Amplification of DNA control samples using PCR.

The efficiency of bisulphite-mediated conversion of DNA controls was assessed by specifically designed primers to amplify non-methylated, methylated and mixed methylation copies of *DAPK1* gene following bisulfite conversion of the control DNA, primers sequences are shown in Table 2.19.

Table 2.19. Control primers used for the amplification of DNA standards

	Primer Name	Primer Sequence (5'-3')	Nucleotide Replacement	Explanation
Forward Primer	DAPK1 Primer I	ATTGGGAAGGTTAAGGYGGAGGGAAATTTGGT	Y= C	With methylated DNA controls at different ratios
			Y=T	With non-methylated DNA control
Reverse Primer	DAPK1 Primer II	CCCCAAACRAACAATCCCCAAAACACATTCCT A	R= G	With methylated DNA controls at different ratios
			R= A	With non-methylated DNA control

The bisulfite-treated control DNA samples were amplified using ZymoTaq premix hot start DNA polymerase, the setup for PCR conditions are represented in Table 2.20.

Table 2.20. Designed PCR conditions for amplifying modified DNA samples

Component	Volume	Final Concentration
DAPK1 Primers	2 µl	1 µM
Bisulfite-Converted DNA Control Samples	10 µl	
ZymoTaq Premix (2x)	25 µl	
ddH ₂ O ₂	13 µl	
Total Volume	50 µl	

The same thermocycler conditions described in section 2.9.4 were used with Control DNA samples, with a difference in annealing temperature of control DNA samples ($T_m = 59^\circ\text{C}$) as

recommended by manufacturer. A 2 % (w/v) electrophoresis gel with gel imager (Syngene G Box, Software GeneSys) was used to analyse and visualise the results of PCR amplification.

2.17. Quantification of PCR products prior to sequencing

The template DNA concentrations for all samples used in previously described experiments were quantified via agarose gel prior to sending for sequencing (Eurofins, Germany). PCR products were sent as unpurified samples at concentration of each PCR sample of 10 ng/ μ l and volume 20 μ l (as recommended by the company for PCR product length between 300-500 bp). Agarose gel (2 % w/v) with 100 bp DNA ladder (Thermofisher Scientific, SM1553) was used to estimate template concentration (Figure 2.10).

All samples (unconverted, converted and DNA standards) were prepared as 10 ng/ μ l at total volume of 20 μ l in the unpurified form.

Cat. No.	Contents	Amount
SM1553	GeneRuler™ Express DNA Ladder, ready-to-use	50 µg (for 100 applications), 0.1 µg/µL
	6X TriTrack DNA Loading Dye	1 mL

Figure 2.10. Quantification of PCR products prior to sequencing.

Agarose gel (2 %) with 100 bp DNA Ladder was used to do an estimate quantification of template concentration.

2.18. Direct bisulphite sequencing (Sanger sequencing)

Modified and unmodified samples from BEAS2B cells (n=4) and primary human epithelial cells (n=2) were sent to Eurofins Genomics (Germany) in order to perform direct-bisulphite sequencing using Sanger sequencing. Samples were sequenced using the cycle sequencing technology (dideoxy chain termination/cycle sequencing) on an Applied Biosystems ABI 3730XL sequencing machines. 'SupremeRun Tube GATC' service was the option chosen to perform direct bisulphite sequencing, as this service include adaptation protocols for Sanger sequencing for difficult templates such as bisulphite modified samples. Reverse primers (wild

type specific primers and BSP primers) at concentration of 10 μ M and minimal volume of 15 μ l/reaction were sent for sequencing the DNA from unconverted and converted DNA templates; however, the forward primer (DAPK1 primer I) was used for sequencing the control DNA samples. Raw data of sequenced samples from the ABI 3730XL machine were returned as .ab1 format files; also a PDF report of electropherograms was attached to observe the sequence of each sample after modification. Only passed samples were considered as successful sequencing results, these samples showed well-formed and distinctive single coloured peaks, the peaks are evenly separated and no background signals were detected. An example of a passed and successful sample is presented in Figure 2.11. Sequences were observed using Chromas software for PC (version 2.6.6, 2018) (Figure 2.11) and presented in the relevant results chapter. The software is programmed to automatically interpret the chromatogram data and make base calls determined by the results from the DNA sequencing data (Parrish, Day and Lubin, 2012b).

Figure 2.11. Successful sequencing reactions.

(A) The original .ab1 file gives the best chance to precisely compare raw and analysed data traces. (B) Electropherogram of a normal DNA sequencing read, peaks are evenly separated, well-formed distinctive single coloured peaks with absence of background signals.

2.19. Analysis of Direct Bisulphite Sequencing Data

Analysis of the sequencing results was performed by Dr. David McGuinness (Glasgow Polyomics, University of Glasgow, Wolfson Wohl Cancer Research Center, Glasgow, and Bearsden). The ab1 sequencing files obtained from the Sanger Sequencing run by Eurofins were initially viewed in Unipro UGENE software (v44.0, <http://ugene.net/>)(Okonechnikov *et al.*, 2012). To check the integrity and quality of the data, the raw sequence data was then extracted in the standardised Fasta file format which contains just the raw sequence in 4 letter nucleotide format. These raw fasta files were then used to complete multiple Sequence alignments using Clustal Omega (Madhusoodanan, 2019). These alignments were then viewed and checked using Unipro UGENE software (v44.0).

2.20. Statistical analysis

All data are presented as means \pm standard error of the mean (SEM) with at least n=3 independent observations per experiment and each experiment was carried in triplicate. When comparing only two means to demonstrate synergism, paired Student's *t*-test was performed. Unpaired Student's *t*-test was used when comparing ELISA and RT-qPCR data of HBEC to COPD-HBEC at baseline levels. When comparing more than two means (control, H₂O₂, TNF- α , TGF- β and LPS) One-Way ANOVA with Multiple Comparison Test was used. In some experiments, two way ANOVA were also used to analyse the results from HBEC compared to COPD-HBEC with different treatments. GraphPad Prism software (7. 05. 237, La Jolla California USA) was used to evaluate the data. Differences were considered significant for *P* values of <0.05.

**Chapter 3. Establishment,
characterisation and regulation of a
simple *in vitro* model for chronic
oxidative stress in BEAS-2B human
lung epithelial cells**

3.1. Introduction

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a prevalent clinical condition characterised by irreversible or only partially reversible airflow obstruction. COPD is ranked now as the third leading cause of death worldwide causes 3.23 million deaths in 2019 (WHO, 2023) due to a rise in smoking rates and demographic changes in several countries (Alonso and Paredes, 2018; Barnes, 2022). Many chronic inflammatory lung illnesses, including COPD, are thought to involve cell and tissue damage, which is believed to be mainly caused by ROS (Sundar, Yao and Rahman., 2012); however, the exact mechanisms underlying the aetiopathogenesis of COPD have not yet been determined. Antioxidant enzymes are defined as ROS scavengers, and it is speculated that the primary cause of COPD is an elevated oxidant burden and oxidant-antioxidant imbalance (Wang *et al.*, 2019).

Cigarette smoke and other ambient environmental oxidant pollutants directly trigger airway leucocytes to generate more oxidative stress, also indirectly by the production of elevated amounts of ROS (Shapiro and Ingenito., 2005; Singh *et al.*, 2017). Cigarette smoke is the key aetiological element in the pathogenesis of COPD, which causes oxidant excess in the lower airways. Cigarette smoke comprises 4700 compounds, including peroxy nitrite, superoxide radicals, and nitrogen oxides, as well as more than 10^{16} - 10^{17} oxidant molecules per puff (Rajendrasozhan, Yao and Rahman., 2009). Cigarette smoke makes a considerable contribution to COPD development; however, other risk factors are also essential as they play a significant role in disease development, since not all smokers develop COPD and studies reported cases of COPD in non-smokers. Beside cigarette smoking, other risk factors have been identified, for example age, asthma, respiratory infection, poor socioeconomic status, occupational exposure to organic dust, and biomass fuel combustion (Salvi and Barnes., 2009; Clancy and Nobes., 2012; Forteza, Casalino-Matsuda *et al.*, 2012). In normal conditions, various intracellular and extracellular antioxidants effectively protect the lungs and blood from the detrimental effects of oxidants. Both smokers and COPD patients have indications of an imbalance between oxidants and antioxidants in their blood and lungs (Tavilani *et al.*, 2012; Singh *et al.*, 2017).

Numerous studies have shown the presence of oxidative stress markers in the epithelial lining fluid, breath, and sputum of COPD patients, and many abnormalities of the antioxidant system have been identified in COPD patients (Ahmad, Shameem and Husain, 2012a). One of the crucial biomarkers of oxidative stress is malondialdehyde (MDA), which is the principal by-product of lipid peroxidation (LPO). Patients with COPD have higher levels of these chemicals in their sputum and exhaled breath condensate (Tsukagoshi *et al.*, 2000; Taniguchi *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, during COPD exacerbations, alterations in antioxidants, such as decreased glutathione levels in the lungs and lower antioxidant capacity of blood plasma, have been detected (Cipollina *et al.*, 2022).

Oxidative stress has a significant impact on various processes in lung physiology as well as the pathogenesis of COPD. These include extracellular matrix remodeling, oxidative inactivation of anti-proteases and surfactants, mucus hypersecretion, membrane LPO, mitochondrial respiration, alveolar epithelial damage, and apoptosis (Khan *et al.*, 2014). Patients with COPD have elevated levels of oxidative stress markers in the airspaces, sputum, breath, lungs, and blood due to the accumulation of ROS, produced in the airways, which are linked to the pathogenesis of a number of human diseases. The restriction of airflow in COPD is linked to an abnormal inflammatory response of the lungs to long-term repeated exposure to cigarette smoking, dust, and other air pollutants (Hogg *et al.*, 2004; Singh *et al.*, 2017). Cigarette smoke promotes the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), forming oxidative stress. Subsequently, the generation of excessive ROS alongside a defect in the antioxidant system impacts the imbalance between oxidants/anti-oxidants favoring oxidants which leads to oxidative stress (Thimmulappa, Chattopadhyay and Rajasekaran, 2019) .

Inflammation is a key feature of COPD that persists even after smoking cessation(Khan *et al.*, 2014). Besides elastase-anti elastase imbalance, oxidants and anti-oxidants dysregulation and apoptosis, chronic inflammation is a major cause of COPD pathogenesis (Shapiro and Ingenito, 2005). Inflammation that is generated by cigarette smoking is an important driver of COPD. The proposed mechanism involves the production of elevated levels of pro-

inflammatory cytokines and chemokines, and this was been detected in the serum of COPD patients (Shen *et al.*, 2011; ; Barnes, 2022). Furthermore, chronic inflammation of lung tissues in COPD is mainly achieved by activation of airway epithelial cells and fibroblasts, as well as various immune cells. When the lung is exposed to similar kinds of oxidants from environmental challenges, oxidative stress can be generated, thus producing inflammatory reactions (Titz *et al.*, 2015; Staniguchi *et al.*, 2021).

When oxidative stress is induced by pathogens (endogenous source of ROS), pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) stimulate nitric oxide (NO) synthase to generate unstable NO. In phagocytes, NO is the common ROS, and when NO combines with superoxide anion, it generates peroxynitrite, which specifically targets protein thiols and tyrosine (Miller *et al.*, 2013); however, superoxide dismutase (SOD) catalyzes the dismutation of superoxide generating oxygen (O₂) and H₂O₂ (Horiyama *et al.*, 2016). H₂O₂ undergoes several intracellular reactions to produce other oxidant species, for example, reactive nitrogen species (RNS) and reactive carbon species by the Fenton reaction (Marotta *et al.*, 2011; Fischer, Voynow and Ghio, 2015). Several studies reported elevated levels of oxidants in exhaled air or breath condensates of smokers and COPD patients (Paredi, Kharitonov and Barnes, 2002; Borrill, Roy and Singh, 2008). Consequently, an increased concentration of H₂O₂ in exhaled breath condensate in patients with COPD was reported (Rysz *et al.*, 2007; Montuschi, 2012).

A range of potential COPD biomarkers have been proposed so far, from gene expression profiling of lung tissue (Shaw *et al.*, 2014) and factors released in blood and sputum. Many clinical studies found increased levels of pro-inflammatory mediators, such as TNF- α , transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β), interleukin IL-6, and IL-1 β , in the serum of patients with COPD when compared with healthy individuals (Peter J. Barnes, 2009). Other potential target blood biomarkers proposed include C-reactive protein (CRP) (Broekhuizen *et al.*, 2006), neutrophil elastase (Nikolakopoulou *et al.*, 2014) , white blood cell count (Koo *et al.*, 2017), surfactant protein-D (Peck *et al.*, 2018), and pulmonary and activation-regulated chemokine/CCL-18 (Sin *et al.*, 2011).

Infections are not the main cause of COPD development nor disease initiation, but have an important role in worsening the symptoms and lung function in patients with pre-existing COPD. Among respiratory tract infections, bacterial infection was recognised as the main type responsible for exacerbations of clinical COPD symptoms (Postma, Bush and van den Berge, 2015). Bacterial infection induces COPD progression, the lower respiratory tract of patients with COPD is chronically colonised with gram-negative bacteria and this is suggested to contribute to disease progression (White *et al.*, 2003; Leung *et al.*, 2017). LPS, when inhaled, causes in a dose-dependent manner clinical symptoms including fever, chills and bronchoconstriction accompanied by pro-inflammatory response in sputum and bronchoalveolar lavage fluid. LPS as a stimulus can accelerate the development of COPD by increasing inflammation in the airway and lungs (Kline *et al.*, 1999; Michel, Murdoch and Bernard, 2005; Shu *et al.*, 2018).

TGF- β is also involved in COPD development; it is a cytokine with dual function, it can act as either pro- or anti-inflammatory mediator, depending on context. The former activity occurs only in the presence of high TGF- β concentrations (Yang *et al.*, 2012). Because of its chemotactic activity for mast cells and macrophages, TGF- β 1 is implicated in the influx of inflammatory cells (Rostkowska-Nadolska *et al.*, 2009). TGF- β 1 is expressed in alveolar macrophages and airway epithelial cells of patients with COPD and is released from epithelial cells of small airways in a latent form (Liebhart and Dobek, 2009; Yang *et al.*, 2014). In response to CS, lung epithelium and low tract airway as well as other inflammatory cells such as macrophages and neutrophils can induce the secretion of cytokines alongside TGF- β (Halwani *et al.*, 2012). Also, TGF- β signaling pathway can be induced by various factors, including MMP-9 and oxidative stress (OS). TGF- β can cause chronic airway inflammation, and is one of the main causes of lung remodeling (El Mabrouk *et al.*, 2008). It is involved in the influx of inflammatory cells by inducing chemotaxis of mast cells and macrophages. Also, it affects proteases/anti-proteases balance, inhibiting MMP-9 (Liebhart and Dobek, 2009).

Another important pro-inflammatory stimuli is TNF- α , essential in the pathogenesis of COPD. An increased levels of TNF- α was detected in the sputum samples from COPD patients,

specifically during exacerbations (Peter J. Barnes, 2009). TNF- α induces differential change in redox status by depleting the cells of glutathione and related enzymes (Mukhopadhyay, Hoidal and Mukherjee, 2006). Upon stimulation with TNF- α , ROS is generated from epithelial cells, neutrophils and macrophages. At subcellular levels, TNF- α potential ROS generation sites is nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate oxidase (NADPH oxidase) and mitochondria, this promotes subsequent OS. OS generation results in the amplification of inflammatory responses through NF- κ B (Gueders *et al.*, 2006; Matera *et al.*, 2010). The proinflammation generated from TNF- α stimulation leads to tissue damage and remodeling (Barnes, 2009).

Cigarette smoke can also inactivate histone deacetylase (HDAC2), and this leads to NF- κ B mediated transcription of neutrophil chemokines/cytokines (TNF- α and IL-8) and MMPs (To *et al.*, 2017). The master regulator of several response genes, including those encoding immunological and inflammatory mediators, is NF- κ B. The pathogenesis of COPD is thought to be partly driven by NF- κ B-mediated inflammation, which results in remodeling of the small airways and deterioration of the lung parenchyma (Barnes, 2008; Khan, 2014). OS and inflammatory stimuli trigger the NF- κ B signalling pathway promoting the expression of multiple inflammatory genes and the release of cytokines, including IL-6, IL-8 and adhesion molecules that can lead to COPD development (Watters *et al.*, 2007; Khan, 2014). NF- κ B is highly activated in COPD and its activity increases during exacerbation (Schuliga, 2015b). Inflammation in COPD appears to be significantly driven through the NF- κ B activation signalling pathway as it is activated by numerous inflammatory stimuli.

Several cell-based models of OS exposure have been developed (Kirkham *et al.*, 2004; Merry, 2004; Rahman and Adcock, 2006) but these systems may lack repeated and cumulative exposure elements necessary to COPD, also they may fail to take account of the existing inflammatory microenvironment and chronic effect of OS leading in COPD. Despite the fact that several OS models (both *in vivo* and *in vitro*) have been identified (Hanazawa *et al.*, 2004; Marwick, Kirkham *et al.* 2004; Ito, 2007; Churg *et al.*, 2008; Wright, Cosio *et al.*, 2008), most experimental models are still based on acute (4 h) exposure to ROS. As a result, it is important

to study *in vitro* chronic oxidative stress models further, and this chapter describes such a model utilising H₂O₂ as an oxidant in conjunction with pro-inflammatory stimuli in human bronchial epithelial cells (BEAS-2B).

3.1.1. Aims

Therefore, the aims of the following experiments are to:

1. Establish a simple chronic oxidative stress model *in vitro* using transient, repeated hydrogen peroxide exposure.
2. Characterise and compare inflammatory responses in BEAS-2B induced by a range of pro-inflammatory mediators (LPS, TNF- α , TGF- β).
3. Investigate how chronic exposure to H₂O₂ alone or in combination with other inflammatory mediators influences airway epithelial cell responses.
4. Assess a potential transcriptional control of NF- κ B in the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines in this model.

3.2. METHODS

3.2.1. Chronic exposure to H₂O₂ alone or in combination with pro-inflammatory stimulants

BEAS-2B cells were chronically treated with H₂O₂ (15 μ M) for 2h/day for 3 days in a chronic repeated transient model. Alternatively, BEAS-2B cells were also treated chronically for 48 h continuously with 500 ng/ml of LPS, 10 ng/ml of TGF- β and TNF- α . Also, cells were treated with H₂O₂ (15 μ M) in combination with TGF- β , TNF- α and LPS for 2h/ day for 3 days, the combined treatments were then replaced with TGF- β , TNF- α and LPS alone every day after the 2h treatment, TGF- β , TNF- α and LPS were kept all the time and replaced each day with H₂O₂ in combination with TGF- β , TNF- α and LPS. This developed model was referred to as “standard combined exposure protocol”. (Further details in Chapter 2 Section 2.3).

3.2.2. Effect of H₂O₂, TGF-β, TNF-α and LPS (alone or in combination) on BEAS-2B cell viability

Methylthiazolyldiphenyl-tetrazolium bromide (MTT) assay was used to assess BEAS-2B cell viability after being treated with insults according to the standard combined exposure protocol. Cells were then washed with pre-warmed PBS and were incubated with 10 µl of MTT reagent in 90 µl pre-warmed media with no FBS at 37°C and 5% CO₂ for 4 h. At the end of the incubation 80 µl of 10% sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) was added to lyse the cells and they were incubated overnight to dissolve the formazan crystals to produce a violet colour solution. The absorbance was measured at λ570 nm. Alternatively Trypan Blue assay was used as a direct assay of cell viability (Further details in Chapter 2 Section 2.4).

3.2.3. Measurement of pro-inflammatory cytokines protein production from treated cells

BEAS-2B cells were seeded in 24- well plates at density 8x10⁴ cells/well for 24 h. Cells were further treated according to the “standard combined exposure protocol”. At the end of treatment days, supernatants were removed and tested for IL-6 and IL-8 production by ELISA according to manufacture protocol (Refer to Chapter 2 Section 2.5).

3.2.4. COPD related genes expression measured by RT-qPCR in BEAS-2B

BEAS-2B cells were seeded at density 8x10⁴ cells/well and treated according to the standard combined exposure protocol. Total RNA was extracted, converted to cDNA and subjected to RT-qPCR analysis using SYBR Green chemistry. The amount of *IL6*, *IL8*, *RELA*, *F2RL1*, *CAT*, *SOD2*, *NFE2L2* and *NFKB2* were normalised by measuring *GAPDH* transcript levels and applying the ΔΔCt method. (Refer to Chapter 2 Sections 2.6.1, 2.6.3, 2.6.4, 2.7).

3.2.5. Measurement of intracellular oxidative stress using Dichlorofluorescein assay

BEAS-2B cells were seeded in 96-well black plate at concentration of 6x10⁴ cells/well for 24 h prior to being treated according to the standard combined exposure protocol. At the end of

the experiment, culture media with treatments were removed and cells were washed with 1x HBSS buffer and then incubated with 10 μM of CM-H2DCFDA for 45 min in HBSS buffer in the dark. Tert-Butyl hydroperoxide ($(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{COOH}$) of concentration 100 μM was introduced to cells as a positive control 2 h prior to finishing the experiment. The fluorescence of the cells from each well was detected and measured by fluorescence microtitre plate reader. Fluorescein intensity was correlated to intracellular ROS (Refer to Chapter 2 Section 2.8).

3.2.6. Effect of TPCA-1 (IKK β inhibitor) on IL-6 and IL-8 gene expression and protein production

BEAS-2B cells were pre-treated with TPCA-1 (0.1-10 μM) diluted in DMSO as a vehicle for 1 h, followed by treatment with LPS (500 ng/ml) or TNF- α (10 ng/ml) alone or in combination with H_2O_2 (15 μM) according to the “standard combined exposure protocol”. Cell viability was assessed by MTT assay. Supernatants were assayed for the production of IL-6 and IL-8 by ELISA according to manufacture protocol. RNA was extracted from treated/untreated cells, cDNA was synthesised and RT-qPCR was performed to detect the mRNA transcript levels of IL6, IL8 and RELA genes.

3.3. RESULTS

3.3.1. Optimisation of seeding density for BEAS-2B cells.

In the preliminary work, the optimal seeding density of BEAS-2B cells was determined. Cells were seeded at different seeding densities ranging between 5×10^3 to 2×10^4 cell/well in a complete growth media and left to settle and proliferate for 24 h. BEAS-2B cells reached 60 % confluence when seeded at 10^4 cells/well after 24 h, while cell number reached a steady state between the densities 10^4 and 2×10^4 cells/well (Figure 3.1). Accordingly, 10^4 cells/well was found to be the optimum seeding density for BEAS-2B cells in 96-well plate format.

Figure 3.1. MTT cell proliferation assay for optimisation of seeding density

BEAS-2B cells were seeded at different seeding densities in 96-well plates for 24 h to ensure cell attachment. Cells were incubated with MTT reagent for 4 h and the purple formazan crystals were dissolved with SDS. The absorbance was measured at 570 nm in a plate reader using GENE5 software. The color intensity is assumed proportional to cell number.

3.3.2. The effect of exogenous H₂O₂ treatment on BEAS-2B cell viability

Cells were treated in a repeated exposure manner to OS (H₂O₂) for 2h/day for 3 days to stimulate in a transient but repeated exposure (similar to smoking) which is enough to impact cell behavior but maintain cell viability. In this work it was attempted to develop more faithful model of disease (chronic treatment) than short-term exposure based model. MTT assay (metabolic activity assay) was performed at the end of treatments with chronic H₂O₂ in order to define appropriate H₂O₂ concentrations for subsequent studies of the effects of OS. In this experiment, cells were seeded at the optimum density (10⁴ cells/well) previously chosen (Figure 3.1). Cell viability was reduced to 80 % at 10 μM H₂O₂ and to less than 40 % at higher concentrations, whereas 5 and 7 μM produced no significant change in cell viability (Figure

3.2 A). However, since most previous studies have employed considerably higher concentrations of H₂O₂, it was decided to assess the effect of seeding cells at a higher density (3x10⁴ cells/well), to assess whether a stronger challenge could be tolerated (Khan *et al.*, 2014). Indeed, cells were able to tolerate up to 15 μM H₂O₂ when seeded at 3x10⁴ cells/well with no significant change in cell viability (Figure 3.2 B). However, cell viability was reduced significantly to less than 50% at higher concentrations. Accordingly, 3x10⁴ cell/well was used as the revised optimum seeding density for BEAS-2B cells in subsequent experiments, suitable to explore oxidant-induced cellular responses to sub-cytotoxic challenge.

Figure 3.2. The effect of H₂O₂ on BEAS-2B viability

(A) 10⁴ cells/well were exposed to a range of concentrations of H₂O₂ for 2 h/day for 3 days. **(B)** BEAS-2B cells were seeded at 3x10⁴ cell/well and exposed to H₂O₂ for 2 h/day for 3 days. MTT was used to assess cell viability. Results represent the mean ± SEM (n=4), each experiment was measured in triplicate. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test **p*<0.05; ****p*<0.001 (Control vs. treated).

3.3.3. Effect of FBS concentration and OS in BEAS-2B cell

In order to further define an appropriate OS model, cells were exposed chronically to different concentrations of H₂O₂ ranging from 5-75 μM with or without 10 % (v/v) FBS in a repeated exposure manner for 2 h/day for 3 days or they were treated chronically in a continuous manner for 48 h with H₂O₂ concentrations ranging between 5-75 μM. At the end of treatments, cell viability was assessed with both Trypan Blue dye exclusion assay (Figure 3.3 A and C) and with MTT assay (Figure 3.3 B and D), to provide further confidence that the MTT signal represented a reliable surrogate for direct viability measurement in this system. When cells were treated continuously for 48 h in a media without FBS, both Trypan Blue and MTT assays showed a consistent reduction of cell viability. The viability reduced significantly to 50 % with 5 μM and below 40 % with higher concentrations (Figure 3.3 A and B). A similar trend was observed when FBS was added to the media, where the presence of FBS did not preserve cell viability during continuous exposure to H₂O₂ (Figure 3.3 C and D). However, when cells were exposed chronically in a repeated exposure manner to H₂O₂, both Trypan Blue (Figure 3.4 A) and MTT (Figure 3.4 B) assays confirmed a significant reduction in the viability when FBS was absent; conversely, the presence of FBS moderately enhanced the BEAS-2B cell viability, such that cells were able to tolerate up to 15 μM of H₂O₂ without any significant loss of viability as demonstrated by Trypan Blue (Figure 3.4C) and MTT (Figure 3.4 D) assays. Importantly, cells retained increased viability in the repeated exposure model (Figure 3.4) compared to the continuous model (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3. Effect of FBS on cell viability in chronic continuous oxidative stress model

BEAS-2B cells were exposed to a range of H₂O₂ concentrations (5-75 μM) for 48 h in a chronic continuous exposure manner in the absence (A, B) or presence of FBS (C, D). (A, C) Trypan Blue exclusion and (B, D) MTT assays were performed to assess cell viability. Results are expressed as mean ± SEM (n=4); each experiment was measured in triplicate. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test. ***p*<0.01; ****p*<0.001 (Control vs. treated).

Figure 3.4. Effect of FBS on cell viability in chronic repeated oxidative stress model

BEAS-2B cells were exposed to a different concentrations of H₂O₂ (5-75 µM) in a repeated exposure manner for 2h /day for 3 days in a media without FBS (A, B) and in the presence of FBS (C, D). At the end of treatments, Trypan Blue exclusion (A, C) and MTT (B, D) assays were performed to assess cell viability. Results are expressed as mean ± SEM (n=4); each experiment was measured in triplicate. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test. **p*<0.05; ***p*<0.01; ****p*<0.001 (Control vs. treated).

The morphology of the cells was examined under a bright field by EVOS microscope (ThermoFisher Scientific). H₂O₂ (15 μM) did not have any obvious effects on cell morphology, affecting neither the size nor shape of cells when exposed to repeated chronic exposure (Figure 3.5). Taking all these results into account, the chronic repeated exposure to 15 μM of H₂O₂ in a media with FBS was considered the optimum model for sub-cytotoxic oxidative stress, and this was used in all subsequent experiments.

Figure 3.5. Effect of chronic repeated stress model on BEAS-2B cell morphology

Cells were exposed to 15 μM H₂O₂ for 2 h/day for 3 days. Each day, cells were washed twice with 1x PBS and were examined under an EVOS microscope using bright field; images were captured using 4x and 10x objective lens. Images shown are representative of 4 independent experiments.

3.3.4. The effect of TGF- β , TNF- α and LPS on BEAS-2B cell viability

Since OS in COPD lungs occurs in the context of a chronic pro-inflammatory environment, it was decided to augment the cell model to include a more complex challenge, which might more closely align with disease conditions. As a first step, a range of relevant pro-inflammatory mediators were assessed alone. Cells were seeded in a 96-well plate 24 h prior to stimulation in complete growth media, prior to chronic treatment with different concentrations of TGF- β or TNF- α ranging between 2.5 -20 ng/ml, or with LPS ranging between 0.1-10 μ g/ml, for 48 h continuously without changing the media. Cell viability was assessed by MTT assay at the end of the experiment. Results demonstrated no significant effect of TNF- α or TGF- β on BEAS-2B cell viability when cells were treated with 2.5, 5 and 10 ng/ml; however, the viability was reduced to approximately 80% with 20 ng/ml of either factor in chronic treatment (Figure 3.6 C and E). In comparison to TNF- α and TGF- β , the viability markedly decreased when cells were treated with higher concentrations of LPS (1-10 μ g/ml), where the viability was reduced to 70% with 1 μ g/ml and to only 5% with 10 μ g/ml, whereas no significant change in viability was detected at lower concentrations (0.1-0.5 μ g/ml) (Figure 3.6 A). Taking these results into account, 10 ng/ml of TGF- β and TNF- α , and 500 ng/ml of LPS were used in subsequent experiments.

In order to investigate the effect of exogenous H₂O₂ in combination with different cytokines, cells were treated chronically with different concentrations of H₂O₂ ranging between 5-75 μ M and inflammatory stimulants (500 ng/ml of LPS, 10 ng/ml of TGF- β , and TNF- α) for 2 h/day for 3 days; cell viability was assessed by MTT assay at the end of the experiment. H₂O₂ in combination with 500 ng/ml of LPS caused a significant reduction in cell viability where the viability reduced to 70 % with 5, 7 and 10 μ M of H₂O₂, and to 65 % at 15 μ M of H₂O₂, but to less than 25 % at higher concentrations, suggesting that H₂O₂ and LPS together induced extra cellular stress that caused significant loss of viability even at lower H₂O₂ concentrations (Figure 3.6 B). In comparison with LPS, the combination of different H₂O₂ concentrations with 10 ng/ml of TGF- β or TNF- α did not show any significant change in cell viability at lower concentrations; however, similarly to H₂O₂ exposure alone, the viability was reduced to 75 %

at 15 μM H_2O_2 and to 40 % at 25 μM of H_2O_2 and below 20 % at higher concentrations (Figure 3.6 D and F). Accordingly, 15 μM of H_2O_2 with 500 ng/ml LPS or 10 ng/ml TGF- β or TNF- α were used for repeated chronic exposure treatments in subsequent experiments.

Figure 3.6. Establishing viability profile for combined (oxidative + inflammatory) exposure conditions for chronic treatments

Cells were treated with a range of pro-inflammatory mediators (A) LPS (0.1- 10 µg/ml), (C) TNF- α and (E) TGF-β (2.5- 20 ng/ml) in a continuous manner for 48 h and cell viability was assessed at the end of treatments with MTT. In subsequent experiments, cells were further treated with LPS (500 ng/ml) (B) or 10 ng/ml of TNF-α (D) or TGF-β (F) in combination with H₂O₂ concentrations ranging between (5- 75 µM) for 2 h/day for 3 days, cell viability was assessed by MTT assay at the end of the exposure. Results are expressed as the mean ± SEM; n=4; each experiment was measured in triplicate. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test. **p*<0.05, ***p*<0.01, ****p*<0.001 (Control vs treated).

3.3.5. Pro-inflammatory mediators stimulated release of IL-6 and IL-8 in the chronic OS model

3.3.5.1. Hydrogen peroxide enhances inflammatory mediator production in the presence of LPS

Downstream inflammatory effects of H₂O₂ and LPS treatments were investigated in the first instance by measuring IL-6 and IL-8 release by ELISA. BEAS-2B cells were induced by LPS/ H₂O₂ according to the “standard combined exposure protocol” described previously in the methods section. Release of IL-6 and IL-8 were tested by ELISA at the end of treatments. H₂O₂ alone induced minimal inflammatory induction of IL-8 (120±3 pg/ml) and IL-6 (115±2 pg/ml) compared to control of untreated BEAS-2B cells, and as expected LPS caused a marked elevation in secretion of IL-6 (2469±72 pg/ml) and IL-8 (2487±21 pg/ml) when compared to control. Importantly, H₂O₂ significantly enhanced LPS-induced IL-8 (LPS, 2487±21 vs. LPS+ H₂O₂, 2898±109 pg/ml) (Figure 3.7 A) and IL-6 (LPS, 2469±72 vs. LPS+ H₂O₂, 3277±62 pg/ml) (Figure 3.7 B) in the chronic oxidative stress *in vitro* model.

Figure 3.7. LPS-induced release of IL-8 and IL-6 enhanced under chronic oxidative stress

BEAS-2B cells were treated chronically with LPS (100 or 500 ng/ml) and H₂O₂ (15 μM) according to the standard combined exposure protocol. The secretion of IL-6 and IL-8 were tested by ELISA. Bar graphs show quantitative analysis of IL-8 (A) and IL-6 (B) in chronic H₂O₂ treated cells in the absence and presence of 100 ng/ml and 500 ng/ml of LPS. Results are expressed as mean ± SEM (n=3 experiments); each experiment was measured in triplicate. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test. *** $p < 0.001$ when compared to control; ### $p < 0.001$ (LPS 100 ng/ml vs. 15 μM H₂O₂ + 100 ng/ml LPS) also (LPS 500 ng/ml vs. 15 μM H₂O₂ + 500 ng/ml LPS).

To assess whether or not H₂O₂ in the chronic oxidative stress model synergistically enhanced LPS-dependent production of IL-8 and IL-6, paired *t*-tests were performed comparing the sum of additive treatments (LPS and H₂O₂) to the combined treatments (LPS + H₂O₂). Results showed a significant increase in IL-8 (sum of LPS and H₂O₂, 1378 ± 65 vs LPS+H₂O₂, 3298 ± 205 pg/ml) and IL-6 (sum of LPS and H₂O₂, 2607 ± 147 vs LPS+H₂O₂, 3635 ± 191 pg/ml) levels in treatments with LPS+H₂O₂ compared to the sum of additive treatments, suggesting that H₂O₂ in chronic exposure synergistically enhanced LPS-dependent production of both IL-8 and IL-6 (Figure 3.8).

Figure 3.8. H₂O₂ in chronic exposure synergistically enhanced LPS-dependent production of IL-8 and IL-6

Paired *t*-tests were used to assess potential treatment synergy, comparing the sum of 15 μM of H₂O₂ and LPS (100 or 500 ng/ml) treatments versus combined treatments. The dot-plot graph shows quantitative analysis of IL-8 and IL-6 in chronic H₂O₂ treated cells in the presence of 100 ng/ml of LPS (A, C) or 500 ng/ml of LPS (B, D). Results are expressed as mean ± SEM; n=3; each experiment was measured in triplicate. Data were analysed using Paired *t*-test. **p*<0.05; ***p*<0.01; ****p*<0.001, when comparing sum of 15 μM of H₂O₂ and LPS 100 or 500 ng/ml vs. 15 μM H₂O₂ + 100 or 500 ng/ml of LPS

3.3.5.2. TNF- α and TGF- β stimulated IL-8 and IL-6 release in a chronic oxidative stress model

The effect of H₂O₂-derived oxidative stress on pro-inflammatory proteins (IL-6 and IL-8) released from BEAS-2B cells, either alone or in combination with TNF- α or TGF- β was investigated. Cells were exposed to 10 ng/ml of TNF- α or TGF- β and 15 μ M of H₂O₂ according to the standard combined exposure protocol. ELISA was performed to test the secretion levels of IL-6 and IL-8 proteins. As expected, when compared to control, treatments with 10 ng/ml of TNF- α or TGF- β induced a significant elevation in IL-8 and IL-6 protein levels (Figure 3.9 and Figure 3.10 A, B); however, repeated exposure to 15 μ M of H₂O₂ for 3 days stimulated only a modest release of IL-8 (H₂O₂, 39 \pm 3 vs. control, 38 \pm 2 pg/ml) and IL-6 (H₂O₂, 84 \pm 13 vs. control, 85 \pm 2 pg/ml). Furthermore, the repeated exposure to 15 μ M of H₂O₂ for 3 days enhanced both TNF- α and TGF- β induced IL-8 release (TNF- α , 210.1 \pm 24.4 vs. TNF- α +H₂O₂, 311 \pm 19 pg/ml; TGF- β , 194 \pm 13 vs. TGF- β +H₂O₂, 279 \pm 10 pg/ml) (Figure 3.9 A and Figure 3.10 B) but the repeated exposure to 15 μ M of H₂O₂ significantly enhanced TNF- α induced IL-6 (TNF- α , 771 \pm 109 vs. TNF- α +H₂O₂, 1279 \pm 128 pg/ml) (Figure 3.9 B), but not in the case of TGF- β (Figure 3.10 B).

Paired *t*-tests demonstrated that H₂O₂ in chronic repeated exposure synergistically enhanced TNF- α and TGF- β dependent production of IL-8 (Figure 3.9 C and Figure 3.10 D); for IL-6 however, H₂O₂ had a synergistic effect only on TNF- α induced IL-6 but not with TGF- β treatment (Figure 3.9 C and Figure 3.10 D) respectively.

Figure 3.9. Effect of H₂O₂ and TNF-α on cytokine secretion from BEAS-2B cells

BEAS-2B cells were treated with H₂O₂/TNF-α according to the standard combined exposure protocol. The secretion of IL-6 and IL-8 were tested by ELISA. The bar graphs show quantitative analysis of IL-8 (A) and IL-6 (B) release in chronic H₂O₂ treated cells in the absence and presence of TNF-α. (C, D) Paired t-test was used to test the synergism between the sum of 15 μM H₂O₂ and 10 ng/ml of TNF-α treatment versus combined stimulus. Results are expressed as mean ± SEM (n=4); each experiment was measured in quadruplets. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test in A and B. **p*<0.05 when comparing sum of 15 μM of H₂O₂ and TNF-α 10 ng/ml vs. 15 μM H₂O₂ + 10 ng/ml of TNF-α treatments; *** *p*<0.001 when compared to control; ###*p*<0.001 when comparing 10 ng/ml of TNF-α vs. 15 μM of H₂O₂ + 10 ng/ml of TNF-α.

Figure 3.10. Effect of H₂O₂ and TGF-β on cytokine secretion from BEAS-2B cells
(A, B) BEAS-2B cells were chronically treated with H₂O₂/TGF-β according to the standard combined exposure protocol. ELISA was used to test the production levels of IL-8 and IL-6 after treatments. **(C, D)** Paired t-test was used to test the synergism between the sum of 15 μM H₂O₂ and 10 ng/ml TGF-β treatments versus combined treatments. The dot-plot graph shows quantitative analysis of IL-8 and IL-6 in chronic H₂O₂ treated cells in the presence of 10 ng/ml TGF-β. Results are expressed as mean ± SEM (n=3); each experiment was measured in triplicates. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test in **A** and **B**. **p*<0.05 when comparing sum of 15 μM of H₂O₂ and TGF-β 10 ng/ml vs. 15 μM H₂O₂ + 10 ng/ml of TGF-β treatment; *** *p*<0.001 when compared to control; ### *p*<0.001 when comparing 10 ng/ml TGF-β vs. 15 μM H₂O₂ + 10 ng/ml TGF-β.

3.3.6. Intracellular ROS accumulation in chronic oxidant/inflammatory stress model

To examine whether H₂O₂ and inflammatory mediators were able to induce intracellular ROS, cells were exposed to LPS, TNF- α and TGF- β according to the standard combined exposure protocol described previously. Tert-butyl hydroperoxide ((CH₃)₃COOH) was added as a positive control 2 h prior to finishing the experiment. Cells were washed with 1x HBSS and incubated with 10 μ M CM-H₂DCFDA fluorescent probe for 45 min. Intracellular ROS was significantly elevated as a consequence of H₂O₂ treatment alone with an additive effect of combined treatment (control, 105.2 \pm 1.8 %; H₂O₂, 445 \pm 12 %; LPS, 330 \pm 12 %; LPS+H₂O₂, 604 \pm 35 %). Interestingly, LPS (100 and 500 ng/ml) itself was able to enhance the production of intracellular ROS (100ng/ml, 301 \pm 10 %; 500 ng/ml 330 \pm 12 %), but with no significant concentration effect (Figure 3.11 A, B). Thus, intracellular ROS was produced through both H₂O₂ and LPS treatments and significantly increased when both treatments were presented together.

Like LPS, TNF- α (10 ng/ml) caused a significant raise in the level of intracellular ROS (TNF- α , 378.6 \pm 7.8 %) with the combined stimulus significantly enhanced compared to TNF- α challenge alone (TNF- α , 378.6 \pm 7.8 %; TNF- α + H₂O₂, 549.5 \pm 11.7 %), but not compared to H₂O₂ alone (Figure 3.11 C).

Treatments with a range of TGF- β concentrations (1-20 ng/ml) did not enhance the level of intracellular ROS (Figure 3.11 D), and indeed, TGF- β appeared to enhance ROS-inducing effect of H₂O₂, perhaps consistent with an anti-inflammatory function in this particular context (H₂O₂, 219 \pm 3 % vs. TGF- β +H₂O₂, 427.9 \pm 5 %) (Figure 3.11 E).

Figure 3.11. Effect of chronic treatments on intracellular ROS levels in BEAS-2B

Cells were treated as indicated according to the standard combined exposure protocol. **(A and B)** Cells were treated with LPS/ H₂O₂. **(C)** Cells were exposed to 10 ng/ml of TNF- α /H₂O₂. **(D and E)** Cells were exposed to TGF- β (1-20ng/ml)/ H₂O₂. Following the addition of CM-H₂DCFDA fluorescent probe for 45 min, the fluorescence was assessed at 495 and 525 nm. ((CH₃)₃COOH) was added as a positive control 2 h prior to finishing the experiment. Results are expressed as mean \pm SEM (n=4); each experiment was measured in quadruplets. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test. * $p < 0.05$ and *** $p < 0.001$ when compared to control; ## $p < 0.01$ when comparing LPS + H₂O₂ vs. H₂O₂; ### $p < 0.001$ when comparing LPS + H₂O₂ vs. LPS; 15 μ M H₂O₂ + 10 ng/ml TGF- β . # $p < 0.05$ when comparing TNF- α +H₂O₂ vs. TNF- α , also when comparing TGF- β + H₂O₂ vs. TGF- β .

3.3.7. Induction of COPD related genes in BEAS-2B

3.3.7.1. Impact of H₂O₂ \pm LPS, TNF- α or TGF- β on oxidative stress biomarker gene expression

Since it was found that H₂O₂ in chronic exposure synergistically enhanced LPS and TNF- α dependent production of IL-6 and IL-8 (IL-8 only for TGF- β), this implies the involvement of multiple pathways, so it was important to look at mechanisms underlying response to the combined model. Thus, to assess any oxidant stress response, the effect of 15 μ M H₂O₂ alone or in combination with inflammatory mediators (LPS, 500 ng/ml; TNF- α and TGF- β , 10 ng/ml) on the expression of oxidative stress-related genes in BEAS-2B cells, namely *NFE2L2* (Nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2, Nrf2), *SOD2* (Superoxide dismutase) and *CAT* (Catalase) genes were investigated by comparative RT-qPCR. All conditions were compared to control (untreated cells).

The expression of *NFE2L2* that encodes for Nrf2 protein, is one of the important redox-sensitive transcription factor that is responsible for the induction and regulation of anti-oxidant enzymes such as SOD2 and catalase. This gene was not enhanced when cells were treated with LPS (Figure 3.12A) or TNF- α (Figure 3.12D), despite these mediators increasing intracellular ROS. However, treatment with 10 ng/ml of TGF- β , which had no effect on ROS itself, but curtailed H₂O₂-induced ROS, significantly enhanced the expression of *NFE2L2* (4.7 \pm 0.7 fold) (Figure 3.12G). H₂O₂ (15 μ M) alone significantly enhanced the expression of *NFE2L2*

(6.2 ±0.3 fold) (Figure 3.12 A, D, G), showing that a transient (2 h) repeated exposure was sufficient to induce a stress response.

Interestingly, when cells were treated with 15 µM of H₂O₂ in combination with LPS, TNF-α and TGF-β, the expression of the *NFE2L2* gene was significantly promoted compared to control (H₂O₂+LPS, 6.4 ± 0.2; H₂O₂+TNF- α, 3.6±0.2; H₂O₂+TGF- β, 12.7±3.8 fold) (Figure 3.12A, D, G).

The effect on expression of *SOD2*, one of the major antioxidant defence genes against ROS, was also investigated. *SOD2* expression was observed to be significantly heightened when cells were treated with 15 µM of H₂O₂ alone (H₂O₂, 10±1 vs. control 1±0; H₂O₂, 12±3 vs. control 1.06±0.32; H₂O₂, 10.7±3.8 vs. control, 1.03±0.18 fold) (Figure 3.12 B, E, H). However, LPS (500 ng/ml), TNF-α and TGF-β (10 ng/ml) did not significantly affect the expression of *SOD2* (LPS, *p*=0.2; TNF-α, *p*=0.06 ; TGF-β vs. control, *p*= 0.0779) (Figure 3.12 B, E, H), but interestingly the combined treatments of H₂O₂ with LPS, TNF-α and TGF-β potentiated the expression of the *SOD2* gene compared to control (LPS+ H₂O₂, 13.7±1.2, *p*=0.006; TNF- α + H₂O₂, 18.6±2.5, *p*=0.001; TGF-β+ H₂O₂; 10±3, *p*=0.043) (Figure 3.12 B, E, H).

Similar findings were observed with the *CAT* gene. LPS, TNF-α and TGF-β alone had no effect on *CAT* gene mRNA level (Figure 3.12 C, F, I), but treatment with H₂O₂ alone and the combined treatments of H₂O₂ with LPS, TNF-α and TGF-β significantly promoted the expression of *CAT* mRNA gene compared to control (H₂O₂, 9.6±1.4; LPS+ H₂O₂, 13.5±2.1 fold) (Figure 3.12 C) (H₂O₂, 6.1±0.6; TNF-α + H₂O₂, 5.4±0.5 fold) (Figure 3.12F); (H₂O₂, 8.6±1.3;TGF-β+ H₂O₂, 8.6±1.2 fold) (Figure 3.12I).

Figure 3.12. Expression of oxidative stress biomarkers in BEAS-2B cells

Cells were treated with pro-inflammatory mediators and OS according to the standard combined exposure protocol described previously. RNA was extracted and cDNA was produced. The transcript levels of *NFE2L2* (A), *SOD2* (B), *CAT* (C) in presence of LPS alone or in combination with H₂O₂, *NFE2L2* (D), *SOD2* (E), *CAT* (F) in presence of TNF-α alone or in combination with H₂O₂ *NFE2L2* (G) *SOD2* (H) and *CAT* (I) in presence of TGF-β alone or in combination with H₂O₂ were quantified by comparative RT-qPCR using SYBR Green chemistry and were normalised by measuring *GAPDH* transcript levels and applying the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method. Results are expressed as mean \pm SEM (n=3); each experiment was measured in duplicates. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$ when compared to control. # $p < 0.05$ when comparing *SOD2* expression level in treatment with LPS+H₂O₂

3.3.7.2. Impact of H₂O₂ ± LPS, TNF-α and TGF-β on inflammatory genes expression

To examine whether 15 μM H₂O₂ alone or in combination with inflammatory mediators (LPS, 500 ng/ml; TNF-α and TGF-β, 10 ng/ml) had an effect on the expression of inflammatory COPD-related genes in BEAS-2B cells, the level of mRNA expression of *IL8* (Interleukin-8), *IL6* (Interleukin-6), *RELA* (transcription factor p65) and *F2RL1* (Proteinase-activated receptor 2, PAR2) genes were determined by comparative RT-qPCR. All conditions were compared to control (untreated cells). Parallel with ELISA results, H₂O₂ alone had no or only modest effect on *IL8* (Figure 3.13, Figure 3.14 and Figure 3.15 A) and *IL6* (Figure 3.13, Figure 3.14 and Figure 3.15 B) mRNA levels, and as expected, treatments with LPS, TNF-α and TGF-β alone significantly up-regulated the expression of *IL8* (LPS, 8.3 \pm 1.8; TNF-α, 4.2 \pm 1.2; TGF-β, 6.5 \pm 1.7 fold) (Figure 3.13, Figure 3.14 and Figure 3.15A) and *IL6* (LPS, 7 \pm 1; TNF-α, 5 \pm 1; TGF-β, 6 \pm 1

fold) (Figure 3.13, Figure 3.14 and Figure 3.15 B) and the combined treatments significantly promoted the mRNA levels of *IL8* compared to control (LPS+ H₂O₂, 13.9±1.6; TNF-α+ H₂O₂, 6.7±1.6; TGF-β+H₂O₂, 9±2 fold) (Figure 3.13, Figure 3.14 and Figure 3.15 A) and *IL6* (LPS+ H₂O₂, 9±2; TNF-α+ H₂O₂, 11.1±1.4; TGF-β+H₂O₂, 7.8±0.9 fold) (Figure 3.13, Figure 3.14 and Figure 3.15 B). Interestingly, treatments with H₂O₂ significantly enhanced *IL6* expression levels when co-treated with TNF-α compared to treatment with TNF-α alone (TNF-α+ H₂O₂, 13.5±1.7 vs. TNF-α, 6.8±1.2 fold; *p*=0.033) (Figure 3.14 B).

Similar findings were observed with the *RELA* gene, where H₂O₂ alone had no effect on *RELA* gene expression (Figure 3.13, Figure 3.14 and Figure 3.15 C) but the expression of *RELA* was significantly enhanced with LPS and TNF-α alone compared to control (LPS, 5.3±1.1; TNF-α, 9±2 fold), and the *RELA* mRNA expression level was observed to be significantly heightened compared to the control when H₂O₂ was added in combination with LPS and TNF-α (LPS+ H₂O₂, 8.1±1.2,; TNF-α+ H₂O₂, 12.±3,) (Figure 3.13 and Figure 3.14C). In contrast, TGF-β alone or in combination with H₂O₂ had no significant effect on *RELA* transcript levels (Figure 3.17C).

Expression of the *F2RL1* gene, which encodes PAR2 protein, a key receptor vital in orchestrating inflammatory responses involving innate as well as adaptive immunity (Heuberger and Schuepbach, 2019b), was also investigated. Treatments with LPS and TGF-β alone were found to significantly trigger the expression of *F2RL1* (LPS, 9±2 fold; TGF-β, 8.5±2.3 fold) (Figure 3.13 and Figure 3.15 D), with no effect of TNF-α alone (3.14D). Interestingly, H₂O₂ alone and in combination with LPS, TGF-β and TNF-α were all observed to promote the expression of *F2RL1* (Figure 3.13, Figure 3.14 and Figure 3.15D) compared to control (H₂O₂, 12.8±2.6; LPS+H₂O₂, 17.45±2.15) (Figure 3.13D); (H₂O₂, 8±2; TNF- α+ H₂O₂, 4.9±1.3) (Figure 3.14D); (H₂O₂, 7.4 ±1.1; TGF- β+H₂O₂, 12.9±2.3) (Figure 3.15D). Interestingly, LPS alone effectively enhanced the expression of *F2RL1* gene expression compared to control (LPS, 9±2) (Figure 3.13D).

Figure 3.13. Expression of inflammatory genes in response to LPS in BEAS-2B

Cells were treated with LPS and H₂O₂ according to the standard combined exposure protocol. RNA was extracted and cDNA was produced. The transcript levels of *IL8* (A), *IL6* (B), *RELA* (C) and *F2RL1* (D) in presence of LPS alone or in combination with H₂O₂ were quantified by comparative RT- qPCR using SYBR Green chemistry and normalised by measuring *GAPDH* transcript levels and applying the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method. Results are expressed as mean \pm SEM (n=3); each experiment was measured in triplicates. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control.

Figure 3.14. Expression of inflammatory genes in response to TNF-α in BEAS-2B

Cells were treated with TNF-α and H₂O₂ according to the standard combined exposure protocol. The Transcript levels of *IL8* (A), *IL6* (B), *RELA* (C) and *F2RL1*(D) in presence of TNF-α alone or in combination with H₂O₂ were quantified by comparative RT- qPCR using SYBR green chemistry and were normalised by measuring *GAPDH* transcript levels and applying the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method. Results are expressed as mean \pm SEM (n=3); each experiment was measured in triplicates. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$ when compared to control; # $p < 0.05$ when comparing TNF-α + H₂O₂ vs. TNF-α in (B).

Figure 3.15. Expression of inflammatory genes in response to TGF-β in BEAS-2B

Cells were treated with TGF-β and H₂O₂ according to the standard combined exposure protocol. RNA was extracted and cDNA was produced. The transcript levels of *IL8* (A), *IL6* (B), *RELA* (C) and *F2RL1* (D) in presence of TGF-β alone or in combination with H₂O₂ were quantified by comparative RT-qPCR using SYBR green chemistry and were normalised by measuring *GAPDH* transcript levels and applying the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method. Results are expressed as mean \pm SEM (n=3); each experiment was measured in triplicates. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$ when compared to control.

3.3.8. IL-6 and IL-8 expression is mediated via NF- κ B

3.3.8.1. Effect of IKK-2 inhibitor on BEAS-2B cell viability

Since LPS and TNF- α in combination with H₂O₂ enhanced the expression of *IL6* and *IL8* genes and significantly elevated the secretion of IL-6 and IL-8 proteins, and in light of previous literature on the regulation of these cytokines, it was decided to determine whether these proteins were under transcriptional control of NF- κ B. An IKK-2 selective inhibitor, TPCA-1, was pre-incubated prior to induction of chronic oxidative/inflammatory stress. TPCA-1 is a potent inhibitor of IKK- β subunit of I κ B kinase complex, which interferes with NF- κ B DNA binding and expression of many inflammatory genes (Shu *et al.*, 2018). It blocks IKK- β subunit phosphorylation, consequently blocking the phosphorylation of I κ B α and NF- κ B translocation into the nucleus; therefore, attenuate LPS-stimulated airway inflammation (Shu *et al.*, 2018). TPCA-1 was used at concentrations ranging between 0.1-10 μ M (Nan *et al.*, 2014) diluted in DMSO (vehicle) and introduced into the cells 1 h prior to treatments with LPS (500 ng/ml) or TNF- α (10 ng/ml) alone for 48 h continuously or in combination with H₂O₂ (15 μ M) for 2h/day for 3 days. The MTT assay was used to investigate viability changes of BEAS-2B cells following incubation with TPCA-1 followed by treatments with LPS or TNF- α alone or in combination with H₂O₂. IL-6 and IL-8 proteins were ELISA tested in cell supernatant media and mRNA transcript levels were quantified by RT-qPCR.

An MTT assay showed that TPCA-1 (0.1-3 μ M) had no obvious effect on BEAS-2B viability in the presence of LPS or TNF- α alone, while at 10 μ M, cell viability decreased significantly to approximately 30 % with TPCA-1 and LPS compared to LPS alone (LPS + DMSO, 86.9 \pm 5.3 % vs LPS+TPCA-1(10 μ M), 30.2 \pm 1.1 %) and to 26.5 % with TPCA-1 and TNF- α compared to TNF- α alone (TNF- α + DMSO, 88 \pm 5 vs TNF- α +TPCA-1 (10 μ M), 26.5 \pm 1.7 %) (Figure 3.16 A, C). However, when LPS was added in combination with H₂O₂, cell viability was significantly reduced even at lower concentrations of TPCA-1 (0.1-3 μ M), but the majority of cells (>80 %) remained viable up to 3 μ M (Figure 3.16 B). In contrast to LPS in combination with H₂O₂, treatments with TNF- α with H₂O₂ did not affect the viability in co-treatment conditions until 10 μ M TPCA-1 (Figure 3.16 D).

Figure 3.16. The effect of IKK-2 inhibitor on BEAS-2B cell viability

BEAS-2B cells were pre-treated with TPCA-1 (0.1 -10 μ M) diluted in DMSO as a vehicle 1 h prior to including treatments with **(A)** LPS or **(B)** TNF- α alone for 48 h continuously or with LPS /TNF- α in combination with 15 μ M of H₂O₂ **(C, D)** for 2h/day for 3 days. MTT assay was used to assess the effect of IKK-2 inhibition on BEAS-2B cell viability. Results are expressed as mean \pm SEM; n=3; each experiment was measured in triplicates. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test. * p <0.05; ** p <0.01; *** p <0.001 when compared to control. ### p <0.001 when comparing LPS+TPCA-1 to LPS+DMSO **(A)** or LPS + H₂O₂ +TPCA-1 to LPS + H₂O₂ +DMSO **(B)** and when comparing TNF- α +TPCA-1 (10 μ M) to TNF- α + DMSO **(C)** or TNF- α + H₂O₂ + TPCA-1 (10 μ M) to TNF- α + H₂O₂ +DMSO **(D)**.

3.3.8.2. Effect of TPCA-1 on IL-6 and IL-8 release in BEAS-2B cells

To confirm the cell-based activity of TPCA-1, BEAS-2B cells were treated with TPCA-1 at concentrations ranging between 0.1-10 μM (Nan *et al.*, 2014) diluted in DMSO (vehicle) and introduced into the cells 1 h prior to treatments with LPS (500 ng/ml) or TNF- α (10 ng/ml) alone for 48 h continuously or in combination with H₂O₂ (15 μM) for 2h/day for 3 days. IL-6 and IL-8 proteins were ELISA tested in cell supernatant media. TPCA-1 significantly inhibited the production of IL-6 and IL-8 in the presence of LPS alone or in combination with H₂O₂ in a concentration-dependent manner when compared to LPS +DMSO or LPS+ H₂O₂+DMSO.

In both LPS- and combined LPS + H₂O₂ stimulated cells, IL-6 release was suppressed progressively from 0.1 μM to 3 μM , e.g. (LPS 2555 \pm 16 vs LPS+ TPCA-1 (0.1 μM), 1258 \pm 6 pg/ml) (Figure 3.17 A), (LPS+ H₂O₂; 3065 \pm 4 vs. LPS+ H₂O₂ + TPCA-1 (0.1 μM), 2049.7 \pm 18.4 pg/ml) (Figure 3.17 B).

Similar results were obtained for IL-8 in LPS-treated cells (significant inhibition by TPCA-1 concentrations from 0.1 μM) but for the combined LPS+ H₂O₂ challenge, 1 μM TPCA-1 was the minimum effective inhibitory concentration (Figure 3.17 C, D). TPCA-1 at 10 μM curtailed IL-6 and IL-8 release to levels similar to control, but these data could not be interpreted reliably due to the observed effects of this inhibitor concentration on cell viability.

When cells were treated with TNF- α alone or in combination with H₂O₂, a qualitatively similar pattern of inhibition was observed, particularly in the case of IL-6, although 1 μM TPCA-1 was the minimum effective inhibitory concentration for either the single or combined challenge (TNF- α , 701.5 \pm 81.3 vs TNF- α + TPCA-1 (1 μM), 411.9 \pm 54.2 pg/ml) (Figure 3.18A); (TNF- α + H₂O₂, 1287 \pm 112.4 vs TNF- α + H₂O₂ +TPCA-1 (1 μM), 951 \pm 48.5 pg/ml) (Figure 3.18 B). Interestingly, TPCA-1, even at 0.1 μM , effectively suppressed TNF- α or TNF- α + H₂O₂ induced IL-8 secretion (TNF- α 243 \pm 35 vs TNF- α + TPCA-1 (0.1 μM), 52.6 \pm 1.7 pg/ml)(Figure 3.18 C); (TNF- α + H₂O₂, 268.1 \pm 12.3 vs TNF- α + H₂O₂ +TPCA-1 (0.1 μM), 47.1 \pm 2.6 pg/ml)(Figure 3.18 D), indicating a higher degree of NF- κ B dependence for the secretion of IL-8.

Figure 3.17. The effect of TPCA-1 in combination with LPS/ H₂O₂ on IL-6 and IL-8 release in BEAS-2B cells

Cells were pre-treated with TPCA-1 (0.1 -10 μ M) diluted in DMSO as a vehicle 1 h prior to including treatments with LPS alone for 48 h continuously or with LPS in combination with 15 μ M of H₂O₂ for 2h/day for 3 days. (A, B) IL-6 and (C, D) IL-8 proteins were ELISA tested in cell supernatant media. Results are expressed as mean \pm SEM; n=3; each experiment was measured in triplicates. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test *** $p < 0.001$ when compared to control+ DMSO. ## or ### $p < 0.001$ when comparing LPS+TPCA-1 to LPS+DMSO or LPS + H₂O₂+TPCA-1 to LPS + H₂O₂+DMSO.

Figure 3.18. The effect of TPCA-1 in combination with TNF- α /H₂O₂ on IL-6 and IL-8 release in BEAS-2B cells

Cells were pre-treated with TPCA-1 (0.1 -10 μ M) diluted in DMSO as a vehicle 1 h prior to including treatments with 10 ng/ml of TNF- α alone for 48 h continuously or with 10 ng/ml of TNF- α in combination with 15 μ M of H₂O₂ for 2h/day for 3 days. **(A, B)** IL-6 and **(C, D)** IL-8 proteins were ELISA tested in cell supernatant media. Results are expressed as mean \pm SEM; n=3; each experiment was measured in triplicates. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by a Multiple Comparison test * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$ when compared to control+ DMSO. # $p < 0.05$, ## $p < 0.01$, ### $p < 0.001$ when comparing TNF- α + TPCA-1 to TNF- α + DMSO or TNF- α + H₂O₂ + TPCA-1 to TNF α + H₂O₂ + DMSO.

3.3.8.3. Effect of TPCA-1 on IL-6 and IL-8 mRNA expression in BEAS-2B cells

Following assessment of cytokines protein expression, the effect of TPCA-1 on *IL6* and *IL8* mRNA transcript levels was investigated and quantified by RT-qPCR, along with *RELA*. *RELA*, encoding the protein p65, NF- κ B p65 transcription factor belongs to the Rel family. It was important to study the change in the expression level of the *RELA* gene in response to TPCA-1 as the binding of inflammatory stimuli such as TNF- α or LPS has been shown to activate the canonical pathway through the phosphorylation cascade of the kinase (IKK) complex and through a series of mechanism it leads to the translocation of NF- κ B p65 into the nucleus where it binds to the promoter region of inflammatory genes such as *IL-6* and *IL-8* (Sakai *et al.*, 2017). It was decided to use 3 μ M of TPCA-1, as this concentration was effective at inhibiting cytokine release and was well tolerated (Sections 3.3.8.1 & 3.3.8.2).

Consistent with earlier experiments, co-stimulation with 500 ng/ml of LPS or 10 ng/ml TNF- α alone or in combination with 15 μ M of H₂O₂ induced a significant increase of *IL6*, *IL8* and *RELA* in BEAS-2B cells (Figure 3.19 A- F). Consistent with ELISA data, pre-treatment with TPCA-1 robustly prevented the induction of *IL6*, *IL8* and *RELA* mRNA by both LPS and TNF- α , alone and in combination with H₂O₂. For example, *IL6* induction was reduced to almost basal levels with either LPS or TNF- α (LPS+ H₂O₂, 10 \pm 1 fold vs LPS + H₂O₂+TPCA-1, 0.6 \pm 0.2 fold); (TNF- α + H₂O₂, 12 \pm 2 fold vs TNF- α + H₂O₂ + TPCA-1, 1.1 \pm 0.4 fold), with similar patterns apparent for *IL8* and *RELA* (Figure 3.19 A- F).

These data strongly suggest transcriptional regulation as a major part of the mechanism of cytokine down-regulation by TPCA-1, and that both *IL6* and *IL8* induction in this chronic oxidative/inflammatory stress model are likely to be largely mediated by the NF- κ B signalling pathway. Furthermore, the effect on *RELA* expression is supportive of a role for the canonical pathway, whilst not excluding a role for non-canonical mechanisms.

Figure 3.19. Effect of TPCA-1 selective inhibitor on *IL6*, *IL8* and *RELA* transcript levels. Cells were pre-treated with TPCA-1 (3 μM, TPCA-1) followed by the treatment with 500 ng/ml of LPS or 10 ng/ml of TNF-α alone for 48 h continuously or with 15 μM of H₂O₂ in combination with 500 ng/ml of LPS or 10 ng/ml of TNF-α for 2 h/day for 3 days in a repeated exposure manner. The mRNA levels of *IL6*, *IL8* and *RELA* in BEAS-2B cells in response to TPCA-1 with LPS (A, B and C) and TNF-α (D, E and F) were quantified by RT-qPCR and were normalised with respective to *GAPDH* mRNA levels and applying the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method. Results (expressed as fold change) are represented as mean \pm SEM; (n=3); each experiment was measured in triplicates. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by a Multiple Comparison test. ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ when compared to control. # $p < 0.05$, ## $p < 0.01$, ### $p < 0.001$ when comparing LPS + TPCA-1 to LPS or LPS + H₂O₂ + TPCA-1 to LPS + H₂O₂. # $p < 0.05$, ## $p < 0.01$, when comparing TNF-α + TPCA-1 to TNF-α or TNF-α + H₂O₂ + TPCA-1 to TNF-α + H₂O₂.

3.4. Discussion

Previously, a number of OS models (*in vitro* or *in vivo*) have been developed (Marwick, *et al.* 2007; Churg, Cosio and Wright, 2008; Sahiner *et al.*, 2011; Khan *et al.*, 2014); however, short-term based exposure (acute) to ROS was the basis of these experimental models, which may thus fail to appropriately reflect the circumstances of COPD disease development, as the latter arises from chronic exposure to OS. Consequently, this study aimed to establish a chronic transient but repeated exposure to OS model, referred to herein as “standard combined exposure protocol”, featuring repeated chronic exposure to H₂O₂ as an OS for 2 h/day for 3 days - alone or in combination with inflammatory mediators, to mimic (within the limitations of a simple cell model) exposures that might be experienced in smoking (the major recognised COPD driver).

In preliminary work, the optimal seeding density of BEAS-2B cells and optimum concentrations of H₂O₂ as well as for LPS, TGF- β and TNF- α for chronic treatments were determined. This showed that BEAS-2B cells reached optimum viability at seeding density 10⁴ cells/well when seeded in 96-well plate. However, a significant reduction on viability upon treatment with H₂O₂ was observed; cells were later seeded at density 3x10⁴ /well, at which cells better tolerated repeated exposure to 15 μ M of H₂O₂ insult without significant loss of viability or altered morphology (in presence of 10 % FBS). Furthermore, cells exhibited the capacity to survive in presence of 10 ng/ml of TNF- α or TGF- β , as well as, 500 ng/ml of LPS without reducing cell viability. Accordingly, the *in vitro* conditions for modelling chronic oxidative stress were optimised, with 15 μ M H₂O₂ in combination with 10 ng/ml TNF- α or TGF- β or 500 ng/ml LPS was used for chronic treatments of BEAS-2B cells.

Recently, a study conducted by Wilkes and colleagues found that when pancreatic cells were exposed to a ROS-induced drug (2-methoxyestradiol) for 3 months continuously, they acquired strong resistance to this drug due to enhancing levels of antioxidant enzyme SOD2 (Wilkes, Alexander and Cullen, 2017). Previously, it was shown that BEAS-2B cells were able to tolerate up to 100 μ M H₂O₂ when treated in an acute model (for 4 h); however, upon prior

challenge up to 50 μM H_2O_2 for 2h/day for 5 days, these cells were able to tolerate 50 μM of H_2O_2 up to 15 days. This survival was explained in terms of developed resistance due to repeated high chronic exposure to OS inducing antioxidant genes (Khan, 2013).

Previously, Bose et al. demonstrated that lung fibroblasts exhibit stable resistance to very high doses of H_2O_2 (200-1000 μM), but this observation was noticed only when cells were challenged previously by lower doses of H_2O_2 (30 μM) for 7 days. This resistance to OS and enhanced survival was found to be due to the increased enzymatic activities of antioxidants catalase, SOD2, and glutathione peroxidase (Gpx) content (Bose and Bhaumik, 2005). The OS model developed in the current study differ from these studies primarily with concentrations of H_2O_2 used and period of exposure. In these studies they mostly aimed to challenge the cells with higher concentrations of H_2O_2 in order to choose the accepted cytotoxicity with maximum concentrations of H_2O_2 which is appropriate to induce cellular resistance against OS; however, in the present research, the developed OS model represents an “initial-inducing OS phase” model. In this work, it was aimed to induce maximum OS but not inducing significant loss of viability and to maintain a sub-cytotoxic level. Furthermore, in the current study, when BEAS-2B cells were treated with a range of H_2O_2 concentrations (5-75 μM) in a chronic continuous exposure manner for 48 h, the cell viability was significantly reduced and when 25 μM of H_2O_2 was used for 2h/day for 3 days in a repeated exposure manner, the viability was found to be decreased significantly, this observation was reflected by significant reduction of IL-6 and IL-8 secretion levels (data not shown).

In the current study, the expression of two important pro-inflammatory cytokines, IL-6 and IL-8, were analysed. The expression of these cytokines has been importantly linked to disease severity, and they were found to be markedly elevated in BAL fluids, sputum of patients with COPD, and plasma (El-Shimy *et al.*, 2014b). Interestingly, the level of H_2O_2 used in the current chronic exposure system did not have any effect alone, but synergistically enhanced LPS, TNF- α and TGF- β dependent production of IL-8 and IL-6, and these observations were mirrored by *IL6* and *IL8* gene expression. It may be suggested that transient/repeated chronic low exposure to 15 μM H_2O_2 alone induced an alteration in cell sensitivity to OS such that cells

developed their own resistance to ROS over repeated chronic exposure by promoting the expression of antioxidants (Gloire *et al.*, 2006; Caramori *et al.*, 2014) consequently, additional inflammatory stress was required to enhance the production of these key pro-inflammatory cytokines. Alternatively, it can be suggested that a cross-talk between pro-inflammatory pathways and ROS plays a major role in inducing inflammatory mediators. Similar findings were reported by Khan *et al.*, it was shown that when BEAS-2B cells were treated with 50 μM of H_2O_2 alone for 2h/day for 5, 10 and 15 days did not enhance IL-6 or IL-8 secretion, but in combination with 1 ng/ml of TNF- α or IL-1 β added 20 h at last day of treatment (5th, 10th and 15th day), it interestingly enhanced both the expression of *IL6* and *IL8* genes as well as their proteins production (Khan *et al.*, 2014).

In the present research, it was shown that H_2O_2 and interestingly, LPS and TNF- α alone were able to induce significant elevation of intracellular ROS, and the combination treatments enhanced the ROS production. Sul and Ra showed that when A549 cells were treated with 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of LPS for 6 h this induced a significant elevation of intracellular ROS; furthermore, pre-treating cells with quercetin, a natural and potential anti-oxidant (Hu *et al.*, 2015) with anti-viral, anti-carcinogenic (Wu *et al.*, 2015) and anti-inflammatory activities (Rauf *et al.*, 2018), markedly reduced intracellular ROS production in response to LPS. The study confirmed that the inhibition of OS induced by LPS occurred through the suppression of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate oxidase 2 (NOX2) protein due to quercetin (Sul and Ra, 2021).

The lungs are considered the major site of interaction with bacteria (Chaby *et al.*, 2005). LPS has been reported to play a very important role in COPD development and progression (Barnes, 2009; Choi, Lim and Kim, 2018). It was suggested that LPS induces the production and upregulation of ROS species such as O_2^- , H_2O_2 and hydroxyl radical ($\cdot\text{OH}$), either from NADPH oxidase or from the mitochondrial electron transport chain in A549 cells (Lin *et al.*, 2015; Dong and Yuan, 2018). Several studies have demonstrated the production of ROS by LPS, although the source of ROS due to LPS is not fully understood. Glorie *et al.* found that LPS triggers the release of intracellular ROS (Gloire, Legrand-Poels and Piette, 2006; Choi, Lim and Kim, 2018). Also Park and colleagues (Park *et al.*, 2004; Lee *et al.*, 2012) discovered that LPS induced

significant levels of ROS in kidney epithelial cells. ROS generation and activation of the redox-sensitive transcription factor NF- κ B are enhanced due to the direct interaction of Toll-like receptor 4 with a subunit of NADPH oxidase enzyme (NOX4). The main function of NOX4 is to transfer electrons from NADPH to O₂ to generate O₂⁻; the latter is rapidly converted to H₂O₂ and O₂ in cells. ROS generated by NADPH oxidase enzyme can induce signal transduction mechanisms associated with inflammation and immunity in pulmonary epithelial cells (Lambeth, 2007; Choi, Lim and Kim, 2018). Importantly, NOX2 and NOX4 subunits of the NOX family, were reported to be widely expressed in human lung epithelial cells (Carnesecchi *et al.*, 2011). Previous studies revealed that LPS potentiates NADPH oxidase activity, specifically NOX4, thus increases intracellular ROS production in human lung epithelial cells (Wang *et al.*, 2022). Accordingly, it may be speculated that the LPS-induced intracellular ROS generation in the present study could be linked to the activation of NADPH oxidase via LPS-induction and activation of Toll-Like Receptor 4 (TLR4) signalling pathway within the cells; however, the mechanism behind the activation of NOX4 and NOX4-mediated effects due to LPS stimulation is still not fully elucidated (Choi, Lim and Kim, 2018).

It was reported by Sandoval *et al.* that treatments with TNF- α potentially increased the production of ROS in HEK293 cells approximately by 50 % when compared to control, suggesting that the source of ROS is the activation of NADPH oxidase activity by TNF- α (Sandoval *et al.*, 2018). Further studies reported that TNF- α as a pro-inflammatory cytokine induces ROS production through the modulation of NOX activity in different cell types, including lung epithelial cells (Chen *et al.*, 2008; Lin *et al.*, 2016; Blaser *et al.*, 2016). Moreover, IL-6 and IL-1 β are highly involved in ROS generation through NOX enzymes, and this observation was reported in different cellular models (Kim *et al.*, 2010; Pang *et al.*, 2012 ; Kuhn, 2014). It was reported by Russell *et al.* that bronchial epithelial cells differentially expressed NOX1, 2 and 4 isoforms between healthy and COPD patients, favouring the expression of NOX2 and 4 in preference to NOX 1 in patients with COPD, with a significant increase in NOX 2 and NOX 4 (Russell *et al.*, 2016). Accordingly, in the present study, it may be speculated that the production of intracellular ROS by TNF- α alone is due to high

expression of NOX 2 and NOX4 members in BEAS-2B cells, but this requires further investigation to test this possibility.

The present study did not show any effect of TGF- β alone on ROS production, but interestingly when added with H₂O₂ it enhanced ROS production when compared to H₂O₂ alone. Previous studies have confirmed that TGF- β is a potent growth factor that significantly induces ROS production thereby induces OS and imbalance between oxidants and antioxidants; this redox imbalance is importantly linked to the pathological effects of TGF- β including fibrosis (Weidinger and Kozlov, 2015). It was suggested that TGF- β 1 increases mitochondrial ROS generation in different cell types, leading to cell apoptosis, senescence and epithelia-mesenchymal transition (Wu *et al.*, 2014). Similar to TNF- α , TGF- β has been reported to induce ROS generation within lung epithelial cells through the activation of NADPH oxidase (NOX) family, specifically NOX1, 2 and 4; however, the role and induction of NOX4 in TGF- β induced fibrogenesis was the most studied (Liu and Desai, 2015).

NF- κ B is a key transcription factor that is mainly activated by ROS and inflammation in patients with COPD. OS triggers the NF- κ B p65 signaling pathway, promoting the expression of multiple inflammatory genes and release of cytokines that lead to COPD development. NF- κ B is highly activated in COPD, and its activity increases during exacerbations (Zhou *et al.*, 2018). In the present model, H₂O₂ by itself did not have any effect on *IL6*, *IL8* or *RELA* gene expression, its effect was noticeable only when combined with pro-inflammatory mediator TNF- α where it significantly enhanced TNF- α induced *IL6* gene. One possible explanation for this observation is H₂O₂ indirectly primes NF- κ B p65/RelA to robustly respond to LPS, TNF- α and TGF- β signals. A paper reviewed by Lemon and Walker demonstrated that previous studies reported that NF- κ B was activated by micromolar concentrations of H₂O₂ in T lymphocytes, and the activation of NF- κ B was significantly blocked when cells were treated with N-acetyl cysteine (NAC) antioxidant; however, recently, it was recognised that H₂O₂ has a more modulatory role rather than as a direct inducer for NF- κ B signalling (Lemon and Walker, 2019). Furthermore, it was shown that H₂O₂ can trigger the phosphorylation of p65 of a NF- κ B heterodimer by phosphorylating the tyrosine residue 42 on I κ B- α which is targeted

for ubiquitination and degradation by proteasomes. Degradation of I κ B α allows the translocation of the NF- κ B p65/50 dimer into the nucleus, where it binds to promoter regions of inflammatory genes (Lingappan, 2018). Alternatively, H₂O₂ can reduce the activity of Histone Deacetylase 2 (HDAC2) and activates the expression of Histone Acetyl Transferase (HAT). Studies confirmed a modulation of the acetylation/deacetylation balance favouring acetylation in patients with COPD, which results in inflammation (Fischer, Voynow and Ghio, 2015; Zhang *et al.*, 2020); the activation of HAT heightened histone acetylation and enhanced NF- κ B-mediated gene expression (Giridharan and Srinivasan, 2018).

The present study demonstrated significant elevation of antioxidant genes *SOD2* and *CAT* as well as the transcription factor *NFE2L2* in presence of H₂O₂ alone and in combination with other inflammatory mediators. *SOD2* and *CAT* are regulated and induced by the Nrf2 transcription factor in patients with COPD; the expression of these genes and their induced transcription factor were found to be reduced in COPD due to the high levels of OS that impair the antioxidant system (Bellezza, 2018). Several reports have indicated a vital role of Nrf2 in lung diseases; one demonstrating an increased risk of developing emphysema due to the exposure of Nrf2-deficient mice to CS (Harvey *et al.*, 2011; Audousset, McGovern and Martin, 2021). Furthermore, a reduction of Nrf2 expression levels in pulmonary macrophages of COPD patients and smokers was reported (Zhang *et al.*, 2020). Zhang *et al.* also reported that the activation of Nrf2 was down regulated and impaired only in severe COPD patients, and this was highly linked to excessive oxidant burden and abnormally high oxidative stress. The study reported that the stage of COPD disease and the grade of bronchial obstruction can be one of the main determining factors of the response of Nrf2 to OS in patients with COPD (Zhang *et al.*, 2020). Accordingly, in the present study, although the standard combined exposure protocol was able to induce intracellular ROS, it may be suggested that the level of ROS induced by the chronic exposure might not be considered a high abnormal oxidative stress reflecting actual levels of OS in severe COPD conditions that can significantly impair the expression of antioxidant transcription factor Nrf2 and its respective antioxidant enzymes (*SOD2* and catalase). Rather, the increase in antioxidant expression levels described here confirm a 'normal' cellular response to induced intracellular ROS by the standard combined

exposure protocol. This may be more reflective of early disease-promoting events rather than emulating advanced stage disease.

Interestingly, the mRNA transcript levels of the *F2RL1* gene was found to be significantly enhanced by LPS, TGF- β and H₂O₂, alone and in combination compared to the control. Several studies have reported that increased PAR protein expression can induce chronic lung diseases. For instance, the level of PAR2 was found to be significantly higher in asthmatic bronchial epithelium compared to non-asthmatic tissues. Furthermore, studies using animal models showed that LPS-dependent inflammation is associated with enhanced PAR levels (Ostrowska, Sokolova and Reiser, 2007). Furthermore, Jesmin *et al.* showed that the expression of PAR2 increased by 5 to 10-fold in endothelial cells (EC) when they were exposed to LPS *in vitro*, demonstrating an important involvement of PAR2 protein in endotoxemia (Jesmin *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, Chao *et al.* reported that pre-treating vascular EC with LPS (0.1-10 μ g/ml) augmented PAR2 expression and enhanced monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 secretion (Chao *et al.*, 2017).

Previous studies also revealed different regulation of PAR expression by inflammatory mediators in various human respiratory cells cultured *in vitro*. For example, TNF- α induced the expression of PAR2 but not PAR1 in pulmonary artery endothelial cells (Fujiwara *et al.*, 2004). Also, in vascular smooth muscle cells IL-1 β enhanced the expression of PAR2 (Hamilton, Frauman and Cocks, 2001). In pulmonary fibroblasts, TGF- β , a profibrotic growth factor, stimulated PAR2 expression (Gruber *et al.*, 2004). Ostrowska and colleagues identified that LPS upregulated the expression level of PAR2; also they found that LPS in combination with PAR2 activation synergistically enhanced inflammatory signalling in human primary airway epithelial cells by increasing PAR expression level, thus causing a significant increase in IL-8 levels (Ostrowska, Sokolova and Reiser, 2007; Chao *et al.*, 2017).

Widera *et al.* postulated models for potential direct interaction and receptor cooperation between TLR4, the main receptor of LPS, and PAR2, which enhances cytokine release and inflammation (Widera, Aguilar and Cottrell, 2019a). In this chapter, it was demonstrated that

RELA gene, encoding NF-κB p65 protein, was upregulated by pro-inflammatory mediators (LPS and TNF-α) alone and when combined with H₂O₂; however, the expression of *RELA* along with *IL6* and *IL8* genes were down-regulated when TPCA-1 was used; this was mirrored by the significant decrease of IL-6 and IL-8 protein secretion. These data are consistent with the suggestion that inflammation in the present study was mainly caused through the activation of the NF-κB classical pathway, which is activated by LPS and TNF-α stimulants. In a similar study, Khan et al. confirmed that the expression of *IL6* and *IL8* genes were mediated through the expression of NF-κB redox-sensitive transcription factor. In the study conducted by Khan and colleagues, an IKK selective inhibitor known as AS602868 was used in BEAS-2B cells co-treated with IL-1β and H₂O₂. Similar to the findings in the present study, Khan *et al.* found that IKK selective inhibitor completely suppressed *IL6* and *IL8* gene and their respective proteins, thus data from both studies are in agreement, confirming a direct link between NF-κB and inflammation through cytokines production in these cells (Khan *et al.*, 2014). The findings from the current “*standard combined exposure protocol*” model described here further support the potential for NF-κB blockade as a therapeutic strategy to ameliorate chronic inflammation in COPD.

In the next chapter these findings, utilising the BEAS-2B *in vitro* oxidative stress model to define a standard combined exposure protocol, will be further developed and translated to primary human bronchial epithelial cells as a more disease-relevant model system, using H₂O₂ as an oxidant and LPS as model inflammatory stimulus. Following work will also aim to identify potential differences between ‘healthy’ and COPD cells when exposed to OS and inflammatory insult, offering potential disease insight.

Chapter 4. Modelling chronic oxidative and inflammatory stress in normal and COPD primary human bronchial epithelial cells

4.1. Introduction

There is growing evidence that COPD is primarily driven by increased oxidative stress in the lungs, which is accomplished by numerous and interrelated molecular processes (Kirkham and Barnes, 2013b; McGuinness and Sapey, 2017). The accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) impairs and/or overwhelms endogenous antioxidant defences, resulting in oxidative stress. The destruction of the lung parenchyma (emphysema), chronic and persistent inflammation and fibrosis of the small airways are all main features of COPD (Hogg and Timens, 2009; Barnes *et al.*, 2015). A remarkable and clinically important feature of COPD is its failure to resolve even after smoking cessation. It has been suggested that oxidative stress persists in ex-smokers indicating that additional oxidative stress factors arise endogenously, such as persistent infection or autoimmunity, and underlie this striking feature of COPD driving disease progression (Barnes *et al.*, 2015).

Many of the pathogenetic mechanisms underlying COPD and its progression seem to be driven by oxidative stress. Patients with COPD experience higher levels of oxidative stress, especially during acute exacerbations. Smoke from biomass burning, air pollution, and smoking cigarettes are the main exogenous sources of oxidative stress in the lungs. Endogenously, the abundance and activity of alveolar macrophages is greatly enhanced in the lungs of COPD patients compared to healthy individuals, generating greater levels of ROS in the form of superoxide anions and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) (Schaberg *et al.*, 1995; Barnes *et al.*, 2015). Moreover, patients with COPD have more activated neutrophils in their lungs; specifically the activated peripheral blood neutrophils from COPD patients produce more ROS, especially during exacerbations (Noguera *et al.*, 2001; Barnes, 2020). The lungs of COPD patients exhibit elevated levels of lipid peroxidation as represented by the lipid peroxidation marker 4-hydroxy-2-nonenal (4HNE), which reflects the impact of ROS on endogenous lipids (Rahman *et al.*, 2002; Liu and Xu, 2012).

By evaluating different oxidative stress markers in the breath condensate of COPD patients, it has been shown that patients with COPD have increased lung oxidative stress. For example,

patients with COPD exhale more ethane, a volatile byproduct of lipid peroxidation, and this is connected to disease severity (Paredi *et al.*, 2000; Barnes, 2020). COPD patients demonstrate higher levels of H₂O₂, malondialdehyde, 4HNE, and 8-isoprostane in their exhaled breath condensate (Montuschi *et al.*, 2000; Paggiaro *et al.*, 2011; Sutaria *et al.*, 2022), which rise even higher during exacerbations (Biernacki, Kharitonov and Barnes, 2003; Barnes *et al.*, 2015). The enhanced oxidative stress markers continues to increase in ex-smokers, indicating that they have resulted from endogenous oxidative stress and likely reflect persistent lung inflammation (Montuschi *et al.*, 2000; Barnes, 2020). Furthermore, a decrease in endogenous antioxidant defences is a result of increased oxidative stress in COPD patients. For instance, extracellular superoxide dismutase (SOD2) enzymes well known as effective anti-oxidant enzyme and it is a marker of OS in COPD. The expression of SOD2 was found to be significantly lower around small airways compared to sputum from COPD patients (Regan *et al.*, 2011). Numerous antioxidant genes are regulated by the transcription factors FOXO3a (Forkhead box O3a) and Nrf2 (nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2), both of which are decreased in COPD lungs (Hwang *et al.*, 2011; Barnes, Baker and Donnelly, 2019).

Due to its sensitive anatomical makeup, the lung is particularly susceptible to damage from environmental oxidative stress. However, sources of endogenous ROS produced by mitochondrial respiration and inflammatory reactions to bacterial and viral infections within the lung are also persistent sources of endogenous ROS. Oxidative stress persists in COPD because of active neutrophils and macrophages, as well as lung epithelial cells. In fact, lung epithelial cells of COPD patients generate oxidative stress as a result of mitochondrial respiration (Barnes, 2020b). The cytoplasmic ROS-producing enzymes, like membrane-bound NADPH oxidases (NOX), as well as neutrophil-derived myeloperoxidase (MPO) (Kirkham and Barnes, 2013b), are additional intracellular ROS sources. Superoxide anions are relatively weak oxidising agents produced endogenously, primarily by NOX, but they are quickly transformed into more harmful ROS species, such as the hydroxylradicals, or the extremely powerful and harmful peroxynitrite radicals created in the presence of nitric oxide (Osoata *et al.*, 2009; Barnes, 2022). Additionally, MPO generated by active neutrophils deployed into the lungs of COPD patients releases particularly detrimental hypochlorous acid, that also

chlorinates tyrosine residues in proteins, leading to the production of 3-chlorotyrosine, which is elevated in sputum of COPD patients (O'Donnell *et al.*, 2010; Barnes, 2020). In healthy cells, intracellular antioxidant defences are sufficient to effectively sweep up these destructive ROS species, minimising their physiological consequences, however in COPD, these antioxidant defences are overwhelmed.

ROS production may also result in the synthesis of reactive carbonyls via lipid peroxidation and glycooxidation of carbohydrates, which results in the formation of numerous aldehydes that cause protein carbonylation (Negre-Salvayre *et al.*, 2008; Barnes *et al.*, 2015). The accumulation of reactive carbonyls and consequent protein carbonylation is known as 'carbonyl stress,' and it has recently been linked to chronic disease and aging (Zinellu *et al.*, 2016b). Protein carbonylation is found in both smokers and COPD patients and is found to be linked to chronic disease symptoms (Kirkham *et al.*, 2011). Protein carbonylation has the potential to alter protein function, interfering with normal cell function and physiological mechanisms.

More than 50 cytokines and chemokines are secreted in the lungs of COPD patients such as IL-1 β , TNF- α , IL-8 and IL-6 (El-Shimy *et al.*, 2014a). Sputum from COPD patients has higher levels of IL-6, IL-8 and TNF- α , which associate with disease severity (Barnes, 2022). The levels of IL-6 are considerably elevated in plasma, sputum and bronchoalveolar lavage from COPD patients (Khan *et al.*, 2014; Barnes, 2016). Bronchial epithelial cells from COPD patients release more IL-1 β than healthy people, indicating that the cells are pre-programmed to secrete IL-1 β (Rusznak, Mills *et al.* 2000; Barnes 2004; Singh, Arora *et al.* 2010; Khan *et al.*, 2014). IL-8, the most prominent chemokine secreted by neutrophils, is crucially involved in the advanced stages of COPD airway inflammation (Zeng *et al.*, 2019). IL-8 can trigger neutrophils to move toward the inflammatory site, increasing the inflammation there (Higham *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, bronchial epithelial cells are significantly induced to release IL-8 and IL-6 by IL-1 β , a more potent proinflammatory cytokine (Osei *et al.*, 2020). Numerous intracellular signalling pathways that initiate and/or promote the secretion of these pro-inflammatory cytokines are redox-sensitive molecular targets, including the

transcription factor NF- κ B and signalling molecules including Jun-N-terminal kinase (JNK), and p38 mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK). NF- κ B pathways are highly activated by oxidative stress, and NF- κ B expression and activation are heightened in COPD, notably in airway epithelial cells and macrophages (Li *et al.*, 2016). The transcription factor NF- κ B regulates a large number of genes involved in inflammation. Smokers and COPD patients have higher expression of these genes, which are activated by oxidative stress (Caramori *et al.* 2002; Edwards, Bartlett *et al.* 2009; Khan *et al.*, 2014). When activated, NF- κ B binds to the promoter regions of inflammatory genes, causing hyper-acetylation of nearby histones. This enables local DNA unwinding and permits the binding of other transcription factors and transcriptional regulatory complexes. In COPD patients and smokers, cigarette smoke has been proven to promote histone acetylation and boost NF- κ B activity (Schuliga, 2015c).

Numerous antioxidant genes are regulated by the transcription factor Nrf2, whose function appears to be compromised in COPD cells, because it does not respond to ROS by increasing activity as it does in healthy cells (Zhao *et al.*, 2017). This may be due to the fact that Nrf2 is acetylated in COPD cells as a result of decreased HDAC2, and this acetylated form does not efficiently transactivate antioxidant genes like heme oxygenase-1, which plays a protective role in the lungs (Mercado *et al.*, 2011; Barnes, 2020).

About 90% of people with COPD are either smokers or ex-smokers, and in developed countries, COPD is predominantly triggered by prolonged exposure to the oxidative stress derived from cigarette smoke. Chapter 3 described the characterisation of an *in vitro* oxidative stress (OS) model based on a chronic repeated exposure of BEAS-2B cells to oxidative stress insult, modelled by H₂O₂ and inflammatory mediators (LPS, TGF- β or TNF- α) according to “standard combined exposure protocol” described previously in Chapter 2.

The role of OS and inflammatory stimulants on pro-inflammatory cytokines production (IL-6 and IL-8), and on the expression of COPD-related biomarkers was investigated. Furthermore, a key role for NF- κ B in the expression and regulation of IL-6 and IL-8 genes was delineated.

In order to better understand these processes at a cellular level in a more disease-relevant system, work described in this chapter utilised both normal (from healthy donors) and COPD primary human bronchial epithelial cells (HBEC/COPD-HBEC), and the *in vitro* oxidative stress model was adapted to these cell types; treatments of primary cells were limited to H₂O₂ alone or in combination with LPS only without considering other inflammatory mediators (TGF- β and TNF- α), due to more limited access to and replication of primary cells, which also exhibited slower growth rates than the BEAS-2B line. LPS was detected to play a very important role in COPD development and progression. LPS which is known also as endotoxin, is a major constituent of the outer cell membrane of gram negative bacteria and it stimulates the activation of the innate immune response after binding to Toll like receptor 4 (TLR4) (Akira, Uematsu and Takeuchi, 2006). LPS has been used experimentally in patients with asthma to cause acute neutrophilic airway inflammation. LPS can also increase the recruitment of neutrophils in the airways of COPD patients causing an elevation in inflammation levels (Gupta *et al.*, 2015).

4.1.1. Hypothesis

It was hypothesised that the cellular response to oxidative stress (H₂O₂) and inflammatory stimuli (LPS) of HBEC and COPD-HBEC may share similarities but also exhibit differences that need to be identified, compared to BEAS-2B cells. Furthermore, the responses of COPD-HBEC may differ quantitatively and/or qualitatively to those of HBEC, offering potential disease insight.

4.1.2. Aims

1. To investigate whether findings using the BEAS-2B *in vitro* oxidative stress model can be also translated to primary cells, considering key experiments only, using H₂O₂ as an oxidant and LPS as model inflammatory stimulus.

2. To study the effect of both H₂O₂ and LPS alone or in combination on the production of inflammatory mediators (IL-6 and IL-8), the mRNA gene expression of COPD-related biomarkers, and intracellular ROS in HBEC and COPD-HBEC.
3. To compare the cellular responses of HBEC to COPD-HBEC under key experimental conditions.
4. To investigate the role of NF-κB in oxidative stress-induced inflammation in HBECs and COPD-HBEC.

4.2. METHODS

4.2.1. Standard combined exposure protocol

Primary cells (HBEC and COPD-HBEC) were chronically treated with H₂O₂ (25 μM or 50 μM) for 2h/day for 3 days in a chronic repeated transient model. Alternatively, primary cells were also treated chronically for 48 h continuously with 500 ng/ml of LPS. Also, cells were treated with H₂O₂ (25 μM or 50 μM) in combination with LPS (500 ng/ml) for 2h/ day for 3 days, the combined treatments were then replaced with 500 ng/ml of LPS alone every day after the 2h treatment, LPS was kept all the time and replaced each day with H₂O₂ in combination with LPS. This developed model was referred to “*standard combined exposure protocol*” (Further details in Chapter 2 Sections 2.2.3 & 2.3).

4.2.2. Effect of H₂O₂ and LPS (alone or in combination) on the viability of primary cells

An MTT assay was used to assess primary cell viability after being treated with different insults according to the “*standard combined exposure protocol*”. Cells were then washed with pre-warmed PBS and were incubated with 10 μl of MTT reagent in 90 μl pre-warmed media at 37°C and 5% CO₂ for 2 h. At the end of the incubation 80 μl of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was added to lyse the cells and they were incubated for 30 min at 37°C until cells have lysed and purple crystals have dissolved. The absorbance was measured at λ570 nm in a plate reader (BioTeK) using GENE5 software (Further details in Chapter 2 Section 2.4.1).

4.2.3. Measurement of intracellular ROS production using Dichlorofluorescein assay

Primary cells were seeded in 96-well black plates at a density 6×10^4 cells/well 24 h prior to being treated according to the “standard combined exposure protocol”. At the end of the experiment, culture media with treatments were removed and cells were washed with 1x HBSS buffer and then incubated with 10 μ M of CM-H₂DCFDA for 45 min in HBSS buffer in the dark. Tert-Butyl hydroperoxide ((CH₃)₃COOH) of concentration 100 μ M was introduced to cells as a positive control 2 h prior to finishing the experiment. The fluorescence of the cells from each well was detected and measured by fluorescence microtitre plate reader. Fluorescein intensity was correlated to intracellular ROS (Refer to Chapter 2 Section 2.8).

4.2.4. Measurement of pro-inflammatory cytokines protein production from treated cells

Primary cells were seeded in 24- well plates for 24 h at density 8×10^4 cells/well. Cells were further treated according to the “standard combined exposure protocol”. At end of treatment day, supernatant was removed and tested for IL-6 and IL-8 production by ELISA according to manufacture protocol (Refer to Chapter 2 Section 2.5).

4.2.5. COPD related genes expression measured by RT-qPCR in primary cells

HBEC and COPD-HBEC were seeded in 24 well plate at density 8×10^4 cells/well and treated according to the “standard combined exposure protocol”. Total RNA was extracted, converted to cDNA and subjected to RT-qPCR analysis using SYBR Green chemistry. The amount of *IL6*, *IL8*, *RELA*, *F2RL1*, *CAT*, *SOD2*, *NFE2L2*, *IL1 β* and *NFkB2* were normalised by measuring *GAPDH* and *EIF* transcript levels and applying the $\Delta\Delta$ Ct method (Refer to Chapter 2 Sections 2.6.1,2.6.3,2.6.4 and 2.7).

4.2.6. Effect of TPCA-1 (IKK β inhibitor) on IL-6 and IL-8 gene expression and protein production

HBEC and COPD-HBEC cells were pre-treated with TPCA-1 (5 μ M) diluted in DMSO as a vehicle for 1 h, followed by treatment with LPS (500 ng/ml) alone or in combination with H₂O₂ (25 μ M) according to the “standard combined exposure protocol”. Cell viability was assessed by MTT assay. Supernatants were assayed for IL-6 and IL-8 production by ELISA according to manufacture protocol. RNA was extracted from treated/untreated cells, cDNA was synthesised and RT-qPCR was performed to detect the mRNA transcript levels of *IL6*, *IL8* and *RELA* genes.

4.3. RESULTS

4.3.1. The effect of chronic repeated exposure to H₂O₂ and LPS on primary cell viability and morphology

4.3.1.1. Estimating cell viability by metabolic activity assay

Metabolic activity assay (MTT- tetrazolium salt) was used as an indication of cell viability in both HBEC and COPD-HBEC to demonstrate the effect of chronic treatment with oxidative stress modelled by H₂O₂ alone or in combination with inflammatory stimuli (LPS) on cell viability. Initially cells were treated chronically in a repeated exposure manner for 2h/day for 3 days to a range of H₂O₂ concentrations (5-75 μ M) alone. The cell viability was significantly reduced in both HBEC and COPD-HBEC even at the lowest H₂O₂ concentration (5 μ M) to less than 70 %, in case of HBEC (Figure 4.1 A), cell viability reduced gradually to reach approximately 50 % at 25 μ M of H₂O₂ and below 50 % at 50 μ M; whereas in case of COPD-HBEC (Figure 4.1 C), cell viability was reduced to approximately 65 % with 5 μ M and remained unchanged at higher concentrations, to significantly drop again to less than 50 % at 75 μ M H₂O₂. The presence of LPS alone (500 ng/ml) did not have any effect on HBEC, but dramatically reduced the HBEC cell viability to 60 % in combination with 25 μ M H₂O₂ (Figure 4.1 B);

however, LPS significantly affected COPD-HBEC alone or in combination with 50 μM H_2O_2 (Figure 4.1 D). In contrast to BEAS-2B cells, it was demonstrated that primary cells were able to tolerate higher concentrations of OS when treated chronically in a repeated transient exposure manner.

Examination of primary cells by inverted microscope revealed that chronic treatments with higher concentrations of H_2O_2 (50 μM in HBECs and 75 μM in COPD-HBECs) significantly reduced the cell viability and altered cell morphology from a well-defined polygonal shape to rounded shape (Figure 4.2) demonstrating that the cells were under stress conditions due to chronic treatments. However, lower concentrations of H_2O_2 (5 - 25 μM in HBEC and 5 - 50 μM in COPD-HBEC) did not change cellular morphology, and images showed that the majority of the cells remained viable and attached. Accordingly, to study and compare the cellular response of HBEC and COPD-HBEC to different stimulants, representing a significant challenge falling short of overt/excessive cytotoxicity, 25 μM was considered the optimum concentration of H_2O_2 and was used in further experiments to directly compare responses of both HBEC with COPD-HBEC.

Figure 4.1. The effect of repeated oxidative stress and inflammatory stimulants on cell viability estimated via MTT

HBEC (A) and COPD-HBEC (C) were exposed chronically in a repeated exposure manner for 2 h/day for 3 days to a range of H₂O₂ concentrations (5-50 μM for HBEC and 5-75 μM for COPD-HBEC) alone or in combination with LPS (500 ng/ml) (B and D). Viability was assessed by MTT assay. Results are expressed as mean ± SEM (n=4). **p*<0.05, ***p*<0.01, ****p*<0.001 (Control vs. treated).

Figure 4.2. Effect of H₂O₂ on HBEC and COPD-HBEC morphology

HBEC and COPD-HBEC were treated with 25 50 and 75 μM of H₂O₂ for 2 h/day for 3 days in a chronic repeated transient exposure manner. At the end of treatments, cells were washed with 1X PBS and imaged using Evos microscope (BF) at magnification lens 10X objective. Results are representative of 4 independent experiments.

4.3.1.2. Characterisation of primary cells morphology after chronic treatments

HBEC and COPD-HBEC were imaged using the bright field filter of an EVOS microscope (ThermoFisher Scientific) in order to confirm that chronic treatments with H₂O₂ for 2 h/day for 3 days that might induce cellular stress did not have an excessive effect on cell viability (approximately 75 % viability was considered suitable) or morphology. Cells were treated with 25 µM of H₂O₂ in HBEC (Figure 4.3) and 25 µM or 50 µM of H₂O₂ in COPD-HBEC (Figure 4.4) at the end of the experiment cells were washed with warm 1x PBS, PBS was removed and cells were quickly imaged using 20x objective lens. Treatments with OS at chosen concentrations did not have any obvious effect on primary cell morphology. Although the MTT results indicated that OS and inflammatory stimulant induced a significant reduction in cell viability (Figure 4.1), as shown here the majority of cells remained viable after repeated transient exposure for 2h/day for 3 days. This suggests that the challenge applied to cells had an effect short of overt cytotoxicity, perhaps retarding cell proliferation.

Figure 4.3. Effect of H₂O₂ on HBEC morphology

HBEC were treated with 25 μM H₂O₂ for 2 h/day for 3 days in a chronic repeated transient exposure manner. At the end of treatments, cells were washed with 1X PBS and imaged using Evos microscope (BF) at magnification lens 20X objective. Results are representative of 4 independent experiments

Figure 4.4. Effect of H₂O₂ on COPD-HBEC morphology

COPD-HBEC were treated with 25 μM or 50 μM H₂O₂ for 2 h/day for 3 days in a chronic repeated transient exposure manner. At the end of treatments, cells were washed with 1X PBS and imaged using Evos microscope (BF) at magnification lens 20X objective. Results are representative of 4 independent experiments.

4.3.2. The effect of H₂O₂ alone or in combination with LPS on intracellular ROS in primary cells

To examine whether exogenous LPS and H₂O₂, alone and in combination, were able to induce oxidative stress within the cells by elevating intracellular ROS, cells were incubated with CM-H₂DCFDA fluorescent probe for 45 min after stimulant exposure. As expected, intracellular ROS was elevated compared to control when H₂O₂ was added to both HBEC (H₂O₂, 426.3±30.7 %) and COPD-HBEC (H₂O₂, 288.8±28.5 %). Interestingly, LPS alone was able to induce oxidative stress compared to control in HBEC (LPS, 316.6±23.8 %) and COPD-HBEC (LPS, 243.1±28.7 %). Importantly, the combined treatments markedly potentiated the level of intracellular ROS in both cell types compared to the treatments with H₂O₂ alone (HBEC, H₂O₂+LPS, 792.6±70.8 vs. H₂O₂, 426.3±30.7; COPD-HBEC, H₂O₂+LPS, 440.5±42.4 vs. H₂O₂, 288.8±28.5 %); indeed to a level higher than the positive control ((CH₃)₃COOH) (Figure 4.5 A and B).

To demonstrate whether or not LPS had a synergistic effect on intracellular ROS in combination with H₂O₂, paired *t*-tests were performed to compare the sum of intracellular ROS values of LPS and H₂O₂ treatments and those of the combined treatments (LPS + H₂O₂). This did not show any significant difference between the sum of treatments and combined treatments in either cells type (Figure 4.5 C and D), suggesting that chronic treatments with LPS and H₂O₂ did not have any synergistic effect but additively enhanced the production of intracellular ROS. Similar observations were reported in BEAS-2B cell line.

Furthermore, the level of intracellular ROS as a result of OS (H₂O₂) insult and inflammatory stimuli (LPS) were compared between HBEC and COPD-HBEC. Figure 4.5 E shows no significant difference in intracellular ROS between HBEC and COPD-HBEC when treated with LPS and H₂O₂ alone, although COPD-HBEC had elevated baseline intracellular ROS levels compared to HBEC (COPD-HBEC, 166.5±15.8 vs. HBEC, 100 %). Interestingly, the intracellular ROS level produced as a result of combined treatments from HBEC was significantly higher than in COPD-HBEC (HBEC, H₂O₂+LPS, 792.6±70.8 vs. COPD-HBEC, H₂O₂+LPS, 440.5±42.4 %). Together with the elevated basal ROS of COPD-HBEC, this perhaps suggests that cells from COPD

patients exhibit reduced sensitivity to exogenous ROS-generating stimuli, whilst experiencing a persistent, elevated ROS load. The reduced response to $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{COOH}$ in COPD-HBEC would appear to be consistent with this view.

Figure 4.5. Effect of chronic treatments on intracellular ROS levels in primary cells. (A and B) HBEC and COPD-HBEC were treated according to the “*standard combined exposure protocol*” following the addition of CM-H₂DCFDA fluorescent probe for 45 min, the fluorescence was assessed at 495 and 525 nm. ((CH₃)₃COOH) was added as a positive control 2 h prior to finishing the experiment. **(C and D)** Paired *t*-test was used to test the synergism between the sum of 500 ng/ml LPS and 25 μM H₂O₂ treatments versus combined treatments in both HBEC and COPD-HBEC. The dot-plot graph shows a quantitative analysis of intracellular ROS in chronic H₂O₂/LPS treated cells. Results are expressed as mean ± SEM (n=5); each experiment was measured in triplicates. **(E)** Intracellular ROS levels as a result of different treatments in HBEC vs COPD-HBEC. In A&B, data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test. In C&D, data were analysed using paired *t*-test. * *p*<0.05; ** *p*<0.01 and *** *p*<0.001 when compared to control; # *p*<0.05; ### *p*<0.001 when comparing LPS + H₂O₂ vs. H₂O₂. In E, Two-way ANOVA test was used to compare HBECs and COPD-HBEC: * *p*<0.05. ** *p*<0.01. *** *p*<0.001 when comparing COPD-HBEC to HBEC.

4.3.3. Spontaneous cytokine release in COPD-HBEC

The baseline levels of pro-inflammatory mediators (IL-6 and IL-8) released from HBECs and COPD-HBECs were next investigated. Figure 4.6 presents a significant elevation of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-6 (Figure 4.6 A) and IL-8 (Figure 4.6 B) in COPD-HBEC compared to HBEC (IL-6, COPD-HBEC, 526.6 ± 96.8 vs HBEC, 212.2 ± 22.4 pg/ml; IL-8; COPD-HBEC, 526.6 ± 96.8 vs HBEC, 212.2 ± 22.4 pg/ml) demonstrating increased production and release of pro-inflammatory cytokines at baseline within COPD-HBEC which supports the rationale of spontaneous increase in cytokines levels in COPD-HBEC compared to HBEC.

Figure 4.6. Comparison of IL-6 and IL-8 spontaneously released by healthy and COPD-HBEC Human primary epithelial cells were cultured for 24 h after which the conditioned media was collected. The conditioned media was tested for pro-inflammatory cytokine concentrations **(A)** IL-6 and **(B)** IL-8 by ELISA. Results were analysed using unpaired *t*-test and are represented as mean \pm SEM (n=5); ** p <0.01, *** p <0.001 when comparing COPD-HBEC to HBEC.

4.3.4. LPS/H₂O₂-stimulated secretion of pro-inflammatory mediators in healthy and COPD-HBEC

4.3.4.1. Cytokines release in healthy HBEC

The effect of oxidative stress derived from H₂O₂ on pro-inflammatory mediators (IL-6 and IL-8) release from HBEC was investigated. Cells were treated according to the “*standard combined exposure protocol*” described in Chapter 2. As expected, and similar to what observed in BEAS-2B cells, LPS alone induced a significant elevation of IL-6 (LPS, 535.7±73.3 pg/ml) and IL-8 (LPS, 258.4±27.5 pg/ml); however, chronic exposure to H₂O₂ did not have any effect on cytokine production (IL-6, control, 120.2±22.1 vs H₂O₂, 72.1±25.7 pg/ml; IL-8, control, 68.2±3.4 vs H₂O₂, 57.9±5.7 pg/ml). Interestingly, the combined treatments significantly heightened IL-8 (LPS+H₂O₂, 568.8±51.3 vs LPS, 258.4±27.5 pg/ml), but not IL-6 (LPS+H₂O₂, 772.8±173.3 vs LPS, 535.7±73.3 pg/ml) levels, when compared to LPS alone (Figure 4.7 A and B). Paired *t*-test demonstrated that H₂O₂ synergistically enhanced LPS-dependent production of IL-8 (Figure 4.7 D) but not IL-6 in this chronic exposure model (Figure 4.7 C), suggesting a role of H₂O₂ as oxidative stress in promoting the selective release of pro-inflammatory mediator (IL-8) in combination with other stimuli.

Figure 4.7. LPS/H₂O₂-induced pro-inflammatory mediators release in HBEC.

HBEC were treated chronically with LPS (500 ng/ml) and H₂O₂ (25 μM) according to the “*standard combined exposure protocol*”. The secretion of IL-6 and IL-8 were tested by ELISA. Bar graphs show quantitative analysis of IL-6 (A) and IL-8 (B) in chronic H₂O₂ treated cells in the absence and presence of 500 ng/ml of LPS. (C and D) Paired *t*-test was used to assess treatment synergy, comparing the sum of 25 μM of H₂O₂ and LPS (500 ng/ml) treatments versus combined treatments. The dot-plot graph shows quantitative analysis of IL-6 and IL-8 in chronic H₂O₂ treated cells in the presence of 500 ng/ml of LPS. Results are expressed as mean ± SEM (n=5 independent experiments); each experiment was measured in triplicate. In A&B, data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test. * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$ when compared to control; ### $p < 0.001$ (LPS 500 ng/ml vs. 25 μM H₂O₂ + 500 ng/ml LPS). In C&D, data were analysed using Paired *t*-test. ** $p < 0.01$, when comparing sum of 25 μM of H₂O₂ and LPS 500 ng/ml vs. 25 μM H₂O₂ + 500 ng/ml of LPS treatments.

4.3.4.2. Cytokines release in COPD-HBEC

In this study, it was aimed to make a direct comparison of cellular response between HBEC and COPD-HBEC under identical experimental conditions, for this reason, the cytokines released by COPD-HBEC under low chronic oxidative stress conditions using 25 μM of H_2O_2 were studied. In contrast to what was observed in BEAS-2B cells and in HBEC, the increased secretion observed with 500 ng/ml of LPS alone did not reach significance when compared to control and similar to what was observed with BEAS-2B cells and HBEC, H_2O_2 alone did not enhance IL-6 production, conversely, the level of IL-6 mediator significantly elevated compared to control when cells were exposed chronically to 25 μM of H_2O_2 in combination with 500 ng/ml of LPS, but this did not reach statistical significance when compared to LPS alone (LPS+ H_2O_2 , 719.8 \pm 97.2 vs LPS, 504.1 \pm 43.9 pg/ml) (Figure 4.8 A).

Since it was observed that COPD cells were able to tolerate a higher concentration of H_2O_2 , it was decided to also examine the impact of combined inflammatory challenges at the higher H_2O_2 concentrations (50 μM), which will allow exploring if synergy operates at these higher OS levels in COPD-HBEC that have already been established to be less sensitive to H_2O_2 than HBEC.

However, COPD-HBEC were able to tolerate up to 50 μM H_2O_2 (Section 4.3.1.1), for this reason, it was important to check the cytokines released from COPD-HBEC under chronic oxidative stress treatments. Results from treatments with 50 μM H_2O_2 revealed a similar trend to what was observed with 25 μM H_2O_2 (Figure 4.8 A), where IL-6 levels significantly increased compared to the control only when 50 μM of H_2O_2 were added in combination to LPS; however, in contrast to 25 μM H_2O_2 , 50 μM H_2O_2 in combination with 500 ng/ml LPS significantly induced IL-6 levels compared to LPS treatment alone (LPS+ H_2O_2 , 769.8 \pm 96.2 vs LPS, 504.1 \pm 43.9 pg/ml) (Figure 4.8 A) and this effect of H_2O_2 was found not to be synergistic when paired *t*-test was performed where (Figure 4.8 B, $p>0.05$). When comparing directly the level of cytokine produced when cells were treated with both concentrations of H_2O_2 . Figure 4.8 A demonstrated that COPD-HBEC had the same response when treated with low chronic

(25 μM of H_2O_2) and high chronic (50 μM of H_2O_2) OS concentrations as no significant differences were observed between the two conditions.

Figure 4.8. LPS/ H_2O_2 -dependent production of IL-6 in COPD-HBEC

Cells were treated with 500 ng/ml of LPS and H_2O_2 (25 μM or 50 μM) according to the “*standard combined exposure protocol*”. The secretion of IL-6 was ELISA tested. **(A)** Bar graph show quantitative analysis of IL-6 in low and high chronic H_2O_2 treated cells in the absence and presence of 500 ng/ml of LPS. **(B)** Paired *t*-test was used to assess treatment synergy, comparing the sum of 50 μM of H_2O_2 and LPS (500 ng/ml) treatments versus combined treatments. The dot-plot graph shows quantitative analysis of IL-6 in chronic H_2O_2 treated cells in the presence of 500 ng/ml of LPS. Results are expressed as mean \pm SEM (n=4 independent experiments); each experiment was measured in triplicate. In A, data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test. $P > 0.05$ when no significant difference was shown; *** $p < 0.001$ when compared to control; # $p < 0.05$ (LPS 500 ng/ml vs. 50 μM H_2O_2 + 500 ng/ml LPS). In B, data were analysed using Paired *t*-test

In contrast to IL-6 production, and similar to what observed in BEAS-2B and HBEC, IL-8 released from COPD-HBEC significantly increased in the presence of 500 ng/ml of LPS alone (control, 351.7 ± 38.4 vs LPS, 724.1 ± 70.17 pg/ml), as well as in combination with, either 25 μ M of H₂O₂ (LPS + H₂O₂, 1845 ± 92 pg/ml) (Figure 4.9 A) or 50 μ M of H₂O₂ (LPS + H₂O₂, 1115 ± 148 pg/ml) (Figure 4.9 B) when compared to control. Also, the repeated exposure to 25 or 50 μ M of H₂O₂ in combination with 500 ng/ml of LPS significantly enhanced the level of IL-8 compared to 500 ng/ml of LPS alone (LPS + H₂O₂ (25 μ M), 1845 ± 92 vs LPS, 975 ± 71 pg/ml; LPS + H₂O₂ (50 μ M), 1115 ± 148 vs LPS, 724.1 ± 70.17 pg/ml). Accordingly, it was instructive to verify if there was any synergistic effect of repeated chronic exposure to low (25 μ M) or high (50 μ M) oxidative stress on LPS-dependent production of IL-8, in order to gain mechanistic insight; indeed the paired *t*-test demonstrated a synergistic effect of H₂O₂. Interestingly, the synergism was detected only when COPD-HBEC were exposed to low chronic 25 μ M of H₂O₂ in combination with 500 ng/ml of LPS but not at high chronic OS exposure (50 μ M of H₂O₂) in combination with 500 ng/ml of LPS (Figure 4.9 C and D, $P > 0.05$). Interestingly, when comparing IL-8 production in COPD-HBEC in presence of 25 μ M of H₂O₂ with LPS to 50 μ M of H₂O₂ with LPS, it was found that IL-8 secretion level was significantly higher when 25 μ M of H₂O₂ compared to 50 μ M of H₂O₂ when added to LPS (Figure 4.9 E) and this can be related to COPD-donor heterogeneity, which may explain the lower response at 50 μ M.

Figure 4.9. Chronic exposure to OS synergistically enhanced the LPS-dependent production of IL-8 in COPD-HBEC
 COPD-HBEC were treated chronically with LPS (500 ng/ml) and H_2O_2 (25 or 50 μM) according to the “standard combined exposure protocol”. The secretion of IL-8 were tested by ELISA. Bar graphs show quantitative analysis of IL-8 in chronic 25 μM (A) and 50 μM (B) of H_2O_2 treated cells in the absence and presence of 500 ng/ml of LPS. (C and D) Paired *t*-test was used to assess treatment synergy, comparing the sum of 25 or 50 μM of H_2O_2 and LPS (500 ng/ml) treatments versus combined treatments. The dot-plot graph shows quantitative analysis of IL-8 in low and high chronic H_2O_2 treated cells in the presence of 500 ng/ml of LPS. (E) Level of IL-8 secretion in HBEC vs COPD-HBEC under low and high OS concentrations. Results are expressed as mean \pm SEM (n=5 independent experiments); each experiment was measured in triplicate. In A&B, data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ when compared to control; ### $p < 0.01$ (LPS 500 ng/ml vs. 50 μM H_2O_2 + 500 ng/ml LPS), ### $p < 0.001$ (LPS 500 ng/ml vs. 25 μM H_2O_2 + 500 ng/ml LPS). In C&D, data were analysed using Paired *t*-test. * $p < 0.05$, when comparing sum of 25 μM of H_2O_2 and LPS 500 ng/ml vs. 25 μM H_2O_2 + 500 ng/ml of LPS treatments. In E, Two-way ANOVA was performed to directly compare the IL-8 released from COPD-HBEC under low and high H_2O_2 concentrations.

When comparing protein secretion levels of IL-6 and IL-8 between HBEC and COPD-HBEC, it no significant change in IL-6 and IL-8 levels were observed (Figure 4.10 A). However, treatments with oxidative stress and inflammatory stimulants heightened the level of IL-8 protein in COPD-HBECs compared to HBEC (Figure 4.10 B), over and above the markedly elevated basal secretion, supporting an important role for IL-8 as a key pro-inflammatory mediator in COPD.

Figure 4.10. Comparison of LPS/H₂O₂-dependent cytokine production between HBEC and COPD-HBEC Primary cells were treated with 25 μM of H₂O₂ alone or in combination with 500 ng/ml of LPS according to “standard combined exposure protocol”. Supernatant media were tested for the production of IL-6 (A) and IL-8 (B) by ELISA. Results represent the mean ± SEM; n=5; ***p<0.001 when comparing HBEC to COPD-HBEC.

4.3.5. Effect of H₂O₂ and LPS on COPD-related genes in healthy and COPD HBEC

4.3.5.1. Spontaneous increase in COPD related gene expression in COPD-HBEC

To examine whether or not 25 μ M H₂O₂ had a direct effect alone or in combination with 500 ng/ml of LPS in the expression of COPD-related genes, potential differences in gene expression of inflammatory-related genes (*IL6*, *IL8*, *F2RL1*, *RELA* and *IL1B*) and OS biomarkers (*SOD2*, *CAT* and *NFE2L2*) at baseline levels between healthy and COPD cells were first assessed. Results showed potential elevation in mRNA transcript levels of inflammatory biomarkers *IL6* (2.2 \pm 0.2 fold), *IL8* (6.9 \pm 1.1 fold), *F2RL1* (4.9 \pm 0.8 fold), *RELA* (2.1 \pm 0.2 fold) and *IL1B* (3.5 \pm 0.3 fold) (Figure 4.11 A, B, C, D and E) and oxidative stress gene *catalase* (3.4 \pm 0.7 fold) (Figure 4.11 F) in COPD-HBEC compared to HBEC. No differences were observed in the mRNA expression of *NFE2L2* or *SOD2* mRNA between cell types (Figure 4.11 G and H).

Figure 4.11. Expression of pro-inflammatory genes and oxidative stress biomarkers at baseline levels
 HBEC and COPD-HBEC were seeded in 24 well-plates and left for 24 hrs. Cells were collected, RNA was extracted and cDNA was synthesised. Expression of inflammatory genes *IL6* (A), *IL8* (B), *F2RL1* (C), *RELA* (D), *IL1B*(E), *CAT*(F), *NFE2L2* (G) and *SOD2* (H) were quantified by comparative RT-qPCR using SYBR Green chemistry and were normalised by measuring *GAPDH* transcript levels and applying the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method. Results are expressed as mean \pm SEM (n=3); each experiment was measured in duplicates. Data were analysed using unpaired *t*-test between HBEC and COPD-HBEC. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; when compared to control (HBEC).

4.3.5.2. Effect of LPS/H₂O₂ on COPD-related gene expression in HBECs and COPD-HBEC

To investigate the effect of H₂O₂ alone or in combination with LPS on the expression of COPD-related genes in healthy and COPD cells, the level of the mRNA expression level of each gene was determined by comparative RT-qPCR. All conditions were compared to control (untreated cells). Similar to what was observed in BEAS-2B cells previously, in this study, H₂O₂ (25 μM) alone had no effect on *IL6*, *IL8*, *RELA* and *NFKB2*, mRNA levels in either healthy or COPD cells (Figure 4.12 and Figure 4.13 A, B, C and D); furthermore, in contrast to what reported in BEAS-2B cells, in both HBEC and COPD-HBEC, this concentration of H₂O₂ alone did not induce the expression levels of *CAT*; however, the combined treatments promoted the mRNA level of *CAT* in COPD-HBEC only when compared to control (H₂O₂+LPS, 3.9±0.4 fold change)(Figure 4.12 and Figure 4.13 H). Interestingly, H₂O₂ (25 μM) alone or in combination with LPS enhanced the expression of the *F2RL1* gene in HBEC (H₂O₂, 4.2±1.2; H₂O₂+LPS, 5.3±1.1 fold change) and in COPD-HBEC compared to control (H₂O₂, 2.9±0.6; H₂O₂+LPS, 4.9±0.7 fold change)(Figure 4.12C and Figure 4.13 E). In contrast to COPD-HBEC, the mRNA transcript levels of *NFE2L2* were induced when HBEC were treated with H₂O₂ alone (7.9±1.2 fold change) and with the combined stimulus (H₂O₂+LPS, 10.8±3.1 fold change) (Figure 4.12 F). *SOD2* expression was observed to be significantly heightened due to H₂O₂ alone or in combination with LPS in HBEC (H₂O₂, 11.6±3.3; H₂O₂+LPS, 15.1±2.2 fold change) (Figure 4.12 G) and in COPD-HBEC (H₂O₂, 5.1±1.6; H₂O₂+LPS, 9.8±2.1 fold change) compared to control (Figure 4.13 G).

Similar to the findings in BEAS-2B cells, LPS alone had no significant effect on *NFKB2*, *NFE2L2*, *SOD2*, and *CAT* in both HBEC and COPD-HBEC (Figure 4.12 and Figure 4.13 D, F, G and H), but opposite to what observed in BEAS-2B cells, treatments with LPS, alone did not have any significant effect on the mRNA level of *F2RL1* gene expression in both HBEC and COPD-HBEC (Figure 4.12 and 4.13 E). However, treatments with LPS alone enhanced *IL6*, *IL8* and *RELA* in both healthy and COPD cells when compared to control (*IL6*, HBEC, 3.6±0.9, COPD-HBEC, 4.1±0.7; *IL8*, HBEC, 5.2±0.7; COPD-HBEC, 6.8±0.5; *RELA*, HBEC, 3.8±0.5; COPD-HBEC, 10.3±1.2 fold change) (Figure 4.12 and Figure 4.13 A, B and C) and this is similar to what observed in BEAS-2B cells.

The combined treatments (H₂O₂+LPS) significantly elevated the expression of inflammatory genes *IL6*, *IL8* and *RELA* in HBEC and COPD-HBEC when compared to control (*IL6*; HBEC, 5.3±0.7; COPD-HBEC, 3.5±0.6; *IL8*; HBEC, 10.7±1.9; COPD-HBEC, 16.8±1.5; *RELA*; HBEC, 10.6±2.6; COPD-HBEC, 16.7±1.7 fold change). Importantly, the co-treatment with LPS and further chronic repeated treatments with H₂O₂ significantly enhanced the expression of *IL8* and *RELA* mRNA transcripts compared to LPS alone in both HBEC and COPD-HBEC (*IL8*; HBEC, H₂O₂+LPS, 10.7±1.9 vs LPS, 5.2±0.7; *p*=0.032; COPD-HBEC, H₂O₂+LPS, 16.8±1.5 vs LPS, 6.8±0.5, *p*=0.005; *RELA*, HBEC, H₂O₂ +LPS, 10.6±2.6 vs LPS, 3.8±0.5; COPD-HBEC; 16.7±1.7 vs LPS, 10.3±1.2, *p*= 0.0149 fold change), suggesting an additive or synergistic effect of H₂O₂ on LPS-induced *IL8* and *RELA* gene expression in both healthy and COPD cells (results are not presented here) (Figure 4.12C and Figure 4.13 B and C).

Figure 4.12. Expression of COPD-related biomarkers in healthy HBEC

Cells were treated with 25 μM of H₂O₂ alone or in combination with 500 ng/ml of LPS according to the “standard combined exposure model”, RNA was extracted and cDNA was produced. The transcript levels of *IL6* (A), *IL8* (B), *RELA* (C), *NFKB2*(D), *F2RL1*(E), *NFE2L2* (F), *SOD2* (G) and *CAT* (H) were quantified by comparative RT-PCR using SYBR Green chemistry and were normalised by measuring *GAPDH* transcript levels and applying the ΔΔCt method. Results are represented as mean ± SEM (n=3); each experiment was measured in duplicates; Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$ when compared to the control; # $p < 0.05$ when comparing LPS and H₂O₂ to LPS alone.

Figure 4.13. Expression of COPD-related biomarkers in COPD-HBEC

Cells were treated with 25 μM of H₂O₂ alone or in combination with 500 ng/ml of LPS according to the “standard combined exposure model”, RNA was extracted and cDNA was produced. The transcript levels of *IL6* (A), *IL8* (B), *RELA* (C), *NFKB2*(D), *F2RL1*(E), *NFE2L2* (F), *SOD2* (G) and *CAT* (H) were quantified by comparative RT-PCR using SYBR Green chemistry and were normalised by measuring *GAPDH* transcript levels and applying the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method. Results are represented as mean \pm SEM (n=3); each experiment was measured in duplicates; Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by a Multiple Comparison test. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to the control; # $p < 0.05$; ## $p < 0.001$ when comparing LPS and H₂O₂ to LPS alone.

The stimulated mRNA transcript levels of COPD-biomarkers were compared between HBEC and COPD-HBEC, and results demonstrated a potential increase in *IL8* and *CAT* expression in COPD-HBEC compared to HBEC (although the latter appears to merely reflect basal expression differences). However, *SOD2* gene expression in response to LPS/H₂O₂ was reduced in COPD-HBEC compared to HBEC (Figure 4.14 B, E, and F). No significant changes in stimulated levels of *IL6*, *F2RL1*, and *RELA* were observed between HBEC and COPD-HBEC (Figure 4.14 A, C and D).

Figure 4.14. The effect of oxidative stress and inflammatory stimulants on COPD-related genes in HBECs vs. COPD-HBECs

Cells were cultured in the presence of 25 μM H₂O₂ alone or in the presence of LPS (500 ng/ml) prior to RNA extraction and cDNA synthesis. Relative expression of *IL6* (A), *IL8* (B), *F2RL1* (C), *RELA* (D), *SOD2* (E) and *CAT* (F) were quantified by comparative RT-PCR using SYBR Green chemistry and were normalised by measuring *GAPDH* mRNA transcript level reference gene and applying the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method in HBEC vs COPD-HBEC. Results are represented as mean \pm SEM (n=3); each experiment was measured in duplicates; Data were analysed using Two-way ANOVA was used to demonstrate the difference in COPD-related gene expression between the two cell types.

4.3.6. IL-6 and IL-8 secretion are mediated via the NF- κ B signalling pathway

Similarly to BEAS-2B cells, in this present study the work was extended to use TPCA-1 to determine whether the expression and production of IL-6 and IL-8 were directly controlled by NF- κ B. Therefore, an IKK β selective inhibitor, TPCA-1, was used at a concentration of 5 μ M (Khan *et al.*, 2014) diluted in DMSO (vehicle) and introduced into the cells 1 h prior to treatments with H₂O₂ (25 μ M) and LPS (500 ng/ml) according to “*standard combined exposure protocol*”. The MTT assay was used as an indication of cell viability. IL-6 and IL-8 proteins were ELISA tested in cell supernatant media and mRNA transcript levels were quantified by RT-qPCR. Results from the MTT assay showed that the prepared vehicle (DMSO+media) did not affect the cell viability of HBEC or COPD-HBEC, either at baseline level or when treated with OS in combination with inflammatory stimulant LPS (Figure 4.15 A and B). Moreover, the cell viability for both HBEC and COPD-HBEC was not significantly compromised at 5 μ M of TPCA-1 (Figure 4.15 and B).

Figure 4.15. The effect of TPCA-1 on HBEC and COPD-HBEC cell viability

HBEC and COPD-HBEC were pre-treated with TPCA-1 (5 μM) diluted with DMSO as a vehicle 1 h prior to including treatments according to “*standard combined exposure protocol*”. MTT assay was used to assess the effect of TPCA-1 on primary cells viability. Results are expressed as mean ± SEM; n=3; each experiment was measured in triplicates. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test.

The addition of DMSO as a diluent for TPCA-1 did not affect the basal secretion of IL-6 or IL-8 in either HBEC or COPD-HBEC and when treated with 500 ng/ml of LPS and 25 μ M of H₂O₂ (Figure 4.16 and Figure 4.17 A and B). Co-stimulation with H₂O₂ and LPS induced a potential release of IL-6 and IL-8 protein levels which was completely suppressed by the IKK-2 (TPCA-1) inhibitor in both HBEC and COPD-HBEC (Figure 4.16 and Figure 4.17 A and B). Comparing cell types directly, no significant difference in IL-6 or IL-8 protein levels was detected between HBEC and COPD-HBEC when cells were treated with 500 ng/ml of LPS and 25 μ M of H₂O₂ in presence of TPCA-1 (Figure 4.18 A and B), suggesting robust and effective inhibition in both cell types.

Figure 4.16. The effect of TPCA-1 on IL-6 release in HBEC and COPD-HBEC

Cells were treated (or not) with 25 μ M of H₂O₂ and 500 ng/ml of LPS in media containing DMSO as a vehicle for TPCA-1. HBEC (A) and COPD-HBEC (B) were pre-treated with TPCA-1 (5 μ M), followed by treatment with 25 μ M of H₂O₂ and LPS (500 ng/ml) for 2h/day for 3 days. The IL-6 secretion levels in both HBEC and COPD-HBEC was assayed by ELISA. Results are presented as mean \pm SEM (n=4); each experiment was measured in triplicates. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test; *** $p < 0.001$ when comparing to the control+DMSO; ### $p < 0.001$ when comparing LPS + H₂O₂ + DMSO to LPS + H₂O₂ + TPCA-1.

Figure 4.17. The effect of TPCA-1 on IL-8 release in HBEC and COPD-HBEC

Cells were treated (or not) with 25 µM of H₂O₂ and 500 ng/ml of LPS in media containing DMSO as a vehicle for TPCA-1. HBEC (A) and COPD-HBEC (B) were pre-treated with TPCA-1 (5 µM), followed by treatment with 25 µM of H₂O₂ and LPS (500 ng/ml) for 2h/day for 3 days. The IL-8 secretion level was assayed by ELISA. Results are presented as mean ± SEM (n=4); each experiment was measured in triplicates. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by Multiple Comparison test; *** *p* < 0.001 when comparing to the control+DMSO; ### *p* < 0.001 when comparing LPS + H₂O₂ + DMSO to LPS + H₂O₂ + TPCA-1.

Figure 4.18. Effect of TPCA-1 on LPS-dependent IL-6 and IL-8 secretion; comparison of healthy and COPD HBEC.

The LPS-dependent production levels of IL-6 (A) and IL-8 (B) in the presence and absence of TPCA-1 (5 μM) were assayed by ELISA and compared between HBEC and COPD-HBEC using Two-way ANOVA. Results are represented as mean ± SEM; (n=4); *** $p < 0.001$ when comparing HBEC and COPD-HBEC (LPS (500 ng/ml) + H₂O₂ (25 μM)).

Furthermore, the effect of the TPCA-1 on *IL6* and *IL8* mRNA transcript levels was investigated and quantified by RT-qPCR in both HBEC and COPD-HBEC, along with *RELA*. Co-stimulation with 25 μ M of H₂O₂ in combination with 500 ng/ml of LPS induced a significant increase of *IL6*, *IL8* and *RELA* in HBEC (Figure 4.19 A, B and C) and COPD-HBEC (Figure 4.19 D, E and F). Consistent with ELISA data, the pre-treatment with TPCA-1 robustly prevented the induction of *IL6*, *IL8* and *RELA* mRNA by LPS and H₂O₂ in both HBEC (Figure 4.19 A, B, and C) and COPD-HBEC (Figure 4.19 D, E and F), suggesting transcriptional regulation as at least part of the mechanism of cytokine down-regulation. These data strongly suggest that the expression of pro-inflammatory genes (*IL6* and *IL8*) are mediated by the NF- κ B signalling pathway in this *in vitro* oxidative stress model, and the effect on *RELA* expression is supportive of a role for the canonical pathway, whilst not excluding a role for non-canonical mechanisms.

Figure 4.19. The effect of TPCA-1 on *IL6*, *IL8* and *RELA* transcript levels

Cells were pre-treated with TPCA-1 (5 μM) or remained un-treated followed by the treatment with 25 μM H₂O₂ in combination with 500 ng/ml of LPS for 2 h/day for 3 days in a repeated exposure manner. The mRNA levels of *IL6*, *IL8* and *RELA* in HBEC (A, B and C) and COPD-HBEC (D, E and F) were quantified by RT-qPCR (SYBR Green chemistry) and were normalised with respect to *GAPDH* mRNA levels and applying the ΔΔCt method. Results (expressed as fold change) are represented as mean ± SEM; (n=3); each experiment was measured in triplicates. Data were analysed using One-way ANOVA followed by a Multiple Comparison test. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control. # $p < 0.05$, ## $p < 0.01$, ### $p < 0.001$ when comparing LPS + H₂O₂ + TPCA-1 to LPS + H₂O₂.

The mRNA transcript levels of *IL6*, *IL8* and *RELA* were compared between HBEC and COPD-HBEC stimulated with H₂O₂ in combination with LPS, with or without TPCA-1. Although there was a significant difference in *IL8* mRNA levels in COPD-HBEC compared to HBEC in the absence of TPCA-1 (*IL8*; LPS (500 ng/ml) + H₂O₂ (25 μM); COPD-HBEC, 18.7±1.2 vs HBEC, 9.9±2.7 fold change), results demonstrated that no significant change on the mRNA levels of *IL6* (Figure 4.20 A), *IL8* (Figure 4.20 B) and *RELA* (Figure 4.20 C) between HBEC and COPD-HBEC when cells were pre-treated with TPCA-1.

Figure 4.20. The effect of TPCA-1 on *IL6*, *IL8* and *RELA* transcript levels

Cells were pre-treated or kept untreated with TPCA-1 (5 μM) followed by the treatment with 25 μM H₂O₂ in combination with 500 ng/ml of LPS for 2 h/day for 3 days in a repeated exposure manner. The mRNA levels of *IL6*, *IL8* and *RELA* in HBEC and COPD-HBEC were quantified by RT-qPCR (SYBR Green chemistry) and were normalised with respect to *GAPDH* mRNA levels and applying the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method. Results (expressed as fold change) are represented as mean \pm SEM; (n=3); each experiment was measured in triplicates. Data were analysed using Two-way ANOVA followed by a Multiple Comparison test. ** $p < 0.01$ when comparing when comparing HBEC and COPD-HBEC.

4.4. Discussion

Several cell types have been used as models to investigate the effect of OS and inflammation in COPD including primary cell cultures and cell lines cultured in 2D and 3D models. Cell lines such as bronchial epithelial cells (BEAS-2B cells) as utilised in Chapter 3 are widely used and established to model the pulmonary epithelium in the study of respiratory lung diseases; also primary human bronchial epithelial cells from healthy and COPD donors (HBEC and COPD-HBEC) as described in this chapter can be used importantly as a more disease-relevant system, to validate initial findings drawn from immortalised models. Regardless of the cell source, using primary cells has the benefit of allowing researchers to examine cells from particular patients that have respiratory illnesses such as COPD and consequently having increased risk for the selected inhaled toxin (Cipollina *et al.*, 2022). As a drawback, when compared to cell lines such as BEAS-2B cells, these are more challenging to obtain as they are directly isolated from human participants, produce widely variable results due to inherent donor heterogeneity, and require a higher sample size to generate statistically significant results. Additionally, they require expensive culture media and supplements.

The initial aim of this work was to compare primary human bronchial epithelial cells from healthy (HBEC) and COPD donors (COPD-HBEC) to BEAS-2B cell line in order to establish if these cells respond similarly to pro-inflammatory stimuli modelled by LPS and oxidative stress stimuli modelled by H₂O₂. Moreover, it was important to address any quantitative and qualitative differences in response to inflammatory and oxidative stress stimulants between HBEC and COPD-HBEC, providing potential disease insights. In contrast to BEAS-2B cells, treatments of primary cells were limited to LPS as pro-inflammatory mediator, without considering TNF- α and TGF- β . Recently, LPS has been considered an interesting inflammatory marker in COPD, especially it strongly reflects the model of bacterial COPD exacerbation. Bacterial lipopolysaccharide (LPS) prompts ROS generation through multiple mechanisms including the hyper-activation and induction of NADPH oxidase, and *in vivo* models showed that if LPS inhaled at very high concentrations, it causes repression of anti-oxidative enzymes (SOD2 and catalase) that are important in ROS clearance (Li *et al.*, 2010). LPS is thought to play

a very important role in COPD development and progression. LPS, known also as bacterial endotoxin, is a major constituent of the outer cell membrane of gram-negative bacteria and a contaminant in CS and air pollution; it stimulates the activation of the innate immune response after binding to Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4) (Akira, Uematsu and Takeuchi, 2006). LPS has been used experimentally in animal models with asthma to cause acute neutrophilic airway inflammation (Ghorani *et al.*, 2017). LPS can also increase the recruitment of neutrophils in the airways of COPD patients, causing an elevation in inflammation levels (Gupta *et al.*, 2015).

In the characterisation work demonstrated in Chapter 3, BEAS-2B cells were found to be able to tolerate up to 15 μM of H_2O_2 without significant loss of cell viability; however, the combined treatment with LPS produced significant cellular stress, though a majority of cells remained viable. Repeated exposure to a range of H_2O_2 for 3 days induced a significant decrease in cell viability in both HBEC and COPD-HBEC, both groups of primary cells but cells, they were able to withstand higher repeated H_2O_2 insult (interestingly exhibiting different sensitivity; 25 μM in HBEC, 50 μM in COPD-HBEC) compared to BEAS-2B. Although MTT assays showed a significant decrease in viability after chronic treatment of cells, microscopy demonstrated that the majority of cells remained viable after chronic treatments with 25 μM in HBEC and 50 μM in COPD-HBEC of H_2O_2 even in combination with LPS; this may indicate that cells were challenged sufficiently to enhance cellular stress and retarding cell proliferation. This supposition may be addressed in future work directly using a cell proliferation assay such as ^3H -thymidine metabolic incorporation assay to monitor cell proliferation, or directly through Trypan Blue exclusion.

Similar to what was observed with BEAS-2B cells (Chapter 3), the oxidative stress indicator dye (CM- H_2DCFDA) revealed that treatments with LPS and H_2O_2 alone or in combination potentiated the production of intracellular ROS in both HBEC and COPD-HBEC. However, the combined treatments did not have any synergistic effect, but enhanced the production of intracellular ROS in an apparently additive fashion. Interestingly, when comparing HBEC to COPD-HBEC, the intracellular ROS level of combined treatments from HBEC was significantly

higher than in COPD-HBEC. This might be explained by a persistent and elevated load of ROS due to endogenous sources in COPD-HBEC (as was observed), thus leaving these cells with reduced sensitivity to exogenous ROS stimuli. OS that is generated endogenously within the lungs of COPD patients mainly arises from activated neutrophils and macrophages (Fischer, Voynow and Ghio, 2015b). In patients with COPD, airway lung epithelial cells also generate OS via mitochondrial respiration that causes the production of mitochondrial ROS (mROS) which is considered a major source of OS in COPD (Birch, Barnes and Passos, 2018; Cloonan *et al.*, 2020) and inflammatory responses to toxic inhaled pathogens such as viruses and bacteria (Van Der Toorn *et al.*, 2009). Other sources of endogenous ROS include cytoplasmic ROS generating enzymes such as membrane-bound NADPH oxidases (NOX) and neutrophil-derived myeloperoxidase (MPO)(Sies, Berndt and Jones, 2017).

The work was extended to investigate the level of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-6 and IL-8) produced at baseline from HBEC and COPD-HBEC and when treated with LPS/H₂O₂. As anticipated there was a spontaneous cytokine increase secreted from COPD-HBEC compared 'healthy' HBEC, suggesting an increased inherent pro-inflammatory phenotype in COPD cells. Over 100 different cytokines and chemokines are produced in COPD, which amplify and perpetuate lung inflammation; these include IL-6, IL-8 and IL-1 β (Barnes, 2017). Some observational studies revealed that IL-6 levels were markedly higher in the peripheral blood of COPD patients, and this was linked to more rapid loss of FEV₁ (Garcia-Rio *et al.*, 2010; Hussein *et al.*, 2022).

Additionally, a study by Rossi *et al.* demonstrated clearly a significantly high level of circulating cytokines in COPD patients from smokers compared to ex-smokers and to non-smokers, suggesting a role of OS in promoting inflammation (Rossi *et al.*, 2017). Interestingly in this study, when cells were treated with H₂O₂ alone (25 or 50 μ M) in a chronic system, this did not affect the production of IL-6 and IL-8, but synergistically enhanced LPS dependent production of cytokines (only IL-8 but not IL-6); this observation was similar to that observed in BEAS-2B cells when treated with LPS in combination with 15 μ M of H₂O₂, suggesting that repeated chronic exposure to H₂O₂ (either low or high) may have altered cell sensitivity to OS

by inducing antioxidant genes, and thus further stimulus was required to enhance pro-inflammatory pathways, resulting in a different pattern of inflammatory/immune gene expression (Khan *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, treatments with H₂O₂ (25 µM) and LPS (500 ng/ml) synergistically potentiated the level of IL-8 in both HBEC and COPD-HBEC; however, IL-8 levels was found to be significantly heightened in COPD-HBEC compared to HBEC as a response to treatments with oxidative stress and inflammatory stimulants, supporting a key role for IL-8 as a major inflammatory mediator in COPD. One study conducted by El-Shimy *et al.* analysed IL-8 levels in serum and BAL in fifty COPD patients, (25 patients suffering from severe COPD, 25 from mild and moderate COPD); 10 healthy subjects were used as controls. Results from this study confirmed significantly higher levels of IL-8 in serum and BAL of COPD patients compared to healthy donors, and the level of IL-8 was markedly higher in severe conditions compared to mild and moderate COPD (El-Shimy *et al.*, 2014b). In addition, Zhang *et al.* demonstrated a direct correlation between higher IL-8 levels and frequent COPD exacerbations compared to non-frequent exacerbators (Zhang and Bai, 2018).

When comparing cytokines release from COPD-HBEC in presence of low (25 µM) or high (50 µM) H₂O₂ in combination with 500 ng/ml of LPS, the absolute IL-8 (though not IL-6) levels secreted were lower with the high chronic OS. The most likely explanation for this observation is that the higher concentration of OS may be more effective in inducing a state of partial resistance to OS as only response to combined stimulus is significantly lower when cells treated with high concentration of H₂O₂ compared to lower concentration. Consistent with what observed in BEAS-2B, the use of TPCA-1 as NF-κB pathway inhibitor significantly suppressed IL-6 and IL-8 protein secretion in both cell types, and parallel to this data, the mRNA induction of *IL6*, *IL8* and *RELA* were completely prevented by the IKK-2 inhibitor. Interestingly, the inhibitor appeared even more effective in COPD cells; this may be related to higher expression of *RELA* gene in COPD cells at baseline, suggesting that in this simple oxidative stress model, (both in primary cell types and BEAS-2B) the expression of these pro-inflammatory cytokines is mediated largely via the NF-κB signalling pathway.

The work was extended to check the mRNA expression levels of COPD-related genes (OS and inflammatory biomarkers) in HBEC and COPD-HBEC at baseline and when treated with LPS/ H₂O₂ alone or in combination. Parallel with ELISA results, at baseline levels, COPD-HBEC demonstrated increased basal expression of pro-inflammatory genes (*IL6* and *IL8*), as well as, elevated levels of *F2RL1*, *RELA* and *IL1B*. In terms of OS response genes, only *CAT* mRNA levels was found to be potentiated in COPD-HBEC compared to HBEC but not *SOD2* or *NFE2L2* transcript levels, when OS response genes were assessed. This discrepancy could be explained by either impaired anti-oxidant effect, due to OS generated endogenously within COPD-HBEC resulting in de-sensitisation, or perhaps because the level of OS was not high enough to trigger *SOD2* or *NFE2L2* anti-oxidant genes expression. The elevated levels of *IL6*, *IL8* and *IL1B* gene expression were as expected in COPD-HBEC. IL-1 β is considered a key pro-inflammatory biomarker in COPD, its overexpression is highly linked with infiltration of neutrophils and enlargement of the distal airspaces, and it is highly associated with increased sputum production in COPD patients (Lappalainen *et al.*, 2005; Eerden, 2019).

Similar to what was observed with BEAS-2B cells and consistent with ELISA data, in both cell types, as expected, LPS treatments enhanced induction of *IL6* and *IL8*. Also, treatments with 25 μ M of H₂O₂ alone had no effect on the expression of *IL6* and *IL8*, its effect was only noticeable when combined with LPS with an additive or synergistic effect on LPS dependent production of *IL8* transcripts, suggesting a pivotal role of ROS in the induction of key pro-inflammatory genes at mRNA level. This observation was further noticed for *RELA* gene expression; similar to the observation in BEAS-2B cells, LPS induced *RELA* expression with no effect of H₂O₂ alone, but significantly enhanced or synergistically increased the expression of *RELA* in combination with LPS in both cell types.

As explained previously, it has been suggested that the LPS dependent induction of inflammation is mainly mediated through OS, modelled here by H₂O₂. *RELA* encodes the protein NF- κ B p65, a master transcription factor in COPD. The activation of NF- κ B p65 occurs largely due to response to inflammatory insults (LPS, TNF- α and IL-1 β), also it is a redox regulator, being highly influenced by oxidant/anti-oxidant imbalance, suggesting a role for OS

in inducing the NF- κ B canonical pathway (Schuliga, 2015d) (see discussion of Chapter 3 for more details). In this chapter, the expression of the member of NF- κ B family was assessed to shed further light on the hypothesis that the expression of *IL6* and *IL8* genes are mediated through the classical NF- κ B pathway. The activation of *NFKB2* is mediated through the non-classical NF- κ B pathway which is activated in the development of lymphoid organs and the adaptive immune system (Sasaki and Iwai, 2015) and triggered by the interaction of stimuli such as LT β , BCAF and CD40 via their distinct receptors (Khan *et al.*, 2014). Results from this study showed no significant change in the level of *NFKB2* in both cell types when treated with H₂O₂ and LPS, so these findings (*RELA* induced, *NFKB2* not induced) are consistent with the idea that the classical NF- κ B pathway is induced and consistent with the proposed hypothesis of classical activation; however, further investigation should be performed for confirmation. However, a study conducted by Zhou *et al.* suggests a role for multiple NF- κ B pathways. In their study, these workers demonstrated a significant overexpression of NF- κ B genes (*NFKB1*, *NFKB2*, *cREL* and *RELA*) in patients with COPD compared to healthy subjects. Interestingly, it was found that among the NF- κ B genes family, *NFKB2* and *c-REL* were significantly over-expressed compared to *RELA* and *NFKB1* in COPD patients, and this was linked with increased IL-1 β , IL-8 and COX-2 levels, suggesting that the alternative NF- κ B pathway has a vital role that is related to COPD (Zhou *et al.*, 2018).

The transcript levels of OS biomarkers that were demonstrated here with *SOD2*, *CAT* and *NFE2L2* were detected in both cell types ('healthy', COPD) when treated with LPS/ H₂O₂ alone or in combination. Results showed that the activation of *NFE2L2* gene is induced in HBEC only but not in COPD-HBEC when treated with H₂O₂ alone or in combination with LPS; this can be explained by the substantial induction of ROS as a result of H₂O₂ (but not LPS) in healthy, but not in COPD cells. This observation in COPD-HBEC can be speculated as a result in COPD cells being less responsive to OS than healthy as they under OS conditions and data from intracellular ROS supports this observation or that the anti-oxidative stress machinery in COPD-HBEC is overwhelmed with OS that impairs the expression of *NFE2L2* gene levels.

NFE2L2 gene encodes the protein Nrf-2, a redox-sensitive transcription factor that regulates the expression of phase 2 anti-oxidant genes (*SOD2*, *CAT* and *GSH*) and confers cytoprotection against OS (Bellezza, 2018). Nrf2 is highly activated in normal smokers, but its activation is impaired in COPD due to OS through epigenetic modification (post-translational modification)(Audousset, McGovern and Martin, 2021b), consistent with the current findings. When the level of OS is high, a reduction of histone deacetylase (HDAC)-2 activity in COPD lung tissues promotes oxidation and protease activity, this is linked with an increase in histone acetylation (H4) localised to the promoter of *IL8*. The down regulation of HDAC2 impairs Nrf2 activation in the lung; also this is linked to increased NF- κ B mediated gene transcription (To *et al.*, 2017).

Interestingly, *SOD2* gene expression was reduced in COPD-HBEC compared to HBEC when LPS and H₂O₂ were presented in combination; this important observation may imply reduce protective response to challenges in COPD cells. SOD is an antioxidant enzyme that catalyses the dismutation of O₂⁻ to oxygen and H₂O₂. The study of SOD activity in COPD has been mainly assessed in COPD erythrocytes or in the plasma of COPD patients. However, contradicting results have been observed, as some studies found an increase in SOD activity (Montaño *et al.*, 2010), whilst others demonstrated a decrease (Zeng *et al.*, 2013), or no difference in SOD activity between COPD patients and healthy controls (Barreiro *et al.*, 2013).

The increase in *CAT* gene expression, encoding catalase protein (antioxidant enzyme) in COPD-HBEC can be explained by the increase in the ROS that are generated due to the exposure treatments, in addition to the endogenous ROS. Catalase is the main anti-oxidant defense a H₂O₂-mediated toxicity, and is normally very effective when H₂O₂ is produced. At normal levels, catalase is able to detoxify H₂O₂ into oxygen and water (Ben Anes *et al.*, 2014); however, when oxidants elevated to a very high levels, this can alter the oxidant/anti-oxidant balance favouring oxidants that can overwhelms the antioxidant machinery, thus impairs catalase activity and significantly reduces *CAT* activity (Zinellu *et al.*, 2016c). Ahmad *et al.* recorded a significant decrease in erythrocyte SOD activity as well as catalase activity in COPD patients compared to healthy subjects, and this was directly linked to very high levels of OS

(Ahmad, Shameem and Husain, 2012b). This was also reported previously by some studies that demonstrated a significant down regulation in antioxidant enzymes during severe or chronic oxidant exposure in healthy individuals (Singh *et al.*, 2017).

The qPCR results also demonstrated a significant higher level of *F2RL1* transcript encoding PAR2 protein in COPD-HBEC compared to HBEC at baseline. In contrast to what was found in BEAS-2B cells, the mRNA levels of this gene significantly increased only when H₂O₂ was presented alone or in combination with LPS, suggesting an important role of OS in modulating the expression of PAR2, which is well known to play a vital role in promoting inflammation.

The activation of PARs is initiated by proteolytic-mediated cleavage of the extracellular region of the receptors, which is orchestrated by serine-proteases. Trypsin-Like Serine Proteases (TLSPs), including tryptase, neutrophil elastase and matriptase are all activating proteases for PAR2 (Heuberger and Schuepbach, 2019b), while proteases that are associated with COPD pathogenesis include the serine proteases, tryptase, neutrophil elastase and matrix-metalloproteinase (Pandey, De and Mishra, 2017).

Tryptase is a protease that is released by mast cells in the airway epithelium. It has been reported as a major driver of airway inflammation and remodeling processes, and is involved in the development of asthma and pathogenesis of COPD (Hallgren and Pejler, 2006; Carroll *et al.*, 2021). Mast cell tryptase activates the classical pathway of PAR2 via G_{αq} signaling and calcium flux, which is associated with the augmentation of inflammatory responses through the internalisation and degradation of PAR2 protein. The final product of this cascade of reactions is activation of NF-κB and subsequent secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-6 and IL-8)(Macfarlane *et al.*, 2005; Carroll *et al.*, 2021). Tryptase and PAR2 have been shown to enhance the hyper-proliferation and responsiveness of smooth muscle cells in airways of subjects with asthma (Barrios, Jarosinski and Wright, 2003); also tryptase is involved in fibroblast proliferation in COPD and asthmatic patients (Akers *et al.*, 2000; Carroll *et al.*, 2021). Recently, a vital role of tryptase and PAR2 in the migration and remodeling of human lung fibroblasts has been identified (Bagher *et al.*, 2018).

Human Airway Trypsin-like protease (HAT) was identified to be associated with chronic airway diseases as well as activation of PAR2. A HAT-PAR2 signalling cascade was linked to fibroblast proliferation in human bronchial airways (Sisson and Spagnolo, 2016); furthermore, it was found that the activation of PAR2 through HAT is linked with high levels of MUC5AC in airway epithelial cells, proposing a significant role for the PAR2 receptor linked with the hypersecretion of mucus in airway diseases (Adler, Tuvim and Dickey, 2013). Studies conducted in human airway epithelial cells (hAEC) suggest PAR2 expression to be directly associated with high secretion levels of IL-8 (Miki *et al.*, 2019), and increased expression of PAR2 has been detected on bronchial epithelium in COPD, where it initiates and triggers inflammatory signalling pathways, inducing the release of IL-6 and IL-8 (Miotto *et al.*, 2002). Interestingly, PAR2 has been also associated with lung fibrosis via the increased production of IL-8 (Carroll *et al.*, 2021a).

In this study, OS was found to enhance the expression of PAR2 alone or in combination with LPS, this observation can be explained by an induction of expression of PAR2 due to H₂O₂ /LPS. LPS was reported to modulate PAR2 expression levels through different mechanisms of interaction (Widera, Aguilar and Cottrell, 2019b). However, this observation was only identified with BEAS-2B cells but not in primary cells, suggesting that PAR2 expression can be related to cell type.

In summary, it was shown that human primary bronchial epithelial cells were challenged with OS and inflammatory stimuli at concentrations that were able to induce stress but preserved cell viability. However, these cells were able to tolerate slightly higher concentrations of H₂O₂ compared to BEAS-2B. In both cell models, H₂O₂ synergistically enhanced LPS dependent production of cytokines (only in IL-8 in primary cells), and this observation was also reversed when TPCA-1 was introduced, confirming the vital role of redox-sensitive transcription factor NF-κB in inducing inflammation, observations paralleled by mRNA transcript levels. Moreover, H₂O₂, and interestingly LPS alone or in combination, were able to enhance intracellular ROS in both cell models. Primary cells shared similar results

with BEAS-2B cells in terms of the expression of pro-inflammatory mediators and oxidative stress biomarkers. Interestingly, *F2RL1* gene expression was not enhanced with LPS treatment alone (as in BEAS-2B cells); however, H₂O₂ alone and in combination with LPS enhanced *F2RL1* gene expression in both cell models, suggesting an important role of this protein in enhancing inflammation.

There is strong evidence that chronic treatments with OS and inflammatory stimuli affects signalling pathways and has a role in inducing epigenetic modifications in regulatory genes, this may explain the ROS persistence even after smoking cessation (Zong, Ouyang and Chen, 2015). For this reason it is important to address and explore the correlation between ROS and inflammation with DNA methylation of the promoter regions of inflammatory genes. Recently, Wu et al. recently reported a strong link between PAR2 hypo-methylation, which upregulated PAR2 expression and potentiated lung adenocarcinoma progression (Wu, Xu and Cheng, 2021b). Conversely, Tahara *et al.* found that PAR2 promoter differential methylation was associated with severe disease phenotypes of Ulcerative Colitis (Tahara *et al.*, 2009).

Many studies to date have confirmed potential relation between DNA methylation and COPD, which can be considered as pivotal biomarker for disease prevention, diagnosis, and prognostic evaluation (Qiu *et al.*, 2012; Sundar *et al.*, 2017). In patients with COPD some loci were identified as hyper-methylated and others are hypo-methylated (Busch *et al.*, 2017; Wilson *et al.*, 2013). An important loci that was identified as hyper-methylated is the gene component of anti-oxidant NFE2-related factor-2 (Nrf2) pathways (Emily A. Vucic *et al.*, 2014a). The hypermethylation in CpG dinucleotide in Nrf2 gene associates with reduced expression of its gene product. The Nrf2 pathway is an important oxidative stress pathway as it has an anti-inflammatory role and protects against oxidative stress. On the other hand, the HDAC6 promoter region is associated with the hypomethylation mechanism, and this process was clearly seen to be linked with over expression of HDAC6 in COPD (Lam *et al.*, 2013). HDAC6 has been reported to contribute to epithelial dysfunction in COPD patients due to cigarette smoke by promoting autophagy (Jeanmonod, Rebecca and Suzuki, 2018).

Hypomethylation of DNA in blood samples from COPD patients has previously been demonstrated to be correlated with disease severity (Zinellu *et al.*, 2017). According to some research studies OS and DNA hypomethylation are related via a number of different processes (Fomenko *et al.*, 2007; Franco *et al.*, 2008; He *et al.*, 2020). A high degree of oxidation alters the redox state of the cell, which can lead to the reduction of DNMT1 (enzyme responsible for hypermethylation). *SERPINA1* gene was reported to be hypomethylated and this was found to be closely linked to COPD and pulmonary dysfunction (Ponce-Gallegos *et al.*, 2020). Other DNA methylation biomarkers were detected in sputum of COPD patients among these *GATA4*, an essential transcription factor that is crucial for normal lung development. *GATA4* gene methylation was found to control the level of OS and airway inflammation, thus regulating health status in COPD patients (Meek *et al.*, 2015).

Epigenetic modifications such as methylation was highly found to impact COPD development, for this reason, it was decided in Chapter 5 to investigate whether or not treatments with OS and inflammatory stimuli had any effect in changing the methylation levels of the *F2RL1*, as this gene has a significant role in enhancing inflammation in several diseases which may include asthma and COPD.

Chapter 5. Is PAR2 promoter methylation changed by oxidative and inflammatory stimuli in BEAS-2B and human primary epithelial cells?

5.1. Introduction

Although genetic causes are well defined in COPD, inconsistent results of some genetic approaches suggest that not only genetics, but other factors are highly involved in COPD development; such factors are related to epigenetics modifications (Sakao and Tatsumi, 2011). At a molecular level, epigenetic phenomena are heritable changes that involve altering the phenotypic makeup of a gene of interest by the addition of chemical groups to the DNA sequence that does not affect the DNA sequence context but may affect gene expression and function (protein–DNA modifications) (Waddington, 2012; Singer, 2019). By epigenetics, the environmentally induced phenotypes can persist for several generations.

Epigenetic regulation of gene expression is a normal process that occurs during somatic cell differentiation, also in response to environmental stresses. These modifications can be passed from mother to daughter cell during dividing population constituting epigenetic inheritance (Lind and Spagopoulou, 2018). Mechanisms responsible for these phenomena include methylation of DNA cytosine residues, specifically the addition (hyper-methylation) or removal (hypo-methylation) of methyl groups from methylated cytosines, and covalent modifications of histone proteins where DNA is twisted in the chromosome, this resulting in either activation or suppression of genes (Zong, Ouyang and Chen, 2015) and noncoding RNA species (Goldberg, Allis and Bernstein, 2007). DNA methylation is the predominant epigenetic modification that has a significant effect in controlling gene expression (Bonvicini *et al.*, 2012) (Reinius *et al.*, 2012a), it was estimated that 50% of protein coding genes are highly rich with CG dinucleotides in the promoter region of DNA known as CpG islands. It was reported that as much as 80% of all CpG dinucleotides are methylated within the human genome (Zong, Ouyang and Chen, 2015). DNA methylation is considered one of the best characterised epigenetic processes that has a vital role in biological processes (Patterson *et al.*, 2011), for example, cell differentiation and development which contributes significantly in controlling gene expression (Ding, Maiuri and O'Hagan, 2017).

DNA methylation is the covalent addition of a methyl group into carbon 5' of a cytosine residue (C) (Reinius *et al.*, 2012b). Although not exclusively (Schultz *et al.*, 2016), DNA methylation in animals mainly happens at cytosine residues that are followed by a guanine on their 3' end in a single linear DNA sequence in its 5' → 3' direction. The cytosine and guanine nucleotides are separated by one phosphate group that links any two nucleotide together in a DNA known as cytosine-phospho-guanine (CpG) dinucleotides in order to differentiate them from CG interstrand base pairing (Bird, 2002). Importantly, CpG residues accumulate in a highly non-uniform distribution, clustering together with high frequency in genomic regions known as CpG islands (Morrow *et al.*, 2016), which are defined with specific parameters such as >200-bp regions often not more than 450 bp but potentially up to ~1 kb, with a GC fraction greater than 0.5 and an observed-to-expected CpG ratio greater than 0.6 (Gardiner-Garden and Frommer, 1987a; Singer, 2019). These CpG islands usually localise near or within the gene promoters but have also been detected within other gene-regulatory elements (enhancers), and tend to be hypo-methylated (Cain, Montibus and Oakey, 2022).

In general, CpG hyper-methylation is associated with transcriptional suppression; conversely, hypo-methylation is linked to enhanced gene expression. Furthermore, patterns of methylation are non-uniform, just as the distribution of CpG dinucleotides, as these methylated residues accumulate together in patterns that considerably vary between different cell types, functional states, and disease conditions (Bird, 2002; Singer, 2019). In patients with COPD some loci have been identified as hyper-methylated and others are hypo-methylated (Busch *et al.*, 2017; Wilson *et al.*, 2013). An important loci identified as hyper-methylated is the gene component of anti-oxidant Nrf2 pathway (Vucic *et al.*, 2014). The hyper-methylation in CpG dinucleotides in the *NRF2* gene associates with reduced expression of its gene product. Recently, studies reported that epigenetic modifications may enhance the development of chronic inflammation by controlling the expression of pro-inflammatory TNF- α , interleukins (IL-6, IL-8, etc.) and activation of NF- κ B (Barnes, 2009).

Extremely important findings showed that there is a great influence on the risk of developing COPD and alteration of lung function due to smoking-related differential

methylation signals in peripheral blood (Lee *et al.*, 2017; Machin *et al.*, 2017; Qiu *et al.*, 2012; Sood *et al.*, 2010; Wielscher *et al.*, 2015). One interesting result detected is the hypomethylation of the CpG site cg02181506 in the *SERPINA1* gene on chromosome 14, this gene being of particular interest as the main genetic factor associated with COPD development (Qiu *et al.*, 2011). DNA methylation can play a vital role in developing pulmonary inflammation; Monick *et al.* proposed that cigarette smoking can affect DNA methylation levels in both pulmonary alveolar macrophages and lymphoblast (Monick *et al.*, 2012). Further studies also posit that levels of DNA methylation are highly correlated with cigarette smoking and elevated levels of C-Reactive Protein (CRP), a biomarker of systematic inflammation (Morrow *et al.*, 2016). This will lead to an important conclusion that cigarette smoking is a key factor that can increase the level of DNA methylation, which results in the local and systematic inflammation of COPD (Zong, Ouyang and Chen, 2015). The process can be linked to OS.

OS was found to up-regulate the activity and expression of DNA methyl-transferase 1 (DNMT1), the enzyme which is responsible for the hyper-methylation of DNA promoter sequences, this in turn causes a repression modification in gene expression (Patterson *et al.*, 2012). Additionally, Camarori *et al.* reported that the majority of the over-expressed inflammatory proteins produced by COPD macrophages are mainly regulated by NF- κ B, these macrophages are detected at a heightened level during the exacerbation phase (Caramori *et al.*, 2003; Colarusso *et al.*, 2017). Together, inflammation and ROS production can promote pathophysiological changes correlated to COPD. This suggests that DNA methylation due to oxidative stress and inflammation can play a vital role in the development of smoking related illness such as COPD (Zong, Ouyang and Chen, 2015).

PAR2, also known as *F2RL1*, is a member of the PAR family is a G protein-coupled receptor (Rothmeier and Ruf, 2012; Yau, Liu and Fairlie, 2013). The functionality of PAR2 was studied in several processes including cell growth, pathological stimuli, microtubule regulation and other physiological mechanisms (Weithauser *et al.*, 2013; Weithauser and Rauch, 2014). PAR2 has been shown to be expressed in a variety of cells types including epithelial, smooth muscle cells, fibroblasts, as well as, inflammatory and immune cells such as monocytes, T cells,

eosinophils, and mast cells (Santulli *et al.*, 1995; Ramelli *et al.*, 2010; Adams *et al.*, 2011; Rothmeier and Ruf, 2012; Yau, Liu and Fairlie, 2013; Crilly *et al.*, 2016; Kandel *et al.*, 2016). PAR2 has been extensively studied and has been shown to be heavily involved in promoting inflammation and tissue remodelling in the airways (Kunzelmann *et al.*, 2002; Schmidlin *et al.*, 2002; Unice Jk Soh *et al.*, 2010; Arizmendi *et al.*, 2011; Mark N. Adams *et al.*, 2011; Yau, Liu and Fairlie, 2013). It has been shown to play important role in asthma (Palikhe *et al.*, 2015). There is evidence that PAR2 promoter methylation might be associated with serious inflammation and result in intensive clinicopathological phenotypes. A study by Tahara *et al.* was the first to investigate a potential correlation between PAR2 methylation and Ulcerative Colitis (UC); importantly, they demonstrated that the higher methylation level of PAR2 in inflammatory rectal mucosa is associated with severe disease phenotypes of UC, such as extensive colitis, steroid-dependent, and refractory phenotypes (Tahara *et al.*, 2009). As the chemical addition of methyl group to cytosine residue of DNA significantly alters the gene expression and activation, this epigenetic modification was reported to take place in CpG islands of various types of cancers (Tahara *et al.*, 2009).

Most recently, a significant finding by Wu, Xu and Cheng (Wu, Xu and Cheng, 2021b) revealed that PAR2 promoter hypo-methylation enhanced Lung Adenocarcinoma (LUAD) cell progression affecting the prognosis of LUAD patients. Furthermore, the methylation status of PAR2 promoter region in LUAD cell lines was found to be hypo-methylated, which in turn potentiate PAR2 expression in LUAD cells (Wu, Xu and Cheng, 2021b). Many studies related to cancer research confirmed that the presence of significant modifications in gene exogeneity such as alterations in CpG islands methylation status are believed to be behind the malignant progression of human cancers (Bian *et al.*, 2002; Hardie *et al.*, 2005; Tahara *et al.*, 2009).

For instance, in human lung cancer, early clinical diagnosis revealed that DNA methylation was found to be mainly occur in tumor-related genes and this observation was noticed to be gradually heightened with disease progression (Wu, Xu and Cheng, 2021c). Other types of alteration reported in some genes in non-neoplastic tissues were found to be linked to aging

mechanism, known as age-related methylation (Issa *et al.*, 1994; Paulsen and Ferguson-Smith, 2001; Tahara *et al.*, 2009). For instance, studies related to irritable bowel disease (IBD) showed that gene alteration due to methylation was presented in non-neoplastic colorectal mucosa in patients with IBDs (Sato *et al.*, 2002) similar findings were reported in esophageal mucosa in patients with Barrett's esophagitis (Galipeau *et al.*, 1999; Jiao, Feng and Wang, 2018) also in liver tissues in chronic hepatitis (Csepregi *et al.*, 2010) such findings suggest that chronic inflammation can be a cause of gene methylation (Maiuri *et al.*, 2018).

5.1.1. Hypothesis

PAR2 is directly involved in lung inflammatory diseases by promoting inflammation and tissue remodeling in the airways. Moreover, since DNA methylation is a vital biochemical process that directly and significantly impacts gene regulation and expression, also it has been established that DNA methylation can be modulated during chronic inflammation, it is hypothesised that oxidative stress and inflammatory challenges may regulate PAR2 expression (a key inflammatory regulator), thus explaining a potential role in diseases such as COPD. In the present study, we investigated how environmental challenges such as oxidative stress (OS), modelled by H₂O₂, and inflammatory stimuli (exemplified by LPS) affect the methylation levels of the PAR2 promoter region, with potential implications for inflammation and COPD development.

5.1.2. Aims

1. To investigate, whether or not, PAR2 gene has potential methylation targets and CpG sites using *in silico* analysis
2. To identify potential PAR2 transcription motifs and transcription factors binding sites within PAR2 promoter region in particular transcription factors that are associated with oxidative stress using bioinformatics analysis.
3. To optimize the conditions for bisulphite conversion DNA modification and bisulphite-specific PCR prior to sequencing

4. By bisulphite sanger sequencing, to investigate if oxidative stress and inflammatory stimuli affected the differentially methylated levels of potential CpG islands and individual CpG sites identified within the PAR2 promoter region in lung cells (BEAS -2B cells and human primary epithelial cells).

5.2. Methodology

5.2.1. Selection of *F2RL1* promoter region

The National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/>) was accessed to find PAR2 promoter and gene sequence. PAR2 was detected under the name of *F2R* like trypsin receptor 1 [Homo sapiens (human)], it is located in chromosome number 5 in position q13.3, and has an accession number NC_000005.10. A length of 2110 bp relative to the transcription starting site (TSS) of *F2RL1* promoter region was selected for further analysis (Further details are provided in Chapter 2 Section 2.1.1.1).

5.2.2. Prediction of CpG Islands

MethPrimer (Li and Dahiya, 2002) bioinformatics software was used to predict CpG islands in the 2110 bp promoter region of the *F2RL1* gene. Methprimer software 2.0 (2016 version) was accessed through <http://www.urogene.org/methprimer2/> (Further details are provided in Chapter 2 Section 2.1.1.2).

5.2.3. Prediction of Transcription Factors

Tfsitescan software was accessed using the link <http://www.ifti.org/cgi-bin/ifti/Tfsitescan.pl>. Using the default parameter (IFTI Tfsite, 10896 entries, 7/30/11) and Tfsites query parameters: Mammalian sites, the promoter sequence was submitted and analyzed through the online platform (Further details are provided in Chapter 2 Section 2.1.2).

5.2.4. Detection of Transcription Factors binding profiles

JASPAR software was accessed using the following link <http://jaspar.genereg.net/>, it is a database used to detect transcription factor binding profiles (sites) (Further details are provided in Chapter 2 Section 2.1.3).

5.2.5. Genomic DNA extraction

Untreated BEAS-2B cells were seeded and then collected from a T-75 flask. Alternatively, BEAS-2B cells and human primary epithelial cells were seeded in 24 well plate, cells were treated with different stimuli (LPS, H₂O₂, LPS and H₂O₂) or remained untreated (as a control). DNA extraction was done using Quick-DNA Miniprep Plus Kit (Zymo research) according to the provided manufacture protocol. Nanodrop was used to deduce the purity of DNA samples (Further details are provided in Chapter 2 Sections 2.6.2, 2.6.3).

5.2.6. Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

Wild type-specific primers that only amplify unconverted DNA samples from untreated and treated BEAS-2B and primary human epithelial cells were designed manually. Primer details were checked by Thermoprimer analyser. Three different primer sets were designed specifically to amplify each CpG island 1 and 2. “*HotStartTaq*” Plus DNA polymerase Master Mix kit (Qiagen) was used to perform the PCR reaction according to the manufacturer protocol to amplify the two CpG islands of *F2RL1* gene from extracted DNA (T-75 flask) untreated BEAS-2B cells using the unmodified designed primers (Further details are provided in Chapter 2 Sections 2.9.1 & 2.9.2).

Alternatively, ZymoTaq premix Hotstart DNA polymerase was used in order to amplify the DNA samples from treated/untreated BEAS-2B, HBEC and COPD-HBEC pre and post-bisulphite conversion (Further details are provided in Chapter 2 Sections 2.9.3 & 2.9.4).

5.2.7. Bisulphite Conversion of DNA Samples and Perform Quality Controls

The extracted DNA samples from treated/untreated BEAS-2B, HBEC and COPD-HBEC were converted by bisulfite reagents using EZ DNA Methylation-Direct Kit (ZymoResearch) according to manufacturer protocol (Further details are provided in chapter 2, sections 2.11). Nanodrop calculations were undertaken to ensure the quantity and purity of the converted DNA. The quantity of the converted DNA was assessed as RNA with $Ab_{S_{260\text{ nm}}} 1.0\text{ cm} = 40\ \mu\text{g/ml}$. The level of fragmentation and recovery of the converted DNA was assessed by 2 % agarose gel (Further details are provided in Chapter 2 Sections 2.12, 2.17).

5.2.8. Bisulphite-Specific PCR Testing

Primer designing software (MethPrimer Express Software v2.0, 2016 version) was used to design the Bisulphite-Specific primers (BS primers) for methylation mapping (Refer to details mentioned in Chapter 2 Section 2.13).

An annealing gradient temperature using samples of bisulphite modified DNA with the selected BS primer sets (1 and 2) was undertaken, followed by Bisulphite-Specific PCR (BSP) to amplify bisulfite converted samples (Refer to details mentioned in Chapter 2 Sections, 2.14). The procedure was followed by electrophoresis with 2 % (w/v) agarose gel. DNA controls (methylated and non-methylated DNA) were used and amplified by specifically designed primers as recommended by the manufacturer (Refer to details mentioned in Chapter 2 Sections, 2.16).

5.2.9. Quantification of PCR Products and Sanger Sequencing

The template DNA concentrations for all samples used in previously described experiments were quantified via agarose gel prior to sending for sequencing (Eurofins, Germany). PCR products were sent as unpurified samples at concentration of each PCR sample of 10 ng/ μl and volume 20 μl . Samples were sequenced using the cycle sequencing technology (dideoxy chain termination/cycle sequencing) on an Applied Biosystems ABI 3730XL sequencing

machines. Reverse primers (wild type specific primers and BSP primers) at concentration of 10 μ M and minimal volume of 15 μ l/reaction were sent for sequencing the DNA from unconverted and converted DNA templates (Refer to details mentioned in Chapter 2 Section 2.17).

5.3. RESULTS

5.3.1. Prediction of CpG Islands

MethPrimer is an online platform which provides a number of tools and databases to facilitate the study of DNA methylation and epigenetics, including tools for designing primers and probes for various bisulphite conversion-based PCRs, predicting CpG islands, and manipulating sequences (Li and Dahiya, 2002). MethPrimer software was used to predict the presence of potential CpG islands and sites in the 2110 bp sequence upstream of the transcription start site of the *F2RL1* promoter region. MethPrimer software (default parameter values for the software are CpG island length > 100 bp, Obs/Exp > 0.6 and CG% > 50%) predicted two potential CpG islands within the 2110 bp *F2RL1* promoter region. CpG island 1 had a length of 115 bp and is located at the position -457 bp and finishes at -342 bp upstream the Transcription Starting Site (TSS). CpG island 2 was found to be bigger in size compared to CpG island 1, with a 400 bp size and it starts at -167 bp upstream of TSS; interestingly, the majority of CpG island 2 was found to be located within TSS and overlaps with *F2RL1* coding sequence, the end of CpG island 2 is located at + 233 downstream TSS. CpG sites were found to be more densely situated within CpG island 2 (43 site) compared to CpG island 1 (6 sites), as more of these sites were detected in CpG island 2.

CpG sites were also found to be distributed randomly upstream, downstream and between the two CpG islands (Figure 5.1). These results indicate that the analysis of the *F2RL1* promoter region using MethPrimer software demonstrated the presence of potential methylated sites and areas (CpG islands) that could be potential targets to study the effect of oxidative stress (H_2O_2) and inflammatory stress (LPS) challenges on the methylation levels of these regions.

Figure 5.1. MethPrimer software 2.0 prediction of CpG islands

A 2110 bp *F2RL1* promoter sequence (GenBank Accession: NC_000005.10) as input to the Methprimer program using the web interface. CpG island prediction was used as an input parameter, all other parameters were kept as default. The graphic view shows potential CpG islands and sites and other sequence features such as % GC.

5.3.1.1. Visualisation of Primer Selection Results

To visually display results for CpG island prediction and primer selection for BSP, the Methprimer software was used with all parameters kept as default and only CpG island prediction was used specifically as a parameter for primer selection. The 2110 bp *F2RL1* promoter sequence was used as the test sequence as it is the gene of interest in this study. For each island, five sets of BSP primers were returned, reverse and forward, specifically designed by the platform to amplify bisulphite converted template. The software was programmed to avoid the selection of primers that have CpG sites within the primer sequence itself.

An example of primer searching for BSP is shown in Figure 5.2. Five sets of bisulphite specific primers were designed by Methprimer to amplify specifically CpG Island 2; however the input sequence was 614 bp of the 2110 bp of *F2RL1* promoter region in order to cover the full length of CpG island 2 (400 bp) for primers selection. In this example, the size of CpG Island 2 was between the minimal (100 bp) and maximal product size (400 bp), so the program was forced to identify primer sets overlapping the CpG island 2 region (Figure 5.2 A).

Importantly, the designed primers did not contain any CpG sites, and each primer set spanned the maximal number of CpG sites (31 CpG sites of interest among the 43 CpG sites initially identified within 400 bp CpG island 2); this indicated that the BSP primers detected by Methprimer software were considered theoretically good primer sets assigning high weighing scores between 3~4.1, which is considered as an important feature for defining a good primer set (Figure 5.2 B).

A)

B)

BSP Pair 1													
Primer name	Sequence (5'-3')	Len	Start	End	Degenerate	CpG's	C's	Self_ony	Self_end	Tm	GC%	Stability	Score
F1	TTTTAGGAGTAAGTAAAGATTAAGG	26	85	90	No	0	2	400	0	53.6	26.9	8.5	4.1
R1	AAAATCAACCTCTCACCTACCC	22	412	391	No	0	3	200	0	58.5	45.5	8.4	3.4
Product size	Pair start	Pair end	CpG's	Comp_ony	Comp_end	Tm	Tm_diff	Score					
348	65	412	31	500	200	75.7	4.9	2.4					

BSP Pair 2													
Primer name	Sequence (5'-3')	Len	Start	End	Degenerate	CpG's	C's	Self_ony	Self_end	Tm	GC%	Stability	Score
F2	TTTTAGGAGTAAGTAAAGATTAAGG	26	85	90	No	0	2	400	0	53.6	26.9	8.5	4.1
R2	AAATCAACCTCTCACCTACCC	21	411	381	No	0	3	200	0	57.1	47.6	8.4	3.4
Product size	Pair start	Pair end	CpG's	Comp_ony	Comp_end	Tm	Tm_diff	Score					
347	65	411	31	500	200	75.8	3.5	1.7					

BSP Pair 3													
Primer name	Sequence (5'-3')	Len	Start	End	Degenerate	CpG's	C's	Self_ony	Self_end	Tm	GC%	Stability	Score
F3	TTTTAGGAGTAAGTAAAGATTAAGG	26	85	90	No	0	2	400	0	53.6	26.9	8.5	4.1
R3	AAAAAATCAACCTCTCACCTACC	23	414	380	No	0	4	200	0	57.8	39.1	6.9	2.9
Product size	Pair start	Pair end	CpG's	Comp_ony	Comp_end	Tm	Tm_diff	Score					
350	65	414	31	500	200	75.6	4.2	1.0					

BSP Pair 4													
Primer name	Sequence (5'-3')	Len	Start	End	Degenerate	CpG's	C's	Self_ony	Self_end	Tm	GC%	Stability	Score
F4	TTTTAGGAGTAAGTAAAGATTAAGG	26	85	90	No	0	2	400	0	53.6	26.9	8.5	4.1
R4	AAAAAATCAACCTCTCACCTAC	24	416	380	No	0	5	200	0	57.1	33.3	6.9	2.9
Product size	Pair start	Pair end	CpG's	Comp_ony	Comp_end	Tm	Tm_diff	Score					
352	65	416	31	500	200	75.6	3.5	1.4					

BSP Pair 5													
Primer name	Sequence (5'-3')	Len	Start	End	Degenerate	CpG's	C's	Self_ony	Self_end	Tm	GC%	Stability	Score
F5	TTTTAGGAGTAAGTAAAGATTAAGG	26	85	90	No	0	2	400	0	53.6	26.9	8.5	4.1
R5	AATCAACCTCTCACCTACCC	20	410	395	No	0	3	200	0	55.6	50.0	8.4	3.5
Product size	Pair start	Pair end	CpG's	Comp_ony	Comp_end	Tm	Tm_diff	Score					
346	65	410	31	500	300	75.8	2.0	1.4					

Figure 5.2. Visualisation of primer selection results

(A) Selected region of *F2RL1* promoter sequence containing CpG island 2 was input to the program and primers selection using CpG island 2 prediction was picked, other parameters kept as default. (B) Primer selection criteria for BSP using Methprimer software predicts primer sets that did not contain any CpG sites within their sequence and spanning the maximal number of CpG sites within the potential region of interest.

5.3.1.2. Input Sequence Format

Methprimer software predicts the specific position of CpG sites within an input target sequence. . The input sequence format of *F2RL1* promoter region is illustrated Figure 5.3. The upper sequence represents the input *F2RL1* DNA promoter sequence, while the lower sequence illustrates the bisulphite modified sequence. The non- CpG sites are presented as (C::T), in these sites the non-CpG cytosine residue cannot be methylated and it would be converted to uracil due to bisulphite conversion mechanism, and later to thymine after bisulfite specific PCR (BSP). The CpG dinucleotides were methylation possibly or predicted to occur were detected as (++) CpG), and these cytosine residues if methylated, they are capped or protected by a methyl group (-CH₃) which prevents its conversion to thymine by BSP. MethPrimer allows the design of specific primers for BSP. The bisulphite converted DNA is amplified by PCR using primers that are specific for the bisulphite converted DNA but do not contain any CpG Cs in their sequences denoted as bisulphite-specific primers (BS primers) (Figure 5.2). Positions of the Forward (F1) and Reverse (R1) primers that were identified by the software as BS primers that amplify bisulphite converted CpG island 2 are also presented in Figure 5.3.

Figure 5.3. Part of *F2RL1* Promoter input sequence format as identified by MethPrimer software.

The text view shows sequence alignment of bisulphite treated and untreated sequences and location of BSP primers. Index: Upper row: Original sequence, Lower row: Bisulphite modified sequence ++ CpG sites, ::: Non-CpG 'C' converted to 'T', F1 >>>>> forward primer, R1 <<<<<< reverse primer.

5.3.2. Position of CpG Islands, CpG Sites and Transcription Factors Binding Sites within *F2RL1* DNA Promoter Region

5.3.2.1. Prediction Results of the Position of CpG Islands and Sites in the Promoter Region

In order to align the positions of CpG islands and sites with the positions of potential transcription factor binding sites, the information provided by the input sequence format in Figure 5.3 were used in order to mark the position of the potential sites and islands in the *F2RL1* DNA promoter region. The two CpG islands were marked in red and the CpG sites are represented in blue in Figure 5.4. CpG island 2 was found to be overlapped with the transcription start site (TSS) and *F2RL1* gene coding sequence.

5.3.2.2. Prediction of Putative Transcription Factors and Transcription Factors Binding Sites (TFBS) in the *F2RL1* Promoter using Online Tools.

TFBS software predicts a number of *F2RL1* promoter motifs presented in Table 5.1. Importantly, potential transcription factor binding sites (cognate for AP-1, c-Jun, Nrf-2 and NF- κ B), related with key mechanisms and functions in COPD, were specifically detected to have binding sites within the 2110 bp *F2RL1* promoter region. JASPAR software predicted the binding sites of these vital transcription factors, associated with oxidative stress mechanisms (Figure 5.4).

Table 5.1. PAR2 promoter motifs

Name	Abbreviation
Activator Protein-1	AP-1
GATA Binding Protein 1	GATA-1
GATA Binding Protein 3	GATA-3
Glucocorticoid Receptor Alpha	GR-alpha
Glucocorticoid Receptor Beta	GR-β
Hepatocyte Nuclear Factor 1	HNF-1
Nuclear Factor Erythroid 2-Related Factor 2	Nrf-2
Nuclear Factor-Kappa B	NF-κB
Signal Transducer and Activator of Transcription 5	STAT5B
Histone acetyltransferase p300	P300 HAT
Specificity Protein-1	SP-1

The position of binding sites of each potential transcription motifs detected within *F2RL1* promoter region are expressed relative to the transcription start site (TSS) in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2. Position of potential transcription motifs relative to transcription start site

Promoter motif	Start	End	Transcription Factor Binding Site Base Sequence
Nrf2	-637	-628	GTGATAAACA
NF-κB	-510	-499	GGGGCGGGA
SP-1	-25	-17	GGGGATTAAGCA
AP-1	+117	+124	TGACTTTCT

Interestingly, the binding sites of SP-1 and AP-1 motifs were found to be located within the CpG island 2 region; Importantly, AP-1 transcription motif was found to be within the TSS, suggesting a potential impact of CpG sites methylation (if occurred due to treatments) within the CpG island 2 in the binding of these transcription factors to their specific binding sites (Figure 5.4).

ACTGGAGTTGAAATGTGATAAACA TTTATACACTGTGTTTATAAGTCGTGTA ACTCTGGCCAATTT
 ATCTGGTCTTTCTAAGCTCACTTTCTCTCGTCTGTAAAATGGGAAGAATAATCATACTTATTGCGCTG
 GTTGTTATGGGGATTAAGCAAGATAATTCTCTAAAGCTTTGGCACTTGGCGCTGAAAGTAGCCATT
 CCATGTCTTCTTTCCCGCCCCGCTCTTGTGCTCCCCACCGCTTTCTGTGATGTCCG CAGTTGCCACCT
 GCCTCTACAATAAGGAAAA CGCATCCCTCCTCTG CAGGGTCCACCGCACCGGGAAGCCCTGTCTGT
 ATCAGTTACCAACCACAATTGCAGTGAGTACGAATCGTGGCTTTCCACAGTCAGGAAAGGCAAG
 GGAGACCGACGACC CGCTTCTCTAGGAGTAAGTAAAGATTAAGGTTAGTTCCGGGTATAGCCTAG
 GCAGGGATTAACCCGTGGTCCCAGCGCTCTGCTATTTGCATTCCAAAGCAGACACCTCATGCGCT
 CAACCCCGCCCGCAGGCGGCTCCCGCAGTCTAAGGGACCTGGCGCGAGTCCGGGAAGCGGAGGG
 CGCAGCTGCGCAGGGAAGGGGGCCGGGGGCGGA CCAGGGCGCGCGTTCCCGTCCCGGGGCGT
 GGCCTCCCGCAGGTGAGTACGCTGCTCCTTCGGTTTCCTGAAACCTAACCCG CCGTGGGGAGGCG
 CGCAGCAGAGGCTCCGATTCCGGGGCAGGTGAGAGGCTTGACTTTCTCTCGGTGCGTCCAGTGGAGC
 TCTGAGTTTGAATCGGCGGCGGCGGATTCCCCGCGCGCCCGCGTCCGGGGCTTCCAGGAGGATG
 CGGAGCCCCAGCGCGGCTGGCTGCTGGGGGCCCGCCATCCTGCTAGCAGCCTCTCTCTCCTGCAGT
 GGCACCATCCAAGGTGAGAAACCTGGCCAAGGAGGGCTCTTATCTCTGAGGAGCTGGGGTCTGG

Index:

CG: Methylated CpG sites

Red region: CpG Island

Purple highlighted sequence: Transcription Starting Site (TSS)

Pink highlighted sequence: coding sequence (ATG)

GTGATAAACA: binding site of Nrf2 transcription factor

GGGGATTAAGCA: binding site of NF-κB transcription factor

GGGGCGGA: binding site of SP-1 transcription factor

TGACTTTCT: binding site of FOS::C-JUN (AP-1) transcription factor

Figure 5.4. Prediction results of positions of CpG islands, sites and transcription factors binding sites

The two CpG islands and CpG sites of the *F2RL1* promoter region were marked in their respective positions as detected by MethPrimer 2.0 software. *F2RL1* transcription motifs were predicted by TFBS and the binding sites of potential transcription factors (AP-1, SP-1, Nrf2, and NF-κB) were predicted by JASPAR software and aligned specifically in their appropriate positions within *F2RL1* promoter region.

5.3.3. Two CpG Islands were Successfully Amplified by PCR

PCR was done using different wild-type-specific primer (un-modified primers that amplify CpG islands from unmodified DNA sequence) sets that were designed specifically to amplify each CpG island respectively prior to bisulphite conversion using gDNA from unstimulated BEAS2B cells. DNA was extracted and PCR was performed. CpG island 1 was successfully amplified by the three manually designed primer sets. Each primer set produced different amplicon sizes with primer set 2 generating the longest amplicon. Amplicon sizes produced were as following: primer set 1: 187 bp, lanes 1 (+Q solution) and 2 (-Q), primers set 2: 287 bp, lanes 3 (+Q) and 4(-Q), and primers set 3: 202 bp, lanes 5 (+Q) and 6(-Q) and the gel results indicates that amplification of CpG island 1 can be done with or without Q-solution as strong bands were shown in all lanes in Figure 5.5 A.

Furthermore, CpG island 2 was also successfully amplified by all designed primer sets leading to different amplicon sizes as following: primers set 1 (388 bp, lane 1), primers set 2 (442 bp, lane 4) and primers set 3 (481 bp, lane 7). CpG island 2 required the presence of Q-solution to enhance amplification as no bands were observed when Q solution was absent (Figure 5.5 B lane 2). This suggests that CpG island 2 is a difficult template to amplify, as it has longer length (400 bp) compared to CpG island 1 (115 bp) and being rich with CG residues. It can be concluded that the designed primers specifically amplified the two CpG islands, generating different amplicon sizes and the presence of Q solution was a must to enhance the amplification of CpG island 2 but not island 1. PCR is also a tool that is used to identify the purity of the extracted DNA. Wells 3 and 6 of gel B had only master mix with primers and without a DNA template, results in Figure 5.5 B (lanes 3 and 6) strongly indicated that the extracted DNA was pure as no bands were observed.

Figure 5.5. Showing successful amplification of CpG islands 1 and 2

DNA was extracted and purified from unstimulated BEAS-2B cells and PCR with different sets of wild type-specific primers was performed with and without Q solution. **(A)** PCR results for CpG island 1: strong bands were shown in all wells with or without Q solution and different primer sets designed specifically to amplify CpG island 1, yielding to different amplicon sizes. **(B)** PCR results for CpG island 2: bands were detected in wells (1, 4 and 7) that had Q solution.

5.3.3.1. Amplification of CpG Island 2 Prior to Bisulphite Conversion by Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

In this experiment, primers set 1 of CpG island 2 was picked up among the other primers and it was identified as wild-type specific primer (unmodified) that is able to amplify specifically CpG island 2 (388 bp) prior to bisulphite conversion, the PCR in this work was performed using the primer set 1 in order to amplify CpG island 2 from cells (BEAS-2B, HBEC and COPD-HBEC) treated with different experimental conditions (H_2O_2 /LPS and in combination). In order to ensure sufficient quantity and quality of the DNA concentration extracted from BEAS-2B and human primary epithelial cells prior to bisulphite conversion, a Nanodrop spectrophotometer was used for measuring the quantity and PCR using wild type-unmodified specific primers for CpG island 2 (Set 1, Table 2.12) followed by an agarose gel electrophoresis to assess the DNA integrity. The gel results confirmed successful amplification of CpG island 2 in all DNA samples extracted from BEAS-2B cells (Figure 5.6 A and B), and from HBEC and COPD-HBEC (Figure 5.6 C and D) treated with LPS alone or in combination with H_2O_2 . As expected, the estimated amplicon size was 388 bp. No Template Control (NTC) was included in each analysis (Figure 5.6 A,B,C and D lane 1). The NTC contains the same reagents as the reactions for analysis, except that the DNA sample was replaced with the same amount of PCR grade water.

Figure 5.6. Assessing integrity of extracted DNA

After extraction of genomic DNA from BEAS-2B cells (A and B) and human primary epithelial cells (C and D), PCR reaction was performed in order to amplify CpG island 2 of *F2RL1* gene promoter region from unconverted DNA samples, using wild type-unmodified specific primers that only amplify unconverted DNA. Following PCR, products were checked by 2 % (w/v) agarose gel using 100 bp marker and analysed using GeneSys software to determine the quality of the amplified DNA as well as to visualise and confirm the right amplicon size, also to verify that no contamination or non-specific amplification occurred.

5.3.4. Assessing the Quality of the Fragmented Bisulphite Converted DNA

Treatment of gDNA with bisulphite is considered an inherently harsh process that dramatically changes both the chemical makeup and physical properties of the DNA. These changes significantly influence quantification, quality assessment, amplification and analysis of the bisulphite-converted DNA. For these reasons, and in order to assess these changes, as well as the fragmentation and recovery of the bisulphite converted DNA, Nanodrop spectrophotometry and agarose gel electrophoresis (2% w/v gel with 100 bp marker), and later downstream BSP was used respectively. The quantity of post-bisulphite converted DNA samples was assessed on Nanodrop with $A_{260\text{ nm}} 1.0\text{ cm} = 40\text{ }\mu\text{g/ml}$ as assessing RNA. The fragmented DNA has the features of RNA and DNA, the assessed DNA is not a normal double stranded DNA; however, bisulphite treatments modify DNA samples from a large, double-stranded DNA molecule into a collection of random single-stranded fragmented DNA with low molecular weight, and where all unmethylated cytosines were completely converted to uracil, this means that the double strands are no longer complementary and they are a fragmented single stranded DNA (Hong and Shin, 2021).

It was proposed that the main cause of fragmentation is the deamination step of bisulphite treatments (Chrysanthia A Leontiou *et al.*, 2015). For this reason the fragmented DNA was assessed as RNA. At least 100 ng of converted DNA was loaded into each lane to visualize the fragmentation.

The quality of converted DNA was checked by agarose gel (Figure 5.7), this was used in order to gauge fragmentation and recovery of modified DNA prior to BSP. As expected, when the gel was first removed from the tank, nothing was visible (Figure 5.7 A, lanes 3 to 10), this was a normal result as the gDNA was significantly fragmented into low molecular weight molecules and almost entirely single-stranded as the strands were no longer complementary, and almost completely devoid of cytosine following bisulphite conversion. When the gel was chilled for several minutes (20 min) in an ice bath, the converted DNA ran as a smear from >

1,500 down to 100 bp, confirming good quality, successful fragmentation and recovery of the modified DNA molecules (Figure 5.7 B, lanes 3 to 10).

When the gel was initially removed from the tank, nothing was observed as the converted DNA is entirely single stranded and ethidium bromide intercalates very effectively only in double stranded DNA and it sticks between the two strands, when gel was placed on ice a smear was observed since ice forces enough base-pairing thus allowing interaction with ethidium bromide to visualise the DNA.

An unconverted DNA was run on the gel as a negative control (Figure 5.7, lane 2: A and B) also non-template control (Figure 5.7, lane 1: A and B) was also loaded into the gel as NTC wells to detect any contamination.

Figure 5.7. Assessment of DNA integrity after Bisulfite Conversion

DNA fragmentation and limited base pairing makes it difficult to see the DNA following bisulfite conversion. Samples (100 ng/well) of bisulfite converted human genomic DNA from BEAS-2B and primary epithelial cells were run on a 2% w/v agarose gel with a 100 bp marker visualised normally (**A**) and after chilling in an ice bath (**B**) using GeneSys software. An unconverted DNA (100ng/ul) was run on the gel as a negative control also non-template control was also loaded into the gel for detecting contamination.

5.3.5. Determining the Efficiency of BSP Primers by Annealing Gradient PCR.

Data from annealing gradient PCR showed that the amplification of converted DNA using BSP primers set 1 was specifically reached at 57 °C (Figure 5.8, lane 6). Results from annealing gradient PCR ensured that primer set 1 achieved the optimal amplification of methylated CpG island 2 (specific target) compared to primer set 2 where non-specific amplification of bisulphite-treated DNA occurred at optimal annealing temperature 57 °C; also primer dimers were observed at lower annealing temperatures. Usually, the annealing temperature for bisulphite-specific PCR should be between 55-60°C; accordingly, primer set 1 with an annealing temperature of 57 °C were considered optimal conditions to use in downstream analysis such as BSP PCR in subsequent experiments.

Figure 5.8. Annealing gradient PCR for primers used for Bisulphite-Specific PCR

Replicates of bisulphite converted DNA samples were amplified using two different bisulphite-specific primer sets (set 1 and set 2) and incubated in a gradient thermal cycler using annealing temperature gradient of 54.7 to 59.9 °C (left to right). Equal volumes of bisulphite PCR products were visualised and analysed in a 2% w/v agarose gel with 100 bp DNA marker using *GeneSys* software.

5.3.6. Amplification of Bisulphite-Converted DNA and Verification of Bisulphite Specific PCR Product

By gel electrophoresis (2 % w/v), the size of the amplicon resulting from BSP amplification was verified prior to proceeding to ensure the correct product size. One strong and clear band with the anticipated product size was observed in Figure 5.9, A and B. Samples containing several bands or primer dimers were excluded and re-processed. The PCR product size resulting from BSP from DNA samples extracted from BEAS-2B cells (A) and primary epithelial cells (B) is 347 bp, and this was the anticipated amplicon size, suggesting successful amplification of the bisulphite converted CpG island 2 of *F2RL1* gene promoter region. NTC suggesting no contamination or unspecific amplification occurred during the experimental procedure.

Figure 5.9. Agarose gel electrophoresis of bisulphite-specific PCR (BSP) analysis of *F2RL1* gene promoter region

PCR products from BEAS-2B cells (n=4) **(A)** and primary epithelial cells (n=2) **(B)** were analysed using 2 % w/v agarose gel with 100 bp DNA marker. At least 100 ng per each PCR reaction of bisulphite converted DNA were used as template and 7 µl from each PCR product was loaded onto each well. The gel was visualised and images were taken using *GENESys* software. L: DNA marker. NTC: Non-Template Control.

5.3.7. Assessment of Conversion Efficiency by PCR

As a quality control (QC) step, the bisulphite converted DNA was used to perform PCR with wild type-specific primers (regular non-bisulphite specific primers, set 1, Table 2.12) in order to amplify any unconverted product and thus make an initial assessment of the conversion efficiency. Bands observed in lanes 1,3,4,7 and 8 indicate unconverted DNA was presented and amplified by regular non-bisulphite specific primers (wild-type primers); however, no bands were detected in lanes 5 and 6 where converted DNA was added as template for wild type-specific primers suggesting complete and fully converted or modified DNA samples. Results from the present study showed and confirmed that the DNA samples were fully converted and under-converted DNA was not detected within the modified DNA. Chrysanthia A. Leontiou et al. emphasised to use this quality control step prior to Sanger sequencing in order to make a general estimation about the bisulphite efficiency prior to the accurate estimation using Sanger sequencing (Chrysanthia A. Leontiou *et al.*, 2015).

Moreover, NTC water was used as a control sample to confirm specific amplification and clean PCR reaction. In Figure 5.10, lane 2, no bands were observed or detected suggesting no contamination or unspecific amplification.

Figure 5.10. PCR amplification using regular primers. As a quality control step, the bisulphite converted DNA was amplified with regular non-bisulphite specific primers that bind to the unconverted DNA sequence. Unconverted DNA from primary cells (lane 1) and BEAS-2B cells (lanes 3, 4, 7 and 8) were used as a positive control and water as negative control. Shown is a picture of the gel run in GENESys software where there is no PCR product in the 2 replicates with the bisulphite treated DNA (lanes 5 and 6) suggesting that all DNA was converted successfully.

5.3.8. Standards Quality Control: Bisulphite-specific PCR Testing

DNA samples varying in % methylation ratios were amplified in order to test for amplification bias. The efficiency of bisulphite-mediated conversion of DNA was assessed by specifically designed primers to amplify non-methylated, methylated and mix methylation copies of *DAPK1* gene following bisulphite conversion of the control DNA samples. Followed BSP for control standards DNA, the expected PCR amplicon length for the methylated, non-methylated and mix methylation copies is 274 bp. Gel image in Figure 5.11 shows clear bands with the expected amplicon size suggesting that complete conversion of mixtures of DNA controls at various methylation levels of the standards was performed and the standards were successfully bisulphite converted. This gives an indication that the bisulphite-conversion experiment was successfully performed.

Figure 5.11. Assessing the efficiency of bisulphite-mediated conversion of DNA samples

Mixtures of fully methylated and non-methylated DNA in various ratios were prepared and converted by bisulphite reagent prior to performing PCR. The efficiency of bisulphite treatment and conversion of controls were assessed by specifically designed primers to amplify non-methylated, methylated and mix methylation copies of *DAPK1* gene. The image shown here is for an agarose gel (2 % w/v) that was used to visualise and analyse the efficiency of conversion using *GENESys* Software. Non-Template Control (NTC) was used as negative control to verify clean PCR products.

5.3.9. Bisulphite Sanger Sequencing interpretation and analysis

5.3.9.1 Quality control/Interpretation of electropherograms

Genomic bisulphite sequencing is considered an efficient technology for the identification of DNA methylation at a single base pair nucleotide associated with CpG pair (Rauluseviciute, Drabløs and Rye, 2019). Sanger sequencing results of treated/untreated samples (LPS, H₂O₂, LPS and H₂O₂) from BEAS-2B cells, HBEC and COPD-HBEC (pre and post bisulphite converted) electropherograms were received as “.ab1” and as “.fasta” format. The electropherograms in the “.ab1” format were viewed by Chromas software prior to analysis to check the quality and correctly evaluate sequencing data. Results demonstrated in Figure 5.12 are examples of sequencing reactions of section CpG island 2 of the *F2RL1* gene promoter region taken from BEAS-2B cells treated with LPS pre (Figure 5.12 A) and post (Figure 5.12 B) bisulphite conversion.

In the present study, reverse primers were used to sequence the PCR products from pre and post-bisulphite modification, this means that results received from Sanger sequencing were electropherograms of the reverse strand, which were converted back to the forward strand for analysis. For example, “ACTCGC” in the displayed sequence in Figure 5.12. A was originally “GCGAGT” in the forward strand. In the sequence displayed in Figure 5.12. A “G” was originally “C” in the forward strand so any methylated “C” (originally in the forward strand) will be represented as methylated “G” in the reverse sequence as in Figure 5.12. A and this will remain “G” post bisulphite modification; however, in the forward strand if “C” is not methylated then it will be converted to “T”, this means that in the results represented in Figure 5.12 A all non-methylated “G” will be converted to “A” and this explains the absence of “G” in Figure 5.12. B, as “A” replaced “G” after conversion.

The first and the last few reads (15-50 bp) showed undefined, non-uniform clear peaks, this was expected as these areas were the primer binding sites (first reads) and the tail-end (last reads), and these were later removed by a process called “trimming” prior to analysis.

However, the middle area is considered a readable area only when the reaction is defined as “passed” reaction. In the present study, only sequences that were reported as ‘passed’ reactions were considered good quality sequences suitable for deep analysis. Raw data suggested successful “passed” sequencing reactions since the presented electropherograms showed well-formed, evenly separated peaks with distinctive single-coloured peaks, and most importantly, the absence of background noise, no overlapping peaks or competing sequences that are considered the criteria for defining a “passed” Sanger reaction. This suggests successful experimental set-up, preparation and purification of PCR samples prior to sequencing, as well as successful sequencing procedure.

A)

B)

Figure 5.12. Electropherograms of DNA sequencing reads pre and post-bisulphite conversion.

A section of electropherograms of CpG island 2 of *F2RL1* promoter region from LPS treated BEAS-2B cells sequencing reaction. **(A)** DNA from LPS treated BEAS-2B cells was amplified by unmodified-wild type specific primers using PCR, samples were purified and sent for Sanger sequencing. Image is a representation of section of sequenced CpG island 2 prior bisulphite conversion. **(B)** BEAS-2B cells LPS treated DNA sample was bisulphite converted and amplified by BSP using BS primers, samples were purified and sent for bisulphite Sanger sequencing. Image is a representation of CpG island 2 post-bisulphite conversion. Each single peak is a representation of a single nucleotide in the amplified DNA region, each base-pair is designated with a colour for differentiation. The nucleotide adenine “A” is green, cytosine “C” is blue, guanine is black “G” and red is thymine “T”. Images were observed using Chromas software (V. 2.6.6).

The quality score for each base pair was identified and represented under each chromatogram peak (Figure 5.13). Assigning each chromatogram peak to its specific base pair is referred to as “base calling” and this gives the identification of quality score. Quality score is classed as low or high quality and each class is differentiated with different colour and range. A range between 0-9 quality score is referred to as low quality and represented as black line under each chromatogram peak (Figure 5.13 A). In the electropherograms represented in the Figure 5.13 B, the low-quality sequences were observed at the beginning of each read and correspond to primer binding sites and this is an indication of low quality score detected at the beginning and tail-end of the readable sequence. Furthermore, the red (10-19) and yellow (20-29) base calling, are considered as an indication of an average good quality as they were detected within areas expected to be unreadable (Figure 5.13 B). The results obtained in this study showed absence of ambiguous bases within the readable sequence, with extensive region of base calling of green colour and quality score above “30”, which confirms high quality and indicates reliable identification of nucleotide.

In summary, the original raw data from bisulphite Sanger sequencing showed appropriate experimental-setup, successful sequencing reactions and high quality score base calling within the readable sequence, this indicates that sequences met quality control criteria and were suitable to proceed for deep methylation analysis.

Figure 5.13. Illustrative example of quality scores of base calling from electropherograms

DNA from COPD-HBEC treated with LPS and H₂O₂ were extracted and PCR amplified by unmodified-wild type specific primers. **(A)** Quality scores were observed in top of each sequencing reaction. **(B)** Electropherograms from COPD-HBEC represent base calling in each nucleotide each; is assigned with a colour which is linked to quality score classification. Green peaks: Adenine "A", Red peaks: Thymine "T", blue peaks: Cytosine "C", black peaks: Guanine "G".

5.3.9.1. Analysis of Sanger sequencing results

The analysis of bisulphite Sanger sequencing was carried out by Glasgow Polyomics using Unipro UGENE software. Initial work was done to reverse complementary of the DNA strands to the forward strand using reverse primers for both pre and post converted DNA sequences for easier visualisation and analysis of the results. Furthermore, the forward sequences from biological replicates of each cell type and from same treatments (pre and post bisulphite conversion) were aligned together, then the consensus sequence was lined up and compared against the aligned multiple sequences of same biological replicates.

Analysis of the sequences obtained from all biological replicates and from all treated/untreated BEAS-2B cells, HBEC and COPD-HBEC pre and post-conversion showed perfectly aligned sequences from different biological replicates per treatment and per cell type. An example is shown in Figure 5.14. Sequences from BEAS-2B cells pre conversion data from all replicates showed the presence of all base pairs (A, C, T and G) and the same base pairs were observed to be aligned in the same position in each sequence (Figure 5.14 A). The same observation was detected in the post-bisulphite conversion sequences of all replicates from BEAS-2B cells samples in the example of Figure 5.14, B. These good replicate alignment were also observed with HBEC and COPD-HBEC samples. This observation confirms the consistency of samples obtained from different biological replicates from each treatment condition, also this revealed that the experimental conditions were well optimised and reproducible (successful experimental set-up), in terms of successful PCR procedure, purification and sequencing. The consensus sequence showed high quality scores within the readable sequence, and low quality scores at the beginning of the sequences nearer to the primer binding site, as expected from raw electropherogram data, which shows that the sequences are highly reliable (Figure 5.14. C).

A)

B)

C)

Figure 5.14. Alignments of all replicates pre and post bisulphite conversion. UGENE software was used in order to align all sequences from all replicates pre (A) and post (B) bisulphite conversion. (C) UGENE was used to align consensus sequence with the multiple sequences, and to show the quality of base calling per nucleotide. The oval shapes represent the alignments of each base pair per each biological sample pre and post conversion. The grey bars are base calling, representation of quality score.

In order to detect if there were originally any methylated CpG sites within the CpG island 2 of the *F2RL1* gene promoter in untreated BEAS-2B cells, HBEC and COPD-HBEC, and whether the treatments with LPS/H₂O₂ alone or in combination caused any differential change in methylation levels if this is initially occurred, pre and post-bisulphite converted sequences from each cell type and from each sample were aligned and matched to each other to detect the efficiency of the bisulphite conversion, as well as, to detect if there was any methylation change occurring due to treatments. The data presented in Figure 5.15 is an example of the alignment of forward strand from BEAS-2B (Figure 5.15 A) and HBEC (Figure 5.15 B) samples pre and post-conversion for methylation analysis. Data showed that all “C” (in green) in the pre-converted sequences have been converted to “T” (in red) after bisulphite conversion, which is shown as “+” sign in the consensus sequence confirming absence of methylation; however, all “G”s, “T”s and “A”s did not change after conversion and this was expected (Oval shape). Similar outcomes were reported with the rest of the samples analysed from different treatments within each cell type.

These data confirm two observations. Firstly, the bisulphite conversion experiment had been successfully performed with all un-methylated “C” converted to uracil due to the bisulphite treatment and thus read as “T” after BSP, confirming high efficacy of bisulphite conversion. Secondly, however, after screening all samples for methylation analysis from all replicates and treatments from both cell types, none of the CpG sites detected within the amplified region of CpG island 2 was found to be methylated. No methylated sites were reported within the control sequences; also treatments with LPS/H₂O₂ alone or in combination did not induce any methylation (Figure 5.15 A) upper sequence and (Figure 5.15 B) lower sequence, this indicates that methylation of *F2RL1* Island 2 CpG sites within the amplified region was not detected in bronchial epithelial cell samples (BEAS-2B and primary cells). These data suggest that at least within the amplified region of CpG island 2 of PAR2 promoter sequence, epigenetic DNA methylation does not occur under basal conditions in any of the cell types tested, and furthermore did not occur in response to LPS/H₂O₂ treatment. This indicates that, at least in this region of PAR2 promoter region, DNA methylation is not

the mechanism that is responsible for controlling the gene expression of the *F2RL1* gene due to the OS and inflammatory insult model, nor its upregulation in COPD cells.

Figure 5.15. Alignment of pre and post-bisulphite converted DNA sequences.

Cells, BEAS-2B (A) and HBEC (B) were treated with LPS and H₂O₂, DNA was extracted, and amplified by unmodified primers then amplified by PCR. Also samples from the same extracted DNA were bisulphite converted and amplified by BSP using BS primers. Both PCR products were sent for Sanger sequencing. Analysis of methylation results were performed using UGENE software to align sequences of pre versus post-bisulphite converted reactions. The ovals represent the unmethylated “C” (green) pre-conversion converted to “T”(red) post-conversion and represented as “+” sign in the consensus sequence, while “G”, “A” and “T” did not change. The grey bars represent the base calling, which gives an indication about the quality score. Green “C” are an indication of pre-conversion sequences.

5.4. Discussion

Epigenetics is described as heritable changes in gene expression and function caused by mechanisms that alter cellular phenotype, and it occurs independent of primary DNA sequence changes (Jeanmonod, Rebecca and Suzuki, 2018). Exposure to environmental challenges such as pollution, toxicants, CS, and inflammation can trigger epigenetic modifications (Zong *et al.*, 2019a). Epigenetic modifications have a role in regulating and controlling gene expression, and are vitally linked to various inflammatory diseases and cancer where several tumor suppressor genes are unexpressed due to epigenetic modifications (Meng and Wang, 2018). CS and other environmental challenges that contribute to inflammation have been proposed to cause permanent changes in epigenetic patterns defined as epimutations, triggering the development of chronic diseases such as COPD (Arrowsmith *et al.*, 2012). Methylation is a vital process that regulates gene expression and activation e.g. gene silencing (Sundar *et al.*, 2011). This is an epigenetic change detected to occur on CpG sites within a gene promoter area. When a gene is hypermethylated this effectively silences the gene expression; conversely, hypomethylation is associated with active gene expression (Liu *et al.*, 2010).

In patients with COPD, several loci are identified to be hypomethylation and hypermethylation sites (Jeanmonod, Rebecca and Suzui, 2018). One potential locus identified as hypermethylated is reported to occur within the *NFE2L2* gene coding for Nrf2 anti-oxidant response protein. This mechanism is mainly correlated with reduced gene expression and down-regulation of its respective product. Nrf2 is a redox-transcription factor that is responsible for controlling the expression of antioxidant enzymes such as SOD2 and catalase. The impaired activity of the Nrf2 transcription factor in COPD has been highly linked to hypermethylation mainly caused by OS; this antagonises the Nrf2 protective pathway, thus regulating the pathophysiology of COPD (Emily A. Vucic *et al.*, 2014b).

Several studies have reported differential changes in methylation levels of gene promoter regions that have a key role in the presence and severity of COPD (Zong, Ouyang and Chen,

2015). Guzmán *et al.* detected a high percentage of hyper-methylation in the promoter regions of *CDKN2A* and *MGMT* genes from induced sputum samples from patients with COPD compared with healthy individuals, and these genes are highly related to heavy smoking (Guzmán *et al.*, 2012). Extremely important findings showed that there is a great influence on the risk of developing COPD and alteration of lung function due to smoking-related differential methylation signals in peripheral blood (Lee *et al.*, 2017; Machin *et al.*, 2017; Qiu *et al.*, 2012; Sood *et al.*, 2010; Wielscher *et al.*, 2015). One interesting result detected is the hypomethylation of the CpG site cg02181506 in the *SERPINA1* gene on chromosome 14; this gene is of particular interest as the main genetic factor associated with COPD development (Qiu *et al.*, 2011).

According to Qiu and colleagues, DNA hypomethylation at two CpG locations (cg24621042 and cg02181506) of the *SERPINA1* gene negatively impact the lung function, it significantly enhances and positively associated with the worsening and progression of the clinical conditions in COPD patients (Qiu *et al.*, 2011; Parris *et al.*, 2019; Anand, 2021). These observations were reported to be highly associated with CS. This will lead to an important conclusion that CS is a key factor that can change or alter the level of DNA methylation, which results in the local and systematic inflammation of COPD (Zong, Ouyang and Chen, 2015b). This process can be linked to OS stress, which was found to up-regulate the activity and expression of DNA methyl-transferase 1 (DNMT1), the key enzyme that is responsible for the hypermethylation of DNA promoter regions, thus causing a modification in gene expression (Patterson *et al.*, 2012).

This research study investigated whether there is an impact caused by OS (H₂O₂) and inflammatory mediator (LPS), alone or in combination, in inducing or changing methylation levels within the CpG island 2 of the *F2RL1* gene promoter region in BEAS-2B cells, HBEC and COPD-HBEC. The aim was to provide a better understanding of how methylation can regulate the expression of *F2RL1*, a key inflammatory regulator, thus underlying a potential role in diseases such as COPD. The expression of the *F2RL1* gene was found to be elevated in patients with asthma, but its role is still unclear in COPD development (Palikhe *et al.*, 2015).

Bioinformatics analysis suggested that the promoter region of the *F2RL1* gene has a significant number of CpG sites including two potential CpG islands, which can be an indication that the *F2RL1* promoter region has potential sites for methylation that may occur after chronic exposure to OS or inflammation, and thus by extrapolation linked to COPD development.

Current knowledge comprises two studies reporting the effect of PAR2 promoter methylation in PAR2 expression in Ulcerative Colitis (UC) (Tahara *et al.*, 2009) and in lung cancer (Wu, Xu and Cheng, 2021c). The outcomes of these two studies will be explained further in the following discussion.

In the present study, it was observed from the bioinformatics perspective that two CpG islands were detected in the *F2RL1* promoter region, with the CpG island 2 (bigger in size), more dense with CpG sites and importantly, overlapping with the *F2RL1* coding sequence and TSS. This study reveals that the PAR2 promoter region is associated with several promoter motifs, among them, GATA-1, AP-1, SP-1 and AP-2; most interestingly, AP-1 and SP-1, which fall within CpG island 2. In particular, an SP-1 transcription motif is located within CpG island 2, and correlated with CpG site number -21 of CpG island 2 (relative to TSS) located within the SP-1 transcription binding site. SP-1, upon binding to the promoter region of a gene, activates transcription. Multiple copies of SP-1 are found to be often distributed within the promoter and enhancer regions of genes (Xin *et al.*, 2018b).

Importantly, results from the present study demonstrated that an AP-1 putative binding site also appeared to overlap with CpG island 2 and within the TSS of PAR2. AP-1 (activator protein 1) signalling was found to be enhanced and upregulated in the epithelium of smokers and patients with COPD (Wu *et al.*, 2017; Parris *et al.*, 2019). OS modulates the activity of redox-sensitive transcription factors including NF- κ B and AP-1, and the upregulation of these transcription factors mediates the production of pro-inflammatory genes (cytokines and proteases) in response to OS (Parris *et al.*, 2019).

It has been reported that a CpG island is highly sensitive to methylation if it is associated with binding sites of SP-1, Myc, USF-1, CREB, CTCF, GATA-1, and AP-2 transcription factors, among other motifs. Reduced gene expression results from lower binding effectiveness at transcription factor binding sites following methylation (Uhm *et al.*, 2012). Consequently, this makes CpG island 2 a potential target of methylation by OS and LPS at the transcription binding sites of AP-1 and SP-1 transcription factors. Any alterations in the specific sequence of a TF-binding motif alters the affinity of the transcription motif to bind to its distinctive regulatory sequence, thus altering expression products of genes (Shir-Shapira *et al.*, 2015).

Accordingly, these observations make CpG island 2 a potential target for methylation analysis. Initially, in the present study, it was reported that the transcript levels of the *F2RL1* gene were enhanced due to treatments with H₂O₂ in HBEC and COPD-HBEC, and in BEAS-2B cells, it was observed that LPS/ H₂O₂ alone significantly elevated *F2RL1* gene expression. It was believed that these observations could be linked to epigenetic modifications mainly DNA methylation caused by OS and inflammatory insult, which is controlling the *F2RL1* gene expression.

Consequently, it was expected that if the expression is regulated by epigenetic modification this would be hypomethylation, which means that at basal level, CpG island 2 of PAR2 promoter region would be methylated and treatments caused hypomethylation. However, in case of COPD-HBEC the expression level of *F2RL1* was found to be significantly higher at basal level compared to HBEC. It can be expected that the basal methylation level of COPD cells would be reduced, and further treatments induced subsequent hypomethylation which enhanced *F2RL1* gene expression in COPD-HBEC.

In the present study, Sanger sequencing analysis confirmed successfully bisulphite conversion as all “C” was converted to “T”; however, the deep methylation analysis did not show any methylated CpG sites. Originally in the amplified region of CpG island 2 in control (untreated) cells, no methylations were detected, also treatments with H₂O₂ and LPS did not induce any methylations in any of the CpG sites in the amplified region of CpG island 2 in any

of the cell types. This suggests that epigenetic methylation in the selected amplified region of CpG island 2 is not the mechanism that is responsible for the increase in the mRNA transcript levels of the PAR2 gene; however, the proposed hypothesis of the role of epigenetic methylation in the regulation of PAR2 expression cannot be totally eliminated in this research study. Initially, the bioinformatics analysis revealed the detection of two CpG islands, in this study, it was decided to focus on CpG island 2 as it was considered a strong and potential target for methylation analysis for several reasons mentioned. Although methylations were not detected in the amplified CpG island 2, this does not eliminate the possibility of epigenetic methylation responsible for controlling *F2RL1* gene expression. CpG island 1 was also detected within the 2110 bp *F2RL1* gene promoter region, and it is further from the TSS. There is a possibility that any epigenetic methylation occurred within this island, enhancing *F2RL1* gene expression.

Importantly, several CpG shores were identified by bioinformatics analysis between the two CpG islands, and it can be proposed that differential methylation have occurred within these sites, which could cause a change in gene expression. CpG shores are regions located on both sides of CpG islands. They are randomly distributed within a gene promoter region, usually highly methylated compared to CpG islands and are usually associated with moderate to high methylated CpG sites (Mitsumori *et al.*, 2020a); it was reported that the further the CpG dinucleotide from CpG island, the higher the chance to be methylated (Shimoda *et al.*, 2014; Skvortsova *et al.*, 2019). However, it was reported by another previous study that methylated cytosines at CpG island shores negatively control gene expression (Doi *et al.*, 2009; Mitsumori *et al.*, 2020b). Despite these uncertainties, CpG shores could be an attractive alternative target to analyse methylation patterns in *F2RL1*.

Regulation of gene transcription by DNA methylation has been reported to be location-dependent (Eunise Martha *et al.*, 2018). Recently, methylation of gene bodies was reported to be more important to study than methylation in promoter regions (Dixon *et al.*, 2018). Gene bodies are areas that are identified as an entire gene starting from the TSS to the end of the transcript (Hahn *et al.*, 2011). Gene bodies were identified to be associated with potentially

differentially methylated CpG sites. In one recent study, this area of a gene was found to be hypermethylated and thus reported to be positively correlated with gene expression and to highly stimulate gene elongation and splicing (Wang *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, if methylation is found upstream in the promoter region or nearer the TSS, this has been found to be negatively affect gene expression, as these areas are considered to be associated with hypermethylation which suppresses gene expression and prevents initiation of transcription (Medvedeva *et al.*, 2014).

Accordingly, it can be speculated that if the *F2RL1* gene expression is controlled by epigenetic methylation then the methylation in gene bodies should be considered a key target to check in future work, as the findings reported in the present study (qPCR data showing enhanced *F2RL1* gene expression due to H₂O₂ and LPS treatments and in COPD), suggest these treatments (or conditions) may induce hypermethylation in the gene bodies downstream of TSS that positively correlated with the *F2RL1* gene expression.

In general, identified sequences downstream and closer to the promoter region and TSS are considerably found to be hypermethylated and effectively these are part of the functional promoter and importantly associated with transcription initiation and enhanced gene expression (Eunise Martha *et al.*, 2018). The data presented in this study showed that CpG island 2 overlapped with *F2RL1* coding sequence and within TSS; this overlapped region of CpG island 2 was thus considered as likely potential region for methylation analysis and speculated to be hypermethylated due to LPS and H₂O₂ treatments.

Enhancers, a short DNA sequence that is usually located thousands of nucleotides away from the coding region of a gene (upstream or downstream), their role is to enhance transcription by the binding of activators to the distal control regulatory elements of the enhancer promoting the interaction with mediators and transcription factors to their binding site within the promoter region, which enhances transcription (Kolovos *et al.*, 2012). Enhancers were identified as potential target regions for differential methylation, and

recently extensive studies were carried out to study effects of DNA methylation in these regions on the gene expression and disease progression (Eunise Martha *et al.*, 2018).

Currently, two studies have shown that epigenetic DNA methylation detected within the PAR2 promoter region significantly affected PAR2 gene expression and disease progression. A study conducted by Tahara *et al.* provided evidence that PAR2 promoter differential methylation is associated with the severe clinical phenotypes of Ulcerative Colitis (UC) (Tahara *et al.*, 2009). This study demonstrated through the use of mucosal specimens from patients suffering from the two different sub phenotypes of UC and healthy individuals that DNA methylation status of PAR2 gene promoter in rectal mucosa correlates with more severe various clinical phenotypes of UC, and this was linked to differential methylation status of *F2RL1* in this sub phenotype compared to total colitis, where methylation detected to be significantly higher (Tahara *et al.*, 2009).

Very recently, a study by Wu, Xu and Cheng, also showed that differential methylation of the PAR2 promoter region is linked to a reverse correlation with *F2RL1* gene expression. Furthermore, the change in PAR2 gene expression due to alteration in DNA methylation levels within the PAR2 promoter region was also associated with lung adenocarcinoma cell progression. Subsequently, they reasoned that malignant cellular behaviour of lung adenocarcinoma (LUAD) including proliferation, migration and invasion are highly controlled by differential methylated levels of the PAR2 promoter region, which was found to be hypomethylated in these cells. The regulation of these cellular mechanisms was proposed to be through up-regulation of PAR2 gene expression due to PAR2 hypomethylation (Wu, Xu and Cheng, 2021c). These two studies confirmed that epigenetic methylation directly regulates PAR2 gene expression and this is associated with disease severity and progression, which provide a strong rationale to deeply investigate the role of *F2RL1* methylation in COPD development and progression.

OS has been extensively shown to alter gene expression through epigenetic methylation. CS was used as an oxidative stimulus in most epigenome-wide methylation association studies

conducted in COPD. These studies confirmed that alteration in DNA methylation levels at several CpG sites is due to exposure to OS, mainly CS (Zhu *et al.*, 2016; Zaghlool *et al.*, 2015 ; Zeilinger *et al.*, 2013; Li *et al.*, 2018; Zong *et al.*, 2019a).

Researchers reported elevated expression levels of *DNMT1* in lung tissues of smoking COPD patients compared to the expression in non-smoking COPD patients, confirming role of OS in altering DNA methylation levels (Joehanes *et al.*, 2016). Moreover, when DNMT1 activity was inhibited, this successfully restored and up-regulated gene expression which had been suppressed due to CS condensate through demethylation (Gao *et al.*, 2015b). Therefore, CS can trigger gene hyper-methylation by upregulating DNMT1 that in turn downregulates target genes expression. In addition to CS, DNMT1 can be also upregulated by other inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6, TGF- β and IL-1 β (Zong *et al.*, 2019b).

A study conducted by Shen *et al.* reported that *DNMT1* expression was downregulated in inflamed peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) after being treated with LPS; this shows that LPS can down regulate the expression of *DNMT1* thus enhancing hypomethylation and up-regulating gene expression (Shen *et al.*, 2017). This supports the idea that DNA methylation modification is directly engaged in signalling pathways linked to inflammation (Meng *et al.*, 2019).

In the present study, H₂O₂ was used to induce OS, and initially it was demonstrated that intracellular ROS was highly elevated due to treatments with H₂O₂. As OS is considered a main cause of altering DNA methylation levels, it was proposed that the level of intracellular ROS caused by the chronic treatments would likely be enough to alter DNA methylation. However, in contrary, sequencing data did not show any methylated sites within the control or DNA sequences from cells treated with H₂O₂. Aside from potentially 'missing' any actual regulated sites through the choice of CpG island 2 for methylation analysis, it can be speculated that experimentally the level of intracellular ROS produced by H₂O₂ was not sufficient to cause any differential methylation changes. Although this level induced cellular stress, but it may be that this concentration of H₂O₂ (15 or 25 μ M) was not high enough to cause DNA methylation

changes. Also, the exposure time might not be long enough to cause epigenetic alteration. For these reasons, other continuous ROS generators such as nitric oxide, CSE and ozone might be considered as powerful alternative oxidants to induce methylation changes. Recently, a study reported that when Jurkat T lymphoma cells were treated with 10 μ M H₂O₂ for 24 h, this highly down regulated *DNMT1* expression and this caused a remarkable disturbance to DNA methylation patterns, however, it was found that site-specific CpG methylation changes occurred immediately 1-2 h after exposure to H₂O₂(Seddon *et al.*, 2021), indicating that it was reasonable to anticipate the treatments used in the current work might lead to modulation of methylation.

Extensive epigenetic methylation research studies have been carried out in COPD, and DNA methylated biomarkers have been identified in blood, sputum tracheal epithelium and lung tissue of COPD patients (He *et al.*, 2020b). Although the current work did not provide additional evidence that the *F2RL1* promoter should be added to the array of methylation loci modulated in COPD, nor does not eliminate this possibility. The recognition of the role of epigenetic mechanisms in the development of COPD may identify novel targets to hatch new therapies for patients with COPD (Wu *et al.*, 2018).

Chapter 6. General discussion & future direction

6.1. General discussion

The pathophysiology of COPD is marked by a chronic persistent lung inflammation that is exacerbated by an imbalance in the protease/anti-protease and oxidant/anti-oxidant OS systems (Mathers and Loncar, 2006; Barnes, 2020). Consequently, aberrant tissue healing, increased mucus secretion, and epithelial cell hyperplasia are all caused by the ongoing inflammatory response. As a result, the small conducting airways are permanently damaged and thickened, which gradually reduces airflow (Rabe and Watz, 2017). CS or repeated exposure to biomass, noxious gases, occupational dust and particulate matter are considered the main cytotoxic insults and risk factors for COPD development and progression (Pauwels *et al.*, 2001; le *et al.*, 2022). CS is considered the predominant source of oxidant agents in the lungs; however, inflammatory cells and phagocytes found in the respiratory tract also produce ROS in the lung (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2021).

OS is generated in lung cells when endogenous anti-oxidant defences are compromised and/or overwhelmed by the increase of ROS. Sources of OS such as H_2O_2 and other ROS such as hydroxyl radical ($HO\bullet$) and superoxide anion (O_2^-) are generated by the transformation of oxygen via a cascade of enzymatic and non-enzymatic reactions (Hayyan, Hashim and Alnashef, 2016). The causes of ROS within the airways may result from either endogenous sources such as cell damage and/or activated inflammatory and structural cells, or exogenous insults such as the case of CS. Structural cells, such as bronchial airway epithelium is the first target of inhaled CS; furthermore, they are considered the initial line of host defence by maintaining barrier function and mucociliary clearance (Chen *et al.*, 2020). They are critical in maintaining lung homeostasis as well as orchestrating the innate and adaptive immune response to secrete an array of inflammatory mediators including cytokines and chemokines, and recruiting immune cells in response to insults from inhaled cigarette smoke (Zhou *et al.*, 2020).

As a result of OS, epithelial cells in the airways trigger an inflammatory response that is amplified by immune cells, resulting in airway inflammation (Serdarevic *et al.*, 2012;

Burgoyne, Fisher and Borthwick, 2021). Chronic inflammation is a fundamental feature of COPD that promotes the disease's pathogenesis and remains even after smoking cessation (Kirkham and Barnes, 2013b). This shows that OS may influence gene expression via epigenetic alterations such as DNA methylation and histone acetylation (Sun *et al.* 2012). Inflammation and OS are two processes that are intrinsically linked. Chronic inflammation is related to high levels of ROS and impaired antioxidant systems (Cipollina *et al.*, 2022).

NF- κ B transcription factors comprise major regulators of the inflammation process. NF- κ B is a key redox-sensitive transcription factor pathway that has been identified to have a master role in COPD (Liu *et al.*, 2017b). The NF- κ B inflammatory pathway is highly activated in inflammatory cells and it controls the gene transcription of several inflammatory mediators such as cytokines, growth factors and proteases that are associated with adaptive and innate immune responses (Sheridan *et al.*, 2015). The activation of NF- κ B by inflammatory molecules induces the secretion of further inflammatory molecules, amplifying the response. Conversely, when NF- κ B pathway is blocked, the expression of IL-6 and TNF- α is downregulated (Zhong *et al.*, 2016).

Moreover, the NF- κ B signaling pathway is regulated by oxidants, and H₂O₂ is one of many oxidants found in CS, and is detected to be elevated in breath condensates of COPD patients and linked to high levels of inflammation (Schuliga, 2015a). H₂O₂ is the by-product of superoxide dismutation, which is catalysed by SOD2 catalytic enzymes. Superoxide is produced in a continuous manner due to mitochondrial respiration, but it can be also generated by other enzymes such as NADPH oxidase and xanthine oxidase (Daiber *et al.*, 2017).

Recently, it was proposed that a relationship between epigenetics and the generation of inflammatory cytokines may possibly be connected to the development of COPD (Sundar *et al.*, 2017c). Epigenetic alterations mainly entail DNA methylation and post-translational modification (PTM), including histone acetylation/deacetylation, methylation, phosphorylation, ubiquitination and sulphonation. Among these PTM, COPD was found to be

primarily associated with histone acetylation. In COPD, there is an imbalance between histone acetylation/de-acetylation favoring acetylation. The reduction of histone deacetylase activity is directly linked in promoting inflammation (He *et al.*, 2020c).

HDACs are essential in the regulation of the inflammatory response. HDACs inhibit the expression of inflammatory genes that are sensitive to oxidative stress. Due to NF- κ B activation and decreased HDAC2 activity, macrophage buildup in the lungs of COPD patients causes an increase in the release of inflammatory mediators and elastolytic enzymes (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2021). In alveolar macrophages and lung tissue from COPD patients, HDAC2 activity is decreased (Liu, Gao and Ci, 2019) and the reduced activity is correlated with increased histone acetylation at the IL-8 promoter. HDAC2 expression in the lungs is decreased by CS, oxidative stress, nitrative stress, and aldehyde (Sundar, Yao and Rahman, 2013). Reduced HDAC2 in the lungs further compromises Nrf2 activation, reducing its half-life and compromising its coordinated antioxidant defence (Mercado *et al.*, 2011; Fischer, Voynow and Ghio, 2015), while also boosting NF- κ B RelA/p65 subunit activation and consequently, promoting pro-inflammatory gene transcription (Sundar, Yao and Rahman, 2013; Rodrigues *et al.*, 2021).

Studies showed that OS is involved in the pathology of many diseases such as chronic kidney disease, neurodegenerative diseases, ageing and cancer (Dalle-Donne, Aldini *et al.* 2006; Kurien and Scofield 2008; reviewed by Liguori *et al.*, 2018). Although various models have been developed to study the link between OS and COPD disease pathology, most have been based on acute exposure (2-4 h) that doesn't accurately reflect the disease pathology, as chronic exposure to OS is the key factor in the pathogenesis of these diseases such as COPD. Consequently, it was important in this study to demonstrate the effect of OS in modulating inflammatory pathways in a chronic exposure cell-based model before expanding the work to more complex systems. Therefore, the initial aim was to induce a model of *in vitro* chronic OS using H₂O₂ as a source of ROS to induce OS, in immortalised epithelial cells (BEAS-2B) and primary human bronchial epithelial cells (HBEC/COPD-HBEC). Although H₂O₂ does not fully reflect the complex mixture of stimulants seen in tobacco smoke (Young, Hopkins *et al.*, 2006;

Barnes 2007), it is a key ROS factor, detected at high concentrations in breath condensates of patients with COPD and this has been associated with the pathophysiology of COPD (Cheng *et al.*, 2016; Barnes, 2020).

It is hypothesised that ROS are responsible for the major effects of CS (Barnes, 2016). This concept supports the use of a simple H₂O₂ stimulus to focus on the effects of ROS. The simple chronic exposure OS model was augmented with pro-inflammatory mediators (TGF- β , TNF- α and LPS, added alone for 48 h or in combination with H₂O₂ for 2h/day for 3 days) to further model the COPD conditions, with the combined challenge referred to within as “standard combined exposure protocol”. It was demonstrated that H₂O₂ induced significant elevation of intracellular ROS in BEAS-2B cells, HBEC and COPD-HBEC. Therefore, transient, repeated H₂O₂ exposure represented an effective model as ROS inducer. Importantly, there was an increased impact of H₂O₂ in combination with LPS, TNF- α , and TGF- β in BEAS-2B cells, and a similar pattern was observed in primary cells when treated with LPS and H₂O₂. This suggests that OS is generated within the cells a result of both stress insults, and may be instructive in reflecting the pattern of OS generation in COPD. Interestingly, H₂O₂ did not have any effect alone, but synergistically augmented the inflammatory response induced by TNF- α , TGF- β and LPS in terms of IL-6 and IL-8 cytokines production; this emphasises the importance of multiple ‘hits’ or cellular challenges required to cause shifts in the pattern of inflammatory/immune gene expression during pathogenesis. It can be postulated that the cells developed resistance to OS generated by H₂O₂ over continuous repeated transient exposure to OS. Also, chronic OS may have affected signaling pathways or epigenetic events and additional inflammatory stimulus was required to enhance inflammation. It can be also proposed that OS sensitive cells went under either necrosis or apoptosis following longer OS challenges.

Consistent with the idea that repeated exposure to OS improved cell survival through the induction of antioxidant genes, qPCR results demonstrated a significant elevation of ROS-related biomarkers *NFE2L2*, *SOD2* and *CAT* genes when treated with H₂O₂. Interestingly, the *SOD2* gene was significantly induced when BEAS-2B cells were exposed to both LPS and H₂O₂, but this was not observed in primary cells, suggesting cell-specific effects of LPS and possible

limitations of the immortalised cell line to mimic 'true' epithelial phenotypes. More importantly, the expression of *SOD2* gene was induced in HBEC significantly more than in COPD-HBEC, suggesting that HBEC are more sensitive to OS than COPD-HBEC. This may reflect that the latter (COPD-HBEC), already exposed to OS during disease, may develop resistance, but on the other hand have impaired capacity to respond to challenge. Jitca *et al.* proposed that transitory oxidative status is essential to activate the adaptation process to high continuous OS (Jîtcă *et al.*, 2022). Accordingly, enduring exposure to low levels of ROS factors enhances cells' capacity to respond to higher levels of stress due to the phenomenon of the endogenous antioxidant systems upregulation (Cunha *et al.*, 2012), which is primarily associated with enzymatic systems that increase the expression of activated manganese-dependent superoxide dismutase (MnSOD)(Ji, Gomez-Cabrera and Vina, 2006; Powers, Radak and Ji, 2016; Jîtcă *et al.*, 2022), catalase (*CAT*) and glutathione peroxidase (GPx)(Finkler, Lichtenberg and Pinchuk, 2014; Jîtcă *et al.*, 2022).

The observation proposed by Jitica *et al.* was also demonstrated by several groups previously, who reported that low exposure to OS amplifies cellular resistance to high OS through the induction of antioxidant systems (Collinson and Dawes 1992; Bose Girigoswami, Bhaumik *et al.* 2005; Khan *et al.*, 2014). However, it was suggested by Circu and colleagues that when cells are exposed to higher concentrations of ROS for prolonged periods of time, this induces cellular necrosis or apoptosis (Circu *et al.*, 2009; Azad and Iyer, 2014).

OS can cause damaging effects in COPD; it is considered as the master predisposing reason behind the pathogenesis of COPD and thus can be a vital target for therapies related to COPD. OS is directly associated with several pathways underpinning the development of the obstructive symptoms detected in COPD (Xu, Liu and Song, 2020). Accordingly, it can be suggested that cells were no more sensitive to OS and this may explain why cells did not enhance IL-6 and IL-8 secretion levels.

In this present research, it was shown that in both immortalised and primary cell models the gene expression of *IL8* and *IL6* were not enhanced by H₂O₂ alone; however, the presence

of H₂O₂ considerably enhanced LPS-induced *IL8* gene expression in HBEC and COPD-HBEC; interestingly, the finding in this work showed heightened levels of *IL8* mRNA in HBEC compared to COPD-HBEC. Furthermore, H₂O₂ markedly promoted LPS-induced *IL6 mRNA transcript* gene expression in BEAS-2B cells. These findings suggest that the expression of these genes are highly regulated by transcription factors whose activity is also induced directly or indirectly by OS. In this work, H₂O₂ did not enhance *RELA* transcription levels in either cell model, but its effect was notable in primary cells when treated in combination with LPS, suggesting that H₂O₂ may indirectly activate *RELA* transcription by priming p65 to activate *IL8* and *IL6* and this may explain the significant induction of *IL8* gene in both HBEC and COPD-HBEC. *IL8* transcriptional activation is directly regulated and activated by inducible transcription factors such as NF-κB p65. Genomic analysis discovered that *IL8* promoter region contains a NF-κB p65 binding site (GGAATTTCC)(Jundi and Greene, 2015).

The impact of prolonged exposure to OS such as CS amplifies aberrant inflammation due to the activation of inflammatory mediators in the airways, which leads to a reduction of airflow, and tissue remodelling that are major features of COPD (Brito *et al.*, 2021a). Bronchial epithelial cells are considered the main sources of cytokines and chemokines, they react to cigarette smoke extract (CSE) by initiating inflammatory pathways such as mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs) and transcription factors such as (NF-κB)(Baskoro *et al.*, 2018). LPS, one of the constituents of CS, was reported to play a vital role in transducing several pro-inflammatory effects of CS in the bronchial epithelium and inducing signalling pathways (Bondi *et al.*, 2014). TLR4 expression rises in response to CSE, and its activation initiates the majority of proinflammatory pathways triggered by CSE in HBEC. Several studies have widely demonstrated the role of NF-κB to control inflammation caused by CSE in HBEC (Chen *et al.*, 2020) (Munakata *et al.*, 2018; Sekine *et al.*, 2019; Ishikawa *et al.*, 2019a; Tan *et al.*, 2021).

It has been reported by Albano and colleagues that treatment of BEAS-2B cells with 2.5 % CSE for 24 h significantly elevated the expression level of NF-κB with a rise of nuclear phospho-p65 levels; such effects amplified IL-8 and IL-6 pro-inflammatory cytokines release (Brito *et al.*, 2021b; Albano *et al.*, 2018). Besides enhancing cytokines and chemokines release, the

activation of NF- κ B pathway by CSE stimulates the expression and release of MMPs that contribute to disruption of the airway tissue (Ishikawa *et al.*, 2019b; Lavrynenko *et al.*, 2020; Yang *et al.*, 2021).

A proteomic study of proteins released at the apical liquid surface of HBEC cultured in 3D Air-Liquid Interface (ALI) culture revealed that oxidative stress triggered the overexpression of MMP-9, MMP-10, and MMP-14, mostly through the ERK1/2 signalling pathway (Ishikawa *et al.*, 2019b). Moreover, when HBEC were stimulated with CSE this in turn activated MAPK2 (ERK2), which has a pivotal role in proliferation and cell survival, and is a kinase that drives inflammation and stress responses (Wu *et al.*, 2016). The ERK1/2 pathway was also linked to increased mucus secretion, a well-known pathophysiological characteristic associated with COPD. MUC5AC transcription was increased in normal HBEC treated with 5% CSE and activated with the viral mimic poly(I:C) (Toll-like receptor 3 ligand) via stimulation of the ERK1/2 pathway (Kanai *et al.*, 2015).

In this work, a representative lung epithelium model was challenged with OS to provide an experimental tool for understanding and studying the molecular and inflammatory mechanisms underlying OS-related respiratory diseases such as COPD, in order to potentially highlight novel therapeutic strategies and ultimately aid development of new drugs. The work demonstrated here showed that proinflammatory cytokines production was highly induced when OS and inflammatory stress stimulants were added together, explaining a direct role of OS in inducing high levels of inflammation, that may be similar to what is found in COPD. Compared to asthma, patients with COPD respond to inhaled corticosteroids (ICS) less effectively, with little improvement in their lung function (Suissa and Barnes, 2009). However, the primary therapeutic justification for using high doses of inhaled ICS is the constant reduction (20-25 %) in exacerbations in COPD patients with severe illness (Kew and Seniukovich, 2014). Conversely, large clinical studies have reported that ICS is not effective in reducing the progression of COPD, which is measured with annual fall in FEV1 (Vestbo *et al.*, 2013b); further ICS failed to reduce mortality in another large study (Calverley *et al.*, 2007) and this was reviewed by (Barnes, 2010). These findings may indicate that pulmonary

resistance to ICS is due to persistent inflammation, mainly caused by continuous generation of OS, and also linked to a decrease in HDAC2 (Barnes, 2010).

A plausible direction for new therapies could rely on strategies that have a role in promoting the endogenous anti-oxidant levels and to relieve OS insults through natural or synthetic antioxidants compounds (Cipollina *et al.*, 2022). Restoring Nrf2 levels through Nrf2 agonists or activators is a potential and promising therapeutic strategy for restoring the activity of ICS (Wu *et al.*, 2007; Rodrigues *et al.*, 2021). When Nrf2 levels are enhanced this triggers the activation of HDAC2 due to the reduction of OS levels; when HDAC2 activity is restored, this represses activated inflammatory genes and pathways, indicating that Nrf2 and HDAC2 would both be involved in restoring ICS sensitivity in COPD treatment (Zhang *et al.*, 2011).

Strategies based on reducing oxidative stress are considered among the important therapeutic targets in COPD (Adcock, Caramori and Barnes, 2010; Biswas *et al.*, 2013; Kirkham and Barnes, 2013b). Antioxidant mimetics have been designed to restore impaired antioxidant enzymes such as SOD, catalase and GPx (Day, 2004). Furthermore, several NOX inhibitors were developed to counteract OS (Cifuentes-Pagano, Csanyi and Pagano, 2012; Altenhöfer *et al.*, 2015). NADPH oxidase (NOX) is a main source of ROS in COPD via production of superoxide anions. Inhaled apocynin, a non-selective NOX inhibitor, was considered an anti-inflammatory agent for treating COPD (Stefanska *et al.*, 2012). Apocynin was found to reduce the levels of nitrite and decreased H₂O₂ in airway of patients with COPD (Oostwoud *et al.*, 2016, Barnes, 2020). Previously, Orosz *et al.* showed that apocynin can effectively inhibit endothelial dysfunction triggered by CS, and it can hinder the NADPH activity in smooth muscle cells (Orosz *et al.*, 2007). Recently, this effect of apocynin was demonstrated *in vivo* using mice model. Apocynin given systemically to CS-exposed mice and was found to reduce inflammation by decreasing the level of pro-inflammatory cytokines and chemokines in BALF (Oostwoud *et al.*, 2016).

Other natural and synthetic antioxidants have been found to ameliorate COPD, and a large number of compounds and molecules were found to act as antioxidants in COPD including thiol compounds (GSH, N-acetyl-L-cysteine (NAC)(Dekhuijzen and van Beurden, 2006; Rodrigues *et al.*, 2021) antioxidant vitamins (e.g. C and E), lipid peroxidation inhibitors/blockers (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2021), myeloperoxidases inhibitors(Lazarevic-Pasti, Leskovac and Vasic, 2015). The role of antioxidant treatments is mainly to reduce free radical levels and ameliorate inflammatory gene expression and related pathways (Menzel *et al.*, 2019; Yang *et al.*, 2021). Due to COPD heterogeneity and the complexity of inflammation, developing anti-inflammatory-based drugs to treat COPD remains a huge challenge. Bronchodilators can lower inflammation levels, but they are ineffective in reducing inflammation and disease progression specifically in severe COPD patients (Rabe and Watz, 2017). Currently, no therapeutic strategies can reverse COPD pathogenesis; however, reducing COPD progression remains a vital therapeutic goal. Decreasing OS and inflammation by supplementation and therapeutic administration of antioxidants could be of great benefit to COPD patients by enhancing endogenous antioxidant levels (Van Eeden and Sin, 2013; Schuliga, 2015).

Importantly, in this study, pre-treatment with TPCA-1 effectively suppressed LPS-induced IL-6 and IL-8 and significantly inhibited H₂O₂-enhanced LPS induction of pro-inflammatory cytokines in BEAS-2B, HBEC and COPD-HBEC, suggesting that oxidative stress-driven cytokine release was largely mediated via activation of the NF- κ B pathway, likely canonical. TPCA-1 also suppressed stressor-stimulated levels of *IL6*, *IL8* and *RELA* transcripts. The synergistic effect of COPD-relevant stimuli in combination was effectively inhibited by blocking a single pathway (NF- κ B), including a transcriptional component. These findings in a simple oxidative stress model further support the potential for NF- κ B blockade as a therapeutic strategy to ameliorate chronic inflammation in COPD.

A recent study reported similar observations using cardiac cells and IL-1 β Mizuno *et al.* showed that pretreatment of cardiac fibroblasts with TPCA-1 significantly attenuated *IL8* gene expression level and IL-8 protein secretion, this observation was also supported by western

blot where IL-1 β induced phosphorylation of p65 and p105 of NF- κ B was clearly reduced when pretreated with TPCA-1, confirming that the induction of IL-8 occurred through the NF- κ B pathway (Mizuno *et al.*, 2022).

TPCA-1 is considered one of the best characterised commercially available small molecule inhibitors of IKK β , and it was demonstrated previously to be efficient at therapeutic levels in a pre-clinical lung cancer model (Prescott and Cook, 2018a). Furthermore, Nan and colleagues have reported a dual effect of TPCA-1 in lung cancer cells. When A549 cells were pre-treated with TPCA-1, this directly inhibited both NF- κ B and STAT3 pathways, this was associated with a significant decrease in IL-6 and COX-2 levels. Furthermore, an important effect of TPCA-1 was confirmed when this was used in combination with tyrosine-kinase inhibitor (TKI) in lung cells, this combination of TPCA-1 with TKI reduced activity of NF- κ B, which showed increased sensitivity and enhanced apoptosis induced by gefitinib (a chemotherapeutic TKI). Therefore, combination treatment of TPCA-1 with TKIs has the potential to be a more effective strategy for lung cancers (Nan *et al.*, 2017). Since persistent NF- κ B signalling is associated with reduced sensitivity to ICS treatments in COPD, the combination of NF- κ B inhibitors or blockers with ICS could be a promising therapeutic approach toward increasing the sensitivity of COPD patients to ICS treatments.

Inhibitors of IKK β have shown great efficacy in pre-clinical models such as in cancer and several inflammatory diseases. For example, in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis (RA), IMD-2560 underwent a phase I trial (Okazaki *et al.*, 2005) (Prescott and Cook, 2018b), and IMD-0354 was accepted in a proof-of-concept (POC) study for the treatment of COPD. Alternative approaches rather than targeting NF- κ B directly are also in development and under current investigation, such as targeting upstream signaling components e.g. induction of NF- κ B by LPS (Miklos *et al.*, 2017), targeting NF- κ B independent functions of IKKs (Colomer *et al.*, 2017) and targeting downstream effectors of NF- κ B dependent pathogenesis (Kleppe *et al.*, 2018), with the aim to develop highly selective therapies that targeting NF- κ B pathways, with the aim of reducing inflammation in different conditions including in cancer therapy (Prescott and Cook, 2018b).

In the present study, the effect of H₂O₂ alone or in combination with inflammatory mediators on the expression of *F2RL1* (encoding PAR2) was examined in BEAS-2B cells, HBEC and COPD-HBEC. In BEAS-2B cells, LPS, TGF- β and H₂O₂ enhanced the expression of *F2RL1* gene; whereas in primary cells, H₂O₂ only had a significant effect on *F2RL1* gene expression, suggesting an important role of OS in increasing the expression of PAR2. A similar finding was reported previously, where OS modelled by low concentrations of H₂O₂ upregulated PAR2 in keratinocytes; it was suggested by Li *et al.* that H₂O₂ elevated intracellular calcium and this was associated with increased PAR2 expression in keratinocytes. The study showed that when extracellular calcium concentrations were inhibited, this in turn impaired H₂O₂-induced PAR2 expression levels (J. Li *et al.*, 2016). This observation can be a proposed mechanism for the increase of PAR2 expression in the research study presented in this thesis, although H₂O₂-induced calcium mobilisation was not directly investigated here. The role of PAR2 in COPD development is not well studied, but studies covering PAR2 roles in asthma and pulmonary fibrosis have been reported. Of relevance to COPD, BEAS-2B cells exposed to CSE upregulated PAR2 expression, and synergistically enhanced neutrophil elastase induction of PAR2, and induced IL-8 production through PAR2 activation (Lee *et al.*, 2018).

DNA methylation is a tissue-specific epigenetic alteration involved in the control of gene expression (Emily A. Vucic *et al.*, 2014c). DNA methylation is part of the foundation of normal physiological development, and has a significant role in many chronic complex disorders, including cancer (Luo *et al.*, 2020) and ageing (Horvath and Raj, 2018). Numerous studies have proven that COPD-related DNA methylation could be a potential marker for disease diagnosis, prognostic evaluation and prevention (Qiu *et al.*, 2012; Sundar *et al.*, 2017). Additionally, its reversibility makes it a potential target for developing medications and disease-related biomarkers.

Epigenetic methylation was also found to have a significant role in COPD development; several promoter regions of COPD-related genes have been identified to be hypo-methylated, which is linked to enhance gene expression; however, hyper-methylation represses the

expression of a gene. Guzmán et al detected a high percentage of methylation in the promoter region of cyclin dependent kinase inhibitor 2A gene (*CDKN2A*), and O-6-Methylguanine-DNA Methyltransferase (*MGMT*) gene are induced in sputum from patients with COPD compared with healthy individuals, and these genes are highly related with heavy smoking (Guzmán *et al.*, 2012); Zong, Ouyang and Chen, 2015). It was found that inflammation and OS are highly linked to the differential methylation detected in COPD inflammatory genes(Sundar *et al.*, 2017a). Epigenetic study and *in silico* analysis of the *F2RL1* promoter region was undertaken in this research study, based on previously reported studies that change in methylation levels of this region is linked with disease severity, development and progression((Tahara *et al.*, 2009; Wu, Xu and Cheng, 2021). The *in silico* studies herein revealed the detection of two CpG islands in 2110 bp *F2RL1* promoter region with potential CpG sites within the islands and CpG shores. Interestingly, CpG island 2 overlaps the TSS and PAR2 coding sequence; also it is associated with transcription factor binding sites (AP-1 and SP-1), which are both associated with important functions in lung diseases such as asthma (Reddy *et al.*, 2012; Elizabeth and Defnet, 2021).

In the present study, CpG island 2 was chosen as a good candidate for methylation analysis, and BSP was used to amplify 347 bp of CpG island 2 after bisulphite conversion. Although CpG island 2 was detected to be dense with CpG sites which are considered potential sites for methylation, results from Sanger sequencing revealed that the selected and amplified CpG island 2 of the PAR2 promoter region did not have any methylated CpG sites in untreated samples in any cell models; furthermore, the chronic treatments with H₂O₂/LPS and in combination did not induce any methylation change (hyper or hypo-methylation) within the selected region.

Several reasons can be suggested for this result. It can be speculated that the region of interest was not, as anticipated, a good potential candidate for methylation analysis as it is very close to the coding sequence. Recently, it has been advised by other groups to choose CpG shores for methylation studies rather than CpG islands, as these are denser with CpG sites and they are naturally associated with moderate levels of methylated clusters, which

can be very good potential target for methylation studies (Mitsumori *et al.*, 2020a). Further, for effective methylation analysis at the gene level, it was proposed by (Huynh *et al.*, 2014) to choose areas of CpG dinucleotides that are far from the promoter region. The further away CpG nucleotides clusters are from CpG islands, it was suggested, the higher the chance of methylation (Skvortsova *et al.*, 2019b).

The choice of H₂O₂ to induce methylation was based on previous studies. Wong *et al.* found that H₂O₂ at a concentration of 25 µM was able to induce hypo-methylation of the *LINE-1* gene, but also caused hyper-methylation of the runt-related transcription factor 3 (*RUNX3*) promoter in a bladder cancer cell line (Wong *et al.*, 2013). Furthermore, global DNA methylation in BEAS-2B cells was investigated by Niu and colleagues, who reported an increase in 5 methyl-cytosine levels from 5.5 % in control to 7% when treated with 150 µM H₂O₂ for 72 h (Niu *et al.*, 2015). Also it can be speculated that the exposure time to OS (H₂O₂) and inflammatory insult (LPS), or the concentrations used, were not sufficient to induce high enough OS levels to cause methylation alteration in the present work.

Recently, in the field of epigenetics, a high-throughput technique is becoming increasingly used in order to detect methylation levels at whole genome scale; the importance of this analysis approach is that it can be used also at a gene level. This technique is a combination between restriction enzyme digestion and bisulphite sequencing to specifically screen a selected DNA region enriched with methylated sites. Using such techniques can provide in-depth analysis of methylated sites within the gene of interest, which can be used to specifically target changes in methylation levels due to different treatments (Berthomieu, 2019).

In summary, the data presented in this study showed that a simple 'chronic' repeated H₂O₂ exposure model in epithelial cells can be useful to study inflammatory and oxidative stress responses relative to COPD. BEAS-2B cells were able to tolerate up to 15 µM of H₂O₂ ; however, HBEC tolerated up to 25 µM and COPD-HBEC up to 50 µM of H₂O₂, suggesting that COPD cells are partially adapted to OS, compared to HBEC and BEAS-2B cells. An interesting

finding was that repeated exposure to chronic H₂O₂ treatment alone did not have any effect but synergistically enhanced the production of IL-6 and IL-8 in cells pre-treated with inflammatory mediators (LPS, TGF- β and TNF- α). Furthermore, this effect of H₂O₂ was mirrored in *IL8* and *IL6* gene expression, enhancing the production of *IL8* transcripts in both HBEC and COPD-HBEC. H₂O₂ treatment also significantly enhanced LPS induced transcription of *RELA*. These data can be explained by the key role of sustained exposure to OS in enhancing inflammation. Treatment with H₂O₂ significantly enhanced SOD2 gene expression in both cell models; interestingly, H₂O₂ effect was noticed to be reduced in inducing the *SOD2* gene in COPD-HBEC when comparing to the level of expression of *SOD2* gene in response to H₂O₂ in healthy cells (HBEC) further indicating reduced sensitivity in COPD cells. Also, treatment with LPS, H₂O₂ and in combination enhanced *F2RL1* gene expression in BEAS-2B cells; but only H₂O₂ effectively increased the *F2RL1* gene in primary cells, perhaps indicating a shortcoming of the immortalised line as a model system. Intracellular ROS was significantly elevated when cell models were treated with H₂O₂ alone and in combination with other mediators; interestingly there was a decrease in intracellular ROS in COPD-HBEC compared to HBEC when treated with LPS and H₂O₂, highlighting further distinct phenotype of cells taken from a disease context. Importantly, it was shown that the induction of IL-6 and IL-8 were critically mediated through the NF- κ B pathway, including synergistic effects of OS, and likely through the canonical pathway.

Bioinformatics analysis showed that *F2RL1* (2110 bp) promoter region is associated with two CpG islands, one bigger in size and denser with CpG sites, overlapping with PAR2 TSS and coding sequences, and associated with key transcription factor binding sites. Sanger sequencing of control and bisulphite-treated DNA from this region confirmed the successful bisulphite conversion and BSP; however, treatments were not able to alter methylation status within the selected CpG island 2 region of *F2RL1* gene, nor was any difference detected in this region between 'healthy' bronchial epithelial cells and those from COPD patients.

6.2. Future directions

In this work, H₂O₂ was used as a source of OS to establish an *in vitro* chronic oxidative stress model. Although H₂O₂ was detected in the Exhaled Breath Condensate (EBC) of COPD patients, it has a short half-life, degrading within an hour from most cell culture media; alternatively, other oxidants could be used to replace or augment H₂O₂ which have been found to represent complex oxidants similar to what is observed in CS; potassium oxide (K₂O), glucose oxidase (Forrester *et al.*, 2018), nitric oxide (Osoata *et al.*, 2009b), ozone (Adamkiewicz, Liddie and Gaffin, 2020b) and CSE (Zhu *et al.*, 2021) could all be used to replace H₂O₂ in analogous experiments, and these agents generate continuous ROS within the culture media.

For further confirmation of NF-κB activation in this study, western blots should be used in order to confirm activation of the NF-κB canonical pathway. Western blotting should show degradation of the IκB α complex, also phosphorylation of p65 and p50 subunits of NF-κB. Furthermore, to confirm that the NF-κB activation pathway induced cytokines release, the western blot should be carried out after cells pre-treatment with TPCA-1; if phosphorylation of p65 and p50 is attenuated due to TPCA-1 treatment this confirms that the inhibitor is blocking NF-κB canonical pathway activation. Also, IKK-2 expression can be confirmed by qPCR after treatment with LPS alone and after pre-treatment with TPCA-1.

The DNA methylation analysis could be extended in several ways. Methylation levels can be tested in regions around CpG island (CpG shores) and in regions further from the coding region of *F2RL1*. Alternative to BSP, Methylated-specific PCR (MSP) or Cobra PCR can amplify and detect methylated regions within the sequence of interest by PCR only and without further sequencing. Also, changing the source of OS from H₂O₂ to CSE or ozone may more effectively disrupt methylation levels within the gene of interest.

Further, the epigenetics work can be extended to study differential methylation in other COPD-related genes such as *IL6* and *IL8* as inflammatory genes and *NFE2L2* as redox-anti oxidative gene; recently, it was reported by Lian *et al.* that a section of *IL6* gene promoter region (1.5 kb) divided into 1 kb upstream and 0.5 kb downstream relative to TSS was analysed

for methylation studies. Several potential CpG sites were detected within the 1.5 kb selected region of *IL6*. These results confirmed that the downstream region at exon 2 is highly methylated at single CpG sites compared to upstream selected region (1 kb) in the *IL6* promoter region, in RAW264.7 cells (Lian *et al.*, 2022). These methylation changes were also associated with a reduction in *IL6* gene expression. Previously, it was suggested that methylation of a single CpG in the *IL6* promoter region was found to affect *IL6* mRNA gene regulation, and this was associated with the pathogenesis of rheumatoid arthritis (Nile *et al.*, 2008).

The effect of methylated/unmethylated enhancers in the regulation of the *PAR2* gene or any relevant COPD-related genes such as *IL6* or *IL8* can be also considered in future work, as enhancers are also potential targets for methylation and predicts gene expression levels better than promoters (Aran and Hellman, 2013).

Recent studies have suggested that various CpG dinucleotides can be useful as biomarkers to identify therapeutic outcomes and illness severity in a range of inflammatory diseases, importantly in cancer, and in other diseases such as paediatric and autoimmune diseases, in addition to conditions caused by the recently discovered COVID-19 virus (Nile *et al.*, 2008; Claus *et al.*, 2012; Shanthikumar *et al.*, 2020; Castro de Moura *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, because of its high specificity and limited off-target effects, targeting even a single CpG dinucleotide may potentially have significant benefit in targeted therapy for altering gene expression in cells. The regulatory function of DNA methylation in gene expression and the regulation of physiological outputs by changes in DNA methylation requires more investigation but shows enormous promise (Lian *et al.*, 2022).

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APPENDIX A.

Publications

PUBLICATIONS

2021: Abstract Published at British Thoracic Society (BTS).

Oxidative stress-driven inflammatory responses in lung epithelial cells

Tarhini, F., Crilly, A., Brzezczynska, J., McGarvey, L., Thornbury, K., Goodyear, C. S., Lockhart, J. C. & Litherland, G. J., 21 Jan 2021, In: THORAX. 76, Suppl 1, A31.

2020: Abstract Published at European Respiratory Society (ERS).

Repeated exposure to hydrogen peroxide enhances TGF- β and LPS-dependent inflammatory responses in BEAS-2B cells.

Tarhini, F., Dunning, L., Crilly, A., Brzezczynska, J., McGarvey, L., Thornbury, K., Goodyear, C. S., Lockhart, J. C. & Litherland, G. J., 28 Oct 2020, In: European Respiratory Journal. 56, Supplement 64, 607.

2018: Abstract Published at the Learning, Teaching & Research conference (LTR).

F. Tarhini¹, L. Dunning¹, A. Crilly¹, L. McGarvey², K. Thornbury³, C.S. Goodyear⁴, J.C. Lockhart¹, G.J. Litherland, “**Genetics of COPD**”

AWARDS

2020: “*BTS Travel Award*” (£350) to speak at the British Thoracic Society meeting (BTS) 2020 in London, United Kingdom.

2018: “*Learning, Teaching & Research conference*” from the University of the West of Scotland: winner of the best lay summary abstract.

2017-2022: “*Fully-funded Research Scholarship*” from the University of the West of Scotland to cover my PhD tuition fees and living expenses.

CONFERENCE TALKS

- BREATH annual meeting, 2021, Glasgow, Scotland:

F. Tarhini, L. Dunning, A. Crilly, L. McGarvey, K. Thornbury, C.S. Goodyear, J.C. Lockhart, G.J. Litherland, “**Mechanisms underpinning inflammatory cytokine production in lung epithelial cells during oxidative stress**”.

-British Thoracic Society, September 2021, Vienna, Austria.

Tarhini, F., Crilly, A., Brzeszczyńska, J., McGarvey, L., Thornbury, K., Goodyear, C. S., Lockhart, J. C. & Litherland, G. J., **“Oxidative stress-driven inflammatory responses in lung epithelial cells.”**

- BREATH annual meeting, 2020, Glasgow, Scotland:

Tarhini, F., Crilly, A., Brzeszczyńska, J., McGarvey, L., Thornbury, K., Goodyear, C. S., Lockhart, J. C. & Litherland, G. J., 21 Jan 2021, In: THORAX. 76, Suppl 1, A31. **“Oxidative stress-driven inflammatory responses in lung epithelial cells”.**

-BREATH annual meeting, 2019, Glasgow, Scotland:

F. Tarhini¹, L. Dunning¹, A. Crilly¹, L. McGarvey², K. Thornbury³, C.S. Goodyear⁴, J.C. Lockhart¹, G.J. Litherland, **“Investigation of PAR2 promoter methylation: a model for epigenetic gene regulation in lung airway epithelia”.**

CONFERENCE POSTER PRESENTATIONS

- European Thoracic Society (ERS), September 2020

Tarhini, F., Dunning, L., Crilly, A., Brzeszczyńska, J., McGarvey, L., Thornbury, K., Goodyear, C. S., Lockhart, J. C. & Litherland, G. J., **“Repeated exposure to hydrogen peroxide enhances TGF- β and LPS-dependent inflammatory responses in BEAS-2B cells”.**

- BREATH annual meeting, June 2019.

Tarhini, F., Dunning, L., Crilly, A., McGarvey, L., Thornbury, K., Goodyear, C. S., Lockhart, J. C. & Litherland, G. J., **“ Genetics and Epigenetics Modifications in COPD”.**

- Learning, Teaching & Research conference, June 2019.

F.Tarhini, L. Dunning, A. Crilly, J.C. Lockhart, G.J. Litherland. “Epigenetics Modifications in COPD”.

Oxidative Stress Driven Inflammatory Responses in Lung Epithelial Cells

COPD, Inflammation, Epithelial cell

F. Tarhini¹, L. Dunning¹, A. Crilly¹, J. Brzeszczynska¹, L. McGarvey², K. Thornbury³, C. S.Goodyear⁴, J. C.Lockhart¹, G. J.Litherland¹

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Cigarette smoke stimulates an inflammatory response and produces oxidants that cause oxidative stress in the lung, promoting pathophysiological changes related to chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) is an important oxidant detected in breath condensate of COPD patients². We aim to understand how chronic exposure to H₂O₂ alone or in combination with other inflammatory mediators influences epithelial cell responses relevant to COPD lung pathology.

BEAS-2B cells were exposed chronically to H₂O₂ for 2 h/day for 3 days at different concentrations, alone or in combination with TGF- β (10 ng/ml) or LPS (100 or 500 ng/ml). Cell viability was assessed by MTT assay. Cytokines were measured by ELISA. Intracellular ROS production was detected by CM-H₂DCFDA assay. Data were analysed using one-way ANOVA, followed by Multiple Comparison Test.

Cells tolerated a repeated exposure of H₂O₂ (up to 15 μ M) \pm TGF- β or LPS without significant loss of viability. Intracellular ROS was significantly elevated in the presence of LPS (mean \pm SEM; 217 \pm 17 %; $p < 0.0001$) or H₂O₂ (331 \pm 13 %; $p < 0.0001$), with an additive effect of combined treatment (H₂O₂, 444 \pm 12 vs. LPS + H₂O₂, 604 \pm 35 %; $p < 0.0001$). H₂O₂ stimulated modest release of IL-8 (38 \pm 2 pg/ml) and IL-6 (84 \pm 13 pg/ml). However, repeated 15 μ M H₂O₂ exposure synergistically enhanced TGF- β induced IL-8 (TGF- β , 194 \pm 13 vs. TGF- β + H₂O₂, 279 \pm 10 pg/ml; $p < 0.0001$) but not IL-6 (TGF- β , 431 \pm 22 vs. TGF- β + H₂O₂, 449 \pm 2 pg/ml). H₂O₂ synergistically enhanced LPS secretion of both IL-8 (LPS, 2487 \pm 21 vs. LPS+ H₂O₂, 2898 \pm 109 pg/ml; $p < 0.0001$), and IL-6 (LPS, 2469 \pm 72 vs. LPS+ H₂O₂, 3277 \pm 62 pg/ml; $p < 0.0001$).

Oxidative stress appears to be generated in BEAS-2B cells by LPS or H₂O₂ alone, and increased in combination. Repeated exposure to H₂O₂ induced minimal inflammatory response, but synergistically enhanced the effect of TGF- β and LPS on cytokine production. These data suggest combined exposure models may be useful to study the effects of epithelial cell challenges relevant to COPD pathology.

1. Kirkham, P., Rahman, I. Oxidative stress in asthma and COPD: antioxidant as a therapeutic strategy. *Pharmacol Ther*, 2006. **111**: 476-94
2. Montuschi, P. Exhaled breath condensate analysis in patients with COPD. *Clin Chim Acta*, 2005. **356**: 22-34

Repeated exposure to hydrogen peroxide enhances TGF- β and LPS dependent inflammatory responses in BEAS-2B cells

COPD, Inflammation, Epithelial cell

F. Tarhini¹, L. Dunning¹, A. Crilly¹, J. Brzezczynska¹, L. Mcgarvey², K. Thornbury³, C. S.Goodyear⁴, J. C.Lockhart¹, G. J.Litherland¹

¹University of the West of Scotland - Paisley, Scotland (United Kingdom), ²Queens University Belfast - Belfast, Northern Ireland (United Kingdom), ³Dundalk Institute of Technology - Dundalk, Ireland (Ireland), ⁴University of Glasgow - Institute of Infection, Immunity & Inflammation (United Kingdom)

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Cigarette smoke stimulates an inflammatory response and produces oxidants that cause oxidative stress in the lung, which promotes pathophysiological changes related to chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) (Kirkham, P. Pharmacol Ther 2006; 111: 476-94). Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) is one of the oxidants detected in the breath condensate of COPD patients (Montuschi, P. Clin Chim Acta 2005; 35: 22-34). We aim to understand how chronic exposure to H₂O₂ alone or in combination with other inflammatory mediators influences epithelial cell responses relevant to COPD lung pathogenesis.

BEAS-2B cells were exposed to H₂O₂ (2 h/d for 3 days) at different concentrations, alone or in combination with TGF- β (10 ng/ml) or LPS (500 ng/ml). Cell viability was assessed. IL-8 and IL-6 were measured by ELISA. Data was analysed using Multiple Comparison Test.

Cells tolerated a repeated exposure of H₂O₂ (up to 15 μ M) \pm TGF- β or LPS without significant loss of viability. H₂O₂ stimulated modest release of IL-8 (mean \pm SEM; 38 \pm 2 pg/ml) and IL-6 (84 \pm 13 pg/ml). However, repeated 15 μ M H₂O₂ exposure significantly enhanced TGF- β induced IL-8 (TGF- β , 194 \pm 13 vs. TGF- β + H₂O₂, 279 \pm 10 pg/ml; $p < 0.0001$) but not IL-6 (TGF- β , 431 \pm 22 vs. TGF- β + H₂O₂, 449 \pm 2 pg/ml). H₂O₂ enhanced LPS secretion of both IL-8 (LPS, 2487 \pm 21 vs. LPS+ H₂O₂, 2898 \pm 109 pg/ml; $p < 0.0001$), and IL-6 (LPS, 2469 \pm 72 vs. LPS+ H₂O₂, 3277 \pm 62 pg/ml; $p < 0.0001$).

Repeated exposure of BEAS-2B cells to H₂O₂ induced minimal inflammatory response, but enhanced the effect of TGF- β and LPS on cytokine production. These data suggest such combined exposure models may be useful to study the effects of epithelial cell challenge relevant to COPD pathology.

Mechanisms underpinning inflammatory cytokine production in lung epithelial cells during oxidative stress.

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Affiliations: Border & REgions Airways Training Hub, Centre for Musculoskeletal Science, Institute of Biomedical and Environmental Health Research, School of Health & Life Sciences, ¹University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, Scotland. ²Queens University Belfast. ³Dundalk Institute of Technology. ⁴Institute of Infection, Immunity & Inflammation, University of Glasgow.

Abstract:

Chronic inflammation in COPD is driven by multiple pro-inflammatory cytokines as well as oxidative stress¹. Inflammatory stimuli such as TNF- α and LPS induce NF- κ B activation, leading to the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-6 and IL-8)². Therapeutics which target NF- κ B, including inhibitors of I κ B kinases are promising treatments for COPD³. We aim to understand how chronic exposure to H₂O₂ alone or in combination with other inflammatory mediators influences the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines, and whether these proteins are under transcriptional control of NF- κ B.

Human epithelial (BEAS-2B) cells were stimulated with LPS or TNF- α in the presence or absence of oxidative stress stimulus H₂O₂ and the effect of pre-treatment with IKK-2 Inhibitor (TPCA-1) was investigated. Pro-inflammatory mediators (IL-6 and IL-8) were measured by ELISA and mRNA transcripts by RT-PCR.

Repeated H₂O₂ exposure synergistically enhanced LPS secretion of both IL-8 (LPS, 2487 \pm 21 vs. LPS+H₂O₂, 2898 \pm 109 pg/ml; p <0.0001), and IL-6 (LPS, 2469 \pm 72 vs. LPS+H₂O₂, 3277 \pm 62 pg/ml; p <0.0001). Pre-treatment with TPCA-1 effectively suppressed LPS induced IL-6 (LPS, 364 \pm 3 vs. LPS+TPCA-1, 157 \pm 24 pg/ml; p <0.001) and IL-8 (LPS, 305 \pm 51 vs. LPS+TPCA-1, 103 \pm 15 pg/ml; p <0.05). Importantly, TPCA-1 also significantly inhibited H₂O₂-enhanced LPS induction of IL-6 (LPS+H₂O₂, 555 \pm 16 vs. LPS+H₂O₂+TPCA-1, 82 \pm 2 pg/ml; p <0.0001) and IL-8 (LPS+H₂O₂, 733 \pm 30 vs. LPS+H₂O₂+TPCA-1, 128 \pm 5 pg/ml; p <0.0001). Interestingly, TPCA-1 more effectively inhibited H₂O₂-enhanced LPS (compared to LPS alone) induction of IL-6 (LPS+TPCA-1, 157 \pm 24 vs. LPS+H₂O₂+TPCA-1, 82 \pm 2 pg/ml; p <0.05), but not IL-8 (LPS+TPCA-1, 128 \pm 5 vs. LPS+H₂O₂+TPCA-1, 103 \pm 5 pg/ml; p =0.1). These effects of TPCA-1 were paralleled by changes in *IL6*, *IL8* and NF- κ B *RELA* transcripts. Furthermore, similar data were observed in treatments with TNF- α alone or in combination with H₂O₂.

The synergistic effect of COPD-relevant stimuli in combination is effectively inhibited by blocking the canonical NF- κ B pathway, including a transcriptional component. These findings in our simple oxidative stress model further support the potential for NF- κ B blockade as a therapeutic strategy to ameliorate chronic inflammation in COPD.

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2. Watters, T. M., E. F. Kenny, et al. (2007). "Structure, function and regulation of the Toll/IL-1 receptor adaptor proteins." *Immunol Cell Biol* 85(6): 411-419.
3. Schuliga M. (2015). NF-kappaB Signaling in Chronic Inflammatory Airway Disease. *Biomolecules*, 5(3), 1266–1283.

Genetics of COPD. 2018: Abstract Published at the Learning, Teaching & Research conference (LTR).

F. Tarhini¹, L. Dunning¹, A. Crilly¹, L. McGarvey², K. Thornbury³, C.S. Goodyear⁴, J.C. Lockhart¹, G.J. Litherland.

We know that chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is primarily caused by inflammatory response to pollutants and gases mainly from smoking cigarettes, which can lead to chronic bronchitis emphysema, and severe breathlessness (all features of COPD). Both genetic and environmental factors have been found to play important roles in the development of COPD, which impairs quality of life, is a leading cause of death, and imparts a high cost to health services.

Ireland and Scotland bear the unfortunate distinction of being among world leaders in COPD prevalence. Accordingly, BREATH (Borders and Regions Airway Training Hub) which is a tripartite consortium (DKIT, QUB, UWS) formed with the aim of training researchers with a focus on combating COPD both by searching for new treatments, and increasing public awareness about the disease.

The aim of my research project is to look at the epigenetic (chemical changes to genes) and environmental factors related to COPD in Scottish population. In this context, I will review clinical parameters of Scottish COPD patients, and data for environmental factors such as smoking, air pollution, and occupational exposure. I will also analyze how environmental exposures can cause chemical changes to genes involved in the inflammatory response, such as protease-activated receptor 2 (PAR2), in order to understand their contribution to the development of COPD. By utilizing sophisticated software tools to analyze the obtained data, the results may help contribute to the development of preventive strategies and therapeutic approaches against COPD.